

**CHANGING TRENDS IN THE LAW OF MEDICAL
NEGLIGENCE UNDER CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT 1986**

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Certificate of the Guide

CERTIFIED that the work incorporated in the thesis **CHANGING TRENDS IN THE LAW OF MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE UNDER CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT 1986** submitted by Dr. Santosh Kakade was carried out by the candidate under my supervision/ guidance. Such material, as has been obtained from other sources has been duly acknowledged in the thesis.

Place: Pune
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Dr. Shashikala Gurpur
Research Guide

CHAPTER I

Introduction, Background and Literature Review

“From inability to leave well alone; from too much zeal for the new and contempt for what is old; from putting knowledge before wisdom, science before art, cleverness before commonsense; from treating patients as cases; and for making cure of a disease more grievous than the endurance, good Lord, deliver.”

Robert Hutchison¹

1.1 Introduction

“The customer is King”-though an old adage, yet, in spite of managerial checks for quality, at the manufacturing end, the customer walks through against all odds. Duplications and legal checks and measures did not guarantee him the minimum and made him more vulnerable. The professional services did not lag behind. And, the good, the bad and the ugly standards in service quality in contrast rendered the very existence of common person- the consumer at peril. Not that the existing law lacks in its operative coverage for any such lapses. Yet, a milestone, in the consumer protection, special law ushered with a special protective coverage. Amongst all professional services, the medical field has become most expansive in the first instance and others to fall in line. Extension of corporate approach in services and the health consciousness by one and all brought in a situation for medical attention at a far in advance stage even before one gets ill. Healthy persons are taking more pills than one who suffers. However, the field at both ends, i. e. the persons getting treated or the treating professionals are at total bay, due to lack of awareness as to their rights and obligations.²

Highlighting cases of medical negligence has ever been a trait of yellow journalism and probably these phenomena cannot be checked. It is to be realized that looking from journalistic point of view, “if a dog bites a man it may or may not be news, but if a man bites a dog it is news”. So also if medical profession cures many with its knowledge and expertise it is no longer newsworthy, but a forceps left inside the body during an operation by an otherwise eminent surgeon through an oversight is definitely newsworthy. Public sympathy on so emotional issue is overall in favour of

¹ Russel, et al.(eds), 2004 as cited in Tapas Kumar Koley, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND

MEDICOLEGAL ASPECTS OF PATIENT CARE (New Delhi, Mehta Publishers, 2004)

² B.Prakash Rao & Justice Y.V.Rao, LAW RELATING TO MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE, 1st edition, 2006, Forward

this step to bring greater accountability in the medical profession. For the doctors point the best policy would be to let the issue take its natural course with gradual maturity of the process, bringing about the desired changes ensuring justice to both sides. Meanwhile the medical profession has to deal with this issue like with any other disease i.e. in a practical and sensible manner. Before tackling any issue it is important to know as much about it as possible.³

One of the most important aspects of any profession is the degree of excellence in results that a person practicing that profession can give. It is not at all expected that each and every professional would deliver the goods in the same expertise. There are so many aspects and factors that determine the relative competence of an individual in a group, vocation or a particular line of personalized and highly skilled practice. What is important is that one acts, conducts himself and discharges his duties in such a manner as would be expected from a prudent contemporary in a similar situation having access to similar facilities and in the know-how of the principles of such a practice in general. One can leave some room for factors like standards of basic education, facilities regarding initial period of training and specialized exposure, conditions of exigencies and stress while executing a given assignment and the like which in the ordinary course of day to day life are sufficient to lead to a difference of performance. But certainly there is no escape at all for contumacious recklessness, blatant dereliction of duty or complete misapplication of mind which comprised of one of the above or several acts or omissions leading to a negligent act and this untoward act is negligence.⁴

Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. The enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being without distinction of race, religion, and political belief, economic or social condition. The health of all peoples is fundamental to the attainment of peace and security and is dependent upon the fullest co-operation of individuals and States. The achievement of any State in the promotion and protection of health is of value to all. Unequal development in different countries in the promotion of health and control of disease, especially

³ Neeraj Nagpal, COMPENDIUM OF CPA MEDICAL JUDGMENTS: INTRODUCTION, Chandigarh, Neelam Prakashan 1996

⁴ Anoop K. Kaushal, Medical Negligence and Liabilities of a Doctor-MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND LEGAL REMEDIES, 3rd edition Delhi, Universal Law publishing, 2004, pp. 8

communicable disease, is a common danger. Healthy development of the child is of basic importance; the ability to live harmoniously in a changing total environment is essential to such development. The extension to all peoples of the benefits of medical, psychological and related knowledge is essential to the fullest attainment of health. Informed opinion and active co-operation on the part of the public are of the utmost importance in the improvement of the health of the people. Governments have a responsibility for the health of their peoples, which can be fulfilled only by the provision of adequate health and social measures.⁵

The diagnosis and the treatment of diseases pertaining to human beings are very risky professions as they are accompanied by a high degree of morbidity and mortality. Previously medical professionals were mainly worried about failing to save the life of a patient or providing satisfactory treatment to a sick person. Now they also worry about the legal consequences of their failure. So, to this ancient risk of professional failure has been added the modern risk of providing economic compensation for the damage caused to the patient as a result of actual or perceived negligent treatment.⁶

The nature of relationship between doctors and patients is determined largely by the practice of the medical profession and shaped by a strong commitment to long standing principles of medical ethics. The law plays a significant role, however, in providing a structure within which the doctor patient relationship is conducted. Whether it is civil, criminal or consumer law, these can only set the outer limits of acceptable conduct, i.e., a “minimal standard of professional care and skill, leaving the question of “ideal” standards to the profession itself. Most doctors seem to carry a notion that the law sets high a standard which does not take in to account the intricacies of medical science. This is far from being true. The courts are rather considerate towards them. This is clearly evident from their decisions. In practice medical negligence means failure to live up to minimal standards of reasonable care and skill, and those standards are set not by the courts but by professionals themselves.⁷

⁵ Ravi Duggal, Healthcare Case Law in India, Report, CEHAT, 2007; pp.8

⁶ Tapas Kumar Koley, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND THE LAW IN INDIA: INTRODUCTION, 1st edition, Oxford University Press, 2010; pp.130-138.

⁷ Jagdish Singh & Vishwa Bhushan, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND COMPENSATION, 3rd edition 2004, reprint with up-to-date Case-law 2007, pp.12.

The law relating to medical negligence finds its genesis in the common law principles of Negligence and was further developed by the judicial pronouncements in the western world. India was no exception to this legal development as one of the first reported judgments in a case of medical negligence dates back to 1969, i. e., case of *Laxman v/s Godbole* ⁸ wherein the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India dealt in detail about the principles involved in medical negligence and further elaborated the duties of doctor and also patients. Not much of hue and cry was raised by the medical fraternity at that point of time, because till then the doctor patient relationship had element of trust in it. Moreover, medical profession was taken to be one of most noble professions on earth.⁹

Negligence can be described as failure to take due care, as a result of which injury ensues. It is not sufficient that the medical professional acted in good faith to best of his or her judgment and belief. A medical professional is expected to have a requisite degree of skill and knowledge. Medical malpractice is not merely the negligence on the part of care giver but it is a conscious decision of the care giver to offer and /or force a product, procedure or investigation upon a patient for monetary gain either personally or for the institution.¹⁰

Three essential components of the modern tort of Negligence propounded by Percy and Charles worth are as follows; ¹¹

- The existence of duty to take care , which is owed by the defendant to the complainant;
- The failure to attain the standard of care, prescribed by the law, thereby breach of such duty; and
- Damage, which is both causally connected to such breach and recognized by the law, has been suffered by the complainant

⁸AIR 1969 SC 129.

⁹ Vidya Yeravdekar & Dr.Ravi Bhardwaj, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE CASE REPORTER: First Edition, Pune, Symbiosis Centre of Healthcare, 2003. Preface

¹⁰. Mihir Desai & Mahabal Kamayani Bali, HEALTH CARE CASE LAW IN INDIA- A READER; REPORT, Mumbai; CEHAT and ICHRL, 2007, pp.163.

¹¹. R.K.Bag, LAW OF MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND COMPENSATION; Second edition 2003; Eastern Law House, pp. 4.

If the plaintiff proves that the doctor was negligent, but fails to establish that any loss or injury was caused thereby, then he/she will not be entitled to claim any compensation.¹² The general test for causation requires the plaintiff to establish that the injury would not have occurred, but for the negligence of the defendant.¹³

Since the application of the Consumer Protection Act (herein after CPA) ¹⁴to the medical field in 1995 in India¹⁵, there have been a large numbers of cases against doctors and there have been many settled principles of law. As per these principles the law has defined responsibilities of doctors and hospitals which include; ¹⁶

- To obtain an informed consent of a patient
- To conduct necessary pre-operative diagnostic tests
- To exercise due care and diligence
- To provide information regarding Birth, Death etc and Certification of Health condition
- Maintenance of Secrecy
- Issuance of death certificate
- Employment of qualified staff, supervision, provision of Ancillary services and engagement of Specialists
- Provision and testing of blood
- In complicated cases assistance of experts/ consultants in relevant field should be availed

While “to err is human”, a hospital and medical professionals entrusted with treatment and often with life of a patient, who generally follows the advice of the professionals unquestioningly, are expected to exercise greater degree of care while discharging their duties. ¹⁷

¹²Sidhraj Dhadha v State of Rajasthan AIR 1994 Raj 68; 1993(1) Raj LW 532. as quoted by Dr. R.K.Bag (2003); pp. 4

¹³ Athey v Leonati [1996] 3 RCS 458 as quoted by Dr.RK Bag (2003) pp. 4

¹⁴ See details in Annexure II

¹⁵ IMA v. VP Shantha and Ors; AIR 1996 SC 550:1995(6) SCC651: 1995(3): CPJ 1(SC): 1995(3) CPR412 (SC)

¹⁶ M.S. Pandit, & Shobha Pandit, MEDICO LEGAL AID TO HOSPITALS & DOCTORS WITH CONSUMER PROTECTION LAW, 2nd edition, pp. 1-14.

¹⁷ Id.

From the judgments given by Supreme Court, High Courts and State and National Commissions various legal principles have emerged which have guided the outcome of the nature of the further cases of medical negligence.¹⁸

The list is as follows,

1. Res ipsa loquitur: infer from things
2. No privilege to any school of medicine where more than one school of medicine exists.
3. Expert evidence is required
4. Vexatious litigation
5. Demand of exorbitant fee
6. Where complainant does not prove medical negligence, no liability can be fastened on the doctor or the hospital. Burden of proof is on the complainant.
7. While code of medical ethics requires a doctor to maintain secrecy and confidentiality, "Right to Life" of an individual as fundamental right is an exception to this rule.
8. Standard of care and skill or judgment or technique used by a doctor
9. Nexus between injury and breach of duty on the part of medical professional or hospital
10. Foreseeability and remoteness of injury
11. Inherent risk of surgery and treatment
12. Error of Judgment
13. Provision of blood
14. Transfer of serious patient from one hospital to another
15. Where non specialists, Health Care workers, Nurses and juniors are held negligent
16. A consultant is negligent if he delegates the responsibilities to a junior
17. Incomplete medical records

¹⁸ M.S. Pandit, & Shobha Pandit, MEDICO LEGAL AID TO HOSPITALS & DOCTORS WITH CONSUMER PROTECTION LAW, 2nd edition, pp. 178-203.

18. Law prohibits ayurvedic, unani or homeopathic doctor prescribing allopathic medicine

1.2 Need for the present Study

Legislations such as CPA are important for the simple reason that they, in a specific manner, operationalize policies of the government. For that matter, the legislation is only one part of the policy literature available for undertaking policy analysis. This does not mean that the legislation always follows the policy. There are instances when the legislation (the law ordinances) are passed first, giving an indication of the policy being pursued by the state. There are also instances, numerous in the field of health care, when no legislation follows the announced policy and thereby, leaving the implementation of the announced policy at the discretion of the administrators and the political environment prevalent. Thus, the legislation cannot be looked at in vacuum; they must be understood in relation to policies.¹⁹

Practice of medicine is capable of rendering great service to the society provided due care, efficiency and skills are observed by the doctors. Medical Profession has its own ethical parameters and code of conduct. This profession is rendering a noble service to humanity and has sustained itself on public trust. According to the Voluntary Health Association of India, the present state of medical profession seems to mirror the rot, which seems to have sent in to the system. Increased mechanization and commercialization of profession have brought in an element dehumanization in medical practice. Healthcare has been reduced to business which determines the doctor patient relationship.²⁰

The concept of “consumer” arises from western countries. It is very much useful to study the concept, while applying it to the medical field. The applicability of this concept to the Indian context is a research area itself. There is need for more research, to evaluate the current and changing trends in the laws related to the medical negligence. The research is needed to bring out the lacunae, to suggest the changes that are acceptable to medical field and the consumers.

¹⁹ Amar Jesani, Laws and Health Care Providers, Report 1996; CEHAT; pp. 8.

²⁰ Samikshya Baskota, Medical Negligence and Consumer Protection Law, An Analytical study of Medical Negligence and its relation with Consumer Protection Act of Nepal. http://www.ksl.edu.np/cpanel/pics/medical_negligence_samikshya.pdf

Since the application of the Consumer Protection Act, due to Judicial Activism a number of legal principles have evolved. The patient has been equated to consumer and this has affected the relationship between doctor and patient. There are number of other factors which are responsible for the decline in Doctor-Patient relationship like advancement of the technology in healthcare, commercialization of the healthcare sector, growth of corporate hospitals and so on. Any medico legal case is a confrontation between medical knowledge of a lawyer and the legal knowledge of a doctor. India is a developing country where it has peculiar characteristics like majority of rural population, Illiteracy and lack of awareness about the consumer rights and legal provisions

In this context the following areas need to be explored.

1. Increased Litigation
2. Weak Control of Law Provisions
3. Variable Consumer Awareness
4. Link between increased litigation and the consumer awareness
5. Illiteracy
6. Poor Medical Infrastructure
7. Discrepancies in Private and Public Sector Healthcare
8. Role of Quacks
9. Gradual Lifestyle Changes
10. Cross Pathy Practice
11. Trends in the litigations against Medical Persons.
12. Judges' unawareness of medical uncertainty

It shows that there is a gap in the knowledge about the above aspects .The limitations for the applicability of the Consumer Protection Act to the Indian health circumstances need to be probed. Considering the above aspects of Indian context, there is a need for further research regarding linking of consumer rights and patients rights to the laws of medical negligence.

Thus probing in the overall aspects of the applicability of the Consumer Protection Act to the medical field is necessary to find out grey areas which can be tackled by solutions that can be suggested thereafter.

1.3 Review of Literature

Law is an instrument of social change. It brings about the change in the society based on the principles of justice and social equity. Law protects the rights of the common People. The instrument is utilized frequently, when the rights of common people are affected. Whenever the procedure involved in the application of the law is simple, it is utilized to the maximum extent by them, for which there needs an awareness of the law in the society.²¹

Since the application of the Consumer Protection Act to the medical field²², there has been an increase in the awareness about the Medical Negligence in the society. In the Landmark case, *IMA v VP Shantha and Others*,²³ the Hon'ble Supreme Court has applied seal of approval on the application of The Consumer Protection Act to the members of medical profession. In the current scenario, there is a phenomenal rise in cases involving alleged medical negligence.²⁴

The Consumer Protection Act aims at better protection of the interests of consumers and for settlement of consumer disputes. It provides for speedy and inexpensive settlement of disputes within a limited timeframe.²⁵ It has been found that, there is a changing trend in the law of medical negligence. The changing trend in the judicial and legislative approach towards the cases of medical malpractice needs to be studied in depth and there is need to find out lacunae for correction in the Consumer Protection Act.

“The principle objective of the medical profession is to render services to the humanity with full respect to the dignity of men.”

²¹ Tapas Kumar Koley, *MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND THE LAW IN INDIA: INTRODUCTION*, 1st edition, Oxford University Press, 2010; p 21

²² AIR 1996 SC 550: 1995 (6) SCC 651:1995(3) CPJ 1(SC): 1995(3) CPR 412 (SC)

²³ Id.12

²⁴ Mihir Desai & Mahabal Kamayani Bali, *Health Care Case Law in India- A Reader*, Report 2007, CEHAT and ICHRL, Mumbai, pp. 163

²⁵ Jagdish Singh & Vishwa Bhushan, *Medical Negligence and Compensation*, 3rd edition 2004, reprint with up-to-date Case-law 2007, pp. 15.

For ages, medical practice has been treated as a noble profession. The relationship between a patient and his/her family doctor was once of trust and total confidence on the part of the patient and one of care and concern on the part of the doctor. The disappearance of the concept of family doctor and the rapid growth of super specialty corporate hospitals in the urban areas has totally changed the age-old doctor-patient relationship based on long-term association and trust.²⁷

Profession

Scrutton L.J has said “‘Profession’ in the present use of language involves the idea of an occupation requiring either purely intellectual skill, or of manual skill controlled, as in painting and sculpture; or surgery, by the intellectual skill of the operator, as distinguished from an occupation which is substantially the production or sale of commodities. The line of demarcation may vary from time to time. The word ‘profession’ used to be confined to the three learned professions, the Church, Medicine and the Law. It has now, I think a wider meaning” ²⁸

According to Rupert M Jackson and John N Powell, ²⁹the occupations which are regarded as professions have four characteristics

- Skilled and specialized nature of work.
- Commitment to moral principles.
- Professional association regulates standards of profession.
- High status in the community

Negligence

Negligence means: the omission to do something which a reasonable man, guided by those ordinary considerations which ordinarily regulate human affairs, would do or the doing something which a reasonable and prudent man would not do.

²⁶ Rajyalaxmi Rao, CONSUMER IS KING, Universal Law Publishers; 3rd Edition; March 1, 2012; pp.24

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Id. 15

²⁹ Id. 15

Negligence as a tort is the breach of a duty caused by omission to do something which a reasonable man would do or doing something which a prudent and reasonable man would not do. The definition involves the following constituents:³⁰

- A legal duty to exercise due care;
- Breach of the duty; and
- Consequential damages

Professional Negligence

In the law of negligence, professionals such as lawyers, doctors, architects and others are included in the category of persons professing some special skill or skilled persons generally. Any task which is required to be performed with a special skill would generally be admitted or undertaken to be performed only if the person possesses the requisite skill for performing that task.

Professional Liability³¹

In the matter of professional liability professions differ from other occupations for the reason that professions operate in spheres where success cannot be achieved in every case and very often success or failure depends upon factors beyond the professional's control. Medical practitioners do not enjoy any immunity and they can be sued in contract or tort on the ground that they have failed to exercise reasonable skill and care. It would thus appear that medical practitioners, though belonging to the medical profession, are not immune from a claim for damages on the ground of negligence. The fact that they are governed by the Indian Medical Council Act, 1956 and are subject to the disciplinary Control of Medical Council of India and/or State Medical Councils is no solace to the person who has suffered due to their negligence and right of such person to seek redress is not affected.³²

Medical Negligence

Negligence can be described as failure to take due care, as a result of which injury ensues. Negligence excludes wrongful intention since they are mutually exclusive. Carelessness is not culpable or a ground for legal liability except in those cases in

³⁰ Id. 15

³¹ Id. 15

³² Id.28

which the law has imposed the duty of carefulness. The medical profession is one such section of society on which such a duty has been imposed in the strictest sense. It is not sufficient that the medical professional acted in good faith to the best of his or her judgment and belief.

Duty of Care ³³

As the proverbial saying goes that the worst case goes to the best profession, yet even the best cannot be sure of success. Just as the best of a lawyer cannot be presumed to give a guarantee to win, the best of a doctor is not presumed to have a guarantee to cure. The duty owed by a medical professional to his patient has been summed up by Lord Hewart, C.J in the following words:

“If a person holds himself out as possessing special skill and knowledge and he is consulted, as possessing such skill and knowledge, by or on behalf of patient, he owes a duty to the patient to use due caution in undertaking the treatment. If he accepts the responsibility and undertakes the treatment and the patient submits to his direction and treatment accordingly, he owes a duty to the patient to use diligence, care, knowledge, skill and caution in administering the treatment” ³⁴

Various Laws dealing with Medical Negligence in India include,

- | | |
|---------------------|--|
| 1. Law of Torts. | 4. Constitutional Law. |
| 2. Law of Contract. | 5. Fatal accidents Act.1855 |
| 3. Criminal Law | 6. Consumer Protection Act 1986. ³⁵ |

Laws dealing with Medical Negligence in India are represented in following diagram.

³³. Jagdish Singh&Vishwa Bhushan, 2007, Medical Negligence and Compensation, 3rd Edition, page 29.

³⁴. Id. at pp.30

³⁵. Figure 1

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Negligence is not susceptible to any precise definition as found by Indian Courts. Various meanings may be attributed to negligence. It connotes careless state of mind which may amount to recklessness or indifference. It is a careless conduct without reference to any duty to take care. As it is pointed out by Hon'ble Justice Chagla, ACJ and Hon'ble Justice Bhagavati J. the actions for negligence in India are to be determined according to the principles of English common Law.³⁷

The essential components of the tort of negligence, as postulated by Percy and Charlesworth³⁸ are as follows

- (a) the existence of duty to take care, which is owed by the defendant to the complainant
- (b) the failure to attain that standard of care, prescribed by law, thereby committing a breach of such duty, and
- (c) damage, which is both causally connected with such breach and recognized by law, has been suffered by the complainant

³⁶. Poster presented by Researcher at Founding Conference of European Association of Health Law, Edinburgh, UK 2008, See Annexure I

³⁷. R.K. Bag, LAW OF MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND COMPENSATION; Second edition 2003; Eastern Law House, pp. 4.

³⁸. Id.

By applying the above principles, medical Negligence has been defined as, want of reasonable care and skill of the part of medical practitioner that results in damage to the patient. Before the application of Consumer Protection Act to the medical field, the medical negligence cases used to be dealt under law of torts. After the application of Consumer Protection Act, with plethora of case laws, various concepts have been evolved which include medical negligence, reasonable skill and care, damages due to negligence, importance of documentation, legally valid consents, second opinion during the treatment of a complicated patient, skill updating by specialist doctors and so on.³⁹

The application of the Consumer Protection Act to the medical field in 1995 is a milestone in the history of legislations for medical negligence. Since the application, there has been a rise in the litigations against medical practitioners. There is also increase in the vexatious complaints to gain the unhealthy mileage of the law. With the plethora of case laws under Consumer Protection Act, various conceptions and principles are being defined. Since the two fields, legal and medical, are different in approach, there are likely to be lacunae in the concepts and implementation of the Consumer Protection Act, which need to be addressed.

At one time it was thought that the state was mainly concerned with the maintenance of law and order and the protection of life, liberty and property of the subject. Such a restrictive role of the state is no longer a valid concept. Today living in an era of a welfare state health is considered to be man's most valuable possession since all his activities is influenced by the state of his health.

The Directive Principles of State Policy under the constitution of India require the state to make effective provision for public health, and for just and humane conditions of work. It is the primary duty of the State to raise the level of nutrition, the standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health.⁴⁰ Articles 42 & 47 indicate that government had become conscious of this modern phenomenon and this provision could serve the function of providing a constitutional footing for further legislative and administrative actions. However, it is submitted that the constitutional

³⁹ Id

⁴⁰ Constitution of India. Art. 47

scheme for the protection of health, as originally envisaged, contained a serious lacuna, which was later removed by judicial innovation. It may be appreciated that Articles 42 and 47, which impose constitutional obligation on the State are, non-justiciable in nature. It means if state fails to discharge its obligation, such failure cannot be questioned in court of law and there is no judicial remedy. But this anomaly has been removed by judicial creativity and innovation. The Supreme Court of India's creativity expanded the contours of Article 21, so as to sub serve the right of health and Medicare in it. Though, fundamental rights are negative rights and can be invoked only when it has been violated without the due process of law. In healthcare the damages are irreparable and cannot be brought back. So the court took the positive step and interpreted this negative as positive right under Article 21 of the Constitution of India.

In *Paramanand Katara v. Union of India*,⁴¹ Supreme Court has declared that right to medical aid is an integral part of right to life. It is an obligation on the State to preserve life by extending required medical assistance. In fact, the Apex court has held that right to health and medical care is a fundamental right under the Constitution of India.

Further, Supreme Court in *Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samiti v. State of WB*⁴² has held that providing adequate medical facilities for the people is an essential part of the obligation undertaken by the government in a welfare state. Article 21 imposes an obligation on the State to safeguard the right to life of every person and on the breach of which s/he can move the Supreme Court or High Court through writ petition.⁴³

⁴¹. 1989 (4) SCC 286 : AIR 1989 SC2039:1989 ACJ 1000:1989 (4) SCC 286

⁴². 1996 (4) Supreme 260 : AIR 1996 SC 2426 : 1996 (4) SCC 37: JT 1996(6)43(SC)

⁴³. Constitution of India. Art.32 and Art 226.

Practice of medicine as part of healthcare is capable of rendering great service to the society provided due care, sincerity, efficiency and skill are observed by doctors. Medical profession has its own ethical parameters and code of conduct.

Certain other factors are of great concern.

First is the standard and parameters for seeking admission to medical course has changed with the change in society. Now the medical profession has degenerated from its earlier service and humble motive, quite frequently the medical practitioners are reportedly being involved in activities like organ sale racket.

Second is the hesitation of qualified doctors to take up rural assignment. These assignments have become more of experience- gaining phenomenon and last resort than the real motive for joining the profession.

Third is the large scale mushrooming of hospitals and nursing homes. The big corporate hospitals having branches all over the country have given rise to strange situation but in reality created a paradox. These phenomena have a cascading effect and started to commercialize health services. On the other hand the patient is developing an attitude of "shopping" with his disease. Consequently, the fourth thing that has emerged and appears to be the most serious one, is, the accountability of remedial action of the professionals in this noble vocation.

Today, the Patient-doctor relationship has almost diminished its fiduciary character. 'Services' of medical establishments are more of purchasable commodities and the 'business' attitude have given an impetus to more and more malpractices and instances of neglect. But the question is, whether, on the whole, branding the entire medical community as a delinquent community would serve any purpose or will it cause damage to the patients. The answer is, no doubt, the latter.

It is not that measures to check such dereliction are absent. Victims of medical negligence, considering action against an erring doctor, have three options.

- Compensatory mode - Seek financial compensation before the Consumer Disputes Redressal Forum or before Civil Courts
- Punitive/Deterrent mode - Lodge a criminal complaint against the doctor

- Corrective/ Deterrent mode - Complaint to the State Medical Council demanding that the doctor's license is revoked.

Jurisdiction of Civil Court was never disputed but its scope was limited to damages only. Doctors were initially excluded from the ambit of the Consumer Protection Act, when these courts were first set up in 1986. The Supreme Court's judgment, in *Indian Medical Association, v. V.P. Shantha and ors.*⁴⁴, has brought them within its purview. There are three tiers of dispute redressal fora. At the lowest level is the District Consumer Disputes Redressal Forum (one in each district), which entertains compensation claims up to Rs.20 Lakh. At the next level is the State Consumer Disputes Redressal Forum (one in each state), where compensation claims between Rs.20 Lakh and Rs. 1 Crore are made. At the National Forum, claims of over Rs. 1 Crore are lodged. Those dissatisfied with the judgment of the lower forum can appeal to a higher forum. The final court of appeal is the Supreme Court.

Criminal cases against doctors are lodged mainly following the unnatural death of a patient under their care. The section employed is usually 304 of the Indian Penal Code for a rash or negligent act not amounting to culpable homicide and carries maximum imprisonment of two years, or a fine, or both.

Following the recent Supreme Court judgment in *Suresh Gupta v. Govt. of NCT of Delhi*,⁴⁵ however, criminal cases against doctors are likely to register a steep fall. The police will have to first provide proof of "recklessness and deliberate wrongdoing" on the doctor's part.

Further a complaint can also be lodged with Medical Council of India together with State Medical Councils seeking cancellation of the doctor's license. It is the Medical Council which gives doctors their license to practice; the license can be withdrawn if the doctor is found guilty of misdemeanours. On past experience it can be said that

⁴⁴ . AIR 1996 SC 550 : 1995 (6) SCC 651 :1995(3) CPJ 1(SC) : 1995(3) CPR 412 (SC)

⁴⁵ . 2004 (6) SCC 422

the chances of the Medical Council taking any such step,⁴⁶ are slender except in certain cases. Recently, the Delhi High Court has upheld the suspension of the license of a city surgeon by the Medical Council of India. Dr. M.M. Bagati, who was not a qualified paediatrician, had administered high dosage of drugs to an infant after which the child developed renal problem. On enquiry doctor was found negligent and Medical Council of India suspended his license for a year. When the doctor moved High Court, upholding the Medical Council of India's decision, Justice Sanjay Kishan Kaul held that "A professional doctor is required to prescribe what is required to be done, including the investigation. Considering all facts, it is apparent that the doctor's conduct is in the category of infamous conduct with respect to medical profession. However, not a single doctor anywhere in India has ever since independence had his license permanently revoked."⁴⁷

Thus it can be said that in spite of remedy under different laws, the patients of medical negligence are still suffering and they need additional protection especially the patient from the Government Hospitals. Consumer Laws can be a great help provided the consumers should be aware of their rights.

"It would not be correct to say that every moral obligation involves a legal duty; but every legal duty is founded on a moral obligation. "Said Lord Chief Justice Coleridge.⁴⁸No greater opportunity, no greater responsibility, and no greater obligation befall to a person who chooses to become a medical doctor. In the care of the suffering he/she needs scientific knowledge, technical skill and human understanding, and those who use these with courage, with humility and with wisdom, provide a unique service to their fellow men and women and build an enduring edifice of character within them. This nature of service gives medicine its unique status of being a noble profession. The bringing of medical services within the purview of the Consumer Protection Act has caused a plethora of suits being filed in consumer forums against imaginary and sometimes real negligence of doctors. 'Consumerism' once

⁴⁶ . Vandana Singh, High Court burns down doctor's pleas, Hindustan Times, New Delhi, Aug 17 2004, From "Medical Negligence and Our Laws-An Overview".

⁴⁷ . Vandana Singh, Medical Negligence and Our Laws-An Overview, Article.

www.cccindia.co/corecentre/Database/Docs/DocFiles/Article60.pdf accessed on April. 20, 2012

⁴⁸R v Instan (1893) 1 Qb at 453

unthinkable of as a term in medical parlance has been referred to now in the Supreme Court judgment. The developed countries jargon of 'producers and consumers' have also been referred to in relation to the once sacred doctor patient relationship. The once noble profession has been put at par with any sundry trade.⁴⁹

Medical negligence has been defined as want of reasonable degree of care and skill or wilful negligence on the part of the medical practitioners in the treatment of a patient with whom the relationship of a professional attendant is established so as to lead to his/her bodily injury or permanent disability or loss of life. The law on the subject is very considerate to the medical profession. In *Hatcher v Black*⁵⁰, Lord Daniel opined that the jury must not find a doctor negligent simply because one of the risks inherent in an operation actually took place or as a matter of opinion he made an error of judgment. They should find him guilty only when he had fallen short of reasonable medical care.

Lord Justice Dealing observed that one should be doing disservice to the community at large, if one were to impose liability on hospitals and doctors for everything that happens to go wrong.....one must insist on due care for the patient at every point, but we must not condemn as negligence that which is only a misadventure.⁵¹

Mr. Justice Barrie in *Moore v Levi sham Group*⁵² observed that, "when there are two responsible schools of thought about the management of clinical situation, those Courts could do no greater disservice to the society or to the advancement of medical science than to place the hallmark of legality upon one form of treatment.

As observed by Lord Nathan⁵³, a mistaken diagnosis is not necessarily a negligent diagnosis. In *Mitchell v. Dickson*⁵⁴Innes, ACJ observed," no human being is infallible and in the present state of science even the most eminent specialist may be at fault in detecting the true nature of the diseased condition. A practitioner can only be

⁴⁹ Nagpal Neeraj, Supra

⁵⁰ Lancet 154-2-880

⁵¹ Roe v Ministry of Health, 1954-2-All E.R. 131

⁵² HMC (1959)

⁵³ Medical Negligence, <http://goodhealthnyou.com/library/reading/mpcpa/Chap7.asp>, accessed on May, 10, 2013

⁵⁴ 1954-AP PD-519

liable in this respect if his diagnosis is so palpably wrong as to prove negligence, that is to say, if his mistake is of such nature as to imply absence of reasonable degree of skill and care on his part, regard being had to the ordinary level of skill in the practitioner.”

The standard of care which is required from the medical practitioners as laid down by McNair, J. in his direction to the jury in *Bolam v Friern Hospital Management Committee*⁵⁵ has been accepted by the House of Lords in a number of cases “But where you get a situation which involves the use of some special skill or competence, then the test as to whether there has been negligence or not is not the test of man on the top of a Clapham omnibus, because he has not got this special skill. The test is the standard of ordinary skilled man exercising and professing to have special skill. A man need not possess the highest expert skill; it is well established law that it is sufficient if he exercises the ordinary skill of an ordinary competent man exercising that art”.

The *Bolam* case summary is as follows,

In this case the plaintiff, John Bolam, was a psychiatric patient suffering depressive illness. He was advised by Dr de Bastarrechea, a consultant psychiatrist attached to Friern Hospital, to undergo electro-convulsive therapy (E.C.T.). He signed a consent form but was not warned about the risk of fracture that can occur because of fit-like convulsions that such treatment induces. In due course, he received this treatment but was not given any relaxant drugs. As a consequence, he suffered several injuries. These included dislocation of hip joints and fractures to the pelvis on both sides caused by the femur on both sides being driven through the cup of the pelvis. The plaintiff claimed that the doctor was negligent in not giving him relaxant drugs. By not doing so, the doctor also failed to provide adequate physical restraints to prevent the injury. He also claimed that the doctor had failed to warn him of the risks involved in the treatment. The judge, however, found the doctor not guilty of negligence as he had acted in accordance with a practice accepted as proper by a responsible body of medical men skilled in that particular area. Expert witness called by either side gave evidence as to the different techniques which they adopted in

⁵⁵ *Bolam v Friern Hospital Management Committee* (1957) 2 All ER 118; 1957, 1 WLR 582

giving E.C.T treatment; some used relaxant drugs, some used restraining sheets and some used manual control, but all agreed that there was a firm body of medical specialists who opposed to the use of relaxant drugs.

In an action for negligence in tort against a surgeon, the Supreme Court Held ⁵⁶ “The duties which a doctor owes to his patient are clear. A person who holds himself out ready to give medical advice and treatment impliedly undertakes that he is possessed of skill and knowledge for the purpose. Such a person when consulted by a patient owes him certain duties, viz., a duty of care in deciding whether to undertake the case, a duty of care in deciding what treatment to give or duty of care in administration of that treatment. A breach of any of those duties gives right of action for negligence to the patient.”

Before the enforcement of the Consumer Protection Act, the field of medical negligence was inevitably governed only by law of Torts. The precise definition of negligence is perhaps not possible and it would remain a somewhat slippery word. The classic attempted judicial definitions of negligence may be noticed from the authoritative treatise of Salmond ⁵⁷ as under.

“Negligence in the objective sense that is in the well known definition of Alderson B. “the omission to do something which a reasonable man, guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulate the conduct of human affairs, would do, or doing something which a prudent and reasonable man would not do.”

The law relating to medical negligence finds its genesis in the common law principle of negligence and was further developed by the judicial pronouncements in the western world. In India also the legal development took place similarly since one of the first reported judgments in a case of medical negligence dates back to 1969, i.e., case of Laxman *Balkrishna Joshi v Triambak Babu Godbole*⁵⁸, wherein the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India dealt in detail about the principles involved in medical negligence and further elaborated the duties of doctors and also the patients.

⁵⁶ 1969(1) SCR 206

⁵⁷ Salmond, LAW OF TORTS, Sweet & Maxwell; 21st Revised edition (24 Oct 1996)

⁵⁸ 1968 ACJ 183 (SC): AIR 1969 SC 128: 1969 (1) SCR 206

Madras High Court had taken a different view about the application of consumer concept to the medical field. It was held that the services rendered to a patient by a medical practitioner or by a hospital by way of diagnosis and treatment, both medicinal and surgical, would not come within the definition of 'service' under section 2(1) (o) Of the Consumer Protection Act and the patient cannot be considered to be a consumer within the meaning of Section 2(1) (d) of the same Act.⁵⁹

The Supreme Court put forth a number of conclusions in the historical judgment, in *Indian Medical Association v V.P.Shantha & Ors.* ⁶⁰While applying the Consumer Protection Act to the medical profession,

- Service rendered to a patient by a medical practitioner would fall within the ambit of 'service' as defined in section 2(1)(o) of the CPA.
- The service rendered by a medical practitioner to be considered to a contract for personal service and that comes within the purview of the CPA
- Services rendered free of charge would not attract the provisions of this Act.

Deficiency ⁶¹

According to Section 2(l) (g) of the CPA, 'deficiency' means any fault, imperfection, shortcoming, or inadequacy in the quality, nature, and manner of performance which is required to be maintained, by or under any law for the time being in force, or has been undertaken to be performed by a person, in pursuance of a contract or otherwise, in relation to any service.

In the context of the medical profession, deficiency means that the treatment provided by the medical practitioner is not correct or not according to accepted medical standards. Deficiency of service may also include treatment by using faulty instruments, lack of ICU or ambulance services, etc. Deficiency of service under the CPA is almost equal to medical negligence under the law of torts. There can be deficiency of service even without any harm or injury to the patient. For example, refusal to give treatment record

⁵⁹Dr. C.S.Subramanian v Kumarswamy & Anr. (1994) 1 MLJ 438

⁶⁰ AIR 1996 SC 550: 1995 (6) SCC 651:1995(3) CPJ 1(SC): 1995(3) CPR 412(SC)

⁶¹ Tapas Kumar Koley, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND THE LAW IN INDIA: INTRODUCTION, 1st edition, Oxford University Press, 2010, pp.139-141

or payment receipt by the medical professional or healthcare institution may be considered as deficiency of service.⁶²

Service

According to Section 2(l)(o) of CPA, 'service' means service of any description which is made available to potential users and includes, but not limited to, the provision of facilities in connection with banking, financing, insurance, transport, processing, supply of electrical or other energy, board or lodging or both, housing construction, entertainment, amusement or the purveying of news or other information, but does not include the rendering of any service free of charge or under a contract of personal service.

Therefore now in the medical profession, treatment given by a medical professional or health care institution will be considered service under the Act. Besides medical care, other services provided for patients like ambulance services, are also included in this definition. Almost all types of service that a patient gets, right from getting inside the hospital till he/she leaves the hospital, are considered service and any shortcoming in this regard will be considered deficiency of service. The negligence of medical professionals comes within the definition of deficiency in service.

In the *IMA* case, the Supreme Court held,

The definition of services in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act can be split up into three parts - the main part, the inclusionary part and the exclusionary part. The main part is explanatory in nature and defines service to mean service of any description which is made available to the potential users. The inclusionary part expressly includes the provision of facilities in connection with banking, financing, insurance, transport, processing, supply of electrical or other energy, board or lodging or both housing construction, entertainment, amusement or the purveying of news or other information. The exclusionary part excludes rendering of any service free of charge or under a contract of personal services. The inclusive part of the definition of 'service' is not applicable and one is required to deal with the questions falling for consideration in the light of the main part and the exclusionary part of the definition. The exclusionary part will require consideration only if it is found that in the matter of consultation, diagnosis and treatment a medical practitioner or a hospital/nursing home renders a service falling within the main part of the definition

⁶² Id.

contained in Section 2(l)(o) of the Act. One has, therefore, to determine whether medical practitioners and hospitals/ nursing homes can be regarded as rendering a "service" as contemplated in the main part of Section 2(1) (o).⁶³

The Learned Judges concluded in *IMA* case as follows.⁶⁴

(1) Service rendered to a patient by a medical practitioner (except where the doctor renders service free of charge to every patient or under a contract of personal service), by way of consultation, diagnosis and treatment, both medicinal and surgical, would fall within the ambit of 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act.

(2) The fact that medical practitioners belong to the medical profession and are subject to the disciplinary control of the Medical Council of India and/or State Medical Councils constituted under the provisions of the Indian Medical Council Act would not exclude the services rendered by them from the ambit of the Act.

(3) A 'contract of personal service' has to be distinguished from a 'contract for personal services'. In the absence of a relationship of master and servant between the patient and medical practitioner, the service rendered by a medical practitioner to the patient cannot be regarded as service rendered under a 'contract of personal service'. Such service is service rendered under a 'contract for personal services' and is not covered by exclusionary clause of the definition of 'service' contained in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act.

(4) The expression 'contract of personal service' in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act cannot be confined to contracts for employment of domestic servants only and the said expression would include the employment of a medical officer for the purpose of rendering medical service to the employer. The service rendered by a medical officer to his employer under the contract of employment would be outside the purview of 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act.

(5) Service rendered free of charge by a medical practitioner attached to a hospital/Nursing home or a medical officer employed in a hospital/Nursing home where such services are rendered free of charge to everybody, would not be

⁶³AIR 1996 SC 550, para. 17.

⁶⁴ Indian Kanoon - <http://indiankanoon.org/doc/723973/>

"service" as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act. The payment of a token amount for registration purpose only at the hospital/nursing home would not alter the position.

(6) Service rendered at a non-Government hospital/Nursing home where no charge whatsoever is made from any person availing the service and all patients (rich and poor) are given free service - is outside the purview of the expression 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act. The payment of a token amount for registration purpose only at the hospital/Nursing home would not alter the position.

(7) Service rendered at a non-Government hospital/Nursing home where charges are required to be paid by the persons availing such services falls within the purview of the expression 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act.

(8) Service rendered at a non-Government hospital/Nursing home where charges are required to be paid by persons who are in a position to pay and persons who cannot afford to pay are rendered service free of charge would fall within the ambit of the expression 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act irrespective of the fact that the service is rendered free of charge to persons who are not in a position to pay for such services.

Free service, would also be "service" and the recipient a "consumer" under the Act.

(9) Service rendered at a Government hospital/health centre/dispensary where no charge whatsoever is made from any person availing the services and all patients (rich and poor) are given free service - is outside the purview of the expression 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act. The payment of a token amount for registration purpose only at the hospital/nursing home would not alter the position.

(10) Service rendered at a Government hospital/health centre/dispensary where services are rendered on payment of charges and also rendered free of charge to other persons availing such services would fall within the ambit of the expression 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act irrespective of the fact that the service is rendered free of charge to persons who do not pay for such service. Free service would also be "service" and the recipient a "consumer" under the Act.

(11) Service rendered by a medical practitioner or hospital/nursing home cannot be regarded as service rendered free of charge, if the person availing the service has taken an insurance policy for medical care where under the charges for consultation, diagnosis and medical treatment are borne by the insurance company and such

service would fall within the ambit of 'service' as defined in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act.

(12) Similarly, where, as a part of the conditions of service, the employer bears the expenses of medical treatment of an employee and his family members dependent on him, the service rendered to such an employee and his family members by a medical practitioner or a hospital/nursing home would not be free of charge and would constitute 'service' under Section 2(1) (o) of the Act.⁶⁵

Inclusion of Medical Services under the CPA

This is probably the most significant issue that was clarified by the Supreme Court in the *IMA* case. It removed all confusions prevailing initially regarding the inclusion of medical services under the purview of the Act. All types of medical services were brought under the purview of CPA.

The Supreme Court observed that medical practice is a profession rather than an occupation and medical professionals provide a service to the patients and thus they are not immune to the claim from damages on the ground of negligence. From this viewpoint the Court concluded that a patient can be a 'consumer' for the purpose of CPA. Besides this, the Court also observed that consumer protection was very well established in both the UK and the USA in the field of medical practice. The Supreme Court referred to the well-known book *Law and Medical Ethics*, by Mason and McCall Smith,⁶⁶ and *Arizona v. Maricopa County Medical Society*,⁶⁷ which is the leading case on price fixing in the health care industry. In that case it was held that the fixing of maximum prices for insured users of medical services constituted per se illegal price fixing under Section 1 of the Sherman Antitrust Act (1890). Considering all these facts the Supreme Court concluded as follows;

*We are, therefore, unable to subscribe to the view that merely because medical practitioners belong to the medical profession they are outside the purview of the provisions of the Act and the services rendered by medical practitioners are not covered by Section 2(1)(o) of the Act.*⁶⁸

⁶⁵ Id

⁶⁶ Fourth edition

⁶⁷ IMA case, para. 26

⁶⁸ IMA case, para. 26

After this judgment, majority of medical negligence cases in India are filed in consumer courts under the Act. The Indian Medical Association had put forward many arguments in its attempt to persuade the Court that doctors should not be brought under the purview of the CPA. All the arguments were taken up by the Court and clear rulings were given.

In the case of *Vinitha Ashok V Laxmi Hospital & Ors*⁶⁹, within the consumer jurisdiction the matter was summed up in the following terms “it is clear that the law does not require that a doctor in the discharge of his duty of care should use the highest degree of skill since they may never be acquired. It is enough for the doctor to show that he acted in accordance with the general and approved practice.....”

In another case in the consumer jurisdiction, Justice Shah opined that, “in any treatment it is never claimed by the medical profession that every person who receives the treatment must and should be benefited by the same because the benefit of a particular type of system or operation or medicine depends upon a number of factors.....”⁷⁰

Since the application of the Consumer Protection Act to the medical field, a number of legal principles have been postulated in various judgments by the consumer courts. The legal system has so far shown remarkable maturity in dealing with complicated technical issues based on expert opinion, standard textbook reference and other evidence. The Court has held that all complaints being brought about deficiency in service based on the ground of negligence in rendering medical services, do not involve complicated questions requiring of evidence of experts. It is now presumed that intricate technical questions of medical negligence requiring expert witnesses to be summoned and cross-examination conducted would have to be referred to civil courts. In the case of *Bhavchandbhai Manjibhai Lakhani v Dr. Bhupendra D Sagar*,⁷¹ the consumer forum has, with help of expert witness cross-examination, held a medical practitioner negligent.

⁶⁹ . AIR 2001 SC 3914: 2001 (8) JT 142: 2001(4) Supreme 225: 2001(6) SLT 735

⁷⁰ .Shri Ram Singh Parmar v Mr.Sampat Raj C Shah & Anr, 1993 (2) CPR 496 (Guj. SCDRC)

⁷¹ . Complaint no.378 of 1991, decided on 26-8-1993 (Guj. SCDRC) Unreported

From the analysis of the literature it is observed that, there is no comprehensive empirical study or any triangular study on the application of CPA on doctors. There has not been any analytical or comparative study or any local study on the trends emerging out of inclusion of doctors in CPA. Critical evaluation on any variable or influencing factor also does not exist. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a thorough research in order to locate these trends at the local, state and national level. Further, there is a need to assess the response of the professionals and the changing nature of doctor-patient relationship in post-CPA period. Moreover, the resistance of IMC also requires to be put in context.

Further, the researcher has a personal pain area of being a litigant and also has observed the ignorance of medical professionals about the working of this law. Thus, the research on trends and changing trends with reference to Medical negligence is designed.

Trend

A 'trend' can be defined by various ways; the accepted definitions of the trend are as follows:

1. A general direction in which something is developing or changing.⁷²
2. A gradual change or development that produces result.⁷³
3. A general tendency in the way a situation is changing or developing⁷⁴
4. A pattern of gradual change in a condition, output, or process, or an average or general tendency of a series of data points to move in a certain direction over time, represented by a line or curve on a graph.⁷⁵

The study of changes taking place after the application of the Consumer Protection Act to the Medical Field, will define the trend in this particular 'Law' and thus being studied by the researcher.

Law

⁷² Available at <http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/trend>

⁷³ Available at <http://www.macmillandictionary.com/dictionary/british/trend>

⁷⁴ Available at <http://www.ldoceonline.com/dictionary/trend>

⁷⁵ Available at <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/trend.html#ixzz2LokXsx1G>

In order to define and study the trends in the “Law” of Medical Negligence under Consumer Protection Act, the term law means:

1. [*mass noun*] (often the law) the system of rules which a particular country or community recognizes as regulating the actions of its members and which it may enforce by the imposition of penalties:⁷⁶
2. The principles and regulations established in a community by some authority and applicable to its people, whether in the form of legislation or of custom and policies recognized and enforced by judicial decision.⁷⁷

Though there is no exact “Law of Medical Negligence”, the laws Governing Medical Negligence like Law of Torts, Criminal Law and Consumer Law has been taken as laws of medical negligence. With these concepts fixed as the basis for the framework, the following objectives are identified.

1.4. Objectives

To study the concept of the Law of Medical Negligence, the objectives of this study can be defined as follows-

1. To study the concept of medical Negligence as a whole under various Indian laws, including case laws and legislation, *inter alia*, decisions of Medical Councils related to the cases of Medical Negligence, Law of Torts, Criminal law, law of Contract, Medical council Act and Consumer Protection Act.
2. To identify and analyze the Changing Trends in the Law of Medical Negligence in India and its impact.
3. To study the comparative position of the law in this regard with reference to foreign laws, to explore the linkages with the International approach towards Medical Negligence.

⁷⁶ Available at <http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/law>

⁷⁷ Available at <http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/law>

1.5 Research Questions

1. How is the Concept of Medical Negligence defined under various laws in India and abroad?
2. What are the various trends visible in the approach towards Medical Negligence in India and abroad?
3. What are the parameters of Consumer Protection that determine the nexus between Medical Negligence and its consequences under Consumer Protection Act? Should the Consumer Protection Act continue to govern it in India?

1.6 Scope of the Study

The concept of medical Negligence has been studied as a whole under various Indian Laws; Law of Torts, Criminal law, law of Contract, Medical council Act and Consumer Protection Act The judgments of various case laws under the Consumer Protection Act are studied from the beginning up to March 2013 combining local trends in Pune and aligning them with state and national trends. The current and Changing Trends in the law of Medical Negligence under various laws and foreign laws are observed and postulate to predict the further changes. The study and evaluation of the lacunae in the Consumer Protection Act and its implementation, have guided the corrective measures that can be recommended. The study of International approach towards the Medical Negligence provided, by studying foreign case laws, thus locating International Trends in the Medical Negligence.

1.7 Methodology

This mixed methods study has addressed the, “Changing Trends in the law of Medical Negligence under Consumer Protection Act 1986”. A triangulation; Mixed Methods Design: Convergence Variant ⁷⁸ was used, a type of design in which different but complementary Data are collected on the same topic. This is the

⁷⁸John Creswell, Vicky L.Plano Clark, DESIGNING AND CONDUCTING MIXED METHODS RESEARCH, Sage Publications,2007, Pp. 64

combination of the result of more than two rigorous approaches conducted to provide a more comprehensive picture of the results than either approach could do alone.⁷⁹

In this study, the Quantitative Instruments, through 31 identified variables that affect the concept of Medical Negligence are used to establish the Theory of Changing Trends in the Law of Medical Negligence. There is an analysis of case laws of Supreme Court obtained as doctrinal data, the decided cases from National Commission from its website as well as MCI Guidelines and Bill as primary data and locally-generated 10 selective cases of Pune appealed at the State Commission as primary data are analyzed and are finally compared.

Also, there is a pure empirical data based component that studies the perception of the affected sections of Society, i.e., the Doctors, Hospital Administrators and Community members in Pune by tool of questionnaires.

Questionnaire for 427 Doctors, Specialists, Super specialists and 41 Hospital Administrators from Pune and Questionnaire for 428 Community Members from Pune⁸⁰

Further, structured schedule was used as a tool to Interview experts such as Prof Graeme Laurie of Edinburgh Law School, Scotland.UK⁸¹, along with 24 doctors, Specialists and 20 community members.⁸²

The tools for the research are the ones used to collect data for both the Doctrinal and Empirical research.

Tools for Doctrinal Research: The case laws decided at Supreme Court available at <http://judis.nic.in> and National Commission available at the website of National Commission www.confonet.in and various books available.

⁷⁹ Abbas Tashakkori&Charles Teddlie, PRINCIPLES OF MIXED METHODS AND MULTIMETHOD RESEARCH DESIGN,2003 edition; HANDBOOK OF MIXED METHODS IN SOCIAL AND BEHAVIOURAL RESEARCH, 2003edition, pp.190.

⁸⁰ Annexure V

⁸¹ See Annexure VII

⁸² See Annexure, V

The case laws were analyzed for 31 variables and their interrelationships.⁸³

Tools for Empirical Research included the following:

- a. Questionnaire for Awareness of Doctors
- b. Questionnaire for Awareness of Community
- c. Questionnaire for Awareness of Hospital Administrators
- d. Interview Schedule for Judges and Medical Law Experts
- e. Case Studies 10 from Pune District Forum that are in Appeal at State Consumer Redressal Commission, Mumbai.

Concurrently, Qualitative methods are used in Surveys of Doctors, Hospital Administrators and Community; and Case laws including 10 cases from Pune District Consumer Forum that approached State and National Commission are used to explore the Changing Trends in the Law of Medical Negligence. The reason for collecting both quantitative and qualitative data is to bring together the strengths of both forms of research to corroborate results.

This Convergence study has defined what similarities and the differences exist across levels of analysis. The study was a concurrent one and was conducted in a Single phase. During the study, an attempt was made, to assess different aspects of reasoning that led to the postulations of various legal principles applied under the Consumer Protection Act.

The researcher has specifically studied foreign case laws on Medical Negligence, in order to compare the similarities and differences. The comparative study of all the case laws is being utilized to evaluate the changing trends in the law of medical negligence.

- Study of Indian and Foreign scenario
- Study of MCI guidelines

⁸³ See Annexure VI

Further, diagrammatic overview of the methodology follows:

Triangulation design

Triangulation Design: Convergence model

Creswell John W, Clark Vicky L Plano, 2007, Designing and Conducting mixed methods Research, Sage Publications , P63

Figure 2

Visual Diagram: Diagrammatical Representation of Methodology

Figure 3

Details

A: Doctrinal Study

Variables for Quantitative Analysis of Case Laws were designed and developed after thorough conceptualization and theoretical study on medical negligence laws.

Sample

The study sample consisted of 40 case laws of Supreme Court and 300 case laws of the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission (hereinafter National Commission) from its inception till March 2013. The cases were selected from the web sources, www.judis.nic.in and www.confonet.in based on the cause of action- "Medical Negligence". The method for the cases section was Purposive sampling, as by March 2013, the number of cases available from Supreme Court was 40 from all available resources. Similarly the total number of cases available from National Commission was 300 from all available resources. So these sample Case laws selected belong to Universal data. Total Universe of Medical Negligence Case law data available till March 2013 was studied for the purpose of research.

Development of variables

After studying the case laws, 31 variables were developed. These are developed by reading and analyzing various concepts from the articles on the topic. The variables are based on the relationship of various factors with the Medical Negligence. Coding was planned and coding was done for all the variables for the samples selected from case laws. Statistical analysis was done after the coding of all the case laws.

Validity

Validity means the researcher can draw meaningful inferences from the results to a population.

Reliability

Reliability means that scores received from participants are consistent and stable over time.⁸⁴

B: Empirical Study

Design and Development of scale: Sample

The study sample consisted of 427 doctors, 41 hospital administrators and 428 Community members constituted the random sample. Three scales were designed to collect the information related to the construct “Concept of Medical Negligence defined under various laws in India and abroad”

Broad themes explored in the Questions for doctors and Hospital Administrators are as follows,

- Awareness about CPA
- Awareness about Trend Setting Cases
- Knowledge of Concepts of Medical Negligence and Deficiency in Service
- Knowledge of *Bolam* and *Bolitho* Principles
- Awareness of MCI Regulations
- Legal Concepts of Valid Consent, Prior Informed Concept and Doctor Patient Relationship
- Knowledge of Professional Indemnity Insurance
- Knowledge the concepts of Evidence Based Medicine, Treatment Protocols
- Knowledge Concepts of Vicarious Liability, Second Opinion and Documentation
- Personal Opinion about applicability of CPA to Medical Field , Impact of CPA and Alternatives

Broad themes explored in the Community Questionnaire are as follows,

- Awareness about CPA

⁸⁴ Abbas Tashakkori & Charles Teddlie, PRINCIPLES OF MIXED METHODS AND MULTIMETHOD RESEARCH DESIGN, 2003 edition; HANDBOOK OF MIXED METHODS IN SOCIAL AND BEHAVIOURAL RESEARCH, 2003 edition, pp.190. and after discussion with Dr.K.P.Suresh, Scientist (Biostatistics), Project Directorate on Animal Disease Monitoring and Surveillance, Bangalore-560024

- Own Experience about Medical Treatment
- Opinion about the applicability of CPA to doctors
- Impact of CPA on Doctors and Doctor Patient Relationship
- Trust in Doctors and Need of Second Opinion.

Technique and Procedure

The objective of developing a scale is to create a valid measure of an underlying construct. The theoretical principles, practical issues, and pragmatic decisions must be considered in construct validity of scales and the subscales. It is essential to conceptualize on the content of the scale and the initial item pool should include items representing all the subsections of the scale, if any.

The method of wording the content and formulation of the statements need careful attention. The item pool should be later tested, along with variables and the objectives of the study to assess closely related constructs, on a heterogeneous sample representing the entire range of the target population.⁸⁵ Finally, in selecting scale items, the goal is uni-dimensionality rather than internal consistency; this means that virtually all inter -item correlations should be moderate in magnitude.

Validity: It is the most important consideration when developing, evaluating and interpreting tests. It refers to the appropriateness, meaningfulness, and usefulness of the specific inferences researchers make based on the data they collect. Validity has been described as 'the agreement between a test score or measure and the quality it is believed to measure'⁸⁶.It is the most important step to be considered when preparing or selecting an instrument for research study and the degree to which evidence and theory support the interpretations of test scores entailed by the proposed test.

⁸⁵Suresh K.P. and Chandrasekhar S (2012).Sample Size estimation and Power analysis for Clinical research studies. Journal Human Reproduction Science,5(1), 7-13.

⁸⁶ Bernard Rosner (2000), Fundamentals of Biostatistics, 5th Edition, Duxbury, page 80-240 ;Kaplan and Jacuzzi, 2001

Creation of item pool and face validity:

Once the objectives and the content domain were tentatively identified, the task of formulating the items /questions for the scale was completed. The formulation of the initial pool of items related to the various domains is a crucial task for developing the scale. The fundamental goal at this juncture is to formulate all content systematically in a sequential manner that is potentially relevant to the target construct. The importance of the initial literature review becomes quite obvious in this process. Loevinger (1957) offered the classic articulation of this process: "The items of the pool should be chosen so as to sample all possible contents which might comprise the putative trait according to all known alternative theories of the trait ".

For the present study the items / questions reviewed from books, journals and electronic media were identified, adapted and compiled in framing of 100 items for doctors and administrators and 20 items for community members that covered the aspects of Concept of Medical Negligence defined under various laws in India and abroad” on a five -points Likert scale – 1: Strongly disagree, 2: Disagree, 3: Neutral, 4: Agree and 5: Strongly agree.

Content Validity: Content Validity is based on the extent to which a measurement reflects the specific intended domain of content⁸⁷. It refers to the conceptualization of the statements for developing the scale for the study. If the researcher has focused in too closely on only one type or narrow dimension of a construct or concept, then it is conceivable that other indicators are overlooked. In such a case, the study lacks content validity. An estimate of content validity of a test⁸⁸ is obtained by thoroughly and systematically examining the test items to determine the extent to which they reflect and do not reflect the content domain.

⁸⁷ Robert H Riffenburg (2005), STATISTICS IN MEDICINE, second edition, Academic press. 85-125;Carmines & Zeller, 1991

⁸⁸ Griner PF, Mayewski RJ, Mushlin AI, Greenland P (1981) SELECTION AND INTERPRETATION OF DIAGNOSTIC TESTS AND PROCEDURES., Annals of Internal Medicine, 94, 555-600

For the present study, the individual statement was drawn from a large pool of items that covered Concept of Medical Negligence defined under various laws in India and abroad. The developed scale was assessed for both face and content validity by a panel of experts from the field of Medical professionals, Community and Hospital administrators. All the items pooled were subjected to face, screened to have 70 for Doctors and Administrators and 15 for Community members. The scales of 70 items and 15 items respectively were further subjected to content validity with 3 panels of experts. The experts were requested to score each item in scale as 1 for not relevant and 10 for not relevant in a 10- point scale. The Scoring pattern obtained by experts analyzed using the AIKEN`s Index. The items which satisfied Aiken`s Index more than 0.70 were included in the scale otherwise it removed. The following procedure in eight steps of Aiken`s V index for content validity are as follows.⁸⁹

- n experts rate the degree to which the item taps an objective on a 1 to c on Likert-scale, where c is the maximum score in grading scale
- Let lo = the lowest possible validity rating (usually, this is 1 on the Likert-scale)
- Let r = the rating by an expert
- Let s = r – lo
- Let S = the sum of s for the n raters
- Aiken`s V is then $V = S / [n*(c-1)]$

Construct validity is done with evidence that the test measures what it purports to measure as well as evidence that the test does not measure irrelevant attributes are both required.

Readability Test: For the present study, 57 items for Doctors/Administrators and 10 items for community items were formulated for studying the Concept of Medical Negligence defined under various laws in India and abroad. After the tool was developed, a draft copy of the tool was prepared and was tested for readability by the investigator so as to ensure that the items of the tool did not have double barrel

⁸⁹ Sunder Rao P S S , Richard J(2006) : AN INTRODUCTION TO BIOSTATISTICS, A MANUAL FOR STUDENTS IN HEALTH SCIENCES , New Delhi: Prentice hall of India. 4th edition, 86-160; Aiken, 1980

questions, the items were not contradicting in nature and also further to ensure that there was no repetition of any items with similar meanings.

Reliability is the extent to which a test or procedure produces similar results under constant conditions on all occasions. For the present study, test- retest method was used to assess the reliability of the instruments. The following reliability test was carried out to estimate the reliability.

Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted on sub sample of 50 doctors and hospital administrators; and 50 community members. The Pilot study ensured that the items in the scales were made easy, understandable by respondents, flexible for administration of scale; the reliability measure such as Spilt-half reliability was performed to know the reliability of scales and Cron bach Alpha was also performed on the pilot study results to find the uni-dimensionality of scales.

The scale for measuring the Concept of Medical Negligence defined under various laws in India and abroad for doctors and administrators consisted of 57 and 10 items for community members finally constructed after meeting criteria of face validity, Content validity and reliability measures. Scales were subjected to Pilot study with sample of 50 doctors/administrators and 50 community members for measuring the spilt-half reliability. The Spilt-half reliability measures shown that, Scale for doctors/administrators has reliability co-efficient of 0.869 and 0.804 respectively and for community it was 0.82. The Cron bach alpha for consistency and uni-dimensionality were 0.806 and 0.791 respectively for the scale of doctors and administrators and 0.911 for the scale of community members. Hence the developed scale was more reliable and valid.

1.8 Limitation

This research study is limited by the jurisdiction which is limited to Pune. Though overall the case laws at National Commission have been studied, actual study of live cases and the awareness survey of Doctors and Patients are restricted to Pune District. Also, the case laws study is restricted to the time from the application of the Consumer Protection Act to the Medical Field i.e. 1987 to present i.e. 2013.. Thus the researcher has studied the trends in the said for the period of about 25 years, but local study is restricted to the Pune District.

Since the concept of Medical Negligence is a complicated issue, is more than a matter between two parties- it is also a political issue.⁹⁰ A subdivision of common law that has engaged the attention of civil courts, in particular consumer forums, for last few decades is 'negligence', especially that of medical professionals. Litigation arising from death or serious physical injury that a patient suffers as a result of negligence in their treatment by medical professional has overburdened courts. It has spread through India like an epidemic, without showing any signs of passing.⁹¹

The next chapter elaborates the concept of Medical Negligence as a whole, extracted and analyzed from various branches of law in India and across the world.

⁹⁰ Mason J.K. ,Laurie GT 2006, LIABILITY FOR MEDICAL INJURY, Law and Medical Ethics, p.296

⁹¹ Tapas Kumar Koley, 2010 MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND THE LAW IN INDIA, Medical Negligence and Civil Laws, p 21

Chapter 2

CONCEPT OF MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AN OVERVIEW

"Knowing is not enough: We must apply"

"Willing is not enough: We must do".

McGeer

“Discourage litigation; persuade your neighbours to compromise whenever you can. Point out to them how the nominal winner is often a loser in fees, expenses and cost of time.”

*Abraham Lincoln*⁹²

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The idea of negligence in medical profession overshadows its credibility. First key concept in this design is medical negligence and it requires greater analysis as discussed further. The service which medical professionals render to us is the noblest. Aryans embodied the rule that, Vaidyo narayano harihi (which means doctors are equivalent to Lord Vishnu). Professionals like doctors, lawyers, etc. are in the category of persons professing special skills. Any man practicing a profession requires particular level of learning, which impliedly assures a person dealing with him, that he possesses such requisite knowledge, expertise and will profess his skill with reasonable degree of care and caution. It should be taken in to consideration that the professional should command the “corpus of knowledge” of his profession. Since long the medical profession is highly respected, but today a decline in the standard of the medical profession can be attributed to increasing number of litigations against doctors for being negligent narrowing down to “medical negligence”.⁹³

Lately, Indian society is experiencing a growing awareness regarding patient's rights. This trend is clearly discernible from the recent spurt in litigation concerning medical professional or establishment liability, claiming redressal for the suffering caused due to medical negligence, vitiated consent, and breach of confidentiality arising out of the doctor-patient relationship. The patient-centered initiative of rights protection is required to be appreciated in the economic context of the rapid decline of State spending and massive private investment in the sphere of the health care system and the Indian Supreme Court's painstaking efforts to constitutionalize a right to health as a fundamental right. As of now, the adjudicating process with regard to medical professional liability, be it in a consumer forum or a regular civil or criminal

⁹²Puteri Nemiebt.JahnKassim,MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE LITIGATION IN MALAYSIA:CURRENT TREND AND PROPOSALS FOR REFORM ,2004,mdm.org.my/downloads/dr_puteri_nemie.pdf , pp. 64, last accessed Oct. 7,2012f

⁹³ Shounak Mitra, Supreme Court and Medical Negligence Necessary Protection, Feb.22,2008 – www.legalserviceindia.com/article/1178-Medical-Negligence.html

court, considers common law principles relating to negligence, vitiated consent, and breach of confidentiality. However, it is equally essential to note that the protection of patient's right shall not be at the cost of professional integrity and autonomy. There is definitely a need for striking a delicate balance. Otherwise, the consequences would be inexplicable.⁹⁴

In the context of obtaining processes, there is a deserving need for a two-pronged approach. On one hand, the desirable direction points towards identification of minimum reasonable standards in light of the social, economical, and cultural context that would facilitate the adjudicators to decide issues of professional liability on an objective basis. On the other hand, such identification enables the medical professionals to internalize such standards in their day-to-day discharge of professional duties, which would hopefully prevent to a large extent the scenario of protection of patient's rights in a litigative atmosphere. In the long run, the present adversarial placement of doctor and the patient would undergo a transformation to the advantage of the patient, doctor, and society at large. Professional negligence, more specifically, medical negligence is, as the term suggests, relates to the medical profession and is the result of some irregular conduct on the part of any member of the profession or related service in discharge of professional duties. But first of all it is essential to analyze what the terms remedy, legal right, legal, duty and most importantly negligence mean.⁹⁵

Negligence is the breach of a legal duty to care. Thus legal duty of a person means the duty the law gives to every person to respect the legal rights of the other. Therefore the legal right of a person can be defined as the provision provided by law to protect the interests of its citizen. We must remember then that where there is a legal right, there is a legal remedy for it. This is inferred from the maxim "*ubi jus ibi remedium*".⁹⁶

Negligence is a breach of duty caused by omission to do something which a reasonable man guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulate the

⁹⁴ SV JOGA RAO, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE LIABILITY UNDER THE CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT: A REVIEW OF JUDICIAL PERSPECTIVE, 2009 , Volume : 25 , Issue : 3 , pp.361-371

⁹⁵ Id.

⁹⁶ .An Introduction To Corporate Regulation and Standardization, legal.practitioner.com/regulation/standards_9_3_6.htm

contract of human affairs would do which a prudent and reasonable man would not do. According to Charlesworth & Percy⁹⁷ in current forensic speech, Negligence has three meanings. There are: (i) a state of mind, in which it is opposed to intention; (ii) careless conduct; and (iii) the breach of duty to take care that is imposed by either common or statute law. All three meanings are applicable in different circumstances but any one of them does not necessarily exclude the other meanings. The essential components of negligence, as recognized, are three: "duty", "breach" and "resulting damage", that is to say,

1. The existence of a duty to take care, which is owed by the defendant to the complainant.
2. The failure to attain that standard of care, prescribed by the law, thereby committing a breach of such duty; and
3. Damage, which is both causally connected with such breach and recognized by the law, has been suffered by the complainant. .⁹⁸

Medical negligence can be seen in various fields like when reasonable care is not taken during operations, during the diagnosis, during delivery of the child, with issues dealing with anesthesia etc. Since this field is very vast the researcher will limit to understanding the basic concepts which are essential for the negligence to be committed. He shall also look into the remedies that the law provides to these patients and on whom the burden of proof lies and when this burden of proof shifts to the other party. He would also be discussing the defenses used by doctors to rescue themselves from the liability and also compare all these things with the English law and also look into the similarities that the Indian law and English law share.⁹⁹

NATURE OF MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE

In the law of negligence, professionals such as lawyers, doctors, architects and others are included in the category of persons professing some special skill or skilled persons generally. Any task which is required to be performed with a special skill would generally be admitted or undertaken to be performed only if the person possesses the requisite skill for performing that task. Any reasonable man entering

⁹⁷ Negligence ,Tenth Edition, 2001

⁹⁸ Jacob Mathew v State of Punjab and Anr., Appeal (Crl.) 144-125 of 2004,decided on 5th August 2005, (2005) 6 SCC 1

⁹⁹ Vasuprabhat, Medical Negligence in India, December 3, 2011, legalservicesindia.com/article/print.php?art_id=944

into a profession which requires a particular level of learning to be called a professional of that branch, impliedly assures the person dealing with him that the skill which he professes shall be exercised with reasonable degree of care and caution. On the same analogy, this assures the patients that a doctor possesses the requisite skill in the medical profession which he is practicing and while undertaking the performance of the task entrusted to him he would be exercising his skill with reasonable competence. Judged by this standard, a professional including medical professional may be held liable for negligence on one of two findings: either he was not possessed of the requisite skill which he professed to have possessed, or, he did not exercise, with reasonable competence in the given case, the skill which he did possess.¹⁰⁰

COMPONENTS OF MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE¹⁰¹

Winfield stated that a negligent act comprises of three main components. They are,

- Existence of legal duty
- Breach of legal duty
- Damage caused by the breach

In order to understand the correct meaning of medical negligence it is essential that one carefully analyzes these components because only after one analyzes these components will we be able to understand the remedies that the law provides.

1. Existence of legal duty: Whenever a person approaches another trusting him to possess certain skill, or special knowledge on a given problem the second party is under an implied legal duty to exercise due diligence as is expected to act at least in such a manner as is expected in the ordinary course from his contemporaries. So it is not that the legal duty can only be contractual and not otherwise. Failure on the part of such a person to do something which was incumbent so, that which would be just and reasonable tantamount to negligence. Every time a patient visits a doctor for his ailments he does not enter into any written contract but there is a contract by implication and any lack of proper care can make the erring doctor liable for breach of professional duty.

¹⁰⁰ AK Agarwal, Medical Negligence: Law and Interpretation, Mar. 3,2011, www.indianexpress.com/news/iima...for...medical-negligence/809105/

¹⁰¹ SnehaPatil, Medical Negligence- Necessary Protection Or Licence To Kill, 14 Aug 2008, www.legalserviceindia.com/article/I251-Medical-Negligence.htm

2. Breach of legal duty: There is a certainly a breach of legal duty if the person exercising the skill does something which an ordinary man would not have done or fails to do that which an ordinary prudent man would have done in a similar situation. The standards are not supposed to be of very high degree or otherwise, but just the relative kind, that is expected from the person in the ordinary course of treatment.

3. Damages caused by the breach: The wrong, the injury occasioned by such negligence is liable to be compensated in terms of money and the courts apply the well settled principles for determination of the exact liquidated amount. One must remember that no hard and fast rule can be laid down for universal application. While awarding compensation, the consumer forum has to take into account all relevant factors and assess compensation on the basis of accepted legal principles on moderation. It is for the consumer forum to decide whether the compensation awarded is reasonable, fair and proper according to the facts and circumstances of the case.

STANDARD OF CARE REQUIRED IN INDIA

There was considerable ambiguity on the standard of care required to be exercised by medical practitioners in order to discharge possible criminal liability arising out of their acts or omissions. Section 304-A of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 [IPC] prescribes punishment for death due to rash or negligent conduct of a person. It is under this section that doctors or other medical practitioners have generally been proceeded against under criminal law. Even though there is protection given to accidents caused during performance of lawful acts [Section 80, IPC] and acts not intended to cause death and done for the person's benefit by his consent and in good faith [Section 88, IPC], the fear of criminal liability has been lingering during the performance of their duty even today.¹⁰²

TESTS USED IN INDIA¹⁰³

In determining the test for medical negligence and prosecution of medical practitioners, the Supreme Court of India has also issued certain guidelines. What goes to the basis of these guidelines is that once a criminal investigation begins

¹⁰²Vasuprabhat, Medical Negligence in India, December 14, 2011
legalservicesindia.com/article/.../medical-negligence-in-india-944-1.h.

¹⁰³Id.

against a doctor, the loss of reputation is nearly irreversible. It has also been taken into account that since the nature of work that doctors perform is one involving public service, it is even more necessary that certain guidelines be issued in this regard.

1. Government of India along with the Medical Council of India should formulate certain rules/regulations etc to regulate aspects of negligence in medical practice. While this exercise is pending, the following guidelines must be kept in mind while prosecuting medical practitioners.

2. To make a case against a doctor, a private complainant has to submit evidence of a prima facie case before the authority taking cognizance of the act. Such authority must also include credible opinion given by another competent doctor to support his case.

3. The investigating officer must also, independently, obtain an impartial and unbiased opinion of a doctor who practices in the same field in the same regard.

4. The doctor concerned should not be arrested like in a regular prosecution. He may be arrested if there is a fear that the doctor will not make himself available for investigation.

Extended ambit of medical negligence ¹⁰⁴

The National Commission as well as the Apex Court in a catena of decisions has held that the doctor is not liable for negligence because of someone else of better skill or knowledge would have prescribed a different treatment or operated in a different way. He is not guilty of negligence if he has acted in accordance with the practice accepted as proper by a reasonable body of medical professionals.

¹⁰⁴ Judicial interpretation of medical negligence under consumer protection, Mar 08, 2012, www.articlesbase.com

In Supreme Court the land mark decision *Indian Medical Association Vs V.P. Shantha and Others* III (1995) C.P.J laid down certain guidelines for medical negligence and defines efficiency of consumer protection. It has held certain exception like

- Service rendered to patient in (free of cost or charity) by a medical professional would not fall under the definition of 'service' under consumer protection act 1986.
- Service rendered by a doctor under contract of personal service was not covered in consumer protection act 1986.

PROOF OF NEGLIGENCE

The principle of *Res-Ipsa-Loquitur* has not been generally followed by the Consumer Courts in India including the National Commission or even by the Apex Court in deciding the case under this Act. The Hon'ble Supreme Court¹⁰⁵ has held the above view that "All medical negligence cases concern various questions of fact, when we say burden of proving negligence lies on the Complainant, it means he has the task of convincing the court that his version of the facts is the correct one". In one case¹⁰⁶, National Commission held that expert opinion in medical negligence played an effective role.¹⁰⁷

2.2 EVOLUTION OF LAWS GOVERNING MEDICAL PRACTICE IN INDIA

With the awareness in the society and the people in general gathering consciousness about their rights, measures for damages in tort, civil suits and criminal proceedings are on the augment. Not only civil suits are filed, the accessibility of a medium for grievance redressal under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 (CPA), having jurisdiction to hear complaints against medical professionals for 'deficiency in service', has given rise to a large number of complaints against doctors, being filed by the persons feeling aggrieved. The criminal complaints are being filed against doctors alleging commission of offences punishable under Sec. 304A or Sections 336/337/338 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 (IPC) alleging rashness or negligence on the part of the doctors resulting in loss of life or injury of varying degree to the patient. This has given rise to a situation of great distrust and

¹⁰⁵ Dr. Laxman Balkrishna vs. Dr. Triambak, AIR 1969 Supreme Court p¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁶ Sethuraman Subramaniam Iyer vs. Triveni Nursing Home and anr., 1998 CTJ7

¹⁰⁷ S.V.Joga Rao, Medical negligence liability under the consumer protection act: A review of judicial perspective, 2009, Volume : 25 ,Issue : www.indianjurol.com/article.asp?issn=0970-1591;year

fear among the medical profession and a legal assurance, ensuring protection from unnecessary and arbitrary complaints, is the need of the hour. The liability of medical professionals must be clearly demarcated so that they can perform their benevolent duties without any fear of legal sword. At the same time, justice must be done to the victims of medical negligence and a punitive sting must be adopted in deserving cases. This is more so when the most sacrosanct right to life or personal liberty is at stake.¹⁰⁸

Medical laws in India are going through a process of evolution. As in England, medical negligence litigation is governed by the general principle of the law of torts. However, all these laws are under development at present, and they will change in future as well, according to the changes in similar laws existing in the UK and the USA. The majority of Indian medical professionals are unaware of these facts. The majority of them are not even aware of the term tort, under which medical negligence cases are tried in civil courts.¹⁰⁹

Under Indian law, the remedies available to a person seeking redress for medical malpractice are:

1. Suit for damages under the Civil Procedure Code,
2. Complaint for negligence under the Criminal Procedure Code,
3. Redressal under the Consumer Protection Act, and
4. Medical Council of India for disciplinary action.

Multiple grievance redress facilities often cause confusion in the mind of aggrieved patients. At present, however, they choose to file their case at the various consumer courts under CPA because it is the easiest way. Although there are so many grievance redress facilities, their methods of proving negligence of medical professional are quite similar.

The most radical change in the laws governing medical negligence was the introduction of the CPA in 1986. Under this Act the patients have been equated with consumers. Some significant recent judgments of the Supreme Court of India, like *Laxman Thamappa Kotgiri*

¹⁰⁸ Medico-Legal, Scientific Approach - Criminal Laws & Justice, www.legalserviceindia.com/medicolegal/medico.htm

¹⁰⁹ TAPAS KUMAR KOLEY, *Supra*, pp. xix

*v. G.M. Central Railway and Others*¹¹⁰ and *Kishore Lal v. Chairman, Employees' State Insurance Corporation*,¹¹¹ decided on 8 May 2007, as well as the judgment of the National Commission in *Jagdish Kumar Bajpai v. Union of India*,¹¹² which will be discussed in details in subsequent chapters, have clearly shown that the laws governing the medical practice have not yet been finalized. The landmark judgment of Apex Court of India in *Laxman Thamappa Kotgiri v. G.M. Central Railway and Others*¹¹³ has given the railway employees the right of consumers while availing treatment in a railway hospital free of cost. Similarly, the beneficiaries of ESI Corporation¹¹⁴ and CGHS¹¹⁵ have also received the right to sue the doctors working in ESI hospitals and CGHS approved hospitals and dispensaries even if the treatment is free of cost. This is in stark contrast to earlier judgments wherein free treatment was considered outside the purview of CPA.¹¹⁶ With the consumer movement gaining strength it will be unsurprising, if in the future, all patients receive the right to sue their doctors both in the government and the private sector irrespective of the mode of payment.¹¹⁷

The recent judgment of Supreme Court of India in *Samira Kohli v. Dr. Prabha Manchanda and Another*¹¹⁸ will definitely change the whole procedure of taking consent before a planned surgery. In this case, the doctor was held negligent as she failed to obtain proper informed consent and carried out the operation for removal of uterus. The Apex Court laid down guidelines regarding consent and forbade the surgeons from performing additional surgeries even if it was for the benefit of the patient without obtaining consent for it. This landmark case upholds the right of autonomy of the patient and clearly marks the end of the days of medical paternalism.

¹¹⁰ (2007) 4 SCC 596

¹¹¹ (2007) 4 SCC 579.

¹¹² Revision Petition No. 570 of 2002, decided by The National Commission on Oct. 20 2005.

¹¹³ (2007) 4 SCC 596

¹¹⁴ *Kishore Lal v. Chairman, Employees' State Insurance Corporation*, decided on 8 May 2007, (2007) 4 SCC 579

¹¹⁵ *Jagdish Kumar Bajpai v. Union of India*, Revision Petition No. 570 of 2002 decided by The National Commission on 20 October 2005, 2007 MLR 175

¹¹⁶ *Harbhajan Singh v. Dayanand Medical College*, 1994(1) CPR 518; *Additional Director, CGHS Pune v. Dr. R.C. Butani*, 1(1996) CPJ 255 (NCDRC).

¹¹⁷ *Supra* note 106

¹¹⁸ Appeal (civil) 1949 of 2004, decided on 16 January 2008, (2008) 2 SCC 1.

This judgment also points out the fact that the patients enjoy certain definite rights which a medical practitioner can not violate. Medical practitioners of our country have hardly ever been taught about the rights of a patient in their medical curriculum. It is now time that they must gain adequate knowledge about the rights of patient so that they do not violate them even unknowingly during their routine practice. They must take into cognizance the changes in doctor-patient relationship that have happened in the last few decades.

As far as criminal cases against doctors are concerned, they are mainly filed following the unnatural death of a patient under section 304A of the Indian Penal Code for a rash or negligent act not amounting to culpable homicide and carry a maximum imprisonment of two years, or a fine, or both. The recent Supreme Court of India judgments in *Jacob Mathew v. State of Punjab and Another*¹¹⁹ and *Dr. Suresh Gupta v. Govt of NCT of Delhi*¹²⁰ have to a great extent determined the laws governing criminal negligence suits against doctors. Since it has given guidelines for prosecuting medical professionals against the charges of criminal negligence, the medical professionals have breathed a sigh of relief. The investigating police officer will have to gather independent and competent medical opinion of a medical professional, preferably from government service, before proceeding against the doctor accused of negligence.

Medical negligence litigation is related to errors in medical practice which should never occur if the basic rules of clinical management are followed, clinical information is accurately recorded and analyzed, and there is appropriate communication with patients. When things go wrong, many patients or their relatives simply want an explanation, instead of taking any legal action, and, by providing explanations, hospitals can reduce the number of medical negligence lawsuits. Unfortunately, in-house grievance redress mechanisms are practically nonexistent in the majority of Indian hospitals.

¹¹⁹ Available at www.judis.nic.in, Criminal Appeal No. 144-145 of 2004 decided by the Supreme Court of India on 5 August 2005, (2005) 6 SCC 1

¹²⁰ Available at www.judis.inc.in, Appeal (crl.) 778 of 2004, decided on 4 August 2004, (2005)6 SCC 422.

2.3 TORT LAW-CIVIL LAWS

As an authority¹²¹ describes, Negligence is the breach of a legal duty to care. It means carelessness in a matter in which the law mandates carefulness. A breach of this duty gives a patient the right to initiate action against negligence.

Persons who offer medical advice and treatment implicitly state that they have the skill and knowledge to do so, that they have the skill to decide whether to take a case, to decide the treatment, and to administer that treatment. This is known as an “implied undertaking” on the part of a medical professional. In the case of the *State of Haryana v Smt.Santra*¹²², the Supreme Court held that every doctor “has a duty to act with a reasonable degree of care and skill”. Doctors in India may be held liable for their services individually or vicariously unless they come within the exceptions specified in the case of *Indian Medical Association v V P Santha*¹²³. Doctors are not liable for their services individually or vicariously if they do not charge fees. Thus free treatment at a non-government hospital, governmental hospital, health centre, dispensary or nursing home would not be considered a “service” as defined in Section 2 (1) (0) of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986.¹²⁴

However, no human being is perfect and even the most renowned specialist could make a mistake in detecting or diagnosing the true nature of a disease. A doctor can be held liable for negligence only if one can prove that she/ he is guilty of a failure that no doctor with ordinary skills would be guilty of if acting with reasonable care¹²⁵. An error of judgment constitutes negligence only if a reasonably competent professional with the standard skills that the defendant professes to have, and acting with ordinary care, would *not* have made the same error¹²⁶.

In a key decision on this matter in the case of *Dr. Laxman Balkrishna Joshi v Dr.Trimbak Bapu Godbole*,¹²⁷ the Supreme Court held that if a doctor has adopted a

¹²¹ K K S R Murthy, Medical negligence and the law, Indian J Med Ethics.2007 Jul-Sep;4(3),

¹²² (2000) 5 SCC 182:: AIR 2000 SC 3335

¹²³ AIR 1996 SC 550

¹²⁴ See Annexure II .

¹²⁵ Observations of Lord President Clyde in Hunter vs. Hanley (1955) SLT 213. See : Nathan HL. MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE. London: Butterworths; 1957.

¹²⁶ Whitehouse vs. Jordan (1981) 1 All ER 267.

¹²⁷ Dr.Laxman Balkrishna Joshi vs Dr.TrimbakBapuGodbole AIR 1969 (SC)128

practice that is considered “proper” by a reasonable body of medical professionals who are skilled in that particular field, he or she will not be held negligent only because something went wrong.

Doctors must exercise an ordinary degree of skill¹²⁸. However, they cannot give a warranty of the perfection of their skill or a guarantee of cure. If the doctor has adopted the right course of treatment, if she/ he is skilled and has worked with a method and manner best suited to the patient, she/ he cannot be blamed for negligence if the patient is not totally cured.¹²⁹ Certain conditions must be satisfied before liability can be considered. The person who is accused must have committed an act of omission or commission; this act must have been in breach of the person’s duty; and this must have caused harm to the injured person. The complainant must prove the allegation against the doctor by citing the best evidence available in medical science and by presenting expert opinion.¹³⁰

In some situations the complainant can invoke the principle of *res ipsa loquitur* or “the thing speaks for itself”. In certain circumstances no proof of negligence is required beyond the accident itself. The National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission applied this principle in *Dr. Janak Kantimathi Nathan vs Murlidhar Eknath Masane*¹³¹.

The principle of *res ipsa loquitur* comes into operation only when there is proof that the occurrence was unexpected, that the accident could not have happened without negligence and lapses on the part of the doctor, and that the circumstances conclusively show that the doctor and not any other person was negligent.

2.4 CONSTITUTIONAL LAW¹³²

The Fundamental Rights and Article 21 (Right to Life with Dignity) form the basis of Right to Health. Article 21 of the Indian Constitution, a fundamental right reads: “No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except through procedure

¹²⁸Smt. J S Paul vs. Dr. (Mrs.) A Barkataki (2004) 10 CLD 1 (SCDRC - MEGHALAYA).

¹²⁹Dr. Prem Luthravslftekhar (2004) 11 CLD 37 (SCDRC - UTTARANCHAL); Mrs. Savitri Devi vs Union of India IV (2003) CPJ 164; Dr. Devendra Madan vs Shakuntala Devi I (2003) CPJ 57 (NC).

¹³⁰. Supra Note 123

¹³¹Dr. Janak Kantimathi Nathan vs Murlidhar Eknath Masane 2002 (2) CPR 138.

¹³² See Annexure III

established by law.” Till the 1970s the courts, by and large, had interpreted ‘life’ literally i.e. right to exist- right not to be killed. In late 1970s, the Supreme Court began to give an expanded meaning to the term ‘life’ appearing in Article 21. Over the years it has come to be accepted that life does not only mean animal existence but the life of a dignified human being with all its concomitant attributes. This would include a healthy environment and effective health care facilities. Today, therefore, the Fundamental Right to Life is seen in a broad context.¹³³

Context of Judicial Intervention and Evolving Understanding of Right to Health

To begin with, the right to health as a fundamental right grew as an offshoot of environmental litigation initiated by environmental activists regarding the environment issues. Undoubtedly the right to environment was crucial because a polluted environment affects public health. A pollution free environment as a fundamental right presupposes right to health as a fundamental right. Logically, the explicit recognition of the fundamental right to health should have preceded the fundamental right to good environment. However, the development of jurisprudence in this branch has been the reverse. The right to unpolluted environment was recognized as a right in the first instance and from that followed the right to public health, health and health care. Secondly, the right to health care has also been debated by the courts in the context of rights of Government employees to receive health care. A number of observations of the Court concerning the importance of these rights are to be found in cases dealing with denial or restriction of health care facilities for Government employees, and not to the general masses. This is the context of judicial pronouncements on health care.¹³⁴

Public Health is State’s Priority:

In one of the earliest instances of public interest litigations *Municipal Council, Ratlam v Vardhichand & Ors*,¹³⁵ the municipal corporation was prosecuted by some citizens for not clearing up the garbage. The corporation took up the plea that it did not have money. While rejecting the plea, the Supreme Court through Justice Krishna Iyer observed: “The State will realize that Article 47 makes it a paramount principle of

¹³³ Mihir Desai & Chand Dipti, *Healthcare Case Law in India*, 2007, CEHAT, pp.17

¹³⁴ *Supra* note, 39

¹³⁵ 1980 AIR 1622

governance that steps are taken for the improvement of public health as amongst its primary duties.”

Right to Health is a Fundamental Right:

In 1991, in *CESC Ltd. vs. Subhash Chandra Bose*,¹³⁶ the Supreme Court relied on international instruments and concluded that right to health is a fundamental right. It went further and observed that health is not merely absence of sickness:

“The term health implies more than an absence of sickness. Medical care and health facilities not only protect against sickness but also ensure stable manpower for economic development. Facilities of health and medical care generate devotion and dedication to give the workers’ best, physically as well as mentally, in productivity. It enables the worker to enjoy the fruit of his labour, to keep him physically fit and mentally alert for leading a successful economic, social and cultural life. The medical facilities are, therefore, part of social security and like gilt edged security, it would yield immediate return in the increased production or at any rate reduce absenteeism on grounds of sickness, etc. Health is thus a state of complete physical, mental and social well being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. In the light of Arts. 22 to 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and in the light of socio-economic justice assured in our Constitution, right to health is a fundamental human right to workmen. The maintenance of health is a most imperative constitutional goal whose realization requires interaction by many social and economic factors.”¹³⁷

People are entitled to adequate health care

This was held in *Mahendra Pratap Singh v Orissa State*¹³⁸, as follows.

The petitioner, an ex-sarpanch of Pachhikote Gram Panchayat approached the court for issuance of appropriate writ commanding the opposite parties to take effective measures to run Primary Health Centre at Pachhikote within Korei block in the district of Jaipur by providing all amenities and facilities for proper running of the said health centre. The Government of Orissa decided to open certain primary health centres in different areas in 1991-92 subject to fulfilment of certain conditions, on basis of demands of the local people and public at large.

¹³⁶ AIR 1992 SC 573,585

¹³⁷ Mihir Desai & Chand Dipti, *Healthcare Case Law in India*, 2007, CEHAT, pp.19

¹³⁸ 103 (2007) CLT 675

Adequate and Quality medical care is part of Right to Health and Right to Life:

The Allahabad High Court in *S.K. Garg vs. State of U.P.*¹³⁹ was dealing with conditions of public hospitals. The Petition had been filed raising concerns about the pitiable nature of services available in public hospitals in Allahabad. Complaints were made concerning inadequacy of blood banks, worn down X- ray equipment, unavailability of essential drugs and unhygienic conditions. The Court appointed a Committee to go into these aspects and report back to the Court.

In *Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samiti vs. State of W.B*¹⁴⁰ the Supreme Court though primarily dealing with the issue of obligation of the State to provide emergency health care to patients made a general observation of significance: "Providing adequate medical facilities is an essential part of the obligation undertaken by the State in a welfare state. The Government discharges this obligation by running hospitals and health centres. Article 21 imposes an obligation on the State to safeguard right to life of every person."¹⁴¹

In the case of *Peoples' Union of Civil Liberties vs. Union of India*,¹⁴² public interest litigation was filed against the Government for backing out of a project to build a psychiatric hospital-cum-medical college in Delhi. The plan had been approved but when it was found that over Rs. 40 Crores would be the expenditure, the Delhi Administration expressed its inability to fund such a project and the Central Government refused to take on its responsibility. The Supreme Court held that setting up of a psychiatric hospital in the capital city was necessary. Once land has been earmarked and on principle a decision taken that hospital should be shifted and part of it should be converted into a teaching institution while the other part should be a hospital, funding should not stand in way of locating such a hospital. As it was difficult to fund such a huge amount in a single year, it was to be taken up as a continuous project spread over a period. Hence, the Central Government and the Delhi Administration were directed to recommence and finish the project.¹⁴³

¹³⁹ 1999 (1) AWC 847, (1998) 2 UPLBEC 1211

¹⁴⁰ AIR 1996 SC 2426, 1996 (4) SCC 37

¹⁴¹ Id

¹⁴² (2003) 4 SCC 399

¹⁴³ Supra pp.23

Compensation Claims against the State

Basis of Compensation by the State: Violation of Article 21 by the State will give rise to a claim under public law remedy.⁹ The State is also vicariously liable for acts of its agents or police or Government hospitals. The earlier notion was that 'king could do no wrong' and the State could not be held liable for the wrongdoings of its servants.

Thus, while public servants could be prosecuted or sued for damages for negligence or dereliction of duty it was not possible for the State to be sued likewise. In the last 20 years this aspect has undergone change. This aspect has also been dealt with in the Chapter 6,¹⁴⁴ but the changed principle needs to be elaborated here because it flows partly from the fundamental right to health and health care.¹⁴⁵

Anuradha Saha Case ¹⁴⁶

The Supreme Court judgment in the *Anuradha Saha* medical negligence case is a landmark in the annals of medical jurisprudence. The apex court not only adjudicated on how to determine criminal negligence on the part of a doctor or a group of doctors in the event of a patient's death but also imposed greater responsibility on them on the universal treatment protocol. It has also reinforced a patient's right to know the line of treatment being followed by doctors, including the risks involved in the treatment¹⁴⁷.

The compensation to be paid by AMRI and the doctors individually will be decided by the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, where Kunal has claimed Rs 77.7 Crore as damages. The judgment is being viewed by many as the judiciary's acknowledgement of the deficiency in the medical service given to Anuradha. The apex court has upheld the Calcutta High Court ruling acquitting three doctors, Dr Abani Roy Chowdhury, Dr.Sukumar Mukherjee and Dr.Baidyanath Halder on the ground that they had no "*mens rea* (intention) of being rash and negligent"¹⁴⁸.

¹⁴⁴Id .

¹⁴⁵ Supra note, 23

¹⁴⁶ Dr Kunal Saha v. Dr Sukumar Mukherjee, (2006) CPJ 142; also see, Anuradha Saha Death: Biggest Case For "Medical Negligence" Starts In Supreme Court, March 22, 2013, <http://pbtindia.com/archives/1805> accessed on March, 18, 2012

¹⁴⁷ Id.

¹⁴⁸ Eshwar Anand, Death by negligence, 02/09/2009, indialawyers.wordpress.com/category/medical-negligence

After a prolonged trial, Kolkata's Chief Metropolitan Magistrate let off Dr Chowdhury, and the High Court the other two doctors in 2004. Kunal Saha then approached the Supreme Court. *Anuradha* was diagnosed with a serious disease called Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN). Also called Lyell's Syndrome, in this disease, the patient gets high fever and occasionally suffers from somnolence and lassitude. Owing to the extensive area of eroded skin, the patient loses huge body fluid with consequent disturbances in the electrolyte and fluid balance. She died in 1998 at the age of 36 following complications from a steroid overdose.¹⁴⁹

Anuradha, a child psychologist, and Kunal, a doctor-researcher on HIV/AIDS, were settled in the US. They visited Kolkata in April 1998 on a vacation. After she suddenly developed fever and skin rash, Dr. Mukherjee examined her and advised her rest without prescribing medicine. After a week, when the skin rash appeared more aggressively, Dr Mukherjee prescribed Depomedrol injection (80 mg) twice daily for three days. Yet, her condition deteriorated.¹⁵⁰

She was admitted to the AMRI hospital on May 11 under Dr Mukherjee's supervision. Dr. Halder found that she was suffering from erythema plus blisters. Dr Chowdhury also examined her. After her condition worsened, she was shifted to Mumbai's Beach Candy Hospital in a chartered plane. She died on May 28.¹⁵¹

Medical opinion has been sharply divided over the administration of steroids, particularly for those suffering from TEN, discovered as far back as 1956. In fact, there are pro- and anti-steroid lobbies, implying that medical science has a grey area in this respect. The treatment protocol for TEN has undergone change throughout the world.

Though doctors used to administer steroid for TEN patients earlier, researchers have later warned against its use after conducting tests of TEN patients with and without the administration of steroids. They found that those treated with steroids did not respond properly thereto. Though researchers have found that the use of steroids was more detrimental than beneficial to TEN patients, some doctors still use

¹⁴⁹Id.,

¹⁵⁰Supra note 60.

¹⁵¹ *Anuradha's Story*, Oct. 30 2011, pbtindia.com/anuradhas-story

steroids. In *Anuradha's* case, experts held that Depomedrol of 80 mg twice daily should not have been prescribed under clinical conditions.

Though some use “quick acting” steroids for a short period, at the very early stage of the disease, they quickly stop the same to check side, effects. Her condition is said to have deteriorated because, in addition to Depomedrol as prescribed by Dr Mukherjee, she was given a new steroid, Prednisolone (40 mg), thrice daily as prescribed by Dr. Chowdhury and Dr.Halder.

The specialists at Beach Candy Hospital were aghast at this patent steroid overdose on *Anuradha* by Kolkata's doctors. According to them, a patient could be given not more than 40 mg Prednisolone, once daily, to be reduced to 5 mg within the next five-six days.

More to the point, as the apex court has observed, the Kolkata doctors did not follow the universal treatment protocol for *Anuradha*. For a TEN patient, supportive therapy is imperative in character, but no such advice was rendered. Despite well laid down procedures in reputed medical journals, they failed to provide primary emergency care, symptomatic therapy, fluid replacement and antibacterial and nutritional support to *Anuradha*.

Worse, the fact that AMRI did not maintain records of *Anuradha's* vital parameters like temperature, pulse rate, blood pressure, etc, was itself an act of “gross negligence”. Still, the apex court rejected Kunal's petition to book the doctors for criminal negligence under Section 304-A of the Indian Penal Code. Charging a doctor under this section, according to the Bench, is very serious as it will affect his professional status and reputation and the burden of proof will be more onerous.

It held that a doctor could not be held negligent only because the treatment resulted in the patient's death. He cannot be held liable for “mischance, misadventure or for an error of judgment” in making a choice where two options are available. Even a doctor's mistake in diagnosis cannot be necessarily construed as a “negligent diagnosis”, according to the Bench.

Even under the law of tort, a doctor can be held liable in respect of an erroneous diagnosis only if his error is “so palpably wrong” as to prove by itself that it was callously arrived at. For imputing criminal liability on a doctor, a very high degree of such negligence is required to be proved, the Bench ruled.

Interestingly, though experts had briefed the Bench and given their evidence about TEN and its treatment protocol, it ruled that the court was not strictly bound by the specialist advice as such evidence was only advisory in nature under Section 45 of the Evidence Act. The court must derive its own conclusion upon considering the expert opinion, it observed.

The judgment is a watershed in medical jurisprudence because it not only put the onus on the doctors for the patients’ treatment but also laid down ground rules on the basis of its judicial pronouncements over the years. The doctors must observe the current practices regarding infrastructure, sterility and hygiene. No prescription should be given to a patient without actual examination.

A doctor should not merely go by the patient’s version about his/her symptoms but also make his/her own analysis, including tests and investigations wherever necessary. Doctors should not experiment unless necessary and even then only after obtaining the patient’s written consent.

The judgment reinforces a patient’s right to know. The Bench has made it clear that doctors must tell patients about the risks involved in any line of treatment they are following. By and large, patients are ignorant about the adverse effects of a medicine. If some reaction is anticipated, the patient must be informed. This was not done in *Anuradha’s* case.

The Bench’s warning that whether or not a doctor kept a patient informed about the pros and cons of a line of treatment will be considered in every case of medical negligence hereafter is expected to serve public interest immensely and fill up the vacuum in this vital discipline.

2.5 CRIMINAL LAWS ¹⁵²

Indian Penal Code, 1860 sections 52, 80, 81, 83, 88, 90, 91, 92 304-A, 337 and 338 contain the law of medical mal practice in India.¹⁵³

A physician can be charged with criminal negligence when a patient dies from the effects of anaesthesia during, an operation or other kind of treatment, if it can be proved that the death was the result of malicious intention, or gross negligence. Before the administration of anaesthesia or performance of an operation, the medical man is expected to follow the accepted precautions.

In such cases, the physician should be able to prove that he used reasonable and ordinary care in the treatment of his patient to the best of his judgment. He is, however, not liable for an error judgment. The law expects a duly qualified physician to use that degree of skill and care which an average man of his qualifications ought to have, and does not expect him to bring the highest possible degree of skill in the treatment of his patients, or to be able to guarantee cures.

It has long been recognized that criminal liability of a physician may result from a high degree of negligent conduct. What the law calls criminal negligence is largely a matter of degree; it is incapable of a precise definition. To prove whether or not it exists is like chasing a mirage. It requires that any of the following to be established in a case of criminal medical negligence.

“Gross Lack of competency or gross inattention, or wanton indifferences to the patient’s safety, which may arise from gross ignorance of the science of medicine and surgery or through gross negligence, either in the application and selection of remedies, lack of proper skill in the use of instruments and failure to give proper attention to the patient.” ¹⁵⁴

¹⁵² Indian penal Code and Medical negligence, www.docshieldconsultant.com/index-.php?option=com.

¹⁵³ See details in Annexure IV

¹⁵⁴ Hampton v State; 425 U.S. 484 (1976) State v Lester, 130 Ohio St.3d 303, 2011-Ohio-5204

In *R. v Bateman*¹⁵⁵, Dr. Bateman was prosecuted for manslaughter and the charges of negligence made against him were:

- Causing the internal ruptures in performing the operations of 'version';
- Removing part of the uterus along with the placenta;
- Delay in sending the patient to the infirmary.

The trial court convicted him. But the Court of Appeal held: “.. in order to establish criminal liability, the facts must be such that, the negligence of the accused went beyond a mere matter of compensation between subjects and should such disregard for the life and safety of others as to amount to a crime against the state and conduct punishment.”

When a FIR (First Information Report) is filed against a doctor for the death of a patient who was under his treatment, under this Indian Penal Code Section 304-A the doctor can be arrested. A doctor charged under this section can obtain bail and if proved guilty, the doctor can be punished with a maximum of two years imprisonment or fine or both. But, if the patient is alive, the doctor is charged under the Indian Penal Code Section 337 and 338.

The Indian Courts have been very careful not to hold qualified physicians criminally (instances of quacks for criminal negligence are there) liable for patients' deaths that are the result of a mere mistake of judgment in the selection and application of remedies and when the death resulted merely from an error of judgment or an inadvertent death.

CRIMINAL NEGLIGENCE¹⁵⁶

Section 304A of the Indian Penal Code of 1860 states that whoever causes the death of a person by a rash or negligent act not amounting to culpable homicide shall be punished with imprisonment for a term of two years, or with a fine, or with both.

¹⁵⁵ [1925] 94 UKB 791

¹⁵⁶ Criminal Negligence, laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/acts/C-46/page-107.html

In the *Santra* case¹⁵⁷, the Supreme Court has pointed out that liability in civil law is based upon the amount of damages incurred; in criminal law, the amount and degree of negligence is a factor in determining liability. However, certain elements must be established to determine criminal liability in any particular case, the motive of the offence, the magnitude of the offence, and the character of the offender.

In *Poonam Verma vs Ashwin Patel*¹⁵⁸ the Supreme Court distinguished between negligence, rashness, and recklessness. A negligent person is one who inadvertently commits an act of omission and violates a positive duty. A person who is rash knows the consequences but foolishly thinks that they will not occur as a result of her/ his act. A reckless person knows the consequences but does not care whether or not they result from her/ his act. Any conduct falling short of recklessness and deliberate wrongdoing should not be the subject of criminal liability.

Thus a doctor cannot be held criminally responsible for a patient's death unless it is shown that she/ he was negligent or incompetent, with such disregard for the life and safety of his patient that it amounted to a crime against the State.¹⁵⁹ Sections 80 and 88 of the Indian Penal Code contain defences for doctors accused of criminal liability. Under Section 80 (accident in doing a lawful act) nothing is an offence that is done by accident or misfortune and without any criminal intention or knowledge in the doing of a lawful act in a lawful manner by lawful means and with proper care and caution. According to Section 88, a person cannot be accused of an offence if she/ he performs an act in good faith for the other's benefit, does not intend to cause harm even if there is a risk, and the patient has explicitly or implicitly given consent.

BURDEN OF PROOF AND CHANCES OF ERROR¹⁶⁰

The burden of proof of negligence, carelessness, or insufficiency generally lies with the complainant. The law requires a higher standard of evidence than otherwise, to support an allegation of negligence against a doctor. In cases of medical negligence the patient must establish her/ his claim against the doctor.

¹⁵⁷ State of Harayana vs Smt. Santra (2000) 5 SCC 182:: AIR 2000 SC 3335

¹⁵⁸ 1996(4) SCC 332, 1996 (2) CPJ 1 (SC)

¹⁵⁹ House of Lords decision in R vs Adomako (1994) 3 All ER 79

¹⁶⁰ Medical negligence, www.supremelaws.in/data/pdf/Medical%20Negligence.pdf.

In *Calcutta Medical Research Institute v Bimalesh Chatterjee*, it was held that the onus of proving negligence and the resultant deficiency in service was clearly on the complainant¹⁶¹. In *Kanhaiya Kumar Singh v Park Medicare & Research Centre*, it was held that negligence has to be established and cannot be presumed.¹⁶²

Even after adopting all medical procedures as prescribed, a qualified doctor may commit an error. The National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission and the Supreme Court have held, in several decisions, that a doctor is not liable for negligence or medical deficiency if some wrong is caused in her/ his treatment or in her/ his diagnosis if she/ he has acted in accordance with the practice accepted as proper by a reasonable body of medical professionals skilled in that particular art, though the result may be wrong. In various kinds of medical and surgical treatment, the likelihood of an accident leading to death cannot be ruled out. It is implied that a patient willingly takes such a risk as part of the doctor-patient relationship and the attendant mutual trust.¹⁶³

RECENT SUPREME COURT RULINGS¹⁶⁴

Before the case of *Jacob Mathew v State of Punjab*,¹⁶⁵ the Supreme Court of India delivered two different opinions on doctors' liability. In *Mohanan v Prabha G Nair and another*¹⁶⁶, it ruled that a doctor's negligence could be ascertained only by scanning the material and expert evidence that might be presented during a trial. In *Suresh Gupta's* case in August 2004 the standard of negligence that had to be proved to fix a doctor's or surgeon's criminal liability was set at "gross negligence" or "recklessness."

In *Suresh Gupta's*¹⁶⁷ case the Supreme Court distinguished between an error of judgment and culpable negligence. It held that criminal prosecution of doctors

¹⁶¹ *Calcutta Medical Research Institute vs Bimalesh Chatterjee I* (1999)CPJ 13 (NC)

¹⁶² *Kanhaiya Kumar Singh vs Park Medicare & Research Centre III* (1999) CPJ 9 (NC)

¹⁶³ *Id.*

¹⁶⁴ Varsha Narasimhan, *Supreme Court and Medical Negligence – Necessary Protection or License to Kill*, September 11, 2009, jurisonline.in/.../supreme-court-and-medical-negligence---necessary-

¹⁶⁵ (2005) 6 SCC 1

¹⁶⁶ *Mohanan vs Prabha G Nair and another* (2004) CPJ 21(SC), of 2004 Feb 4.

¹⁶⁷ *Dr. Suresh Gupta vs Govt. Of N.C.T. Of Delhi & Anr.*, (2005) 6 SCC 422

without adequate medical opinion pointing to their guilt would do great disservice to the community. A doctor cannot be tried for culpable or criminal negligence in all cases of medical mishaps or misfortunes.

On September 9, 2004, Justices Arijit Pasayat and C.K.Thakker referred the question of medical negligence to a larger Bench of the Supreme Court. They observed that words such as “gross”, “reckless”, “competence”, and “indifference” did not occur anywhere in the definition of “negligence” under Section 304A of the Indian Penal Code and hence they could not agree with the judgment delivered in the case of Dr Suresh Gupta.

The issue was decided in the Supreme Court in the case of *Jacob Mathew v State of Punjab*¹⁶⁸. The court directed the central government to frame guidelines to save doctors from unnecessary harassment and undue pressure in performing their duties. It ruled that until the government framed such guidelines, the following guidelines would prevail;

‘A private complaint of rashness or negligence against a doctor may not be entertained without prima facie evidence in the form of a credible opinion of another competent doctor supporting the charge. In addition, the investigating officer should give an independent opinion, preferably of a government doctor. Finally, a doctor may be arrested only if the investigating officer believes that she/ he would not be available for prosecution unless arrested’.

2.6 CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT, 1986¹⁶⁹

Consumer Protection Act and the medical profession: One of the most hotly debated areas in the field of consumer law is that of medical negligence and the issues arising from it. The issue of what amounts to medical negligence in India and when can a doctor/medical professional be said to be negligent in the performance of his duties, and the standard of care that a doctor is expected to meet in his practice has been the topic of a number of landmark decisions/cases in India. The fact that the

¹⁶⁸ AIR 2005 Supreme Court 3180

¹⁶⁹ Medico-Legal Aspects Of Consumer Law Concerning
MedicalmNegligence<http://www.halsburys.in/medico-legal-aspects-of-consumer-law-concerning.html>

medical profession and the services this sector has to offer are covered within the ambit of Consumer Protection Act is well settled.¹⁷⁰

The Consumer Protection Act was enacted in 1986 *“to provide for better protection of the interests of consumers”*. It creates a parallel dispute redressal mechanism and provides for a time limit within which disputes need to be adjudicated upon, making the remedy one of the most favoured with litigants. Under the scheme of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986, any person who hires or avails of any service for consideration (and includes any beneficiary of such services) qualifies to be a consumer, as per the definition in Section 2(d) of the Act. In the event that the services hired or availed of by a consumer suffer from deficiency in any respect, the consumer can approach the consumer fora for redressal of his grievances and for remedies provided under the Act. Deficiency has been defined under the Act as any fault, imperfection or shortcoming in the quality, quantity, potency, purity or standard. Clearly this is a very wide definition, and the determination of this would depend upon and differ in each case.

The consumer protection Act was brought into existence for the protection of interests of the consumer and for settlement of consumer dispute, within a limited time frame and with fewer expenses. In April 1992, the National Commission, on appeal from the Kerala State Commission decided that the medical services be covered under COPRA. This enables a consumer (patient) to make a complaint to a redressal forum in respect of a defective service, if the service has been paid for. Defective in the context of a doctor's services means negligent. Deficiency or negligence means fault or imperfection, shortcoming or inadequacy in quality, nature and manner of performance of the medical service rendered by a hospital and/or member of the medical profession. Several amendments in the Act have been passed in the Consumer Protection (Amendment) Act 1993.

Consumer Disputes Redressal Forums have been established at three different levels as given below. (Section 9)

¹⁷⁰ P.N. Mehta, Consumer Protection Act and Medical Profession ,
www.indianpediatrics.net/sep1997/845.pdf

1. 'District Forum' by the State Government in each district of the state by notification. The jurisdiction to entertain complaints is limited to those where the value of the goods of services and the compensation, if any claimed, does not exceed rupees 20 Lakh.
2. 'State Commission' by the State Government in the state by notification. It compensation, if any, claimed exceeds rupees 20 Lakh but does not rupees 1 Crore and appeals against the orders of any District forum within the state. It can call for the records and pass appropriate order in any consumer dispute which is pending before or has been decided by any District Forum within the state, where it appears to the State Commission that such District Forum has exercised a jurisdiction not vested in it by law, or has failed to exercise a jurisdiction so vested or has acted in exercise of its jurisdiction illegally or with material irregularly.
3. 'National Commission' (National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission) by the Central Government. It has the jurisdiction to entertain complaints, where the value of the goods or services and compensation, if any, claimed exceeds rupees 1 Crore and appeals against the orders of any State Commission. It can call for the records and pass appropriate orders in any consumer dispute, which is pending before or has been decided by any State Commission, where is appears to the National Commission that such State Commission has exercised a jurisdiction not vested in it by law, or failed to exercise a jurisdiction so vested, or has acted in the exercise of its jurisdiction illegally or with material irregularity.

Negligence can be established by a complainant after the production of expert evidence, indicating the negligence, and in the absence of such evidence, the opposite party cannot be said to have been negligent in the treatment of the patient.

Who is a consumer? (Section (1) (d))

Any person who buys any goods against consideration is a consumer (it also includes any user of such goods, other than the person who buys such goods, where such use is made with the original buyer's approval.) However, if the goods are purchased for resale or any commercial purpose, then the buyer is not a consumer and cannot avail the protection under this Act.

Similarly, any person who hires services against consideration is also a consumer and it included any beneficiary of such services, of course with the approval of the original consumer. Strictly speaking, the definition penetrates the essence of consumption and not merely the dereliction based on privity between the parties. Any user of goods or beneficiary of services has also a legal right and locus standi to initiate action under the act. In the course of treatment of a patient, the bills and fees of the doctors may be paid by an attendant or family member. The patient, as beneficiary, remains consumer. The madras high court while deciding Bench of writ petitions in *Dr.C.J Subramanian v. kumaraswamy*,¹⁷¹ interpreted the provision of the act vis a vis medical practitioners as under:

i. The services rendered to a patient by a medical practitioner or a hospital by way of diagnosis and treatment both medical and surgical, would not come within the meaning of 'service' as defined in section 2 (1)(o)of the Consumer Protection Act

ii. A patient who undergoes treatment under a medical practitioner or a hospital by way of diagnosis and treatment, both medical and surgical, cannot be considered to be a 'consumer' within the meaning of section 2(1) (d) of the Consumer Protection Act.¹⁷²

iii. The medical practitioner or the hospital undertaking and providing paramedical services of any category or kind cannot claim similar immunity from the provision of the act and they would fall, to the extent of such services rendered by them, within the definition of service and a person availing of such service would be a 'consumer' within the meaning of this act. The issue now stands finally decided by the supreme court in *V.P Shantha's case; Indian medical association v. V.P Shantha*.

Patients who avail medical services of government hospitals, where no fee or consideration is charged except a nominal amount as registration charges cannot fall within the ambit of "consumer:"

¹⁷¹ I (1994) CPJ 509, (1994) MLJ 438

¹⁷² Refer to Annexure II.

What is service? [Section 2 (1) (o)]

Services are defined in a wide terminology to include most of the general facilities which a consumer avails in day to day activities. A very comprehensive definition of services has been incorporated in the Act. It says 'service' means service of any description which is made available to potential users. The word 'potential' gives any potential user the right to move under this Act. But rendering of any service free of charge or under a contract of personal service does not come under the ambit of this act. Services rendered by doctors and hospital have been held to be within the jurisdiction of the Act.

RIGHTS OF THE PATIENT ¹⁷³

To understand the depth of the logic applied by the consumer courts it is essential that we understand what rights a patient enjoys as a consumer, for the breach of which he can ask for a legal remedy. The rights of a consumer as a patient in the Act are based on the inherent rights. These inherent rights are-

- The right to be protected against marketing of goods and services which are hazardous to life and property. So one should always sport an attitude of 'beware! Don't sell me goods hazardous to my life and property';
- The right to be informed about the quality, quantity, potency, purity, standard and price of goods or services, or as the case may be, so as to protect the consumers against unfair trade practices;
- The right to be assured, whenever possible, access to a variety of goods and services at competitive prices;
- The right to be heard and to be assured that the consumers interests will receive due considerations at appropriate forums;
- The right to seek redressal against unfair trade practices or restrictive trade practices or unscrupulous exploitation of consumers; and
- The right to consumer education.

Hence a consumer can keep in mind these rights and these important conditions of the consumer protection act before filing a suit in the court regarding medical negligence in India.

Generally there is always confusion whether medical negligence is a tort or is it a deficiency in service. In *Dr. Ravinder Gupta v. Ganga Dev*¹⁷⁴ case it has been observed that before the consumer protection act was proposed the laws related to medical negligence was always under the law of torts only. Medical liability under the consumer jurisdiction is on a somewhat different footing and though in certain areas the matter (consumer law & tort law) may overlap, there is a clear line distinction between the two, medical liabilities within the consumer jurisdiction is only a species of the genus of deficiency in services hired. The definition casts the very net wide and extends the somewhat narrower concept of negligence in the law of torts.

¹⁷³Supra 43

¹⁷⁴ 1993(3) CPR 255,

Medical liability under the consumer jurisdiction undoubtedly includes what is negligence in the law of torts, but is somewhat wider and more than the strict liability under the law of torts. A practitioner can be held to be liable if his mistake is of such a nature as to imply an absence of reasonable skill and care on his part, regard being to the ordinary level of skill in the profession.

LIMITATION PERIOD ¹⁷⁵

The District Forum, the State Commission or the National Commission shall not admit a complaint unless it is filed within two years from the date on which the cause of action has arisen, unless the complaint satisfies the forum or the commission as the case may be, that he had sufficient cause for not filing the complaint within such period and the reason for condoning such delay is recorded.

Any appeal preferred from the order of the district or the State Commission under the Act, must be filed within thirty days of the order.

Under s 23 of the Act, any person, who is aggrieved by an order made by the National Commission whether in its original or appellate jurisdiction has a right to prefer an appeal to the Supreme Court within a period of 30 days will not stand as a bar, if the Supreme Court is satisfied that there has been a sufficient cause for not filing it in the period.

A final order is required to be passed within 90 days of the issue of the notice or the receipt of the complaint filed by the opposite party if the goods forming subject matter of the dispute are not required to be sent to a laboratory for testing, and 150 days if such testing is required to be done. No time limit has been laid down for the disposal of an appeal or revision petition.

Thus it is clearly seen from the provisions available to a consumer that, within certain stipulated time the judgment must be passed at both the levels, National Commission and Supreme Court. In reality, over last 3 decades, the period for hearing and final judgment ranges between 5 to 6 years, thus the very purpose is defeated by delaying the justice.

¹⁷⁵Id.

PENALTY

In case of dismissal of frivolous or vexatious complaints-where a complaint instituted before the District Forum, the State Commission or, as the case may be, the National Commission, is found to be frivolous or vexatious, it shall for the complainant shall pay as penalty to the opposite party such cost, not exceeding ten thousand rupees, as may be specified in the order.

Thus, District Forums have original jurisdiction, while the State and the National Commission are vested with original, appellate and revisional jurisdictions.

As per the judgment of the Supreme Court of India, in *Indian Medical Association v V.P. Shantha & Ors*¹⁷⁶, the medical services delivered on payment basis, clearly fall, within the ambit of the Act. Similarly, the hospital or the nursing homes, which provide free service to some of the patients who cannot afford to pay the fees, but the bulk of the service is rendered to the patient on payment basis, are also covered under this treatment and all the charges for consultations, diagnosis and medical treatment are borne by the insurance company, the service rendered to him by a medical practitioner would not be free of charge and would, therefore, constitute service as defined in the Act.

The Supreme Court judgment also enlarges the definition of negligence by enunciating that violation of an established law is also negligence and where a service provider is guilty of such negligence, no further proof is required to hold him liable for his action.

COMPENSATION¹⁷⁷

At the threshold of a claim for compensation upon negligence to be established, it needs to be proved that:

- the defendant owed a duty of care to the consumer;
- there has been a breach in the performance of that duty; and

¹⁷⁶ AIR 1996 550

¹⁷⁷Id.

- There should be some consequent loss caused to the person.

Early on, the Supreme Court of India has in *Dr. Laxman Balkrishna Joshi Vs. Trimbak Bapu Golbole & Another*¹⁷⁸ held that:

“The duties which a doctor owes to his patient are clear. A person who holds himself out ready to give medical advice and treatment impliedly undertakes that he is possessed of skill and knowledge for the purpose. Such a person when consulted by a patient owes him certain duties, viz, a duty of care in deciding what treatment to give or a duty of care in the administration of that treatment. A breach of any of those duties gives a right of action for negligence to the patient. The practitioner must bring to his task a reasonable degree of skill and knowledge and must exercise a reasonable degree of care. Neither the very highest nor a very low degree of care and competence judged in the light of the particular circumstances of each case is what the law requires. The doctor, no doubt, has discretion in choosing the treatment which he proposes to give to his patient and such discretion is relatively higher in cases of emergency.”

In UK, the issue of medical negligence was considered in great detail in the case of *Bolam Vs. Friern Hospital Committee*¹⁷⁹, when McNair, J. held that “in the case of a medical man negligence means failure to act in accordance with the standards of reasonably competent medical men at that time” and that “there may be one or more perfectly proper standards, and if the medical man conforms with one of those proper standards he is not negligent”. The English view is that a doctor is not guilty of negligence if he has acted in accordance with the practice accepted as proper by a responsible body of medical men. But what amounts to reasonable conduct should only be decided upon by the court, based on the views of the experts in the field. As to what other medical professionals do in similar situations, will be a material consideration to be weighed by the court.

The view in *Bolam's* case was finally accepted in India after 2 decades in the landmark case of *Dr. Suresh Gupta*.⁵ However, that case got referred to a larger

¹⁷⁸ AIR 1969 SC 128

¹⁷⁹ 1957, 1 WLR 583

bench of the Supreme Court and finally in *Jacob Matthew*⁶ and *Shiv Ram*⁷ the *Bolam* Test was approved. Recently, the Supreme Court has given far reaching guidelines on medical negligence in *Martin F. D'Souza Vs. Mohd Ishfaq*¹⁸⁰, while following *Jacob Matthew* held as under:

“The law, like medicine, is an inexact science. One cannot predict with certainty an outcome of many cases. It depends on the particular facts and circumstances of the case, and also the personal notions of the Judge concerned who is hearing the case. However, the broad and general legal principles relating to medical negligence need to be understood.

Before dealing with these principles two things have to be kept in mind:

(1) Judges are not experts in medical science, rather they are lay men. This itself often makes it somewhat difficult for them to decide cases relating to medical negligence. Moreover, Judges have usually to rely on testimonies of other doctors which may not necessarily in all cases be objective, since like in all professions and services, doctors too sometimes have a tendency to support their own colleagues who are charged with medical negligence. The testimony may also be difficult to understand, particularly in complicated medical matters, for a layman in medical matters like a Judge; and (2) A balance has to be struck in such cases. While doctors who cause death or agony due to medical negligence should certainly be penalized, it must also be remembered that like all professionals doctors too can make errors of judgment but if they are punished for this no doctor can practice his vocation with equanimity. Indiscriminate proceedings and decisions against doctors are counterproductive and serve society no good. They inhibit the free exercise of judgment by a professional in a particular situation”.¹⁸¹

In the above mentioned background The Supreme Court has further directed that:

“...whenever a complaint is received against a doctor or hospital by the Consumer Fora (whether District, State or National) or by the Criminal Court then before issuing notice to the doctor or hospital against whom the complaint was made the Consumer Forum or Criminal Court should first refer the matter to a competent doctor or

¹⁸⁰ AIR 2009 SC 2049

¹⁸¹Id. pp. 6-7

committee of doctors, specialized in the field relating to which the medical negligence is attributed, and only after that doctor or committee reports that there is a prima facie case of medical negligence should notice be then issued to the concerned doctor/hospital. This is necessary to avoid harassment to doctors who may not be ultimately found to be negligent.”

The rationale behind this decision shows a divergence from the traditional English view, that “The courts and Consumer Fora are not experts in medical science, and must not substitute their own views over that of specialists...”¹⁸²

Consent for medical treatment ¹⁸³

Consent is material to all medical treatments, with the exception of emergent medical care, when consent can be waived/ deferred. The basis for recognizing consent to medical treatment is the individual’s right to autonomy or self-determination. As stated by Cardozo, J:

“Every human being of adult years and sound mind has a right to determine what shall be done with his own body; and a surgeon who performs an operation without his patient’s consent commits an assault.”¹⁸⁴

Consent to treatment could be expressed or implied by the patient’s conduct. Once a patient has come to the doctor for treatment and paid the professional fee, he is said to have impliedly consented to the treatment; such a consent being valid only for examination and not for the performance of any procedure.

The Indian Medical Council (professional conduct, etiquette and ethics) Regulations, 2002, regulation 7.16 requires that:

“7.16: Before performing an operation the physician should obtain in writing the consent from the husband or wife, parent or guardian in the case of minor, or the

¹⁸² Markandey Katju, J. in Martin D Souza Case-para 123. Mentioned in article by Sidharth Luthra and Madhav Khurana “Medico-Legal Aspects Of Consumer Law” Concerning Medical Negligence <http://www.halsburys.in/medico-legal-aspects-of-consumer-law-concerning.html>

¹⁸³ Supranote 72.

¹⁸⁴ Supra note 78.

patient himself as the case may be. In an operation which may result in sterility the consent of both husband and wife is needed.”¹⁸⁵

For there to be a valid consent, it is necessary to ensure that the consent is always expressed in writing. Often standard consent forms only indicate that the general nature and purpose of the treatment have been explained to the patient. They are not always conclusive of the fact that the patient consented to the procedure in question. In *Chatterton Vs. Gerson*¹⁸⁶ the court held that “getting the patient to sign a pro forma expressing consent to undergo an operation ‘the effect and nature of which have been explained to me’ as was done here in each case, should be a valuable reminder to everyone of the need for explanation and consent...The consent would be expressed in form only, not in reality.”

For the consent to be valid in law, it must be an informed consent. The patient must consent to the treatment after understanding the nature of the treatment. Before this, he must have some information about the procedure itself.¹⁸⁷ Without appropriate/adequate consent, a doctor might face the risk of proceedings for assault/causation of injury, in case of any complication arising from the medical procedure. Therefore, to protect him in case of future litigation, it is important for a doctor to have a written consent form, where it should be specified that the procedure, including its risks, has been explained to the patient, and the patient has thereafter decided to go ahead with the treatment. It is advisable to get the form signed in the presence of an independent witness apart from a family member/attendant of the patient. For high risk cases, it is advisable to have a separate form specifying the details of the added risks and the nature of the procedure.

In case of children¹⁸⁸

The difficulty arises in relation for consent of a child. Jones¹² divides children into two categories:

¹⁸⁵ See in Annexure. IV

¹⁸⁶ [1981] QB 432

¹⁸⁷ *Chatterton Vs. Gerson* [1981] QB 432 & *Samira Kohli Vs. Dr. Prabha Manchanda*; SC (2008) 2 SCC 1

¹⁸⁸Id.

- Those who have the capacity to make their own decisions about medical treatment and can give valid consent on their own
- Those who do not have the capacity, in which case parental consent becomes necessary

As per the Indian Majority Act, 1875¹⁸⁹ a person attains majority upon the completion of eighteen years of age. A person below the age is a minor.

The English view in *Gillick Vs. West Norfolk and Wisbech Area Health Authority*¹⁹⁰ is that if the patient is capable of understanding what is proposed, and of expressing his or her own wishes, there is no good reason for holding that he or she lacks the capacity to authorize the doctor to perform an examination or give treatment.

But in cases where the minor (child) lacks the relevant capacity to consent to treatment, parental consent is required unless there is an emergency. As per *Gillick*, parental rights to control a child exist only for the benefit of the child and extend to only so far as they extend them to protect the interests of the child. A slightly different approach was taken by the court in the case of *Re T. (a minor)* (wardship: medical treatment) in which a child was born with a life threatening liver defect. The doctors indicated that the child was likely to have a normal life if it underwent a liver operation, but the mother refused to give her consent. Under wardship jurisdiction, the judge granted permission for the operation in the best interests of the child, but the Court of Appeal held that the welfare of the child depended on the mother, who would be expected to care for him for many years. Thus, the mother's views were held to be relevant, even though the doctors felt that the same was unreasonable.

From this it would follow that it is imperative to get the consent of the parents in cases such as these. An option would be to get an order from the court allowing the treatment despite lack of parental consent. Such an order would protect the interests of the doctor, in case he decides to go ahead with the treatment, even though the parents have indicated their views against the same.

¹⁸⁹The Indian Majority Act, 1875 1 <http://www.indiankanoon.org/doc/1124939/>

¹⁹⁰[1986] 1 AC 112, [1985] 3 All ER 402,

Emergencies¹⁹¹

In India, after *Pt. Parmanand Katara's* case¹⁹² in the context of emergent care of medico-legal cases, it was clarified that *“Every injured citizen brought for medical treatment should instantaneously be given medical aid to preserve life and thereafter the procedural criminal law should be allowed to operate in order to avoid negligent death. There is no legal impediment for a medical professional when he is called upon or requested to attend to an injured person needing his medical assistance immediately...Preservation of human life is of paramount importance that is so on account of the fact that once life is lost, the status quo ante cannot be restored as resurrection is beyond the capacity of man...Every doctor whether at a Government hospital or otherwise has the professional obligation to extend his services with due expertise for protecting life...Every doctor should be reminded of his total obligation and be assured of the position that he does not contravene the law of the land by proceeding to treat the injured victim on his appearance before him either by himself or being carried by others.”* Doctor can provide medical treatment to a child in the absence of parental consent in an emergency, based on the principle of necessity. But what happens in case parents refuse consent to a treatment that could be life saving for a child? Will the doctor be justified in performing the treatment in the light of express prohibition?

It seems that while this position of law is not entirely clear, it could be argued that in some cases, the doctor can act in disregard of parental prohibition. Here the words of Lord Templeman in the *Gillick* Case are to be noted:

“I accept that if there is no time to obtain a decision from the court, a doctor may safely carry out treatment in an emergency if the doctor believes the treatment to be vital to the survival or health of an infant and notwithstanding the opposition of a parent or the impossibility of alerting the parent before the treatment is carried out. In such a case the doctor must have the courage of his convictions that the treatment is necessary and urgent in the interests of the patient and the court will, if necessary,

¹⁹¹ Id.

¹⁹² CRI. L. J. 671

approve after the event treatment which the court would have authorized in advance, even if the treatment proves to be unsuccessful”¹⁹³

In so far as a doctor’s liability in Intensive Care is concerned, the basic principles stated above can be applied to such situations. The courts have recognized that the purpose of saving a life can justify taking risks, which have to be balanced against the consequences of not taking the risk. They also have to be weighed in light of the expected benefits to the patient. Thus, if the chances of a patient’s survival are not very high, it would justify taking greater risks and vice versa.¹⁹⁴

SAFEGUARDS¹⁹⁵

As in all medical negligence cases, even for minors in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), the most vital safeguard against an action under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986, or civil liability would be to exercise the necessary degree of care, not only in discharging the duties, but also in recording the manner in which the treatment has progressed.

It would be advisable to maintain files/records even for out patients, and all documentation to be recorded therein. The prescriptions/summaries that are prepared during taking of history/diagnosis/treatment be recorded in detail, and the differential diagnosis also be recorded. It is sometimes impossible for a doctor to recollect the incident after a long time has elapsed between the incident and the complaint, and this would only serve as a tool for refreshing of memory. It would also help the patient’s family/attendants in analyzing the course of treatment being given to him, and also enable any other medical professionals that he may consult subsequently to make informed decisions. All advice that is given to the patient or communicated to family members/guardians, such as precautions that need to be taken should also be noted and confirmation (in writing) taken from the family members/patient. At times, it is possible that the patient suffers damage because of not following medical advice; it becomes essential to show that such advice was in fact given to the patient. Detailed consent forms describing the risks of the procedures that are being undertaken should be considered with a view that the well-

¹⁹³. 1986, 1 AC 112

¹⁹⁴ Michael A. Jones, *Medical Negligence*, Sweet & Maxwell, London, 1991, P.82

¹⁹⁵ *Supra* 72.

known and most likely complications and pitfalls of various procedures are informed to the patient and the guardian/parent in advance. While all this may lead to more paperwork and reduce the medical professional's dealing time, in the longer run, the benefits of the comprehensive case histories/treatment records would deter vexatious/frivolous litigation/claims.

JURISDICTION OF CONSUMER COURTS¹⁹⁶

Medical negligence gives rise to civil and criminal liability. As already mentioned that as regards civil wrongs, an aggrieved person can claim compensation either through a civil suit or a complaint lodged with consumer forum. Since the enactment of Consumer Protection Act, 1985 there has been a significant rise in medical negligence cases being filed. In one sense, the passing of this law has given a boost to consumers for approaching courts in respect of negligence.

For quite some time after the passage of the Consumer Protection Act, furious debate was raging whether it at all applies to doctors, hospitals and nursing homes and if so under what situations. The Supreme Court finally set at rest this controversy in the case of *Indian Medical Association vs. V.P. Shantha*¹⁹⁷. The Court held that proceedings under the Consumer Protection Act are summary proceedings for speedy redressal and the remedies are in addition to private law remedy. The issue was whether patients are consumers under the Consumer Protection Act and could they claim damages for injury caused by the negligence of the doctor, hospital or nursing home.

Apart from submitting that patients could not be classified as consumers under the Consumer Protection Act, the Medical Association argued the following points that are briefly reproduced¹⁹⁸

- a) Deficiency in service, as defined under the Act, means any fault, imperfection, shortcoming or inadequacy in the quality, nature and manner of performance which is required to be maintained under any law or has been undertaken to

¹⁹⁶ Dhananjay Joshi, Supreme Court on the jurisdiction of Consumer Forums - A welcome trend, Nov 11, 2009, <http://barandbench.com/brief/3/281/supreme-court-on-the-jurisdiction-of-consumer-forums-a-welcome-trend>

¹⁹⁷ 1996 AIR 550

¹⁹⁸ Id.

be performed by a person in pursuance of a contract or otherwise in respect to any service. Thus, deficiency is ascertained on the basis of certain norms relating to quality, nature and manner of performance, and since medical services cannot be judged on the basis of any fixed norms, therefore, practitioners are not covered under the definition of 'services'.

- b) Only such persons can fairly and justly decide on medical malpractice cases who are themselves qualified in medical field as they will be able to appreciate the complex issues involved in such cases. The District Forum comprises of President who is or was a District Judge and the other two members who shall be persons having adequate knowledge or experience of, or having shown capacity in dealing with, problems relating to economics, law, commerce, accountancy, industry, public affairs or administration. Similarly State Commission and National Commission comprise of two non-judicial members who are concerned with economics, law, commerce, accountancy, industry, public affairs or administration, while the President shall be a person who is or was a judge of a High Court and Supreme Court, respectively. It was submitted that as the members of the Forum are not qualified to deal with medical malpractice claims medical practitioners should be exempted from the ambit of the Act.
- c) Medical malpractice claims involve complex issues that will require detailed examination of evidence, deposition of experts and witnesses. This is contrary to the purpose of summary proceedings involving trial by affidavits, which is to provide speedy results. Hence Consumer Forum should not adjudicate medical malpractice cases.
- d) If the medical practitioners are brought within the purview of the Act, the consequences would be a huge increase in medical expenditure on account of insurance charges as well as tremendous increase in defensive medicine, that medical practitioners may refuse to attend to medical emergencies and there will be no safeguards against frivolous and vexatious complaints and consequent blackmail.

The Supreme Court, however, rejected all these arguments and held,

- a) The Act defines 'consumer' as any person who *hires* or *avails* of any services for a *consideration* which has been paid or promised or partly paid and partly promised

under any system of deferred payment and includes any *beneficiary* of such services other than the person who hires or avails of the services for the consideration paid or promised, or partly paid and partly promised, or under any system of deferred payment, when such services are availed of with the approval of the first mentioned person.

‘Service’ means service of any description which is made available to potential users and includes the provision of facilities in connection with banking, financing, insurance, transport, processing, supply of electrical or other energy, boarding or lodging or both, housing construction, entertainment, amusement or the purveying of news or other information, but does not include rendering of any service *free of charge* or under a *contract of personal service*.

The Supreme Court observed that all services are included other than those that are provided for free or under a contract of service.

b) The next question was on what parameters of deficiency in services of medical practitioners, hospitals or nursing homes should be ascertained. Section 14 enumerates the relief that can be granted for deficiency in service. Sub-section 1(d) provides compensation for any loss or injury suffered by a consumer due to negligence of the opposite party. A determination of deficiency in services has, therefore, to be made by applying the same test as is applied in an action for damages for negligence. The test is the standard of medical care a reasonable man possessing same skills and expertise would employ under same circumstances. A medical practitioner need not exhibit extraordinary skills.

c) As regards the expertise of the member of the consumer forum to adjudicate on medical malpractice cases the Supreme Court observed that the object of the Act is to have members who have required knowledge and experience in dealing with problems relating to various fields connected with the object and purpose of the Act, which is to protect the interest of the consumers. Also as a person who is well versed in law and has considerable judicial or legal experience heads all the forums, it will ensure that the deliberation on cases will be guided by legal principles. To say that

the members must have adequate knowledge or experience in the field to which the complaints are related would lead to impossible situation.

If the jurisdiction is limited to the area of expertise of its members then complaints relating to large number of areas will be outside the scope of the Act as the two members in the District Forum have experience in two fields. The problem will arise vertically as at particular times in State Commission there may be members having experience in fields other than that of members of District Forum, would this imply that the State Commission will be ousted of its Appellate jurisdiction in such complaints. The intention of the legislature is to ensure that the members have the aptitude to deal with consumer problems. It is for the parties to place the necessary material before the forum to deliberate upon. It cannot therefore, be said that since the members of the Consumer Dispute Redressal Agencies do not possess knowledge and experience in medicine, they are incapable of dealing with medical malpractice cases.

d) The Appellant had contended that medical malpractice cases involved complicated question of facts that are not fit for summary trials. Such cases should be kept outside the purview of the Act. The Supreme Court observed that in some cases complicated questions requiring recording of evidence of experts may arise but this was not so in all cases. There are many cases where the deficiency of services is due to obvious faults, as for instance, removal of the wrong limb or performance of an operation on the wrong patient or injecting drug to which the patient is allergic without looking into the out-patient card or the use of wrong anaesthetic or during surgery leaving swabs or other foreign objects inside the patient during surgery. Such issues arising in complaint can be easily established and speedily disposed off by consumer courts. In complaints involving complicated question of facts that require recording of evidence of experts, the consumer forum can ask the complainant to approach a civil court for appropriate relief. The Act clearly states that its provision is in addition to and not in derogation of the provisions of any law for the time being in force.

e) The Supreme Court drew the following conclusions:

i) Services rendered to patient by a medical practitioner (except where the service is free of charge to every patient or under a contract of personal service), by way of

consultation, diagnosis and treatment, both medical and surgical, would fall within the ambit of services as defined in Section 2(1)(o) of the Act

ii) The fact that medical practitioners belong to the medical profession and are subject to the disciplinary control of the Medical Council of India and /or State medical Councils would not exclude the services rendered by them from the ambit of the Act.

iii) Services rendered by a medical officer to his employer under the contract of employment is not 'service' under S. 2(1)(o) for purposes of the Act

iv) Services rendered at private or a Government hospitals, nursing homes, health centres and dispensaries for a fee are 'services' under the Act while services rendered free of charge are\ exempted. Payment of a token amount for purposes of registration will not alter the nature of services provided for free. Services rendered at Government or a private hospitals, nursing homes, health centres and dispensaries where services are rendered on payment of charges to those who can afford and free to those who cannot are also 'services' for the purposes of the Act. Hence in such cases the person who are rendered free services are 'beneficiaries' under S. 2(1) (d) thereby 'consumer' under the Act.

v) Services rendered free of charge by a medical practitioner attached to a hospital/ nursing home or where he is employed in a hospital/ nursing home that provides free medical facilities, are not 'services' under the Act.

vi) Where an insurance company pays, under the insurance policy, for consultation, diagnosis and medical treatment of the insurer then such an insurer is a consumer under S.291)(d) and services rendered either by the hospital or the medical practitioner is 'service' under S. 2(1)(o). Similarly where an employer bears the expenses of medical treatment of its employee, the employee is a consumer under the Act.

The remedy under Consumer Protection Act is in addition to civil remedy and it cannot be denied to a consumer merely on the ground that either the facts are too complicated or the complainant's claim is unreasonable.

In *Charan Singh vs. Healing Touch Hospital*,¹⁹⁹ the Appellant had brought a claim of Rs. 34 Lakh for removal of one of his kidneys without his consent during the course of the operation, which resulted in the loss of his job and huge expenses for his treatment and upkeep. The National Consumer Commission dismissed his complaint on the reasoning that his claim was excessive, exaggerated and unrealistic. This was because a consumer is required to approach the District, State or National Commission directly depending on the compensation claimed....the complainant was drawing a salary of Rs.3000 plus allowances...This is his allegation, which is not admitted by the opposite party. Even if we accept his contention is correct and even if we accept that as a result of wrong treatment given in the Hospital he has suffered permanent disability, the claim of Rs. 34 Lakh made by the complainant is excessive. We are of the view that this exaggerated claim has been made only for the purpose of invoking the jurisdiction of this commission...

The Supreme Court opined that the quantum of compensation is at the discretion of the Forum irrespective of the claim. The legislative intent behind the Act is to provide speedy summary trial and the Commission should have taken the complaint to its logical conclusion by asking the parties to adduce evidence and rendered its findings on merits. The Court further held,

a. While quantifying damages, Consumer Forums are required to make an attempt to serve the ends of justice so that compensation is awarded, in an established case, which not only serves the purpose of re compensating the individual, but which also at the same time aims to bring about a qualitative change in the attitude of the service provider.

b. It is not merely the alleged harm or mental pain, agony or physical discomfort, loss of salary and emoluments etc. suffered by the Appellant which is in issue here. It is also the quality of conduct committed by the Respondents upon which attention is required to be founded in a case of proven negligence. (para 13, p. 673)

¹⁹⁹IN THE SUPREME COURT OF INDIA. C.A. No. 767 of 2000. Decided On: 20.09.2000

In the case of *Dr. J.J. Merchant vs. Shrinath Chaturvedi*,²⁰⁰ the Supreme Court observed that in matters involving complicated questions of fact that require recording of evidence, the consumer forum has the discretionary power to direct the complainant to approach civil court for appropriate reliefs. Nevertheless, the procedure provided in the Act is adequate vis-à-vis civil suit to decide medical malpractice cases involving complicated questions of law and fact. For instance affidavits of experts including doctors can be taken as evidence. Thereafter, if cross-examination is sought by the other side and the Commission finds it proper, it can easily evolve a procedure permitting a party who intends to cross-examination to put certain questions in writing and experts including by doctors on affidavit could reply to those questions. In case where the stakes were high and if a party insisted on cross-examining such doctors or experts, there could be video or telephonic conference and at the was argued by the hospital that the parents were not consumers under the Act so could not get any relief. The Court rejected this argument and observed that even parents were covered under the Act and there was nothing in the law which prevented the parents as well as the child from recovering damages. In this case, a child patient was treated for seven days in the Spring Meadows Hospital (Noida) for typhoid. The consultant physician prescribed “Chloromphenical injection”, but the unqualified nurse misread it as “chloroquine” and indented, for the purchase of injection, “Lariago” (i.e. chloroquine). She injected chloroquine 5 mg IV, which was at least 3-1/2times of the normal paediatric dose. The patient suffered irreversible brain damage. Treatment for 21 days in AIIMS, New Delhi, did not help. The patient was compelled to live in a vegetative state.

The National Consumer Commission, whose judgment was confirmed by the Supreme Court, came to the conclusion, that the attending doctor was negligent, as he allowed an unqualified nurse to administer the injection, even though the consultant doctor had advised administration by the attending doctor himself.

The hospital and the nurse were jointly and severally liable. The Court made the following important observations:

Very often in a claim for compensation arising out of medical negligence a plea is taken that it is a case of bona fide mistake which under certain circumstances may

²⁰⁰ MANU/SC/0668/2002

be excusable, but a mistake which may tantamount to negligence cannot be pardoned....Gross medical mistake will always result in a finding of negligence. Use of wrong drug or wrong gas during the course of anaesthesia will frequently lead to the imposition of liability.... Even delegation of responsibility to another may amount to negligence in certain circumstances. A consultant could be negligent where he delegates the responsibility to his junior with the knowledge that the junior was in capable of performing his duties properly.

The Court ordered the following compensation in the case:

(a) Rs. 12.5 Lakh to the child (Rs. 10 Lakh compensation, plus Rs. 2.5 Lakh for equipment).

(b) Rs. 5 Lakh to the parents, for mental agony.

The Supreme Court further held that when a young child is taken to a hospital and treated by the hospital, then

(a) the child's parents would come within the definition of "consumer"; and

(b) the child also becomes a "consumer", being a beneficiary of such services.

[Even where the patient is a married daughter, the parents who are required "to spend for her treatment, are also 'consumers'", *Rajaram S.Parale vs. Dr. Kalpana Desai*²⁰¹

In the case of *Sailesh Munja vs. All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS)*²⁰² the hospital claimed that since the treatment was subsidized by the hospital it would not be covered under the Act. The National Commission rejected this argument and held since the treatment was subsidized and not totally free; the hospital would be covered under the Consumer Protection Act. In *Ranjit Kumar Das vs. ESI Hospital*²⁰³ the Complainant's wife was not given admission to ESI Hospital though the Complainant was registered under the Act. She died and the Complainant was ordered to be paid Rs. 2 lakh as compensation. This case is significant because it

²⁰¹ 1998 3 CPR 398 (BOM)

²⁰² 2004 3 CPR 27 (NC)

²⁰³ 1998 1 CPR 165 (Cal)

lays down that the ESI hospitals, though government run, are covered under the Consumer Protection Act.

In *Suhas Haldulkar vs. Secretary, Public Health Dept., State of Maharashtra*²⁰⁴ the National Commission held that since the hospital concerned was a Government hospital where patients are treated wholly without charge, a complaint before the Consumer Forum was not maintainable. The Complaint was dismissed since all the patients were treated free of charge but with liberty to the Complainant to approach the civil court. If of course some of the patients were being charged for the services provided, the Court would have had the jurisdiction even if the concerned patient was treated free of charge.

Can the consumer court go into the propriety of the fees charged by a doctor or a hospital?

In *B.S. Hegde vs. Dr. Sudhanshu Bhattacharya*²⁰⁵, the State Commission of Maharashtra held the doctor guilty of gross negligence for failure to render necessary post-operative care which was undertaken by him for a consideration (fee). This fee of Rs. 40,000 was paid by cheque a few days after the open-heart by-pass operation performed on the complainant at the Bombay Hospital, for rendering post operative care and treatment for a period of three months. The fee was held to be excessive, unreasonable and unjustifiable though it was conceded that the amount to be charged as fee for medical services was the choice of the medical practitioner. The state commission awarded a sum of Rs. 2 Lakh by way of compensation to the patient. The Complainant approached the Consumer Forum against exorbitant charges levied by the Respondent Cardiologist. Though the National Forum expressed its shock at the charges levelled, it held that it did not have the jurisdiction to go into the propriety of the fees charged by a doctor.

Civil Negligence and Deficiency in Medical Service

The substantial aspects of civil liability in negligence cases have, by and large, remained the same over decades with a few additions. The Indian civil law on negligence essentially is the judge made common law followed in England for

²⁰⁴ 1994 3 CPJ 89

²⁰⁵ (1992) CPJ 449

centuries. The main principles have been as laid out in the introduction to this chapter. This section looks at the application of these principles in concrete situations.

What are the duties of the doctor towards a patient who approaches him?

In *Dr. Laxman Balkrishna Joshi vs. Dr. Trimbak Bapu Godbole*²⁰⁶ the patient had died due to shock when the Appellant attempted reduction of fracture without taking elementary caution of giving anaesthesia. In the light of the surrounding circumstances it was held that the Appellant was negligent in applying too much of force in aligning the bone. The Supreme Court held that doctors have the discretion to choose the course of treatment to be given and such discretion is relatively large in an emergency case. Nevertheless, the doctor owes his patients a duty of care in deciding whether to undertake the case, his line of treatment to be adopted and a duty in administering that treatment. When a doctor gives medical advice and treatment, he impliedly undertakes that he is possessed of skill and knowledge for the purpose. And in executing his duty he must employ a reasonable degree of skill, knowledge and care.

The Supreme Court also cited with approval the observations in Halsbury Laws of England in its Vol. 30²⁰⁷ which state that whether or not he is a registered medical practitioner, such a person who is consulted by a patient owes him certain duties, namely

- a) Duty of care in deciding whether to undertake the case;
- b) Duty of care in deciding what treatment to give;
- c) Duty of care in his administration of that treatment; and
- d) Duty of care in answering a question put to him by a patient in circumstances in which he knows that the patient intends to rely on his answer.

A breach of any of these duties will support an action for negligence by the patient.

What does a complainant have to prove in order to carry home a charge of medical negligence? The Bombay High Court held that in a claim against medical negligence

²⁰⁶ AIR 1969 SC 128

²⁰⁷ Halsbury Laws of England, Vol. 30 Fourth Edition, p.31 para 34

it was not sufficient to show that the patient suffered in some way. It had to be proven that the suffering or death of the patient was the result of negligence on the part of the doctor. In *Philips India Ltd. vs. Kunju Punnu*²⁰⁸ the Bombay High Court held that in an action for negligence against a doctor, the plaintiff has to prove:

- a) That the defendant had a duty to take reasonable care towards the plaintiff to avoid the damage complained of;
- b) That there was a breach of duty on the part of the defendant; and
- c) That the breach of duty was the real cause of the damage complained of and such damage was reasonably foreseeable.

In the instant case the deceased was an employee of the Appellant. He approached the resident doctor of the company complaining of a digestive problem and was treated accordingly. After a week he returned, this time complaining of fever, cold and headache. Within four or five days he was brought in with high fever and was kept in the company's dispensary for observation. In the evening when the doctor found red pigmentation on his body he advised pathological tests and was taken to a nursing home of a specialist who treated him for bacteraemia. He approved of the treatment given by the doctor. Later it was discovered that the deceased was suffering from small pox that eventually caused his death.

The issue before the court was whether the doctor was negligent as he failed to diagnose small pox. The court held that a mistaken diagnosis was not necessarily negligent diagnosis. A practitioner can be liable if his diagnosis is so palpably wrong as to prove negligence, in other words, if his mistake is of such a nature as to imply an absence of reasonable skill and care on his part regard being had to the ordinary levels of skills in the profession. In the instant case there was no evidence to show that when the patient was taken to the company doctor any doctor of ordinary skill and competence could have diagnosed the disease of the patient as small pox or treated him for small pox. There was no epidemic of small pox at that time to induce the defendant doctor from carrying on test for the same. On the other hand, expert evidence showed that fulminating small pox could have occurred within 24 or 36 hours with no outward manifestations at all and that appearances were very indefinite with no findings on which to base a certain diagnosis. Thus, the defendant

²⁰⁸ 1975 M. L.J. 792

doctor was held to be not negligent. However, what is most important about this case is that the court held that just because a doctor is employed by a company to treat its employees, his responsibility is neither higher nor lower than that of an ordinary doctor.

In some circumstances, however, negligence may be attributed to a medical practitioner without proof of direct nexus between injury and conduct of the practitioner. In *Poonam Verma vs. Ashwin Patel*²⁰⁹ Respondent No. 1 was a registered homeopathy doctor who prescribed allopathic medicine for viral fever, which were prevalent in the Appellant's locality. The condition of the Appellant's husband deteriorated and he was admitted in Respondent No.2, a nursing home, for pathological tests and diagnosis. The deceased was treated for two days and as his condition did not improve he was shifted to another hospital where he died within hours of admission. In appeal the Supreme Court set up an ad hoc medical board to determine the cause of death. The board concluded that it was impossible to determine the true cause of the death. Therefore, claims against Respondent No.2 hospital were set aside but Respondent No.1 was held negligent on the ground that he was a homeopathic doctor and was not qualified to administer any other system of medicine. Respondent No.1 was held to be negligent per se.

In Shyam Sunder vs. State of Rajasthan,²¹⁰ the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur* was again discussed. The normal rule is that it is for the plaintiff to prove negligence, but, in some cases, considerable hardship is caused to the plaintiff, as the true cause of the accident is not known to him, but is solely within the knowledge of the defendant who caused it. The plaintiff can prove the accident but cannot prove how it happened (so as) to establish negligence on the part of the defendant. This hardship is sought to be avoided, in certain cases, by invoking the principle of *res ipsa loquitur*, where the thing is shown to be under the management of the defendant or his servants, and the accident is such, as, in the ordinary course of things, does not happen if

²⁰⁹ (1996) 4 SCC 332

²¹⁰ AIR 74 SC 876

those who have the management use proper care, then it affords reasonable evidence, in the absence of an explanation by the defendant, that the accident arose from want of care.

In *Jasbir Kaur vs. State of Punjab*²¹¹ the Petitioner's newborn child's eye was gouged out by a cat that crept into the ward. The infant was kept in a separate room under the charge of the Petitioner's relatives, as there was a shortage of cots. It was contended by the Respondent Government hospital that the incident took place because of the Petitioner's relative's negligence in leaving the child alone. The Court applied the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur* and held the hospital and State negligent. The safety and protection was under the control of the hospital and such an incident would have not have occurred in the ordinary course of things but did so, only because of the negligence of the hospital.

What happens when there is a difference of opinion amongst experts concerning the line of treatment to be adopted? In *Vinitha Ashok vs. Lakshmi Hospital*²¹² the Appellant's uterus was removed because of excessive bleeding during a surgery for termination of pregnancy that was discovered to be cervical pregnancy. The Appellant alleged that had a sonography been performed the nature of the pregnancy would have been determined and she would not have had her uterus removed. The Supreme Court observed that there was a difference of opinion among medical experts on whether ultra sonography could determine cervical pregnancy. The Appellant showed no symptoms of cervical pregnancy and there was no reason for the Respondent doctor to suspect that and resort to a different course of treatment. In Kerala removal of uterus was recommended for tackling excessive bleeding in case of cervical pregnancy, and in the instant case the Respondent had to resort to it to save the Appellant's life. The Supreme Court, thus, held that the course adopted by the Respondent doctor was reasonable and although the risk involved might have called for further investigation, the Respondent doctor's view could not be dismissed as being illogical. A difference of opinion

²¹¹ AIR 1995 P&H 278

²¹² (2001) 8 SCC 731

amongst experts on procedure adopted by a doctor cannot be called negligence if the procedure adopted is commonly in practice in an area.

A totally free treatment in a place which gives free treatment to everybody may not entitle the complainant to approach the Consumer Court. But he would still be entitled to approach the District Court by filing a suit for damages. In *S. Mittal vs. State of U.P.*²¹³ the Court was concerned with negligence in eye camps. An eye camp was organized for extending expert ophthalmic surgical treatment to patients of a particular place in Uttar Pradesh. The operated eyes of several patients were, however, irreversibly damaged, owing to post-operative infection of the “intra ocular cavities of the eyes”, caused by normal saline used at the time of surgery. A public interest litigation was filed, praying (apart from other relief) for compensation to victims for negligence in the arranging of the eye operations. The Supreme Court directed the State Government to pay Rs. 12,500 compensation to each victim (in addition to Rs.5, 000 already paid). The Supreme Court observed that (a) It was no defence, that the treatment was gratuitous or free. (b) The State Government would be liable for negligence in such activities.

In *Eby Minor vs. GEM Hospital*,²¹⁴ a newborn child developed gangrene because of which his hand below the elbow had to be amputated. He was a new born premature child placed in an incubator in the Respondent hospital. The National Commission found that there could have been no cause for gangrene except infection which could only have been contacted due to the negligence of the hospital. A compensation of Rs. 1, 00,000 was awarded.

Does the non-conduct of necessary pre-operative tests amount to negligence? This was the issue before the National Commission in *Dr.Kaligoundon vs. N. Thangamuthu*.²¹⁵ The Complainant’s wife had gynaecological problems in terms of excessive bleeding. She was operated upon and her uterus removed. After this, she complained of giddiness and vomiting and died. The death certificate gave the cause of death as renal failure and septicaemia. The National Commission found the doctor

²¹³ (1989) 3 SCC 223

²¹⁴ 2004 3 CPJ 37

²¹⁵ 2004 3 CPJ 29 (NC)

guilty of negligence on the ground that despite there being no urgency in undertaking the surgery no tests were conducted prior to the surgery to assess renal functioning. Similarly, in *S.V. Panchori vs. Dr. Kaushal Pandey*²¹⁶ the Commission held that omission to do a routine investigation constitutes deficiency in service.

The other issue which the Courts have been concerned with relates to the use of medical literature in dealing with medical negligence cases. Can such literature be used to prove or disprove the findings of negligence? In *P.Venkatalaxmiv. Dr. Y. SavithaDevi*²¹⁷ the National Commission observed that the ground reality was that rarely did doctors testify against doctors and therefore there was nothing wrong in using medical literature for determining a case.

Can a hospital be held guilty of negligence if it does not have adequate infrastructure? In *T. Vani Devi vs. Tugutla Laxmi Reddy*,²¹⁸ the Complainant's wife died in the nursing home where she was admitted for delivery. When she started bleeding no proper care was taken. The National Commission found that the nursing home was not equipped to deal with emergencies nor it had any arrangements to deal with emergencies and as such was guilty of negligence. The Consumer Forum has, however, held that if beds are not available in a hospital, refusing admission to the patient does not amount to deficiency in service. In *Bhajan Lal Gupta vs. Mool Chand Kharati Ram Hospital*²¹⁹ when the patient was refused admission and asked to go to another hospital due to non-availability of beds, the National Forum held that this did not amount to deficiency in service.

The issue of informed consent has been much litigated in foreign jurisdictions. The National Commission was confronted with this issue in the case of *Dr. P.S. Hardia vs. Kedarnath Sethia*²²⁰. The Complainant lost his eye due to a surgery which was not an emergency surgery. The Court found the doctor negligent on the basis that performed an operation which was totally unnecessary and also held that simply taking signature on a form stating "to treat him at his own risk under expressive

²¹⁶ 1999 1 CPJ 332

²¹⁷ 2004 2 CPJ 14 (NC)

²¹⁸ 2003 1 CPJ 180

²¹⁹ 2001 1 CPR 70

²²⁰ 2004 3 CPJ 19 (NC)

consent” did not absolve the doctor from taking a more detailed and direct consent especially when there was no emergency.

Is a doctor responsible for the negligence of his nurse? In *K.G.Krishnan vs. Praveen Kumar (minor)*,²²¹ the minor was admitted to a hospital with fever. He was given a paracetamol injection by the nurse in such a way that his right side was paralyzed. The nurse was not joined as a party to the case but the National Commission held that the nurse was the employee of the doctor and as such the doctor was vicariously liable for her negligence and directed the doctor to pay compensation of Rs. 1 Lakh.

Is a hospital liable for the negligence of its doctors? In *Savita Garg vs. Director, National Heart Institute* ²²² the Appellant’s husband was admitted to the National Heart Institute and according to the Appellant her husband died due to negligence of doctors and nurses treating him. The National Forum dismissed her case as she had not joined the treating doctors and nurses as parties to the case. She approached the Supreme Court. The Supreme Court, in this landmark decision held the following:

- It was not necessary to join the treating doctors or nurses as parties as long as the hospital was made a party
- Only the initial burden of proving negligence is on the Complainant. After this,
- it would be for the hospital to show from records, etc. as to what care and treatment were given. It is for the hospital to satisfy that there was no lack of care or diligence.
- The hospital is responsible for the acts of their permanent staff as well as staff whose services are temporarily requisitioned for the treatment of patients.

The Supreme Court remitted the case back to the National Forum for trying it on merits.

Does the failure to monitor dosage of drugs amount to negligence? In *Mohd. Ishfaq vs. Dr. Martin D’souza* ²²³ the patient was put on haemodialysis and was asked to undergo a kidney transplant. He was administered Amikacin 500 mg injections twice

²²¹ 2003 2 CPJ 125

²²² 2004 8 SCC 56

²²³ 2002 2 CPR 151

a day for 10 days at the end of which he lost his hearing totally. The National Commission held that it was the responsibility of the hospital to monitor the patient and modify the dosage as per the available literature and failure to do so amounted to negligence. The patient was ordered to be paid Rs. 4 Lakh as compensation for treatment and Rs. 2 Lakh towards the mental agony suffered by him.

Can a doctor charge for facilities he does not offer? In *R.M. Joshi vs. Dr. P.B. Tahilramani*²²⁴ the State Commission ordered the recovery of bed charges when the patient was made to sleep on a table amounted to deficiency in service. Can a doctor be charged for performing a surgery, which is not necessary? In *Uttaranchal Forest Hospital Trust vs. Smt. Raisan*²²⁵ the complainant's organ was removed. When the organ was sent for diagnosis no cancer was found. The State Commission found the doctor guilty of negligence for performing a surgery that was wholly unnecessary.

Does the failure of a procedure undertaken by a doctor imply that he was negligent? The Supreme Court has categorically said no. In *State of Punjab vs. Shiv Ram*²²⁶ the Supreme Court was dealing with a case where sterilization had failed and the woman gave birth to a child. This was in a State hospital. The State argued that there was always a small chance of failure in such procedures and the failure of sterilization did not mean that the doctor was negligent. The Supreme Court upheld this argument and cited with approval a decision of the English Court in *Eyre vs. Measday*²²⁷ in which the Court had observed,

In the absence of any express warranty, the Court should be slow to imply against a medical man an unqualified warranty as to the results of an intended operation, for the very simple reason that, objectively speaking, it is most unlikely that a responsible medical man would give a warranty of this nature.

²²⁴ 1993 3 CPR 435 (Bom)

²²⁵ 2004 1 CPJ 257

²²⁶ (2005) 7 SCC 1

²²⁷ 1986 1 ALL ER 488

REVIEW OF JUDICIAL PRONOUNCEMENTS IN INDIA

A review of Indian decisions on medical negligence would be relevant in this regard. In *John Oni Akerele v. The King*²²⁸, a duly qualified medical practitioner gave to his patient the injection of Sobita which consisted of sodium bismuth tartrate as given in the British Pharmacopoeia. However, what was administered was an overdose of Sobita. The patient died. The doctor was accused of manslaughter, reckless and negligent act. He was convicted. The matter reached in appeal before the House of Lords. Their Lordships quashed the conviction and summed up the position as under,

- That a doctor is not criminally responsible for a patient's death unless his negligence or incompetence went beyond a mere matter of compensation between subjects and showed such disregard for life and safety of others as to amount to a crime against the State.
- That the degree of negligence required is that it should be gross and that neither a jury nor a court can transform negligence of a lesser degree into gross negligence merely by giving it that appellation. There is a difference in kind between the negligence which gives a right to compensation and the negligence which is a crime.
- It is impossible to define culpable or criminal negligence, and it is not possible to make the distinction between actionable negligence and criminal negligence intelligible, except by means of illustrations drawn from actual judicial opinion. The most favourable view of the conduct of an accused medical man has to be taken, for it would be most fatal to the efficiency of the medical profession if no one could administer medicine without a halter round his neck

The question of degree has always been considered as relevant to a distinction between negligence in civil law and negligence in criminal law. In *Kurban Hussein Mohamedalli Rangawalla v. State of Maharashtra*²²⁹ while dealing with Section 304A of IPC, the following statement of law by Sir Lawrence Jenkins in *Emperor v. Omkar Rampratap*,²³⁰ was cited with approval,

²²⁸ AIR 1943 PC 72.

²²⁹ indiankanoon.org/search/?formInput=state%20of%20karnatka

²³⁰ 4 Bom LR 679,

"To impose criminal liability under Section 304-A, it is necessary that the death should have been the direct result of a rash and negligent act of the accused, and that act must be the proximate and efficient cause without the intervention of another's negligence. It must be the causa causans; it is not enough that it may have been the causa sine qua non."

The above said view of the law has been generally followed by High Courts in India. The same view has been reiterated in *Kishan Chand &Anr. v. The State of Haryana*.²³¹

In, *Juggankhan v. The State of Madhya Pradesh*²³², the accused, a registered Homoeopath, administered 24 drops of stramonium and a leaf of datura to the patient suffering from guinea worm. The accused had not studied the effect of such substances being administered to a human being. The poisonous contents of the leaf of datura were not satisfactorily established by the prosecution. The Supreme Court exonerated the accused of the charge under Section 302 IPC. However, on a finding that stramonium and datura leaves are poisonous and in no system of medicine, except perhaps Ayurvedic system, the datura leaf is given as cure for guinea worm, the act of the accused who prescribed poisonous material without studying their probable effect was held to be a rash and negligent act. It would be seen that the profession of a Homoeopath which the accused claimed to profess did not permit use of the substance administered to the patient.

The accused had no knowledge of the effect of such substance being administered and yet he did so. In this background, the inference of the accused being guilty of rash and negligent act was drawn against him. Thus the principle which emerges is that a doctor who administers a medicine known to or used in a particular branch of medical profession impliedly declares that he has knowledge of that branch of science and if he does not, in fact, possess that knowledge, he is prima facie acting with rashness or negligence.

²³¹(1970) 3 SCC 904.

²³²(1965) 1 SCR 14

*Dr. Laxman Balkrishna Joshi v. Dr. Trimbak Bapu Godbole and Anr*²³³ was a case under Fatal Accidents Act, 1855. The duties which a doctor owes to his patients came up for consideration. The Supreme Court held that a person who holds himself out ready to give medical advice and treatment impliedly undertakes that he is possessed of skill and knowledge for that purpose.

In *Poonam Verma v. Ashwin Patel and Ors*²³⁴ a doctor registered as medical practitioner and entitled to practice in Homoeopathy only, prescribed an allopathic medicine to the patient. The patient died. The doctor was held to be negligent and liable to compensate the wife of the deceased for the death of her husband on the ground that the doctor who was entitled to practice in homoeopathy only, was under a statutory duty not to enter the field of any other system of medicine and since he trespassed into a prohibited field and prescribed the allopathic medicine to the patient causing the death, his conduct amounted to negligence per se actionable in civil law.

In *Achutrao Haribhau Khodwa and Ors.v State of Maharashtra and Ors*²³⁵ the Supreme Court noticed that in the very nature of medical profession, skills differ from doctor to doctor and more than one alternative course of treatment are available, all admissible. Negligence cannot be attributed to a doctor so long as he is performing his duties to the best of his ability and with due care and caution. Merely because the doctor chooses one course of action in preference to the other one available, he would not be liable if the course of action chosen by him was acceptable to the medical profession. It was a case where a mop was left inside the lady patient's abdomen during an operation. Peritonitis developed which led to a second surgery being performed on her, but she could not survive. Liability for negligence was fastened on the surgeon because no valid explanation was forthcoming for the mop having been left inside the abdomen of the lady. The doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur* was held applicable 'in a case like this'.

²³³ 1969)1 SCR 206

²³⁴ (1996) 4 SCC 332

²³⁵ (1996) 2 SCC 634

In, *Dr. Suresh Gupta v. Govt. of NCT of Delhi and Anr*²³⁶. the legal decision is almost firmly established that where a patient dies due to negligent medical treatment of the doctor, the doctor can be made liable in civil law for paying compensation and damages in tort and the same time, if the degree of negligence so gross and his act was reckless as to endanger the life of the patient, he would also be made criminally liable to offence under Section 304-A IPC. "Thus a doctor cannot be held criminally responsible for patient's death unless his negligence or incompetence showed such disregard for life and safety of his patient as to amount to a crime against the State".

In the case of *Jacob Mathew v. State of Punjab*, three Judge Bench of Supreme Court by order quashed prosecution of a medical professional under Section 304-A/34 IPC and disposed of all the interlocutory applications that doctors should not be held criminally responsible unless there is a prima-facie evidence before the Court in the form of a credible opinion from another competent doctor, preferably a Government doctor in the same field of medicine supporting the charges of rash and negligent act.

The result of all these decisions based on civil and criminal approaches can be summed as

(1) Negligence is the breach of a duty caused by omission to do something which a reasonable man guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulate the conduct of human affairs would do, or doing something which a prudent and reasonable man would not do. Negligence becomes actionable on account of injury resulting from the act or omission amounting to negligence attributable to the person sued. The essential components of negligence are three: 'duty', 'breach' and 'resulting damage'.

(2) Negligence in the context of medical profession necessarily calls for a treatment with a difference. To infer rashness or negligence on the part of a professional, in particular a doctor, additional considerations apply. A case of occupational negligence is different from one of professional negligence. A simple lack of care, an error of judgment or an accident, is not proof of negligence on the part of a medical professional. So long as a doctor follows a practice acceptable to the medical

²³⁶ MANU/SC/0579/2004

profession of that day, he cannot be held liable for negligence merely because a better alternative course or method of treatment was also available or simply because a more skilled doctor would not have chosen to follow or resort to that practice or procedure which the accused followed. When it comes to the failure of taking precautions what has to be seen is whether those precautions were taken which the ordinary experience of men has found to be sufficient; a failure to use special or extraordinary precautions which might have prevented the particular happening cannot be the standard for judging the alleged negligence.

(3) A professional may be held liable for negligence on one of the two findings: either he was not possessed of the requisite skill which he professed to have possessed, or, he did not exercise, with reasonable competence in the given case, the skill which he did possess. The standard to be applied for judging, whether the person charged has been negligent or not, would be that of an ordinary competent person exercising ordinary skill in that profession. It is not possible for every professional to possess the highest level of expertise or skills in that branch which he practices.

(4) The jurisprudential concept of negligence differs in civil and criminal law. What may be negligence in civil law may not necessarily be negligence in criminal law. For negligence to amount to an offence, the element of mens rea must be shown to exist. For an act to amount to criminal negligence, the degree of negligence should be much higher i.e. gross or of a very high degree. Negligence which is neither gross nor of a higher degree may provide a ground for action in civil law but cannot form the basis for prosecution.

(5) The word 'gross' has not been used in Section 304A of IPC, yet it is settled that in criminal law negligence or recklessness, to be so held, must be of such a high degree as to be 'gross'. The expression 'rash or negligent act' as occurring in Section 304A of the IPC has to be read as qualified by the word 'grossly'.

(6) To prosecute a medical professional for negligence under criminal law it must be shown that the accused did something or failed to do something which in the given facts and circumstances no medical professional in his ordinary senses and prudence would have done or failed to do. The hazard taken by the accused doctor should be of such a nature that the injury which resulted was most likely imminent.

(7) *Res ipsa loquitur* is only a rule of evidence and operates in the domain of civil law especially in cases of torts and helps in determining the onus of proof in actions relating to negligence. It cannot be pressed in service for determining per se the

liability for negligence within the domain of criminal law. Res ipsa loquitor has, if at all, a limited application in trial on a charge of criminal negligence.

In comparison to Criminal Negligence, that needs to be defined as gross negligence, the medical negligence under Consumer Protection Act does not require mens rea to be proved. Sometimes the simplification of judicial process under CPA can be equated to res ipsa loquitor.

There is complaint procedure under Medical Council Regulations. A patient can complain to the Medical Council of India in relation to alleged medical negligence seek an action taken against the medical professional. The details of the Medical Council Regulations are as follows.

2.7 Medical Council of India Regulations²³⁷

The code of ethics for medical professionals adopted by the Indian parliament as a part of the Medical Council Act, governs the conduct of the medical professionals in their medical work, in their economic activity and with regards to their relationship with other professionals and the society at large. Medical ethics, particularly those related to medical practice and societal responsibility, are essentially formulated on the basis of the justice theory developed by the moral philosophers. There are four principles, which form the fundamentals of justice theory as applied to the medical care. They are as follows:

- Principle of non-maleficence: It is also summed up in the axiom, first do no harm, or that the medical intervention should not cause harm to the patient seeking care.
- Principle of beneficence: This principle stipulates that the medical intervention not only should not harm, but should also be intended for the benefit of the patient.
- Principle of autonomy: This principle has developed to its fullest extent only in last quarter century and has replaced what was earlier called 'medical paternalism'. It is also in harmony with the liberal democratic ethos of individual liberty and choice. Essentially it means that the patient is an independent individual and any medical intervention should be done only after full information is given and the patient has expressly consented for such an intervention. This also gives the patient a right to make choice as to what kind of medical intervention is best suited for him or her.

²³⁷ See Annexure IV

- Principle of justice: This principle makes it clear that the doctors are responsible to the society and that they must follow the non-discriminatory way of medical practice.

The professionals do face ethical dilemmas in day to day medical practice. These dilemmas are sought to be resolved, in a case to case basis, by weighing each principle as applicable to the situation.²³⁸

In a study aimed to assess the knowledge of, and attitudes to, medical ethics among doctors in the Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences (KIMS), Bhubaneswar, Orissa. A self-administered structured questionnaire was administered to 120 practitioners and it was found that, there was lack of proper and detailed knowledge on the MCI's Code of Ethics among doctors in KIMS, though a little more than half of them had read it once or partially. There is a need to sensitize them to the Code of Ethics and to medical ethics in general. A test on the code at the time of registration could be considered. The medical ethics; acts related to medical practice should be emphasized in the MBBS under graduate so also in post graduate syllabus and examinations. There is always a continuum between practice and education because a medical career is one of life-long learning. Medical ethics teaching and training should help the doctors at any level whatever may be the discipline to assimilate and conceptualize the basic principles of ethical reasoning. The application of ethics to medical practice dates back to ancient civilization as even today, all medical graduates must swear symbolic adherence to the Hippocratic Oath. Codes of conduct and laws regulating the profession are laid down from time to time. The periodical CME programme in medical ethics should be mandatory for all practitioners.²³⁹

The Code of Medical Ethics as described by the Medical Council of India in 2002, states that the medical professional should maintain good medical practice .Chapter 1.2.1 says that, the Principal objective of the medical profession is to render service to humanity with full respect for the dignity of profession and man. Physicians should

²³⁸ Aditi Iyer&Amar Jesani,Medical ethics for self-regulation of medical profession and practice, 2004, CEHAT, pp.7

²³⁹ Shreemanta Kumar Dash, Medical Ethics, Duties & Medical Negligence Awareness among the Practitioners in a Teaching Medical College, Hospital-A Survey;2010,J Indian Acad. Forensic Med, 32(2),p.155

merit the confidence of patients entrusted to their care, rendering to each a full measure of service and devotion. Physicians should try continuously to improve medical knowledge and skills and should make available to their patients and colleagues the benefits of their professional attainments. The physician should practice methods of healing founded on scientific basis and should not associate professionally with anyone who violates this principle. The honoured ideals of the medical profession imply that the responsibilities of the physician extend not only to individuals but also to society.²⁴⁰

The inherent quality of any professional service depends on its ethical values as imbibed by its professionals.; Every profession has to zealously safeguard its autonomy, and at the same time take appropriate measures to extract professional accountability, in the event that the professional indulges in any kind of professional misconduct. The kind of assurance alone infuses confidence in the minds of the public. Therefore, in this respect, the professional bodies prescribe codes of ethical behaviour, which every professional is expected to adopt and comply with. This is how a professional body, in a democratic way, conceives, prescribes and enforces its code of ethics.²⁴¹

The Medical Council of India has established a Code of Ethics called the Indian Medical Council (Professional Conduct, Etiquette and Ethics) Regulations, 2002 for all medical practitioners, which they are bound to follow. This is divided in to 8 chapters. While Chapter 1 to 6 describe Maintaining the good medical practice, duties of physicians to patients, each other and to the paramedics, what constitutes unethical acts; chapter 7 and 8 describe misconduct and punishment and disciplinary action that the medical council can take.

Professional incompetence shall be judged by peer group as per guidelines prescribed by Medical Council of India.²⁴²

²⁴⁰ Code of Ethics Regulations, 2002, Medical Council of India, Chapter 1.2.1

²⁴¹ S.V.JOGA RAO, LAW, MEDICAL ETHICS AND SYSTEMATIC FRAMEWORK: AN OVERVIEW ,MEDICAL ETHICS, A READY REFERENCER, 1st edition,2010,Legalaxy Publications, pp. 37

²⁴² CONSUMER LAW ARTICLES, March 12, 2007, IndLaw.com, Medical Negligence – How far should doctors be held liable?

The Medical Council of India (MCI) in an amendment to its existing code of conduct, the Indian Medical Council (professional conduct, etiquette and ethics) regulations 2002, has proposed sweeping guidelines on the relationship between the pharmaceutical industry and the medical profession in India.

While discussing the MCI guidelines in relation to allied health care sector industry, Dr.Sanjay Nagral says, it is an attempt at a code of ethical conduct for doctors and professional associations in their relationship with the pharmaceutical and allied health sector industry. The MCI is a quasi-judicial body and its code, though not law is ethically binding on all practitioners of modern medicine in India. It is interesting that a council which is not exactly known for its proactive stance on ethics has chosen to issue one of the most explicit and comprehensive set of rules on this subject. The impact of these guidelines on ground reality remains to be seen but, if recent news items are to be believed, by doing so the MCI has at the least succeeded in breaking the conspiracy of silence that surrounded this area in India. In a sense, the guidelines read like a confessional list of a large number of debatable practices in industry marketing that have become commonplace over the years. The guidelines also cover clinical trials sponsored by the industry, an area of current relevance. Following the initial guidelines, the MCI has now gone a step further by announcing a list of punishments which are graded based on the financial quantum of the gift received. For example, those who have received more than Rs 1 Lakh (Rs 100 000) will be deregistered for more than a year. The MCI claims that this is the first time in the world that quantum of punishment have been specified.²⁴³

Maintenance of Medical Records have been a point of discussion and the Medical Council of India, has issued the (Professional Conduct, Etiquette and Ethics) Regulations, 2002, which mentions the following on Maintenance of Medical Records (Section 1.3)

The Existing Medical Ethics Codes and Laws,
http://www.indlaw.com/guest/databasesearch/articles/core_articledisplay.asp?id=medical4_focus

Last Accessed Sept 12,2012

²⁴³ Sanjay Nagral, The Medical Council of India guidelines on industry–physician relationship: Breaking the conspiracy of silence; THE NATIONAL MEDICAL JOURNAL OF INDIA. VOL. 23, NO.2, 2010. pp. 69

- Every physician shall maintain the medical records pertaining to his / her indoor patients for a period of three years from the date of commencement of the treatment in a standard proforma laid down by the Medical Council of India (Section 1.3.1 and Annexure IV).
- If any request is made for medical records either by the patients / authorised attendant or legal authorities involved, the same may be duly acknowledged and documents shall be issued within the period of 72 hours (Section 1.3.2)
- A registered medical practitioner shall maintain a Register of Medical Certificates giving full details of certificates issued. When issuing a medical certificate he / she shall always enter the identification marks of the patient and keep a copy of the certificate. He / She shall not omit to record the signature and/or thumb mark, address and at least one identification mark of the patient on the medical certificates or report. The medical certificate shall be prepared. (Section 1.3.3 and Annexure IV).
- Efforts shall be made to computerize medical records for quick retrieval. (Section 1.3.4)²⁴⁴

The ethical and legal dimensions of the issue of medical negligence, take upper hand while discussing the pros and cons of self regulation of professionals by professional bodies and Medical Council. The medical professional who is ethical, need not be worried about the legal aspects, since he/she follows the ethical guidelines. In other words, the medical professional who follows the ethical guidelines of the Medical Council, is shielded from any legal action being taken by patients.

In response to the changing environment, Code of Medical Ethics has also been subjected to thorough amendments. No doubt, the amended Code itself requires further amendments. Be that as it may, owing to the fact this code is a formal legal document; it is a matter of mandate that it should be enforced meaningfully in a practical context. The present day context clearly reveals the changing landscape of doctor patient relationships. Economics of healthcare delivery seems to be the crucial factor for these developments. A person who is in need of timely health care

²⁴⁴ Jay Mehta, Diana Cyrus, 2010, Effective Management of Medical Records, WEB LINK - <http://www.expresshealthcare.in/201107/market28.shtml>, last accessed Oct.6,2012

is caught between the issues of accessibility and affordability. Similarly a professional doctor who renders health care service is sandwiched between patient satisfaction and professional accountability. Professions are for the people and not for professionals. Hence, professional accountability must be norm. This is equally applicable to every professional service, not only to the medical profession.²⁴⁵

2.8 International Perspective

Law is a response to societies felt needs. Legislation is enacted to deal with problems the society is facing, or expects soon to face. Likewise, courts deciding cases look beyond the situations and interests of the individuals in the particular litigation and try to reach decisions that will also constitute good public policy. Consequently, studying both legislation and adjudication in a particular field is a way of seeing what problems society is facing or feels it is facing in that area and what it regards as workable solutions.²⁴⁶

“It is so easy to be wise after the event and to condemn as negligence that which is only a misadventure. One ought always to be on one’s guard against it, especially in cases against hospitals and doctors. Medical science has conferred great benefits on mankind, but those benefits are attended by considerable risks . . . one cannot take the benefits without taking the risks . . . one must insist on due care for the patient at every point, but one must not condemn as negligence that which is only a misadventure.”

Those were Lord Denning's words in *Roe v Minister of Health*²⁴⁷ a particularly sad case in which two men suffered severe injuries as a consequence of being given spinal anaesthetics. The anaesthetic agents were stored in glass ampoules and the ampoules themselves were kept in a solution of phenol. Unknown to anyone and held to be not capable of reasonable discovery - the glass of the ampoules was

²⁴⁵ S.V.Joga Rao, Conclusion, MEDICAL ETHICS, A READY REFERENCER, 2004, 1st edition., Bangalore. Legalaxy Publications, pp. 113-114.

²⁴⁶ Arnold J. Rosoff, 2004, HEALTH LAW AT FIFTY YEARS: A LOOK BACK, HEALTH MATRIX , Vol. 14:197

²⁴⁷ 1954, 2 WLR 915

awed with invisible hairline cracks through which the phenol penetrated, adulterating the anaesthetic agent and thus causing the injuries to these two patients.²⁴⁸

An essential component of an action in negligence against a doctor is proof that the doctor failed to provide the required standard of care under the circumstances. Traditionally the standard of care in law has been determined according to the *Bolam* test. *Chiu Keow v Government of Malaysia*²⁴⁹ This is based on the principle that a doctor does not breach the legal standard of care, and is therefore not negligent, if the practice is supported by a responsible body of similar professionals.

- The *Bolam* principle, however, has been perceived as being excessively reliant upon medical testimony supporting the defendant.
- The judgment given by the House of Lords in the recent case of *Bolitho* imposes a requirement that the standard proclaimed must be justified on a logical basis and must have considered the risks and benefits of competing options.

The effect of *Bolitho* is that the court will take a more enquiring stance to test the medical evidence offered by both parties in litigation, in order to reach its own conclusions. Recent case law shows how the court has applied the *Bolitho* approach in determining the standard of care in cases of clinical negligence. An understanding of this approach and of the shift from the traditional *Bolam* test is relevant to all medical practitioners, particularly in a climate that is increasingly litigious.²⁵⁰

In medical litigation, the test for the standard of care in law expected of doctors is based on the principle enunciated in *Bolam*. Put at its simplest, the test is that a medical practitioner does not fail to reach the standard of care if a responsible body of similar medical peers supports the action in question. The judgment in *Bolitho*, however, suggests a judicial move at the highest level to shift the balance from an excessive reliance on medical testimony supporting a defendant doctor, to a more enquiring approach to be taken by the court. In order to reach its own conclusion on the reasonableness of clinical conduct, the court will arbitrate on the standard in

²⁴⁸ John R.Griffith, , CLINICAL NEGLIGENCE IN GENERAL PRACTICE THE LAW OF NEGLIGENCE, Edited by Michael Drury 2000, pp.43

²⁴⁹ 1967 1 WLR 813

²⁵⁰ Ash Samanta and Jo Samanta, 2003, Legal standard of care: a shift from the traditional Bolam test, Clinical Medicine Vol.3 No 5 September/October 2003,pp. 443

each case. This would operate within the framework of normative values held by society. Patient empowerment is a strong theme in the new health service. This is likely to act as a conjunctive force in shifting the traditional 'accepted practice' approach to one whereby the standard of care is set by the court, on the basis of 'expected practice'. This would be determined by evaluating the reasonableness of competing options.²⁵¹

The most accepted expression of the duty principle is the one made by Lord Atkin in the leading case of *Donoghue v Stevenson*.¹⁰ The plaintiff's friends bought her a ginger beer in a café, she drank some of it and as she was helping herself to a second glass, the remains of a decomposed snail floated to the top of her glass. The nauseating sight of this and the impurities she already drank resulted in a shock and severe gastroenteritis. The case went all the way to the House of Lords on the preliminary issue as to whether a duty of care existed. The question for the House of Lords to decide was: if a company produced a drink and sold it to a distributor, was it under any legal duty to the ultimate purchaser or consumer to ensure reasonable care that the article was free from defect likely to cause injury to health? Lord Atkin stated.

The English law states that there must be and is, some general conception of relations given rise to a duty of which the particular cause found in the books are but instances. He went on to lay down the basis of the present law in the "neighbour" principle in this much-quoted passage:

"The rule is, you are to "love your neighbour" and the lawyer's question saying 'who is my neighbour', receives a restricted reply. You must take care to avoid acts or omissions which you can reasonably foresee would be likely to injure your neighbour. Who, then in law, is my neighbour? The answer seems to be a person who is so closely and directly affected by my act that I ought reasonably to have them in contemplation as being so affected when I was directing my mind to the acts or omission which is called in question".

²⁵¹Id. pp. 446

This statement suggests the existence of a general duty of care towards anyone who is likely to suffer injury through the defendant's careless conduct. Even though the rule was propounded in the context of a manufacturer/consumer relationship, it is applied as a general principle beyond the initial context in which it was propounded. This text has proved the foundation upon which countless cases of alleged negligence have been tried and still continue to be judged.²⁵²

*Bolam v Friern Hospital Management Committee*²⁵³ is an English tort law case that lays down the typical rule for assessing the appropriate standard of reasonable care in negligence cases involving skilled professionals (e.g. doctors): the "*Bolam test*". Where the defendant has represented him or herself as having more than average skills and abilities, this test expects standards which must be in accordance with a responsible body of opinion, even if others differ in opinion.

Bolam test:

1. Firstly, it must be established that there is a duty of care (between a doctor and patient this can be taken for granted).
2. Second, it must be shown that the duty of care has been breached. This is where the Bolam test is relevant, because falling below the standard of a responsible body of medical men means that person will be considered negligent.
3. Third it must be shown that there was a causal link between the breach of duty and harm.
4. And fourth, it must be shown that the harm was not too remote.²⁵⁴

Health professionals, politicians, and media commentators are rarely in agreement, except when it is to cite a "culture of blame" as the greatest cause of litigation in medical error today. Yet, few stop to question the cultural tableau of doctor, patient, and lawyer, or reflect on what current medical jurisprudence means for the practice of medicine. Blame is the sole form of redress and the legal counterpoint between aggrieved doctors and patients in most developed countries. Like it or not, lawyers,

²⁵²Eric Okojie, Professional Medical Negligence in Nigeria, 1994, www.nigerianlawguru.com/.../PROFESSIONAL%20MEDICAL%20NEG

²⁵³[1957] 1 WLR 583

²⁵⁴ Supra

doctors, and patients have all played leading roles in the history of medical negligence.²⁵⁵

Most countries have, eventually, arrived at a similarly confrontational and definitive legal process of dealing with medical negligence, usually some variant of tort in medical jurisprudence. Yet the social and historical processes that have contributed to the development of medical malpractice and, perhaps more importantly, what one define as medical negligence are little known. Medical negligence, I would suggest, is a complex relationship, a space, more than a “thing”, a shifting, malleable, interaction between time and place and, to varying degrees, society, law, ethics, medical practice, health professionals, and patients.

In common with other contemporary nations, the USA had a brief flirtation with contract law in the 19th century. However, jurisprudence sat uneasily with the unequal doctor-patient relationship; patients could not be expected to understand medical nomenclature or esoteric diagnosis and regimen. Additionally, 19th-century US physicians balked at the thought of being held in the same regard as tradesmen. This echoes a similar anxiety about professional status across Europe and its colonies in this period. However, in post-revolution North America, elitism was frowned upon and there, more than anywhere else, the medical profession struggled for harder and longer to establish itself into a completely amalgamated profession. Revolution also brought individual liberties and rights that, together with a decline in religious fatalism, led to a great number of medical lawsuits in 19th century North America. Lawyers there saw medical malpractice lawsuits as a source of wealth, which further exacerbated the burgeoning malpractice crisis. When, finally, the US medical profession united and raised professional standards, patients' expectations of the acceptable standard of care went up concomitantly. Inevitably, physicians sought liability insurance: mitigating their individual risk but rendering each and every insured medical professional a financially worthy prospect for medical litigation.

The trajectory of medical negligence in the USA contrasts with the British experience, where it is difficult to hold on to one conception through time. Within

²⁵⁵ Kim Price, Towards a History of Medical Negligence, *The Lancet*, [Volume 375, Issue 9710](#), 2010, pp. 192 – 193.

modern history, I would argue that there are at least six distinct periods. Each period offers different notions of what negligence has meant in the past and hints how different it may be again, in the future. During the 18th century until the mid 19th century, patients had a commanding role: they had a great deal of control over diagnosis, the law governing negligence claims, and the contractual process between patient and doctor. Then from the mid-19th century to the end of that century doctors began to gain the upper hand through advances in diagnosis, knowledge, skill, technical innovation, and, particularly, professionalization. However, patients retained the upper hand in law; medical negligence was viewed very much under the light of a trade contract. For the first half of the 20th century, new acts in national insurance, pension rights, state doctoring, and voting brought doctors closer to the state. There were many developments in state medicine, welfare, and public health. In English law, doctors were also beginning to gain the upper hand; the law increasingly viewed doctors' negligence as something apart from regular trade negligence. The decades leading up to the 1980s could be regarded as perhaps a "golden age" for doctors in the UK. During the 1950s, developments in the National Health Service (NHS) and English courtrooms led to the infamous "*Bolam*" precedent in 1957, which was a landmark judgment, empowering doctors within tort law. From then, doctors had complete power of diagnosis and they essentially governed the law of medical negligence. Patients had fewer rights in law, diagnosis, and policy than ever before. From the 1980s to the end of the 20th century, the Conservative government began the gradual introduction of privatization into the NHS, a trend that was continued under Labour. Competition entered the NHS and (some commentators argue) so did an increase in patients' expectations. Doctors retained the power of diagnosis, and, essentially, were self-regulating in medical negligence law. Despite this, medical negligence claims increased. Ethical issues, human rights, patients' rights, and consumer expectations converged during this time to exacerbate an increased use of litigation in cases of medical negligence. In the 21st century, there have been even greater calls for patients' rights. Although doctors have retained the power of diagnosis, there has been greater participation from the lay public in ethical and health-administrative considerations.

Movement from Bolam to Bolitho:

The “Bolam” precedent has come under increasing pressure in the law courts, leading to the “Bolitho” decision, whereby juries, in exceptional cases, are theoretically allowed to judge between medical experts, although, essentially, changing nothing in practice from “Bolam”.²⁵⁶

The case summary of *Bolitho*²⁵⁷ is as follows,

Patrick *Bolitho*, plaintiffs son, at the age of two had been detected with a patent ductus arteriosus, a respiratory disorder, a surgery, in 1983 had been conducted to correct this anomaly from which Patrick recuperated well. A year later he was admitted to St. Bartholomew’s hospital with cough disorder. He was placed under the care of Dr. Horne According to the nurse at duty then, she did not see the patient when she asked her to do so. Again on second occasion Dr. Horne delegated the care to another doctor, Dr. Rodger, her junior. Dr. Rodger too did not see the patient. This led to deterioration of patient’s health leading to brain damage from which he subsequently died.

It was contented by the experts from the plaintiff’s side that had the doctor attended the patient and intubated the patent on time, the patient could have been saved. To this the response of the defendant was that had she attended the patient she would not have attempted intubation and also cited *Bolam* to demonstrate that a responsible body of opinion would have agreed with her. So, hypothetically, the consequence would have been the same even if she had attempted intubation.

The court was of the opinion that there has to be a logical basis for the opinion not to intubate. A judge will be entitled to choose between two bodies of expert opinion and to reject an opinion which is 'logically indefensible'. This has been interpreted as being a situation where the Court sets the law not the profession. However, Lord Browne Wilkinson held that the court would hold a practice that was in conformity with a sound body of expert opinion to be negligent only in "a rare case". On the facts, it was decided that not intubating the child in the particular circumstances at

²⁵⁶ Supra Note 110

²⁵⁷ *Bolitho v City and Hackney Health Authority* (1998) AC, 232.

hand was not a negligent way to take, even though the expert opinion on the matter was divided.

The “*Bolam* test” means that today under English law the medical profession sets its own standard of medical care. This, more than anything else, has led to an awkward juxtaposition for historians assessing negligence in the UK before and after the mid-20th century. Since *Bolam*, modern medical negligence law can be whittled down to three fundamental factors: one, confirming the patient was “owed a legal duty of care” by the health practitioner who is the “defendant” in cases of medical negligence; two, establishing that the defendant was in “breach” of that duty of care in failing to reach the standard of care required by law; three, proving that this breach of duty caused or contributed to the damage or injury to the patient. Establishing causation was always central to negligence law in history, but the approaches, theories, and methods to establish it have changed through time. Since *Bolam*, “reasonable practice” by a reasonable practitioner is used in law to establish what the standard of care is and if this had been breached and, consequently, if the breach was a causal factor in the outcome. Crucially, the by product of a “standard of care” was that patients' rights moved to the centre of medical negligence. This provides us with an interesting prism to observe the past.²⁵⁸

There are a number of difficulties with the *Bolam* test which still apply asymmetrically in negligence cases, mainly to the advantage of the defendant doctor, or health authority; it is often too easy to invoke *Bolam* on the basis of single expert's opinion, and conversely too difficult for the claimant to show that no other doctor could have acted similarly.

As a measure of liability, *Bolam* gives weight to what medical practice is (or what contemporary practice was) rather than what practice should be. So instead of upholding the standard of care that is good, *Bolam* defaults to the standard of care that can be supported, even if it falls below what is objectively acceptable. Consequently, the court has little discretion to decide what is standard of care should have been considering all circumstances of a particular case; there is no

²⁵⁸ Supra Note 110

option to prefer one expert's opinion over the other, the choice is all or nothing- can the action be supported or can it not?

Bolam therefore criticized as a clumsy tool, born out of medical nepotism and implemented through a system of peer review, where doctors set the standards required of them and give testimony in each other's defence. Under *Bolam*, Doctors and defence organizations enjoy a degree of protection that validates and perpetuates outdated medical practice simply because that practice remains entrenched in some doctors.²⁵⁹

Daubert is another point in evidence

The 1993 U.S. Supreme Court's decision in *Daubert v Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals* established a new "Daubert standard".²⁶⁰ The case summary is as follows,

Two boys, Jason Daubert and Eric Schuller, were born with serious defects after their mothers took the anti-nausea drug Bendectin while pregnant. When the boys sued Merrell Dow, the manufacturer of Bendectin, alleging that the drug caused their defects, they became part of a lengthy line of similar plaintiffs making similar allegations: During the 1980s, there were upwards of 1700 suits claiming that Bendectin had caused birth defects in the children of mothers who took the drug while pregnant. When disputes over the admissibility of expert testimony landed the case in the United States Supreme Court.

The district court ruled that this data was not admissible. Drawing on the Frye standard for evaluating the validity of expert testimony, the court rejected the re-interpretations of Bendectin data because they had been prepared expressly for the case and had not been peer reviewed, and rejected the other studies because they attempted to make epidemiological claims in the absence of epidemiological data. Summary judgment was granted to Merrell Dow.

²⁵⁹ Christopher Stone, 2011, From *Bolam* to *Bolitho*: unraveling medical protectionism, www.medicalandlegal.co.uk/.../From-Bolam-to-Bolitho-unraveling

²⁶⁰ *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals* 509 U.S. 579 (1993)

The 9th Circuit affirmed the district court's decision to exclude the studies that formed the basis of the plaintiffs' case. The Supreme Court agreed to hear *Daubert* because it recognized the necessity of clarifying the proper criteria for admissibility of expert testimony. At issue was whether the adoption of Federal Rules of Evidence trumped the Frye standard that was so decisive in this case, and whether Rule 702, which addresses the issue of scientific evidence, supersedes Frye.

The Court found that the Federal Rules of Evidence do indeed trump Frye. In an opinion that closely followed the reasoning of Atlantic Legal's brief, the Court explained that Rule 702's stipulation that expert testimony must be "scientific ... knowledge" is closely grounded in an assumption that such "knowledge" is distinct from speculation, and can only be derived from proper scientific methods and procedures. The Court went on to dismantle the misguided briefs filed on behalf of petitioners, drawing extensively on Atlantic Legal's explanation of why and how those briefs had confounded the difference between how science and the law assess and pursue truth.

This new standard encouraged judges to assume a more active "gatekeeper" role by not only examining the validity of the underlying science more rigorously, but also examining the methodology used by the expert in applying the science to the specific case. In particular, the court opinion recommended four straightforward guidelines for judges to consider when examining the merits of the testimony.

1. Whether the expert's technique or theory can be or has been tested.
2. Whether the theory has been subject to peer review and publication.
3. The known or potential rate of error of the technique or theory.
4. Whether the theory or technique has been generally accepted in relevant field.²⁶¹

Ongoing development of medicine as a scientifically grounded practice reveals that the medical profession shares much with the legal profession. Science-based medical evidence and the *Daubert* trilogy reflect unorchestrated parallel movements in medicine and law about how to assess expertise critically. Although neither has paid any attention to the other, both movements recognize that professional

²⁶¹ The Case for *Daubert*, 2010, Arizona Chamber Foundation • 1850 North Central Avenue, Suite 1433 • Phoenix, Arizona 85004 • 602-248-9 www.ahrq.gov

education and training are necessary but not sufficient to assure expertise. Expertise, in the vision of both science-based medical evidence and the *Daubert* trilogy, begins but does not end with the question of qualifications.

A medical expert's qualifications provide no assurance of the reliability of the expert's methods and procedures. Beyond both professions independently drawing this distinction, the impact of distinguishing qualifications and expertise in medicine and law is also of consequence. Why has the recognition of this distinction not transformed the practice of medicine or law?²⁶²

Science-based medical evidence and the *Daubert* trilogy reveal much about the nature of both professions. Just as the promulgation of myriad clinical practice guidelines that claim to rest on a critical examination of the medical research literature has not precipitated a sea change in medical practice, so the *Daubert* trilogy's pronouncements about the admissibility of expert testimony that claims to rest on a critical examination of expertise has not precipitated a sea change in legal practice. The attitudes and beliefs of attorneys about the conduct of trials have not been fundamentally changed overnight by the *Daubert* trilogy any more than the attitudes and beliefs of physicians about the practice of medicine has been changed overnight by the emergence of clinical practice guidelines. The practices of both professions are determined by myriad intersecting forces that are resistant to sudden change. Charles Darwin's observation about the process of change in natural selection also captures the essence of this process of change in professional practice.²⁶³

In the well-researched paper *The Role of Clinical Guidelines in Medical Negligence Litigation: A Shift from the Bolam Standard*²⁶⁴ the academic writers suggest a fourfold test:-

“(a) is it Bolam-defensible, (b) is it Bolitho-justifiable, (c) is it Daubert-valid, and (d) how does it apply to the particular circumstances of the matter in question (case-specific application)?”²⁶⁵

²⁶³ Id

²⁶⁴ Supra note 110

²⁶⁵ Ian McLellan, Does Bolitho (Bolitho v City & Hackney HA [1997] 4 All ER 771) eclipse Bolam (Bolam v Friern Hospital Management Committee [1957] 1 WLR 582) September, 2007.

The above article discusses the four tests being applied in US for Clinical Guidelines litigation. The decision of such cases depends on the answers to the above four tests.

Why Opt for Negligence (Rather than Strict Liability)?

The negligence rule conveys more of the information required by the market in order to resolve its inherent incomplete information problems, i.e., the moral hazard and adverse selection problems. It serves this legal function by creating a mechanism motivating both parties to any potential lawsuit to invest in seeking and assessing the information they require in order to file or defend against a lawsuit. The negligence rule ensures a very high correlation between the information required for filing and defending against lawsuits and the information required by the market to resolve its inherent moral hazard and adverse selection problems; the judicial process requires both parties to disclose the relevant information. Moreover, any negligence claim requires the court to inquire into questions relevant for conveying the information required by the market. During a trial, the court would inquire whether the doctor acted optimally, including maintaining professional expertise, and whether the MCO (Managed Care Organization in US) acted optimally, including the selection of appropriate medical gear, maintaining an appropriately skilled medical staff, overseeing that staff and determining appropriate medical procedures. The court would expose the routine work methods of the doctor and her employing organization, focusing on their actions pertaining to the case in question. Thus, through the negligence mechanism, the court would convey invaluable information to the market, focused on disclosing the hidden actions and qualities of both the doctor and the HMO (Health Maintenance Organization in US). Where the market “knows” that such information would one day be disclosed, it would be able to rely on presentations by the doctor and the MCO *ex ante* and to trust them to act optimally. Conversely, the strict liability mechanism dispenses with those inquiries and therefore conveys much less information to the market. Without the information or a reliable threat that the information will eventually be conveyed to the market, the

equilibrium in which the public relies *ex ante* on the doctor's and HMO's presentations, to the effect that they have acted optimally, will simply not exist.²⁶⁶

The feasibility of criminal sanction

Criminal sanction is as an indiscriminate prosecution of medical professionals for criminal negligence is counter-productive and does no service or good to the society. There must be a link between fault, blame and justice requirements, significance and relevant to the issues before us are:

- The social efficacy of blame and related sanctions in particular cases of deliberate wrongdoings may be a matter of dispute, but their necessity in principle from a moral point of view, has been accepted. Distasteful as punishment may be, the social, and possibly moral, need to punish people for wrongdoing, occasionally in a severe fashion, cannot be escaped. If we are constantly concerned about whether our actions will be the subject of complaint, and that such complaint is likely to lead to legal action or disciplinary proceedings, a relationship of suspicious formality between persons is inevitable.
- Culpability may attach to the consequence of an error in circumstances where substandard antecedent conduct has been deliberate, and has contributed to the generation of the error or to its outcome. In case of errors, the only failure is a failure defined in terms of the normative standard of what should have been done. There is a tendency to confuse the reasonable person with the error-free person. While nobody can avoid errors on the basis of simply choosing not to make them, people can choose not to commit violations. A violation is culpable.
- A correct balance of the interests of the plaintiff and the interests of the defendant should ensure that tort liability is restricted to those cases where there is a real failure to behave as a reasonably competent practitioner would have behaved. An inappropriate rising of the standard of care threatens this balance. While expectations from the professionals must be realistic and the

²⁶⁶ Noam Sher, New differences Between Negligence and Strict liability and their Implications on Medical Malpractice Reform, 2007, Southern California Interdisciplinary Law Journal, Vol. 16:335, pp.359-60.

expected standards attainable, this implies recognition of the nature of ordinary human error and human limitations in the performance of complex tasks.

- Conviction for any substantial criminal offence requires that the accused person should have acted with a morally blameworthy state of mind. Recklessness and deliberate wrongdoing are morally blameworthy, but any conduct falling short of that should not be the subject of criminal liability. Common-law systems have traditionally only made negligence the subject of criminal sanction when the level of negligence has been high a standard traditionally described as gross negligence. In fact, negligence at that level is likely to be indistinguishable from recklessness.
- Blame is a powerful weapon. It's inappropriate use distorts tolerant and constructive relations between people. Distinguishing between (a) accidents which are life's misfortune for which nobody is morally responsible, (b) wrongs amounting to culpable conduct and constituting grounds for compensation, and (c) wrongs calling for punishment on account of being gross or of a very high degree requires and calls for careful, morally sensitive and scientifically informed analysis; else there would be injustice to the larger interest of the society.

This may not be understood as holding that doctors can never be prosecuted for an offence of which rashness or negligence is an essential ingredient. There is a need for care and caution in the interest of society; for, the service which the medical profession renders to human beings is probably the noblest of all, and hence there is a need for protecting doctors from frivolous or unjust prosecutions. Such malicious proceedings have to be guarded against and genuine complaints must be ensued with extreme punitive stings. Thus, a complainant has to produce prima facie evidence before the Court to support the charge of rashness or negligence on the part of the accused doctor.²⁶⁷

2.9 Interrelationship and Implications for the concept of medical negligence

When one links the international scenario with the concept of Medical Negligence has been defined in Indian Legal System under various laws, Tort law, Criminal law, Consumer Protection Law, the following points emerge: .

²⁶⁷Supra note

- Negligence is the breach of a duty caused by omission to do something which a reasonable man guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulate the conduct of human affairs would do, or doing something which a prudent and reasonable man would not do. Negligence becomes actionable on account of injury resulting from the act or omission amounting to negligence attributable to the person sued. The essential components of negligence are three: 'duty', 'breach' and 'resulting damage'.
- Negligence in the context of medical profession necessarily calls for a treatment with a difference. To infer rashness or negligence on the part of a professional, in particular a doctor, additional considerations apply. A case of occupational negligence is different from one of professional negligence. A simple lack of care, an error of judgment or an accident, is not proof of negligence on the part of a medical professional. So long as a doctor follows a practice acceptable to the medical profession of that day, he cannot be held liable for negligence merely because a better alternative course or method of treatment was also available or simply because a more skilled doctor would not have chosen to follow or resort to that practice or procedure which the accused followed. When it comes to the failure of taking precautions what has to be seen is whether those precautions were taken which the ordinary experience of men has found to be sufficient; a failure to use special or extraordinary precautions which might have prevented the particular happening cannot be the standard for judging the alleged negligence.
- A professional may be held liable for negligence on one of the two findings: either he was not possessed of the requisite skill which he professed to have possessed, or, he did not exercise, with reasonable competence in the given case, the skill which he did possess. The standard to be applied for judging, whether the person charged has been negligent or not, would be that of an ordinary competent person exercising ordinary skill in that profession. It is not possible for every professional to possess the highest level of expertise or skills in that branch which he practices.
- The jurisprudential concept of negligence differs in civil and criminal law. What may be negligence in civil law may not necessarily be negligence in criminal law. For negligence to amount to an offence, the element of mens rea must be shown to exist. For an act to amount to criminal negligence, the

degree of negligence should be much higher i.e. gross or of a very high degree. Negligence which is neither gross nor of a higher degree may provide a ground for action in civil law but cannot form the basis for prosecution.

- The word 'gross' has not been used in Section 304A of IPC, yet it is settled that in criminal law negligence or recklessness, to be so held, must be of such a high degree as to be 'gross'. The expression 'rash or negligent act' as occurring in Section 304A of the IPC has to be read as qualified by the word 'grossly'.
- To prosecute a medical professional for negligence under criminal law it must be shown that the accused did something or failed to do something which in the given facts and circumstances no medical professional in his ordinary senses and prudence would have done or failed to do. The hazard taken by the accused doctor should be of such a nature that the injury which resulted was most likely imminent.
- *Res ipsa loquitur* is only a rule of evidence and operates in the domain of civil law especially in cases of torts and helps in determining the onus of proof in actions relating to negligence. It cannot be pressed in service for determining per se the liability for negligence within the domain of criminal law. *Res ipsa loquitur* has, if at all, a limited application in trial on a charge of criminal negligence.²⁶⁸

In the next chapter, the concept of Consumer Rights in relation to Medical services is discussed. It explains the historical background, development of the concept of consumer rights in India with its international perspective, and explores the relationship of the concept with 'Patient as Consumer' and 'Medical Profession as Service Provider'.

²⁶⁸ Smreeti Prakash, A comparative Analysis of Various Indian Legal Systems regarding Medical Negligence, Criminal, Consumer Protection and Tort Laws; Legalserviceindia.com, Last accessed 10th July 2012.

Chapter 3

CONCEPT OF CONSUMER RIGHTS AND MEDICAL SERVICES

“The good physician treats the disease; the great physician treats the patient who has the disease.”

William Osler

“The right to health cannot be conceived of as a traditional right enforceable against the state. Instead, it has to be formulated and acknowledged as a positive right at a global level one which all of us have an interest in protecting and advancing”.

Former Chief Justice K.G. Balakrishnan ²⁶⁹

The other key concept in the study design is ‘consumer protection’. The notion of service in the medical field was affected by the advent of CPA in India. The development led to a change in the approach of both professionals and patients. The important milestones are presented in this chapter.

The development of consumer protection regime is fairly young and may be traced to the Bill of Consumers’ Rights of US wherein the recognition of consumer rights commenced at the international level.²⁷⁰ This Bill recognized four important rights of the consumers, viz. (i) the right to safety; (ii) right to be informed; (iii) right to choose; and (iv) the right to be heard.²⁷¹ These rights of the consumers were further strengthened by passing of resolution by UN General Assembly on April 9, 1985, wherein general guidelines were issued by the United Nation General Assembly which included: (i) physical safety, (ii) protection and promotion of consumer economic rights, (iii) standards for the safety and quality of consumers goods and services , (iv) measures enabling consumers to obtain redress, (v) measures relating to specific areas like, food, water and pharmaceuticals; and (vi) consumer education and information program. At the domestic front, the consumer movement started with enactment of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986(hereinafter referred as CPA) which aims to provide „*for better protection of interest of the consumers and for the*

²⁶⁹ National seminar on the ‘Human right to health’ Organized by the Madhya Pradesh State Human Rights Commission, Bhopal- September 14, 2008

²⁷⁰ Bill of Rights of the Consumers on March 15, 1962. As mentioned in, Rajiv Kumar Khare, LAW OF TORTS, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND CONSUMER PROTECTION , 2010, Bhopal-National Law University,pp2-3

²⁷¹ Id. at 1-Other four rights added in the document are the ; (i) right to satisfaction of basic needs ; (ii) right to redress ; (iii) right to education ; and (iv) the right to healthy environment .

establishment of the quasi-judicial authorities for the settlement of the disputes".³

This Act has primarily given statutory recognition to the rights of the consumers in India. These rights, given in the Act, include:

- the right to be protected against the marketing of goods and services which are hazardous to life and property;
- the right to be informed about the quality, quantity, potency, purity, standard and price of goods or the services as the case may be so as to protect the consumer against unfair trade practices;
- the right to access to variety of goods and services at competitive prices;
- the right to be heard and be assured that consumer interest will receive due consideration at appropriate forums;
- the right to seek redress against unfair trade practices or unscrupulous exploitation of consumers; and
- the right to consumer education.

However, prior to these developments, the concern for protection of consumers' rights and interests may be located under the Law of Torts which is even now equally effective and enforceable. This section on concepts therefore, attempts to throw light on the relationship of Law of Torts vis-à-vis Consumer Protection with special emphasis on Medical Negligence cases. Consumer protection regime primarily aims to protect against deficiency in services and defect in goods. Thus the discussion shall primarily be around these aspects under the torts law and consumer laws, with sector-specific treatment of consumer cases. The sectors specifically included in this monograph are insurance, transport, banking and finance, medical etc.²⁷²

3.1 Consumer Rights Defined

One often comes across many people who complain of having been supplied with inferior or adulterated goods for which they have paid full price. Similarly some people are seen grumbling that they have paid full fare but their bus and train seats were very un-comfortable. So many a times people do not get the full worth of their money. Don't they have a right to get the full value of their money spend for the

²⁷² Rajiv Kumar Khare, LAW OF TORTS, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND CONSUMER PROTECTION, 2010, Bhopal-National Law University, pp.2-3

goods and services they want to avail of? Sometimes, people themselves are responsible for the inappropriate goods and services that are provided to them. Many a times, they do not know full details of the products or services they are interested in. Sometimes, they take the delivery of goods or avail of the services without caring for their quality. Is it not their responsibility to give full details of the goods and services required by them? The details about the rights and responsibilities of consumers are as follows,²⁷³

Meaning of Consumerism

A consumer uses goods and services from time to time. He/ She may be having the experience of being exploited by some or the other suppliers. Sometimes they over-charge or supply inferior quality goods and services. It is difficult to stop such exploitation by any consumer single handedly. The intensity of such exploitation may be restricted if consumers become alert and collectively take a stand against such malpractices. Self-effort on the part of consumers for safe-guarding themselves is known as “consumerism” .²⁷⁴

Consumerism refers to a movement by consumers to ensure fair and honest (ethical) practices on the part of manufacturers, traders, dealers and services providers in relation to consumers. The movement may be regarded an attempt by individual consumer activists and consumer associations for creating consumer awareness about the malpractices in the market and finding ways and means to protect their interests. This movement will be successful if consumers are aware of their rights and responsibilities while using goods and services. Various rights and responsibilities of consumers are discussed hereinafter.²⁷⁵

Rights of Consumers

Today consumers face various problems on account of competition in the market, misleading advertisements, availability of inferior quality of goods and services, etc. Hence protection of consumers’ interest has become a matter of serious concern for the Government as well as public bodies. To safeguard the interest of consumers the

²⁷³ Consumer Rights and Responsibilities, Lesson 25, [https:// old.nios.ac.in/Secbuscour/25.pdf](https://old.nios.ac.in/Secbuscour/25.pdf)

²⁷⁴ Id.

²⁷⁵ Id.

government has recognized certain rights of consumers. In other words, if consumers are to protect themselves from being exploited or cheated, they have to be given certain rights so that they are in a position to ensure that sellers of goods and service providers are more careful in dealing with them, e.g. Business Studies.

One of the rights of consumers is the right to choose. Those who are aware of different varieties of the same product need to be shown to them by the shopkeeper so that they can choose what you like. Sometimes, shopkeepers try to sell a particular brand of product on which they get higher commission on sale. It may not be of the best quality, or it may be available at a relatively lower price. This practice can be prevented if one exercises your right to choose the product and visit other shops if one shop does not have a large variety of the product.²⁷⁶

Right to Safety

It Means right to be protected against the marketing of goods and services, which are hazardous to life and property? The purchased goods and services availed of should not only meet their immediate needs, but also fulfil long term interests. Before purchasing, consumers should insist on the quality of the products as well as on the guarantee of the products and services. They should preferably purchase quality marked products such as ISI, AGMARK, etc. This gives consumers the demand for safety even in medical services.

Right to be Informed

It Means right to be informed about the quality, quantity, potency, purity, standard and price of goods so as to protect the consumer against unfair trade practices. Consumer should insist on getting all the information about the product or service before making a choice or a decision. This will enable one to act wisely and responsibly and also enable him to desist from falling prey to high pressure selling techniques.

Right to Choose

²⁷⁶ Id.

It Means right to be assured, wherever possible of access to variety of goods and services at competitive price. In case of monopolies, it means right to be assured of satisfactory quality and service at a fair price. It also includes right to basic goods and services. This is because unrestricted right of the minority to choose can mean a denial for the majority of its fair share. This right can be better exercised in a competitive market where a variety of goods are available at competitive prices

Right to be Heard

It Means that consumer's interests will receive due consideration at appropriate forums. It also includes right to be represented in various forums formed to consider the consumer's welfare. The Consumers should form non-political and non-commercial consumer organizations which can be given representation in various committees formed by the Government and other bodies in matters relating to consumers

Right to Seek Redressal

It Is the right to seek redressal against unfair trade practices or unscrupulous exploitation of consumers. It also includes right to fair settlement of the genuine grievances of the consumer. Consumers must make complaint for their genuine grievances. Many a times their complaint may be of small value but its impact on the society as a whole may be very large. They can also take the help of consumer organizations in seeking redressal of their grievance.

Right to Consumer Education

It is the right to acquire the knowledge and skill to be an informed consumer throughout life. Ignorance of consumers, particularly of rural consumers, is mainly responsible for their exploitation. They should know their rights and must exercise them. Only then real consumer protection can be achieved with success.²⁷⁷

These rights have a historical background.

²⁷⁷<http://confonet.nic.in/ConsumerRights.html> last accessed 8th Oct.2012

3.2 Historical Background

Consumer Rights in India

Consumer rights were recognized broadly in many ancient Hindu, Islamic and Christian religious scriptures; however, no literary work formalized them into a concise set until the 1960s. Consumer rights in India and the modern world owe their origin to the consumer revolution of the pre-60s in the United States of America.

On March 15, 1962, US President John F Kennedy made a historical speech about consumer rights as he introduced 'The Consumer Bill of Rights' in the US Congress. Ever since, countries all over the world have celebrated March 15 as the Consumers' Day. However, in India December 24 is celebrated as the National Consumer Day since the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 was enacted on this day by the Indian Parliament.

Kennedy strongly believed that it is vital to United States' National Interest to ensure the welfare of the consumers, as it is the consumer who fundamentally drives the economy. He formulated four rights for consumers, namely the right to safety, right to choose, right to information and right to be heard which, in 1985, was accepted by the United Nations (UN). The UN added to this list the right to basic needs, right to representation, right to consumer education, and right to healthy environment.²⁷⁸

In the field of Indian medical history, historians have paid more attention to the Indian systems of medicine, their scientific and technological aspects and their relationship with the Indian philosophies. Although such writings on Indian medicine have provided some very useful insight into the way medicine was practiced, a systematic exploration of medical care provision and the rules and legislation on it, are yet to be undertaken.

The earliest Indian civilization known to us is the Indus Urban Culture of 3000 to 2000 BC. The archaeological evidence shows that these cities had well-planned drainage system, almost all houses had bathrooms, many houses had latrines and most houses

²⁷⁸ Consumer Daddy, Consumer Rights in India, <http://www.consumerdaddy.com/a-13-consumer-rights-in-india.htm>; last accessed 15th Oct 2012

had wells for water supply. The renowned medical historian Henry Sigerist (1987: 142-3) believed that public health facilities of Mohenjo Daro were superior to those of any other community of the ancient Orient. Unfortunately, there is not much evidence on the way these societies were governed and the kind of entitlements provided by the state or the community to the individuals and the households.²⁷⁹

However, the extent of development of public health system points to some kind of state or community planning which enabled the citizens to get entitlement to hygienic public health arrangements.

The written evidence of the state's involvement and the regulatory function is available from the Kautilya's *Arthashastra*. Kautilya considered famine as a bigger calamity than pestilence and epidemics, as the remedies can be found for the diseases. He believed that the king should order the physicians to use medicine to counter epidemics. The *Arthashastra* also makes mandatory for the doctor to report to the state whenever the doctor is called to a house to treat a severely wounded person. This also applied to treating the one suffering from unwholesome food or drink. Such immediate reporting was mandatory in order not to get accused by the crime committed by such patients. If the doctor failed to provide information to the state, he would be charged with the same offence committed by such patient.²⁸⁰

For not providing proper information to patient, for committing mistake in and for being negligent in treatment, the *Arthashastra* provides for punishment, fine, for the doctor and compensation for victims *Arthashastra* is replete with prescriptions of so-called medieval punishments, including strong recommendations for using torture for getting information or confession, and even using it for punishment. While in the field of ancient medical ethics and laws, the code of Hammurabi prescribing "eye-for-eye" punishment for the doctor injuring patient in the treatment is well known, the punishments prescribed and practiced in Kautilya's time are less known and talked about. *Arthashastra* is a very definitive and practical book. Its identification of each point of state-craft, economic management, infringements and the specific and detailed punishments partly read like a code. It has received less attention perhaps

²⁷⁹ Amar Jesani, LAWS AND HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS A Study of Legislation and Legal Aspects of Health Care Delivery, January, 1996, Centre for Enquiry into Health and Allied Themes, Mumbai

²⁸⁰ Infra

because its writing on the medical practitioners and their duties are part of crisis management, combating recurring famines and epidemics, and also a part of "consumer" protection in general. When India is still trying to properly codify and implement doctor's duty of giving proper information to the patient, the *Arthashastra* had made mandatory for the doctor to give prior information about treatment involving life and having consequence of causing injury.

A failure to give such information invited harsher punishment if the patient died or suffered injury. It prescribes the following punishment for "negligence" in treatment:

Doctor not giving prior information about treatment involving danger to life with the consequence of Punishment prescribed

- Physical deformity or damage to vital organ, same punishment as causing similar physical injury
- Death of patient lowest level standard penalty (primarily fine)
- Death due to wrong treatment Middle level standard penalty (primarily fine but high amount)

Thus, *Arthashastra* equated injury due to treatment given without explaining consequences to patient with the similar injury caused in any criminal offence. The death due to wrong treatment invited more penalty than the death as a consequence of correct treatment. Lastly, compensating injury with money, a practice in the present day medical malpractice litigation was known and practiced during Kautilya's time. This is indeed an advance over the Hammurabi type "eye-for-eye" justice system for medical negligence and draws attention to the advancements made by the ancient justice system in India as compared to other countries of that time.²⁸¹ This detailed description shows that state-craft of that time put certain obligations and regulations on the work of doctors. During the Buddha period, there are evidences to show that the state supported University of Taxila, which among other things, provided medical education to students. Bhikshu Atreya taught there and Jivaka was a product of this University. During the Ashoka period (270 BC) the state showed interest in the public works and the provision of medical care. Ashoka founded hospitals all over his empire with medical attendance at state expense. The state also undertook planting of medicinal herbs, planting of trees and supply of potable water from wells along the

²⁸¹ Rangarajan L.N. (1992), "KAUTILYA: THE ARTHASHASTRA", New Delhi: Penguin Books.

highways. Ashoka also assisted in the establishment of medical centres in the neighbouring countries. Further evidence on the state's interest in medicine is available from the Chinese pilgrim Hsiuan-tsang who studied at the monastic University of Nalanda, which also provided medical education (7th Century AD). The Nalanda University was supported by the revenue collected from more than 100 villages given to it by the King.

The known text books of *Ayurvedic* medicine took many centuries in getting fully compiled. In this process (which also required meeting of scholars and practitioners) the state extended support from time to time. It is suggested that these texts emerged in real fixed form in the first five hundred years AD. Around the 12th century AD the Muslims brought their own physicians with them and thereby introduced a new system of medicine known as, "successful practitioners were those who served successful rulers and, either through regular service or because of some special healing act were granted an area of land. These grants may have been supposed to fund specifically medical activities -a dispensary or a small medical school- or they may have been grants to the man and his heirs, even if they ceased practicing medicine." has documented medical relief in Medieval South India and noted that both state and religious institutions often subsidized and supported medical care.²⁸²

There has not been serious and sustained attempt in our country to document the system of self-regulation of physicians and the state laws to protect people from the misdeeds of physicians in these periods. Chattopadhyay²⁸³ discusses ethics in the *Charaaka-Samhita*, while Sinha²⁸⁴ has argued that "the *Ayurvedic* physicians of ancient India had a well defined medical ethics". Similarly, Pandya²⁸⁵ has summarised various aspects of medical ethics prescribed by Charaaka, Susruta and other Indian physicians. On the other hand, there is almost no sustained evidence on state's special or direct interest in regulating medical practice or the medical practitioners. However, the situation started changing from the British period in the modern history.²⁸⁶

²⁸² Id.

²⁸³ (1977:21)

²⁸⁴ (1983: 266)

²⁸⁵ (1995)

²⁸⁶ Supra note 13

The colonial power brought with it its own physicians and barber surgeons. In the mid-19th century, as the medicine got recognized in England, it slowly started having its impact in India, too. Further, the public health campaigns, the increasing intervention of the state in the provision and regulation of health care, establishment of hospitals and above-all the development of scientific medicine gradually led to the establishment of what we know as the organized health care service systems all over Western Europe. However, the colonial power was not interested in making the necessary investment in developing such well-organized health care and public health campaigns for its subjects. After 1857, the main factors²⁸⁷ which shaped colonial health policy in India were its concern for the troops and the European civil population. The genuine public health measures remained confined to the well planned cantonment areas housing British people. She has also documented that for the general population the sanitary measures were started in ad hoc fashion for pilgrim centres but the realization that they would be very expensive made the colonial government shelve the programme under various pretexts. She also contends that as the era of sanitary reform was superseded by the professionalization of medicine in England, the colonial government shifted the focus from the sanitary reforms to public health research in India.²⁸⁸

Nevertheless, the colonial government could not confine its support to health care only in its well organized cantonments. For various reasons, it had to make some provision of health care for the masses, too. For instance, in a study by Muraleedharan²⁸⁹ of the "Rural Health Care in Madras Presidency: 1919-39", he finds that the colonial state had established dispensaries and hospitals for the people, more in the urban areas but less in the rural areas. In 1924 it introduced a scheme called Subsidized Rural Medical Relief Scheme (SRMRS) which was intended to subsidize private practitioners who agreed to settle down in villages. Such private practitioners were not considered government servants, were required to settle down in the villages specified by the local boards and were asked to treat the "necessitous poor" free of charge. However, this scheme was only partially implemented. Despite such inadequacies in

²⁸⁷ Radhika Ramasubban (1982, also 1985)

²⁸⁸ Thapar Romila (1973), "ASHOKA AND THE DECLINE OF THE MAWYOS" Delhi: Oxford University Press.

²⁸⁹ (1987)

implementation, it was in this period that the establishment of a nation-wide formal and organized health care system was started.²⁹⁰

This process of establishment of health care system also necessitated creation of legislative framework for it and for the practitioners of medicine. In its earlier period of rule, the physicians and surgeons brought by the East India Company and after 1857 by the British government, needed some discipline and regulations. Lt. Colonel D.G. Crawford's "A History of Indian Medical Service, 1600-1913" narrates several instances of in-discipline, insubordination, malpractice etc by such doctors and the punishment (including deportation) meted out to them. It also narrates the regulations devised by the East India Company for the hospitals established by it.²⁹¹

After the enactment of the law establishing General Medical Council in 1857 in England, the British doctors employed in India were registered with the GMC and came under its disciplinary regulation. As the number of doctors qualified in Indian medical colleges increased, creation of laws for them became necessary. Similar development took place for the nursing profession. A brief history of the legislation enacted for health care professionals is given in the subsequent discussion.²⁹²

The connected notion of Consumer protection was always a matter of great concern. In ancient India, effective measures were initiated to protect consumers from crimes in the market place. Ancient law gives ably described various kinds of unfair trade practices and also prescribed severe punishments for wrong doers. Mainly, acts of adulteration and false weights and measures were seriously dealt with. In ancient India, the king was the supreme authority to render justice, but his authority was circumscribed by the rules of *Dharma*. In the medieval period, some Muslim rulers developed well organized market mechanisms to monitor prices and the supply of goods to the markets. During the British period, the modern legal system was introduced in India and many laws were enacted to protect the interests of consumers generally. Today, the civil justice system is tainted with deficiencies that discourage

²⁹⁰ Id.

²⁹¹ Supra note 20

²⁹² Amar Jesani, Right to health care, entitlement and law:Laws and health careproviders, Report 1996, CEHAT,pp. 12-14

the consumer from seeking legal recourse..²⁹³

In conclusion, it is clear that ever-increasing consumer protection seems to be the order of the day. This now includes the injured bystander remedies and damage to goods. The new type of products liability litigation in which attorneys will increasingly be engaged will no longer be limited to breach of warranty, negligence or strict liability.

3.3 International Perspective

'A charter of rights and standards for health care consumers is what's needed to ensure that the entire system benefits by becoming more accountable to the citizens who pay for it and more responsive to the consumers who need to use it.'²⁹⁴

Consumer Protection: International Scenario: The need for consumer protection at international level was also echoed in the thought that consumerism was largely invented by Mr. Ralph Nader, the well-known American Advocate. History of protection of Consumer's rights by law has long been recognized dating back to 1824. Every year the 15th of March is observed as the World Consumer Rights Day. On that day in 1962, President John F. Kennedy of U.S. called upon the U.S. Congress to accord its approval to the Consumer Bill of Rights.

They are (i) right to choose ; (ii) right to information, (iii) right to safety and (iv) right to be heard. President Gerald R. Ford added one more right i.e. right to consumer education. Further other rights such as right to healthy environment and right to basic needs (Food, Clothing and Shelter) were added..

In the history of the development of consumer policy, April 9, 1985 is a very significant date for it was on that day that the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted a set of general guidelines³ for consumer protection and the Secretary General of the United Nations was authorized to persuade member countries to adopt 3 General Assembly Resolution 39/ 85; these guidelines through policy changes or law. These guidelines constitute a comprehensive policy framework outlining what governments

²⁹³ A .Rajendra Prasad, Historical Evolution of Consumer Protection and Law in India, The Journal of Texas Consumer Law, www.jtexconsumerlaw.com/V11N3/JCCL_India.pdf

²⁹⁴ Kate Moore, A Health Consumers' Charter, Health Forum 1993 (As mentioned in- The role of a health rights charter in improving safety and quality in health care – February 2008)

need to do to promote consumer protection in following seven areas:

- Physical safety;
- Protection and Promotion of the consumer economic interest;
- Standards for the safety and quality of consumer goods and services;
- Distribution facilities for consumer goods and services;
- Measures enabling consumers to obtain redress;
- Measures relating to specific areas (food, water and pharmaceuticals) and
- Consumer education and information programme.

Though not legally binding, the guidelines provide an internationally recognized set of basic objectives particularly for governments of developing and newly independent countries for structuring and strengthening their consumer protection policies and legislations. These guidelines were adopted recognizing that consumers often face imbalances in economic terms, educational levels and bargaining power and bearing in mind that consumers should have the right of access to non hazardous products as well as the importance of promoting just, equitable and sustainable economic and social development. These U.N. guidelines for Consumer Protection can assist in the identification of priorities particularly in the light of emerging trends in a globalised and liberalized world economy.

The U.N. guidelines were never intended to be a static document and required to be revisited in the changed social, political and economic circumstances. On re examination of U.N. guidelines in 1999 “sustainable consumption” was also included in the list which is certainly an important step in this direction. It would perhaps be apt to highlight the long back Mahatma Gandhi said that” the rich must live more simply so that the poor may simply live.” There cannot be a better expression championing the cause of sustainable consumption. The increased internationalization of cooperation is also a part of the globalization process. Rules adopted for corporations trading in OECD countries for the protection of the interests of consumers can now also be applied to their conduct for the protection of the interests of the consumers in non-OECD countries. A new investment guideline from the OECD spells out principles to be applied by multinational corporations dealing with consumers. The Guidelines, which deal with fair business, marketing and advertising practices as well as safety and quality of goods and services lend themselves to consumer monitoring and campaigning. Possibilities for action include twinning arrangements in which groups

from non- OECD countries work with groups from the home countries of multinational corporations to hold them accountable for failure to adhere to the Guidelines.²⁹⁵

The enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being...Promoting and protecting health and respecting, Protecting and fulfilling human rights are inextricably linked.²⁹⁶

The Protection of consumer rights is now a global agenda. Bangladesh, a third world country, is struggling to fulfill the basic needs of its population. “Socialism meaning economic and social justice”, a fundamental principle of the state policy and the Constitution is yet to be implemented although 38-years have already passed from its Independence. The world economic giants have enacted a series of Laws on different heading to meet the contemporary global demand on economic progress in one side and protection of the consumers from unfair, misleading and aggressive business propaganda on the other. The United Nations (UN), European Union (EU) and World Trade Organizations (WTO) have adopted a lot of rules to regulate trade and business of various products and services through import or export that impacts seriously on producer or manufacturer, supplier or distributor, seller and ultimately to the consumer. Bangladesh, a country with over population, has enacted “Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009” to deal with the consumer affairs. The law is an addition to a number of around 61 relevant Laws dealing with the consumer rights and their protection mechanisms in a sporadic way.²⁹⁷

Aspects of Consumer Protection

In Bangla Desh, the concept of Consumer Protection is discussed in following way

“There are three aspects of consumer rights protection, which every country must

²⁹⁵S. S. Singh & Sapna Chadah, Consumer Protection in India – Some Reflections, 2005, www.aijsh.org/setup/socialscience/paper30.pdf

²⁹⁶ World Health Organization, Linkages between health and human rights; Web page <http://www.who.int/hhr/en/>(As mentioned in-The role of a health rights charter in improving safety and quality in health care – February 2008)

²⁹⁷Ahamuduzzaman, A contextual analysis of the consumer rights protection Laws with practical approach: Bangladesh perspectives(2nd July 2009) www.asaub.edu.bd/data/asaubreview/v3n2sl15.pdf

consider.

- (i) Voluntary Protectionism
- (ii) Institutional Protectionism
- (iii) Statutory Protection

First, the aspect of 'voluntary protection' which means that consumers themselves would voluntarily set up associations and/or organizations to safeguard their own rights and interests. These associations/organizations generally work as pressure groups on the government for consumer rights issues e.g. the Consumers' Association of Bangladesh (CAB).

Second, the aspect of 'institutional protection'. By establishing national institutions to safeguard and promote consumer rights of citizens this aspect of consumers' protection can be ensured. In Bangladesh Standard and Testing Institute has been active in protecting consumers of Bangladesh in a limited capacity by way of doing laboratory research and testing of commodities to find out whether the same comply with the expected standard. However, currently the country has established a "National Council for the protection of Consumer Rights" and a „District Committee" in every district headed by the DC"s. The Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009 has also established a Department/Directorate headed by a Director General (DG) for the protection of consumer's rights. Except the Government institutions there are some Non-Government Organizations (NGO"s) working for the protection of consumer rights e.g. CAB, Adhunik, PAB, BAPA etc.

Third, the aspect of 'statutory protection' can be guaranteed by enacting relevant laws for protecting the rights and interests of the consumers. Many countries of the world, including those in Asia, have already enacted comprehensive laws in this regard, for example, the Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009 in Bangladesh.

So, the concept of consumer rights depends upon the promotional activities and the protection mechanisms of a particular society or of a state. The protection of a consumer rights ultimately ensures safety in products and security in service whereas the promotion of a consumer rights depends upon the education, monitoring of the supply and marketing systems of various products, examining goods, enforcing proper

scale in weight and measurement, enacting proper laws, creating awareness, upliftment of moral standards etc.²⁹⁸

In summary, there are three types of protections, voluntary, institutional and statutory, that are responsible for protecting consumers.

Concept of Consumer Protection

Consumer protection consists of laws and organizations designed to ensure the rights of consumers as well as fair trade competition and the free flow of truthful information in the marketplace. The laws are designed to prevent businesses that engage in fraud or specified unfair practices from gaining an advantage over competitors and may provide additional protection for the weak and those unable to take care of themselves. Consumer protection laws are a form of government regulation which aims to protect the rights of consumers. For example, a government may require businesses to disclose detailed information about products—particularly in areas where safety or public health is an issue, such as food. Consumer protection is linked to the idea of "consumer rights" (that consumers have various rights as consumers), and to the formation of consumer organizations, which help consumers make better choices in the marketplace and get help with consumer complaints.

Other organizations that promote consumer protection include government organizations and self-regulating business organizations such as consumer protection agencies and organizations, the Federal Trade Commission, ombudsmen, Better Business Bureaus, etc.

A consumer is defined as someone who acquires goods or services for direct use or ownership rather than for resale or use in production and manufacturing. Consumer interests can also be protected by promoting competition in the markets which directly and indirectly serve consumers, consistent with economic efficiency, but this topic is treated in competition law. Consumer protection can also be asserted via non-government organizations and individuals as consumer activism.²⁹⁹

²⁹⁸ Id.

²⁹⁹ See en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumerprotection

The necessity of adopting measures to protect the interest of consumers arises mainly due to the helpless position of the consumers. There is no denying fact that the consumers have the basic right to be protected from the loss or injury caused on account of defective goods and deficiency of services. But they hardly use their rights due to lack of awareness, ignorance or lethargic attitude. However in view of the prevailing malpractices and their vulnerability there to, it is necessary to provide them physical safety, protection of economic interests, access to information, satisfactory product standard, and statutory measures for redressal of their grievances. The other main arguments in favour of consumer protection are as follows:

(a) Social Responsibility

The business must be guided by certain social and ethical norms. It is the moral responsibility of the business to serve the interest of consumers. Keeping in line with this principle, it is the duty of producers and traders to provide right quality and quantity of goods at fair prices to the consumers.

(b) Increasing Awareness

The consumers are becoming more mature and conscious of their rights against the malpractices by the business. There are many consumer organizations and associations who are making efforts to build consumer awareness, taking up their cases at various levels and helping them to enforce their rights.

(c) Consumer Satisfaction

Father of the Nation Mahatma Gandhi had once given a call to manufactures and traders to “*treat your consumers as God*”. Consumers’ satisfaction is the key to success of business. Hence, the businessmen should take every step to serve the interests of consumers by providing them quality goods and services at reasonable price.

(d) Principle of Social Justice

Exploitation of consumers is against the directive principles of state policy as laid down in the Constitution of India. Keeping in line with this principle, it is expected from the manufacturers, traders and service providers to refrain from malpractices and take care of consumers’ interest.

(e) Principle of Trusteeship

According to Gandhian philosophy, manufactures and producers are not the real owners of the business. Resources are supplied by the society. They are merely the trustees of the resources and, therefore, they should use such resources effectively for

the benefit of the society, which includes the consumers.

(f) Survival and Growth of Business

The business has to serve consumer interests for their own survival and growth. On account of globalization and increased competition, any business organisation which indulges in malpractices or fails to provide improved services to their ultimate consumer shall find it difficult to continue. Hence, they must in their own long run interest, become consumer oriented.³⁰⁰

Patient rights in New Zealand

The Medical Council of New Zealand has enforced the Code of Rights under a separate law under the Health and Disability Act 1994 (the HDC Act). Patients have rights as consumers of health and disability services provided by doctors and other health professionals in public and private services, for paid and unpaid services, within hospitals and within private practices. The code of rights is law under the Health and Disability Act 1994 (the HDC Act).

The rights of patients can be summarized into 10 points:

1. Consumers should always be treated with respect.
2. No one should discriminate against consumers, pressure them into anything, or take advantage of them.
3. Services should help consumers to live dignified, independent lives.
4. Consumers should be treated with reasonable care and skill and receive well coordinated services.
5. Service providers should listen to consumers and give them information in a way they can understand and that makes them comfortable to ask questions if they don't understand. This may require the services of an interpreter.
6. Consumers should have any treatment explained to them, including benefits, risks, alternatives, and costs, and have any questions answered honestly.
7. Consumers can make their own decisions about treatment, and are free to change their mind.
8. Consumers can have a support person with them at most times.
9. All these rights apply if consumers are asked to take part in research or teaching.

³⁰⁰ Consumer Protection, Business Studies, Module on Marketing(2004);Chap.24, pp. 199-200

10. Consumers have a right to make a complaint and have it taken seriously.³⁰¹

The rights of patients in Zimbabwe

The Patients Charter was developed from recommendations by the Consumer Council of Zimbabwe (CCZ) and the Ministry of Health and Child Welfare to offer protection to consumers and improve health service delivery. The Charter therefore spells out general consumer rights to access and treatment.

Patients Rights can be described as social and individual rights. Social rights cover aspects such as the quality and accessibility of health care, while individual rights relate to basic human and consumer rights.

1. GENERAL RIGHTS TO ACCESS AND TREATMENT

Patients have a right to access the Health System at the time of need, both as non paying and paying patients. In the event that a patient has contact with the Health Service, it is important for them to remember that the Health Service is there to respond to their needs. Below are some of the rights, patients need to understand.

1.1 Hospitality (Health Care)

A patient has the right to be accorded courtesy and to be treated with respect in a safe and clean environment.

1.2 Confidentiality

Save for the requirements of the law, all information concerning a patient's illness or personal circumstances will be kept in confidence and used only for the purposes of their treatment. A patient has the right to details of his/her treatment and diagnosis.

1.3 Privacy

A Patient has the right to privacy during consultation, examination and treatment. A patient shall therefore be interviewed and treated in surroundings designed to ensure privacy and shall have the right to be accompanied during any physical examination

³⁰¹ Patients' Rights, Fitness to Practise; Medical Council of New Zealand ; <http://www.mcnz.org.nz/fitness-to-practise/standards-for-doctors/patient-rights/> accessed on 31st March 2013

or treatment if they so wish.

1.4 Discrimination (Human Treatment)

A patient has the right to be received and attended to without regard to sex, age, religion, colour, creed, tribe, race and socio-economic status. This also means that optimal health care must be provided to all citizens at the right cost.

1.5 Choice

A Patient must exercise their right to choose health workers who provide them with treatment or advice, the place and type of treatment that is provided. After being informed of the possible options, patients have the right to refuse or halt any medical interventions. Patients are also allowed to seek a second opinion at any given time while consulting the same medical or health care delivery system.

1.6 Redress of Grievances

Patients shall have access to appropriate grievance handling procedures. They have the right to claim damages of injury or illness incurred or aggravated as a result of the failure of the health professional to exercise the duty and standard of care required of him or her while treating them. Patients shall have the right to legal advice as regards any malpractice by health care professionals.

2 SERVICES

2.1 Admission and Stay in Hospital

In the event of an accident or emergency, patient will be attended to by a Health Worker immediately upon arrival, assessed and dealt with appropriately.

Whether patient is admitted as an emergency or not, hospital staff shall inform your relatives or next of kin or whoever you wish, was practicable.

Keep patient kit and valuables in a safe and clean place.

Give patient clear information about his/ her illness and condition and the treatment plan for your recovery.

2.2 Consent

In some cases, treatment might necessitate the need for operative procedures. This is an unnerving experience for most patients.

In the event that surgery is anticipated in your treatment plan, you have the right to be consulted and to be informed about the nature of the operation. Where risks are known, patient will be informed.

If patient is 18 years of age and above, you have the right to give your consent to surgery recommended by health workers.

If patient is 17 years of age and below, your parent or guardian will give this consent.

However, where patient is incapacitated and therefore unable to give patient's consent, health workers have a moral and ethical duty to do everything possible to save patient's life first.

Patient has a right to give your consent to any research which teaching staff wishes to carry out on/with patient.³⁰²

Consumer rights and responsibilities in United States

In United States, in March 1998, the Advisory Commission on Consumer Protection and Quality in the Health Care Industry issued its final report, which included the Consumer Bill of Rights and Responsibilities. The Commission was appointed by President Bill Clinton, and co-chaired by Donna Shalala, Secretary of the Department of Health and Human Services.

The purpose of the Bill of Rights is:

- To build up consumer confidence in the health care system, by making it easy for consumers to participate actively in their own health care.
- To strongly support the importance of a good healthcare provider and that of a good provider-patient relationship.
- To emphasize and support the importance of the consumers' role in making sure they have rights and responsibilities with regard to health improvement.

The following section, Consumer Bill of Rights, was developed by the federal government. This has been used as a foundation for many health plans, including the federal-government-sponsored health plans.

Consumer Bill of Rights

³⁰² Rights of Patients, Article on the website of Zimbabwe Consumer Council; http://www.ccz.org.zw/articles/details.php?article_id=1 last accessed 31 March 13

I. Information Disclosure

You have the right to receive accurate and easily understood information about your health plan, health care professionals, and health care facilities. If you speak another language, have a physical or mental disability, or just don't understand something, assistance will be provided so you can make informed health care decisions.

II. Choice of Providers and Plans

You have the right to a choice of health care providers that is sufficient to provide you with access to appropriate high-quality health care.

III. Access to Emergency Services

If you have severe pain, an injury, or sudden illness that convinces you that your health is in serious jeopardy, you have the right to receive screening and stabilization emergency services whenever and wherever needed, without prior authorization or financial penalty.

IV. Participation in Treatment Decisions

You have the right to know all your treatment options and to participate in decisions about your care. Parents, guardians, family members, or other individuals that you designate can represent you if you cannot make your own decisions.

V. Respect and Nondiscrimination

You have the right to considerate, respectful and nondiscriminatory care from your doctors, health plan representatives, and other health care providers.

VI. Confidentiality of Health Information

You have the right to talk in confidence with health care providers and to have your health care information protected. You also have the right to review and copy your own medical record and request that your physician amend your record if it is not accurate, relevant, or complete.

VII. Complaints and Appeals

You have the right to a fair, fast and objective review of any complaint you have against your health plan, doctors, hospitals or other health care personnel. This includes complaints about waiting times, operating hours, the conduct of health care personnel, and the adequacy of health care facilities.

Consumer Responsibilities

In addition to outlining consumer rights for health care, the Advisory Commission on Consumer Protection and Quality in the Health Care Industry also outlined guidelines for the responsibilities that the consumer has with regard to their own healthcare. The responsibilities outlined are ways that the consumer can work together with the health care provider to achieve the best quality health outcome.

- Take responsibility for maximizing healthy habits, such as exercising, not smoking, and eating a healthy diet.
- Become involved in specific health care decisions.
- Work collaboratively with health care providers in developing and carrying out agreed-upon treatment plans.
- Disclose relevant information and clearly communicate wants and needs.
- Use the health plan's internal complaint and appeal process to address concerns that may arise.
- Avoid knowingly spreading disease.
- Recognize the reality of risks and limits of the science of medical care and the human fallibility of the health care professional.
- Be aware of a health care provider's obligation to be reasonably efficient and equitable in providing care to other patients and the community.
- Become knowledgeable about his or her health plan coverage and health plan options (when available) including all covered benefits, limitations and exclusions, rules regarding use of information, and the process to appeal coverage decisions.
- Show respect for other patients and health workers.
- Make a good-faith effort to meet financial obligations.
- Abide by administrative and operational procedures of the health plans and health care providers.
- Report wrongdoing and fraud to appropriate resources or legal authorities.³⁰³

The Australian Charter of Healthcare Rights

The Australian Charter of Healthcare Rights describes the rights of patients, consumers and other people using the Australian healthcare system. These rights are essential to make sure that, wherever and whenever health care is provided, it is of

³⁰³ *Consumer Rights and Responsibilities, Medline Plus* (A service of the [U.S. National Library of Medicine National Institutes of Health](http://www.nlm.nih.gov/medlineplus/))

<http://www.nlm.nih.gov/medlineplus/ency/article/001947.htm>, last accessed 31st March 2013

high quality and is safe.

Healthcare rights are the rights of patients, consumers and other people using healthcare services. The Charter recognizes that people receiving care and people providing care all have important parts to play in achieving healthcare rights. The Charter allows patients, consumers, families, carers and services providing health care to share an understanding of the rights of people receiving health care. This helps everyone to work together towards a safe and high quality health system. A genuine partnership between patients, consumers and providers is important so that everyone achieves the best possible outcomes.

Guiding principles

These principles describe how this Charter applies in the Australian health system.

1. Everyone has the right to be able to access health care and this right is essential for the Charter to be meaningful.
2. The Australian government commits to international agreements about human rights that recognise everyone's right to have the highest possible standard of physical and mental health.
3. Australia is a society made up of people with different cultures and ways of life, and the Charter acknowledges and respects these differences.³⁰⁴

Patients' rights vary in different countries and in different jurisdictions, often depending upon prevailing cultural and social norms. Different models of the patient-physician relationship—which can also represent the citizen-state relationship—have been developed, and these have informed the particular rights to which patients are entitled. In North America and Europe, for instance, there are at least four models which depict this relationship: the paternalistic model, the informative model, the interpretive model, and the deliberative model. Each of these suggests different professional obligations of the physician toward the patient. For instance, in the paternalistic model, the best interests of the patient as judged by the clinical expert are valued above the provision of comprehensive medical information and decision-making power to the patient. The informative model, by contrast, sees the patient as a consumer who is in the best position to judge what is in her own interest, and thus views the doctor as chiefly a

³⁰⁴Your Rights and Responsibilities, Western Health, http://www.wh.org.au/Patients_and_Visitors/Your_rights_and_responsibilities/index.aspx, last accessed 31st March 2013

provider of information. There continues to be enormous debate about how best to conceive of this relationship, but there is also growing international consensus that all patients have a fundamental right to privacy, to the confidentiality of their medical information, to consent to or to refuse treatment, and to be informed about relevant risk to them of medical procedures.³⁰⁵

Various countries have discussed this aspect of Consumer Protection in detail and came out with consumer rights and responsibilities under different headings. Ultimately the consumer is being respected and his rights are preserved. India is the only country where the Consumer Protection and Consumer rights concept is applied to the Medical Field and implemented at a large scale.

3.3 Development of concept in India

THE PATIENT AS A CONSUMER

Traditionally, patients in India have unquestioning trust in their doctors. Most doctors deserve it. But in some cases, medical negligence has resulted in severe harm physical, mental and financial. In addition, unqualified practitioners have brought suffering to gullible patients. Doctors have been liable to prosecution in civil court, but few malpractice victims sue for compensation, fearing years (even decades) of costly litigation. Fortunately, in 1995 the Supreme Court decreed the medical profession to be a "service" under the Consumer Protection Act; 1986. It set aside a writ Petition challenging the same by the Indian medical Association.³⁰⁶

THE PATIENT'S RIGHTS

In the interest of a healthy doctor patient relationship, A patient should Know his rights as a consumer: This article discusses the patient rights addressing to the patients/ readers for better understanding.

- Patient has a right to be told all the facts about your illness; to have his/ her medical records explained to him/ her; and to be made aware of risks and side effects, if any, of the treatment prescribed for he/ she should not hesitate to question patient's doctor about any of these aspects.

³⁰⁵ Patient Rights, World Health Organization, <http://www.who.int/genomics/public/patientrights/en/#> last accessed 31 March 2013

³⁰⁶ Know your rights, Consumer Guidance Society of India, <http://www.cgsiindia.org/knowyourrights.html>

- When patient is being given a physical examination, he/ she have a right to be handled with consideration and due regard for his/ her modesty.
- Patient has a right to know your doctor's qualifications. If you cannot evaluate them him/ herself, should not hesitate to ask someone who can.
- Patient has a right to complete confidentiality regarding his/ her illness.
- If patient is doubtful about the treatment prescribed and especially an operation suggested, he/ she have a right to get a second opinion from any specialist.
- Patient has a right to be told in advance what an operation is for and the possible risks involved. If this is not possible because of his/ her being unconscious or for some other reasons, his/ her nearest relatives must be told before they consent to the operation.
- If patient is to be discharged or moved to another hospital, he/ she have a right to be informed in advance and to make his/ her own choice of hospital or nursing home, in consultation with the doctor.
- Patient has a right to get his/ her case papers upon request.³⁰⁷

In the light of this comparative perspective, the researcher revisits the Indian developments

Post-independence developments

The independence in 1947 inaugurated a new phase of development of organized health care services creating more entitlement for the people. Along with that, the state also embarked on enactment of new laws, modification of the colonial laws and the judiciary developed case laws to consolidate people's entitlement of health care and to an extent, the rights. This development took place on the basis of numerous recommendations made by various committees. In this section we will briefly review reports of some of the committees while in subsequent sections we will examine in detail provisions of laws enacted.³⁰⁸

Committees on Health Services and their recommendations on health laws:

At the time of independence, and the first few years of planning, the task confronting the

³⁰⁷ *Supra* note 38

³⁰⁸ Amar Jesani, *Right to health care, entitlement and law :Laws and health care providers; A Study of Legislation and Legal Aspects of Health Care Delivery*, 1996, CEHAT,pp. 12-14

country was to create physical and institutional infrastructure for the rapid development or modernization of India.³⁰⁹ Consumer protection initiatives by the Government hinge on 3 basic parameters. Firstly, ensuring a legal framework that comprises of Consumer Protection Act. Secondly, evolving standards for different products to enable the consumers to make an informed choice about different products. Standards which are the essential building block for quality, play a key role in consumer protection. Standards could be on technical requirement (specifications), improved specific standard terminology (glossary of terms), codes of practice or test methods or management systems standards. The standards are set generally by Government or inter-Governmental bodies but worldwide it is being recognized that voluntary establishment of standards plays an equally important role for protecting consumers. Thirdly, consumer awareness and education is the main building block for consumer protection.³¹⁰

Education is the most powerful tool for the progress of the country and is a social and political necessity. Education helps an individual—as a consumer—in making rational choices and protects him from trade and business-related exploitation. But more is needed for the effective functioning of the national market to create an increased level of awareness of consumer rights, and for this consumers have to be educated about rights and responsibilities through concerted publicity and awareness campaigns. In the awareness campaigns, special emphasis needs to be given to vulnerable groups such as women and children, students, farmers and rural families and the working class.³¹¹

Patients' rights in India³¹²

When one considers the conditions in India, the stark difference between the rights in the US and India is highlighted. The Medical Council of India published, in 2002, a Code of Ethics Regulations (COER) which deals with the duties and responsibilities of physicians in addition to certain rights of patients. It must be emphasized that this code does not represent patients' rights; those mentioned are incidental to the duties and responsibilities of physicians. A distinction must therefore be made between a duty-centric approach as represented by the COER and the rights-centric approach of the AAPS. A medical professional may have issues with the rights-centric approach of AAPS, but is duty bound to uphold the rights of patients that are incidental to his/her

³⁰⁹ *Id.*

³¹⁰ Rakesh Kacker, *Jago Grahak Jago-An initiative towards consumer Education and Awareness*, NVONEWS online, 19 January 2011

³¹¹ Consumer Protection and Competition Policy, Eleventh Five Year Plan, p.247

³¹² Ghooi R.B., Deshpande S.R., *Patients' rights in India: an ethical perspective*, Indian Journal of Medical Ethics Vol. IX No 4 October – December, 2012, 278-280

duties.

At the time of registration with the Medical Council of India (MCI), all medical practitioners are required to sign a declaration, stating *inter alia* as follows:

“I shall abide by the code of medical ethics as enunciated in the Indian Medical Council”.³¹³The Consumer Guidance Society of India (CGSI) has a more comprehensive charter on its website listing eight specific rights of patients. Interestingly, the CGSI’s charter does not include the right to refuse treatment. Thus, if the physician decides on a particular course of action, the patient can at the most ask for a second opinion. Apart from this, the rights of patients are similar in the US and India. However, there is no automatic respect for patients’ rights in India, and if they are violated, the only recourse for patients is to approach the consumer courts. Violation of patients’ rights is not a cognizable offence in India as it is in the US and some other countries. This experience is commonly reported in the media, in journals as well as in informal interactions by patients as well as their friends and close relatives. The differences between the responsibilities described in the COER and each point of the CGSI’s charter of rights may be worth discussing.

- Patient has a right to be told all the facts about your illness; to have your medical records explained to you; and to be made aware of risks and side effects, if any, of the treatment prescribed for you do not hesitate to question your doctor about any of these aspects. Physicians and surgeons rarely have the time or the inclination to discuss with the patient the diagnosis, treatment or the prognosis. In those rare situations where the physician is inclined to do so, the close relatives may attempt to keep the patient in the dark. There is little awareness that the patient’s anxiety can increase manifold in the absence of clear information. This may be particularly true in case of diseases like cancer, where patients and relatives believe that there is little chance of recovery. In many cases the patient or relatives may not understand the modalities of treatment; in any case the physicians are rarely keen to discuss this with them. The COER does address this issue, as it enjoins all physicians to give factual information to patients and their relatives stating: The physician should neither exaggerate nor minimize the gravity of a patient’s condition. He should ensure

³¹³ Professional Conduct, Etiquette and Ethics) Regulations 2002.” (Appendix 1, Declaration, clause k)

himself that the patient, his relatives or his responsible friends have such knowledge of the patient's condition as will serve the best interests of the patient and the family. Best interest is often a controversial issue and cannot be the same for all patients. This may have to be evaluated on per case basis and differ from patient to patient.

- When patient is being given a physical examination, you have a right to be handled with consideration and due regard for your modesty. This right is most commonly respected, and physicians do their best to protect the patient from undue exposure. Most doctors also empathize with their patients and show due consideration. Patients are respected and treated with great care as a norm, yet, as an exception, violation of this right cannot be ruled out. However, this is not specifically mentioned in the COER.
- Patient has a right to know your doctor's qualifications. If you cannot evaluate them yourself, do not hesitate to ask someone who can. The unequal nature of the doctor-patient relationship, patients approach doctors when they are in need of help may make patients reluctant to ask their physicians for their qualifications or experience. However, the COER requires that doctors provide this information without being asked, as it states: Physicians shall display as suffix to their names only recognized medical degrees or such certificates/diplomas and memberships/honors which confer professional knowledge or recognizes any exemplary qualification/ achievements.
- Patient has a right to complete confidentiality regarding your illness. The COER supports patients' right to confidentiality: Patience and delicacy should characterize the physician. Confidences concerning individual or domestic life entrusted by patients to a physician and defects in the disposition or character of patients observed during medical attendance should never be revealed unless their revelation is required by the laws of the State. However, in Indian society where the physician may be required to interact with the entire family, and may be asked for information on the patient, physicians are generally willing to discuss the patient's problems with his/ her relatives, violating this clause.
- If patient is doubtful about the treatment prescribed and especially an operation

suggested, you have a right to get a second opinion from any specialist. We may presume that doctors do not discourage their patients from seeking a second opinion on their advice. However, should a patient seek a second opinion, and if the same turns out to be radically different from the first, the patient is in a quandary as to which opinion to accept. The COER supports the right of the patient to take a second opinion, but adds as follows: Differences of opinion should not be divulged unnecessarily but when there is irreconcilable difference of opinion the circumstances should be frankly and impartially explained to the patient or his relatives or friends. It would be open to them to seek further advice as they so desire.

- Patient has a right to be told in advance what an operation is for and the possible risks involved. If this is not possible because of your being unconscious or for some other reasons, your nearest relatives must be told before they consent to the operation. There are multiple therapeutic options for some disorders. Unless there is a clear-cut advantage of one option over another, the patient should be given a choice of options. In fact the option used should be discussed and decided by the patient and the physician. A knowledgeable friend or relative may represent the patient, but someone from the patient's side should always be involved in the decision making process. The physician should also consider the economic burden of a particular therapeutic modality on the patient's family. The benefit of saving a life should be carefully balanced against the possible economic ruin of the family. The COER states: Before performing an operation the physician should obtain in writing the consent from the husband or wife, parent or guardian in the case of minor, or the patient himself as the case may be. In an operation which may result in sterility the consent of both husband and wife is needed.
- If patient is to be discharged or moved to another hospital, you have a right to be informed in advance and to make your own choice of hospital or nursing home, in consultation with the doctor. A hospital may be justified in shifting a patient to another hospital or nursing home if the patient will not benefit from treatment at the hospital, if the services necessary are not available, or if the patient cannot afford the fees (emergency treatment must be provided and the patient stabilized before such a shift). However, it is also believed that private

hospitals sometimes shift seriously ill patients to a public hospital to avoid problems. However, this is not addressed in the COER.

- Patient has a right to get your case papers upon request. Many instances have been reported of hospitals and clinics denying this right to patients and their families, possibly as a way of preventing the patient from seeking treatment elsewhere, or even getting a second opinion. The COER states as follows: If any request is made for medical records either by the patients / authorized attendant or legal authorities involved, the same may be duly acknowledged and documents shall be issued within the period of 72 hours. Despite the rights given in the charter, it is widely believed that patients' rights in India are treated very lightly and are not honored in most medical establishments. Whether recognition is given to the patient's rights or not depends upon a variety of factors. We have identified the following issues based on our own experiences as physicians and also as patients and patients' relatives. The patient's gender, age and education are decisive factors in the disclosure of information or choice for the patient. Female patients may be given less information, or choice about their treatment, though greater confidentiality may be maintained about them. If the patient is uneducated or not highly educated, the treatment meted out to them is pathetic. The authors' experience suggests that even when highly qualified people are ill, they are often treated with total disregard to their qualifications and experience. Patients from the higher economic strata get better treatment and have a higher autonomy than the less privileged, but this is only to be expected since money plays a significant role in ensuring better services. Patients may have more autonomy in urban compared to rural areas. The attitude of the physician is a deciding factor in respect to patients' rights. The higher the status and education of the physician, the less autonomy resides with the patient. There are highly qualified physicians who share all information with the patient, but they are in a minority. The disease suffered by the patient is a major factor that decides the autonomy of the patient; the poorer the prognosis, the less the autonomy. A physician might give all information to the patient if the diagnosis is one of appendicitis, but not if it is of pancreatic cancer. There have to be reasonable limitations on the autonomy of the patient, and not all patients can be given full autonomy. For example, a patient with psychiatric illness should not be given more autonomy, and it is not given. It is

not clear what happens if the physician has a psychiatric illness. After all, physicians come from the same society as patients, and there is no periodic assessment of physicians' mental health. Internationally, there are many problems in mentally incompetent patients enjoying rights like any other patients. The United Nations Principles for the Protection of Persons with Mental Illness of 1991 has significant drawbacks and implementation is far from perfect. The COER states: Medical practitioner having any incapacity detrimental to the patient or which can affect his performance vis-à-vis the patient is not permitted to practice his profession. One wonders whether this clause of the code is, or can be, enforced in practice.³¹⁴

From the above discussion, it can be inferred that, the patients are valued as important consumers and their interests are protected by various rights stated above.

3.5 Relationship of the concept with Patient as Consumer and Medical Profession as Service Provider

Is the Relation between Medical Practitioner and patient- a contract for service?

It was urged in the instant case that the relationship between a medical practitioner and the patient is of trust and confidence and therefore it is in nature of a contract of personal service and the service rendered by the medical practitioner to the patient is not "service" under Section 2(1) (o) of the act. The contention ignores the well recognized distinction between a "contract of service" and "contract for service". A "contract for service" implies a contract whereby one party undertakes to render services e.g. professional or technical services to or for another in the performance of which he is not subject to detailed direction or control but exercises professional or technical skill and used his own knowledge and discretion. A "contract of service" implies a relationship of master and servant and involves an obligation to obey orders in the work to be performed and as to its mode and performance. The court entertain no doubt that parliamentary draftsmen was aware of this well accepted distinction between "contract of service" and "contract for service" and has deliberately chosen

³¹⁴ *Id.*

the expression “contract of service” instead of expression “contract for service” in the exclusionary part of the definition of “service” in Section 2(1)(o). The reason is that an employer cannot be regarded as a consumer in pursuance of a contract of employment.³¹⁵

By affixing the adjective “personal” to the word “service” the nature of the contracts which are excluded is not altered. The said adjective only emphasizes that what is sought to be excluded is personal service only. The expression “contract of personal service” in the exclusionary part of Section 2(1) (o) must therefore be construed as excluding the services rendered by an employee to his employer under the contract of personal service from the ambit the expression “service”.

It is true that the relationship between a medical practitioner and a patient carries within it certain degree of mutual confidence and trust and therefore the services rendered by the medical practitioners can be regarded as services of personal nature. But since there is no relationship of master and servant between the doctor and the patient the contract between medical practitioner and patient cannot be treated as contract of personal service but it is a contract for services and the service rendered by the medical practitioner to his patient under such a contract is not covered by the exclusionary part of the definition of “service” contained in Section 2(1) (o) of the Act Private Doctors services are also covered under the Act.³¹⁶

Adverting to the individual doctors employed and service in the hospitals, the Court was of the view that such doctors working in the hospital/nursing home/dispensaries/whether Government or private belonging to categories (ii) and (iii) would be covered by the definition of “service” under the Act and as such are amenable to the provisions of the Act along with the management of the hospital, etc. jointly and severally.

There may be however, be a case where a person has taken an insurance policy for Medicare where under all the charges of consultation, diagnosis and medical treatment are borne by the Insurance Company. In such a case the person receiving

³¹⁵ Law Teacher-Consumer Protection in India- www.lawteacher.net accessed on 27 June 2012

³¹⁶ Id

the treatment is a beneficiary of the service which has been rendered to him by the medical practitioner cannot be said free of charge and would therefore fall within the ambit of the expression in Section 2(1)(o) of the Act. So also there may be cases where as a part of the conditions of service the employer bears the expense of medical treatment of the employee and his family members' dependant on him. The service rendered to him by a medical practitioner would not be free of charge and would therefore constitute service under Section 2(1) (o).³¹⁷

In *Indian Medical Association v. V.P. Shantha and Ors* ³¹⁸the principal issue which arose for decision before the Supreme Court was whether a medical practitioner renders 'service' and can be proceeded against for 'deficiency in service' before a forum under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. The Court dealt with how a 'profession' differs from an 'occupation' especially in the context of performance of duties and hence the occurrence of negligence. The Court noticed that medical professionals do not enjoy any immunity from being sued in contract or tort (i.e. in civil jurisdiction) on the ground of negligence. However, in the observation made in the context of determining professional liability as distinguished from occupational liability, the Court has referred to authorities, in particular, Jackson & Powell and have so stated the principles, partly quoted from the authorities :-

"In the matter of professional liability professions differ from occupations for the reason that professions operate in spheres where success cannot be achieved in every case and very often success or failure depends upon factors beyond the professional man's control. In devising a rational approach to professional liability which must provide proper protection to the consumer while allowing for the factors mentioned above, the approach of the Courts is to require that professional men should possess a certain minimum degree of competence and that they should exercise reasonable care in the discharge of their duties. In general, a professional man owes to his client a duty in tort as well as in contract to exercise reasonable care in giving advice or performing services.

The Court held that even though services rendered by medical practitioners are of a personal nature they cannot be treated as contracts of personal service (which are

³¹⁷ Supra note

³¹⁸ 1996 AIR 550

excluded from the Consumer Protection Act). They are contracts for service, under which a doctor too can be sued in Consumer Protection Courts.³¹⁹

3.6 Summary

The efficient and effective programme of Consumer Protection is of special significance to everyone because everyone is a consumer. Even a manufacturer or provider of a service is a consumer of some other goods or services. If both the producers/ providers and consumers realize the need for co-existence, then , adulterated products, spurious goods and other deficiencies in services would become a thing of the past. The active involvement and participation from all quarters i.e. the central and state governments, the educational Institutions, the NGO's, the print and electronic media and the adoption and observance of a voluntary code of conduct by the trade and industry and the citizen's charter by the service providers is necessary to see that the consumers get their due. The need of the hour is for total commitment to the consumer cause and social responsiveness to consumer needs..³²⁰

However, the relationship of patient as consumer is debatable as shown above

There should be no basic quarrel holding that a patient harmed by the treatment rendered by a doctor or a hospital for a consideration can claim damages under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. Punishment for medical negligence is made conditional on a number of parameters to serve the longer objective that medical practitioners should conform to the code of medical ethics. It is also established that doctors and hospitals if fail to exercise reasonable skill and care in the treatment of patients entrusting themselves to their care, they are as much liable to pay the price of negligence as others.

³¹⁹ Supra note 315

³²⁰ S. S. Singh & Sapna Chadah, Consumer Protection in India – Some Reflections, 2005, www.aijsh.org/setup/socialscience/paper30.pdf

Therefore the efforts of the Consumer Protection Courts are to cleanse the medical profession and safeguard the consumer rights. But the major apprehension is that the very constitution of the Redressal.³²¹

Invariably, consumers are a vulnerable lot for exploitation, more so in a developing country with the prevalence of mass poverty and illiteracy. India too is no exception to it. Instances like overcharging, black marketing, adulteration, profiteering, lack of proper services in trains, telecommunication, water supply, airlines, etc are not uncommon here. From time to time, the government has attempted to safeguard consumer's interests through legislations and the CPA 1986 is considered as the most progressive statute for consumer protection. Procedural simplicity and speedy and inexpensive redressal of consumer grievances as contained in the CPA are really unique and have few parallels in the world. Implementation of the Act reveals that interests of consumers are better protected than ever before. However, consumer awareness through consumer education and actions by the government, consumer activists, and associations are needed the most to make consumer protection movement a success in the country.³²²

Exploring the impact of such approach and conceptual framework in case of medical negligence, the following chapter presents the data and analysis extracted from the doctrinal study, case law analysis based on variables.

³²¹ Raghunath Pramanik, Medical Service and Consumer Protection, 52 Central India Law Quarterly. Vol.9.1

³²² Gomathi Vishwanathan, : http://EzineArticles.com/?expert=Dr._Gomathi_Viswanathan

Chapter 4

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Judicial Response to Medical Negligence

4.1 Introduction and Methodology

In the preceding chapters, an attempt was made, to synthesize different aspects of reasoning that led to the postulations of various legal principles applied to medical negligence under the Consumer Protection Act.

The researcher has specifically studied foreign legal principles and case laws on Medical Negligence, in order to compare the similarities and differences. The comparative study of all the case laws is being utilized to evaluate the changing trends in the law of medical negligence in India.

The data collected from various sources and their analysis in the form of comments and correlation of these particular data with the concepts, are presented herewith.

To study the Changing Trends in the Law of Medical Negligence under Consumer Protection Act, the mixed methodology was used; wherein multiple methods were used to collect and triangulate the data.

This mixed methods study has addressed the, “Changing Trends in the law of Medical Negligence under Consumer Protection Act”. A triangulation; Mixed Methods Design: Convergent variant was used, a type of design in which different but complementary data will be collected on the same topic. This is the combination of the result of more than two rigorous studies conducted to provide a more comprehensive picture of the results than either study could do alone.³²³

In this study doctrinal Study was undertaken with analysis of case laws of Supreme Court and National Commission done through 31 identified variables that affect the concept of Medical Negligence. These were used to test the Theory of Changing Trends in the Law of Medical Negligence. The interrelationship between all the variables in proving Medical Negligence was specifically studied. Also these studies the Parameters of Consumer Protection definitely influence the affected sections of Society, i.e., the Doctors, Hospital Administrators and Community members in Pune.

³²³ .Abbas Tashakkori & Charles Teddlie, *PRINCIPLES OF MIXED METHODS AND MULTIMETHOD RESEARCH DESIGN- HANDBOOK OF MIXED METHODS IN SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL RESEARCH*, 2003 edition, pp.190

No	Methodology	Details
1	Methodology of the Study (Mixed Methods-Convergent variant)	Triangulation of Doctrinal and Non Doctrinal (Empirical) Methods Convergent Variant
2	Doctrinal: Library Method	Study of the Medical Negligence and related Issues-Acts, Laws, Articles,
		Study of 40 Case laws of Supreme Court and 300 Case laws of National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission 31 Variables were studied of all the case laws
		Study of Indian and Foreign scenario
		Study of MCI guidelines
3	Non Doctrinal Methods: Surveys	Questionnaire for 427 Doctors, Specialists, Super specialists and 41 Hospital Administrators from Pune and Questionnaire for 428 Community Members from Pune
4	Non Doctrinal Methods: Interviews	Interview of Prof Graeme Laurie of Edinburgh Law School, Scotland.UK
5	Non Doctrinal Methods: Interviews	Interviews of 20 doctors, Specialists and 24 Community members from Pune
6	Local Case Analysis	Ten decided Cases From Pune District Consumer Forum in Appeal at State Commission, Mumbai and National Commission, Delhi. These Includes 3 cases directly Filed at State Commission.

Concurrent with this data collection, Qualitative methods were deployed in Surveys of Doctors, Hospital Administrators and Community; interviews of representative doctors, specialists and community members and Case Studies, 10 cases from Pune District Consumer Forum were taken which had approached State and National Commission through appeal. These were used to explore the Changing Trends in the Law of Medical Negligence.

Also Interview techniques were used. One expert at international level, and 20 doctors who are Specialist Consultants in Pune and 24 Community Members were interviewed through a structured interview schedule.

The reason for collecting both quantitative and qualitative data is to bring together the strengths of both forms of research to corroborate results.

This study has defined what similarities and the differences exist across levels of analysis. The study was a concurrent one and was conducted in a Single phase. This is a study involving Mixed Methods-Triangulation-Convergence Method, where by the doctrinal and empirical data has been converged through various stages while analysing. The analysis comprised of 7 stages as mentioned below:

7 Stages: Mixed Methods ³²⁴

Data Analysis

1. Data Reduction
2. Data Display
3. Data Transformation
4. Data Correlation- Triangulation
5. Data Consolidation
6. Data Comparison
7. Data Integration

After going through all these stages, the analysis of the present data with integration is presented herewith

³²⁴ *Supra* note1

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Figure 4

7 Stages: Mixed Methods Data Analysis

1. Data Reduction
2. Data Display
3. Data Transformation
4. Data Correlation-
Triangulation
5. Data Consolidation
6. Data Comparison
7. Data Integration

³²⁵ Abbas Tashakori, Charles Teddlie, 2003, A Framework for Analyzing Data, *Handbook of Mixed Methods*, Ed. P.374

4.2 Data Analysis of Case laws of Supreme Court and National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission

The study sample consisted of 40 case laws of Supreme Court and 300 case laws of the National Commission. The cases were selected from the web sources, www.judis.nic.in and www.confonet.in³²⁶ based on the cause of action-”Medical Negligence”. The method for the cases selection was purposive **sampling**, as by March 2013, the number of cases available from Supreme Court was 40 from all available resources. Similarly the total number of cases available from National Commission was 300 from all available resources. So these sample Case laws selected comprise the whole universe of data starting from 1967. Total Universe of Medical Negligence Case law data available till March 2013 was studied for the purpose of research.

Development of variables

After studying the case laws, in the light of concepts and laws, 31 variables were developed. These variables are based on the relationship of various factors with the Medical Negligence. Coding was planned and coding was done for all the variables for the samples selected from case laws.

Statistical analysis was done after the coding of all the case laws.³²⁷

Validity

Validity means the researcher can draw meaningful inferences from the results to a population.

Reliability

Reliability means that scores received from participants are consistent and stable over time.

Inter coder Reliability

The coding for all variables was done by two assistants. Initially the inter coder reliability was tested by testing the sample variables coding. For both of them the inter coder reliability was found to be 95 %.

The variables developed to analyze the case laws are as follows:

³²⁶ www.judis.nic.in and www.confonet.in last accessed in March 2013

³²⁷ See Annexure VI for details

1. Years of Case laws' Judgments
2. Type of Case laws
3. Patient's Place
4. Specialty of Doctors-who were sued :Specialists X General Practitioner
5. Year of Causation
6. Patient Status: Died X Disabled
7. Appeal Filed by: Doctors, Patient , Hospital
8. Education, Profession of Patient / Complainant
9. Doctor: Specialist / General Practitioner
10. Year of Judgment
11. Hospital Included
12. Complainants/Appellants: One X Many
13. Respondents : One X Many
14. Complainant's Version : Accepted X Not
15. Respondent's Version : Accepted X Not
16. Judge's Version : Acceptance
17. Expert Witness Considered
18. Expert Evidence Considered
19. Case Laws referred
20. Contributory Negligence of Patient
21. Bolam Principle mentioned in Judgment
22. Deficiency in Service
23. Medical Negligence
24. Award of Compensation
25. Previous Court's Decision
26. Consumer Protection Principle
27. New Rule in Judgment

28. Type of Judgment

29. Judicial Behavior

30. Court's Analysis of each issue-Elaboration

31. Judicial Response to each issue and argument

32. Judge's unawareness of fallacies in existing framework

Each of the following tables and graphs presents the overview of this analysis, followed by a comment.

Table No.1

Years of Case laws' Judgments

Year of case laws	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
1981-1990	3	7.5	1	0.03
1991-2000	8	20	47	15.7
2001-2010	28	70	115	38.3
2011-2013	1	2.5	137	45.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.1

Comments:

There is gradual increase in the number of cases in last 3 decades at both Supreme Court and National Commission level along with an upsurge of cases reaching the National Commission, from 2011 till today. So present study comprises of 45.7 % of cases from National Commission, decided after 2011. Fewer cases reached and decided at the Supreme Court when compared with the National Commission cases.

Table No.2
Type of Case laws

Type of case laws	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Original	1	2.5	60	20
Revision	0	0	93	31
Appeal	39	97.5	147	49
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.2

Comments:

In the present study, 97.5 % of the cases reaching Supreme Court were appeals. In case of National Commission 20 % are Original Petitions, 31 % Revision Petitions and 49 % are Appeals against state commissions' judgments.

Table No.3
Patient's Place

Patient Place	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Rural	8	20	58	19.3
Urban	32	80	242	80.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.3

Comments:

At both, Supreme Court and National Commission, the patients from **urban place** predominate, 80 % of the Cases at Supreme Court are filed by patients from Urban Area, while for National Commission 80.7 patients were found to be from urban area.

So 20 % of patients reaching the Supreme Court are from rural areas, while 19.3 % of the National Commission patients are from rural areas.

So the awareness of the medico legal concepts amongst community is more in urban areas, at least 4 times of that of rural areas.

Table No. 4

Specialty of Doctors-who were sued

Specialty	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Hospital	9	22.5	16	5.3
General Practitioner	2	5	7	2.3
Broad Specialty - Medical	5	12.5	40	13.3
Broad Specialty - Surgical	14	35	86	28.7
Super Specialty - Medical	6	15	13	4.3
Super Specialty - Surgical	4	10	85	28.3
Hospital & Specialty	0	0	53	17.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.4

Comments:

In the present study, in Supreme Court, maximum number of cases were against Broad Surgical Specialty 35 %, followed by Hospital 22.5 % and Medical Super specialty 15 %; while in National Commission maximum number of cases are against Broad Surgical Specialty 28.7 % followed by Surgical Super specialty 28.3 %, that is followed by Hospital and Specialty combined 17.7 %

Table No.5
Year of Causation

Year of Causation	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
< =1990	11	27.5	18	6
1991-2000	21	52.5	216	72
2001-2010	8	20	63	21
2011-2013	0	0	3	1
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.5

Comments:

In the present study, for majority of the cases reached and decided at both the Courts, Supreme Court and the National Commission, the causation was in the decade of 1991 to 2000.

For 52.5 % of the cases in the Supreme Court and for 72 % of the National Commission cases the causation was in the same decade.

Table No.6
Patient Status

Patient status	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Disabled	20	50	158	52.7
Died	20	50	142	47.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.6

Comments:

Supreme Court: 50 % of the patients died and same number of cases disabled, in the present study of 40 cases.

National Commission: 47.3 % of the patients died while 52.7 % patients disabled, in the present study of 300 cases at National Commission.

Table No.7
Appeal Filed by

Appeal filed by	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Doctor	12	30	58	19.3
Patient	28	70	209	69.7
Hospital	0	0	33	11
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.7

Comments:

At Supreme Court, 70 % of the patients and 30 % of Doctors filed appeals. While at the National Commission 69.7 % patients, 19.3 % Doctors and 11 % Hospitals filed appeals against lower court's judgments.

Table No.8

Education, Profession of Patient / Complainant

Profession of Patient/Complainant	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Uneducated	4	10	52	18.7
Educated	36	90	236	78.7
Lawyer	0	0	8	2.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.8

Comments:

The appeals were file by 90 % of patients in Supreme Court, who were Educated while only in 10 % cases appeals were filed by uneducated patients.

In case of National Commission, 78.7 % patients were educated, 18.7 % cases were uneducated. Only 2.7 % of the patients at National Commission were Lawyers, while in the present study, no lawyer was found to file appeals in the Supreme Court

Table No.9

Doctor: Specialist / General Practitioner

Doctor	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
General Practitioner	1	2.5	18	6
Specialist	39	97.5	282	94
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.9

Comments:

The 97.5 % of appeals were filed against the doctors, who were Specialists while 2.5 % of the cases appeals were against General Practitioners, in Supreme Court.

In National Commission, 94 % Specialists and 6 % General Practitioners were sued by patients.

Table No.10
Year of Judgment

Year of Judgment	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
< =1990	3	7.5	1	0.3
1991-2000	8	20	47	15.7
2001-2010	28	70	116	38.7
>2010	1	2.5	136	45.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.10

Comments:

In the present study 70 % of the judgments from Supreme Court are from the decade 2001 to 2010, while for the National Commission during same period 38.7 % judgments were delivered.

At the National Commission, there is gradual increase in the judgments announcements in last 3 decades while, in last 3 years, more number of judgments are seen- 45.3 % in the present study. This clearly indicates rapid increase in the number of cases being disposed during last 3 years.

Table No.11
Hospital Included

Hospital Included	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Not included	18	45	123	41
Included	22	55	177	59
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No. 11

Comments:

In the present study, in 55 % of the Supreme Court and 59 % of the cases of the National Commission, along with the doctors hospitals also were involved and were party to the litigation. While in remaining cases hospitals were not made party to the litigation.

Table No.12
Complainants/Appellants

Complainants/Appellants	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
One	31	77.5	205	68.3
Many	9	22.5	95	31.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph 12

Comments:

It was found that, in the Supreme Court, 77.5 % of the cases only one appellant was there while for 22.5 % of the cases many appellants were there.

Similarly in case of the National Commission, in 68.3 % of cases single appellant and in remaining 31.7 % of the cases many appellants were there.

Table No.13
Respondents

Respondents	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
One	21	52.5	142	47.3
Many	19	47.5	158	52.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.13

Comments:

In the present study, 52.5 % of Supreme Court cases found to have single respondent while for 47.5 % of cases there were multiple respondents.

In National Commission cases, 47.3 % cases were involved one respondent while in 52.7 % of the cases multiple respondents were involved.

Table No.14
Complainant's Version

Complainant's version	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Not Accepted	21	52.5	170	56.7
Accepted	19	47.5	130	43.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.14

Comments:

At Supreme Court, in 47.5 % of the cases the Complainant's versions were accepted by the Judges while in remaining 52.5 % of cases the same was not accepted.

In National Commission cases, 43.3 % of the cases the complainant's version was accepted and in remaining 56.7 % of the cases it was not accepted.

Table No.15
Respondent's Version

Respondent's version	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Not Accepted	18	45	170	56.7
Accepted	22	55	130	43.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.15

Comments:

In Supreme Court cases of present study, 55 % of the cases respondent's version was accepted and remaining 45 % cases it was not accepted.

In the National Commission, 43.3 % cases respondent's version was accepted while in remaining 56.7 % cases it was not accepted.

Table No.16
Judge's Version

Judge version	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Expert witness/evidence not accepted	6	15	167	55.7
Expert witness/evidence accepted	34	85	133	44.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.16

Comments:

In 85 % of the Supreme Court cases, the Judges accepted expert witness as well as expert evidence while in remaining 15 % of the cases that was not accepted.

In 44.3 % of the National Commission cases, the Judges accepted expert witness and evidence while in remaining 55.7 % of the cases the same was not accepted.

Table No.17

Expert Witness Considered

Expert Witness considered	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	10	25	182	60.7
Yes	30	75	118	39.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.17

Comments:

In 75 % of the Supreme Court cases, expert witnesses were considered, while in remaining 25 % of the cases that were not considered.

In 39.3 % of the National Commission cases, the expert witness was considered, while in remaining 60.7 % of the cases the same was not considered.

Table No.18

Expert Evidence Considered

Expert Evidence Considered	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	9	22.5	168	55.7
Yes	31	77.5	132	44.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.18

Comments:

In 77.5 % of the Supreme Court cases, expert evidence was considered, while in remaining 22.5 % of the cases the same was not considered.

In 44.3 % of the National Commission cases, the expert evidence was considered, while in remaining 55.7 % of the cases the same was not considered.

Table No.19

Case Laws referred

Case Laws referred	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	10	25	132	44
Yes	30	75	168	56
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.19

Comments:

In 75 % of the Supreme Court cases, the case laws were referred while in remaining 25 % of the cases, case laws were not referred.

In 56 % of the National Commission cases, case laws were referred while in remaining 44 % of the cases, case laws were not referred.

Table No.20

Contributory Negligence of Patient

Contributory Negligence of patient	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Not Proved	29	72.5	254	84.7
Proved	11	27.5	46	15.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.20

Comments:

In the present study, 27.5 % of the Supreme Court cases contributory negligence of the patients was proved, while in remaining 72.5 % of the cases there was no contributory negligence of the patients.

In 15.3 % of the National Commission cases, contributory negligence of the patients, was proved, while in remaining 84.7 % of the cases the same was not proved.

Table No.21

Bolam Principle mentioned in Judgment

Bolam Principle mentioned in Judgment	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	25	62.5	253	84.3
Yes	15	37.5	47	15.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.21

Comments:

In 37.5 % of the Supreme Court, the Bolam Principle was mentioned in the judgment, while in remaining 62.5 % of the case it was not mentioned.

In only 15.7 % of the National Commission cases, the Bolam principle was mentioned in the judgments, while in remaining 84.3 % of the cases it was not mentioned.

Table No.22
Deficiency in Service

Deficiency in Service Proved	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	16	40	200	66.7
Yes	24	60	100	33.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.22

Comments:

At Supreme Court, in the present study, deficiency in service was proved in 60 % of the cases, while in remaining 40 % of the cases the same was not proved.

At the National Commission, in 33.3 % cases, deficiency in service was proved while in remaining 66.7 % of the cases, the same was not proved.

Table No.23
Medical Negligence

Medical Negligence Proved*	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	16	40	190	63.3
Yes	24	60	110	36.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.23

Comments:

In the present study, in the 60 % Supreme Court cases Medical Negligence was proved while in remaining 40 % of the cases it was not proved.

Similarly, in 36.7 % of the cases of the National Commission, Medical Negligence was proved while in remaining 63.3 % of the cases, it was not proved.

Table No.24

Award of Compensation

Compensation awarded-Multiplier method	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	16	40	190	63.3
Yes	24	60	110	36.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.24

Comments:

So, the compensation was awarded in all the Medical Negligence proved cases in the apex judiciary institutions, 60 % of the Supreme Court cases and 36.7 % of the National Commission cases. The accepted method for the calculation of compensation was multiplier method.

Table No.25

Previous Court's Decision

Previous court's Decision	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Not Confirmed	8	20	114	38
Confirmed	32	80	186	62
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.25

Comments:

At Supreme Court, in 80 % of cases previous Court's decisions were confirmed while at the National Commission; in 62 % of the cases same was confirmed. In all remaining case the previous Court's decisions were not confirmed and set aside.

Table No.26

Consumer Protection Principle

Consumer Protection Principle	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Not Confirmed	16	40	190	63.3
Confirmed	24	60	110	36.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.26

Comments:

While delivering judgments, in both the apex institutions, the Consumer Protection Principle was confirmed, it was mentioned in the judgment.

In 60 % of the Supreme Court Cases and in 36.7 % of the National Commission Cases, the Consumer Protection Principle was confirmed.

Table No.27

New Rule in Judgment

New Rule in Judgment	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Not Postulated	14	35	280	93.3
Postulated	16	65	20	6.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.27

Comments:

Regarding new rule in the judgments, 65 % of the Supreme Court Judgments have new rules postulated while only 6.7 % of the National Commission judgments, new rules are seen to be postulated by the Judges.

Table No.28
Type of Judgment

Type of Judgment	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Unstructured	6	15	159	53
Structured	34	85	141	47
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.28

Comments:

85 % o the Supreme Court Judgments are structured one, meaning-having standard structure: Facts of the case, Complainant’s version, Respondent’s version, Judge’s Version, Examination of experts, reference to Medical Literature and Case Laws, Decision of the Judge.

Only 47 % of the National Commission Judgments were found to be structured one, while 53 % of Judgments are unstructured, i.e. not following the standard pattern described above.

Table No.29

Judicial Behaviour

Judicial Behaviour	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Editorship	34	85	109	36.3
Authorship	6	15	191	63.7
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.29

Comments:

Editorship: Judge gives decision after collecting information from, expert witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws etc.

Authorship: Without referring any relevant witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws, Judge gives decision as he thinks fit.

In the present study, in 85 % of Supreme Court cases, the judicial behaviour is Editorship while, 15 % of the cases it is Authorship. In the National Commission, the Editorship was found in 36.3 % as against 63.7 % cases Authorship was found.

Table No.30

Court's Analysis of each issue-Elaboration

Court's Analysis of each Issue: Elaboration	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	0	0	54	18
Minimal	6	15	97	32.3
Mixed	6	15	112	37.3
Full	28	70	36	12
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.30

Comments:

It was found that the Supreme Court's Analysis of each issue, in 70 % of the cases the analysis was full or rather elaborate, while in remaining cases it was minimal or mixed.

With the National Commission cases the analysis of each issue in consideration was full in only 12 % of cases while it was minima with 32.3 % and Mixed with 37.3 % cases.

Table No.31

Judicial Response to each issue and argument

Judicial Response to each issue and arguments	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
Non-responsive	1	2.5	170	56.7
Weak responsive	2	5	51	17
Strongly responsive	37	92.5	79	26.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.31

Comments:

While considering judicial response to each issue and arguments, in 92.5 % of the Supreme Court cases, it was strong one, while remaining 7.5 % cases the no response or minimal response.

In case of the National Commission, there was strong Judicial Response for 26.3 % cases and weak response for 17 % and for 56.7 % cases there was no response.

Table No.32

Judge's unawareness of fallacies in Medical Field and existing framework

Judge's Unawareness of fallacies in Medical Field and existing framework	Supreme Court		National Commission	
	Number of cases	%	Number of cases	%
No	38	95	254	84.7
Yes	2	5	46	15.3
Total	40	100	300	100

Graph No.32

Comments:

In 5 % of the Supreme Court cases, the judges expressed their unawareness about the fallacies of the medical field and the existing frame work. In remaining 95 % cases Judges' have not expressed such a view.

In 15.3 % of the cases of the National Commission, the members have expressed their unawareness about the fallacies of the medical field and for remaining 84.7 % of the cases the judges' have not expressed their unawareness.

Now in next part, the data related to interrelationship between the above variables and medical negligence has been presented in both tabular form and graphical form. The comments interpreting the findings are given immediately below each graph.

4.3 Interrelationships between selected variables and the Medical Negligence

Introduction

After studying the 31 variables, of the case laws, the interrelationship between important selected variables and the medical negligence was quantitatively studied.

The important selected variables are as following:

1. Patient's place: Urban X Rural
2. Patient's status : Died X Disabled
3. Doctor's Type : Specialist X General Practitioner
4. Patient's Education and Profession : Educated X Uneducated X Lawyer
5. Involvement of hospital :
6. Who is the petitioner? : Patient X Doctor X Hospital
7. New rule in the judgment :
8. Previous Court's Decision : Confirmed X Not Confirmed
9. Complainant's version : Accepted X Not Accepted
10. Respondent's version : Accepted X Not Accepted
11. Judge's version : Acceptance of Expert witness / Evidence or not
12. Expert witness :
13. Expert evidence :
14. Reference to case laws
15. Reference to Medical Literature
16. Patient's contributory negligence
17. Bolam Principle : Mentioned in the judgment or not
18. Deficiency in service
19. Award of compensation
20. Consumer Protection Principle
21. Decision of Previous Court : For Patient X Against Patient
22. Informed Consent
23. Type of Judgment : Structured X Unstructured
24. Judicial Behaviour : Editorship X Authorship
25. Court's analysis of each issue : No X Minimal X Mixed X Full
26. Judicial Response : No X Weak X Strong
27. Judge's unawareness of the fallacies in the Medical field

The statistical analysis of the interrelationship between these selected variables and the medical negligence is given herewith.

Tables No.33

**Patient's Place and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

Patient place	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N. proved (N.C)	%	M.N not proved (N.C.)	%
Urban	242	80.66	86	35.53	156	64.46
Rural	58	19.33	24	41.37	34	58.62

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS

Patient place	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N. proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Urban	31	77.5	16	51.61	15	48.39
Rural	09	22.5	8	88.88	01	12.22

Graphs No.33

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

In the present study, 77.5 % cases of Supreme Court were from urban area, and remaining from rural area. Out of Urban cases in the Supreme Court, 51.61 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was proved and in 48.39 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was not proved.

In case of cases where, patient is from rural area, in 88.88 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved and in only 12.22 % of cases, the medical negligence was not proved.

In case of the **National Commission**, 80.66 % cases were from urban region, out of which in 35.53 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved and remaining 64.46 % of the patients it was not proved.

19.33 % of the patients belonged to rural region, out of which in 41.37 % of the cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 58.62 % of the cases it was not proved.

Tables No.34

Patient's Status and the Medical Negligence

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Patient status	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N not proved (N.C)	%
Died	144	48	57	39.58	87	66.02
Diseased	156	52	53	33.97	103	60.41
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Patient status	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Died	20	50	13	65	7	35
Diseased	20	50	11	55	9	45

Graphs No.34

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: 50 % of the patients in the present study **died**, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 65 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 35 %.

In 50 % of the cases, the patients were **disabled**, out of which in 55 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 45 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: 48 % of the patients **died**, out of which in 39.58 % of case Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 60.41 % it was not.

In 52 % of the cases, patients were disabled, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 33.97 % cases and not proved in 66.02 % of cases.

Tables No.35

**Doctor's Type and the Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

Doctors type	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Specialist	282	94	105	37.23	177	62.76
Genpractitioner	18	6	05	27.77	13	72.22
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Doctors type	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Specialist	39	97.5	23	58.97	16	41.02
Genpractitioner	1	2.5	1	100	0	0

Graphs Mo.35

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

In the present study, 97.5 % cases of Supreme Court were from Specialists and Super Specialists were involved, and remaining 2.5 % were General Practitioners. Out of Specialists cases in the Supreme Court, 58.97 % of the cases were proved to be negligent and in 41.02 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was not proved.

In case of General Practitioner cases in 100 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved.

In case of the National Commission, 94 % cases were Specialists and Super specialists involved, out of which in 37.23 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved and remaining 62.76 % of the patients it was not proved.

In 6 % of the cases, **General Practitioners** were involved, out of which in 27.77 % of the cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 72.22 % of the cases it was not proved.

Tables No.36

Patient's Education and Profession and Medical Negligence

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Patient education status	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Educated	236	78.66	78	33.05	158	66.94
Uneducatd	56	18.66	30	53.57	26	46.42
Lawyer	8	2.66	2	25	6	75

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS

Patient education status	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Educated	4	10	4	100	0	0
Uneducate d	36	90	24	55.55	16	44.44
Lawyer	0	0	0	0	0	0

Graphs No.36

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: 90 % of the patients in the present study were educated, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 55.55 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 44.44 %.

In 10 % of the cases, the patients were uneducated, out of which in 100 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved. No lawyer was found to approach the apex Court.

National Commission: 78.66 % of the patients were educated, out of which in 33.05 % of case Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 66.94 % it was not.

In 18.66 % of the cases, patients were uneducated, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 53.57 % cases and not proved in 46.42 % of cases.

In 2.55 % of the appellants of the total cases in the present study were Lawyers. In those cases 25 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 75 % of them the Medical Negligence was not proved.

Tables No.37
Involvement of Hospital and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Hospital involved	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	177	59	67	37.85	110	62.14
No	123	41	43	34.95	80	65.04
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Hospital involved	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N. proved (S.C)	%	M.N not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	22	55	13	59.09	9	40.90
No	18	45	11	61.11	7	38.88

Graphs No. 37

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: 55 % of the cases in the present study involved Hospitals along with Doctors, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 59.09 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 40.09 %.

In 45 % of the cases, the Hospitals were not involved, out of which in 61.11 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 38.88 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: 59 % of the cases involved Hospitals along with Doctors, out of which in 37.85 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 62.14 % it was not.

In 41 % of the cases, Hospitals were not involved, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 34.95 % cases and not proved in 65.04 % of cases.

Tables No.38
Petitioner and the Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Case filed by	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N. Proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Patient	209	69.66	60	28.7	149	71.29
Doctor	58	19.33	34	58.62	24	41.37
Hospital	33	11	16	48.48	17	51.51
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Case filed by	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Patient	28	70	16	57.14	12	42.85
Doctor	10	25	6	60	4	40
Hospital	2	5	2	100	0	0

Graphs No.38

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 70 % of the cases in the present study Patients filed petition, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 57.14 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 42.85 %.

In 25 % of the cases, Doctors filed petition, out of which in 60 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 40 % remaining, it was not.

In 5 % of the cases, Hospitals filed petition, out of which in 100 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was proved.

National Commission: 69.66 % of the cases Patients filed petitions, out of which in 28.7 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 71.29 % it was not.

In 19.33 % of the cases, Doctors filed petitions, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 58.62 % cases and not proved in 41.37 % of cases. Similarly in 11 % cases Hospitals filed petitions, out of which in 48.48 % cases Medical Negligence was proved while in 51.51 % of cases it was not.

Tables No.39

New Rule in Judgment and the Medical Negligence

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

New rule in judgment	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.prove d (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Postulated	20	6.66	7	35	13	65
Not postulated	280	93.33	103	36.78	177	63.21
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
New rule in judgment	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.prove d (S.C)	%	M.N not proved (S.C)	%
Postulated	26	65	18	69.23	8	30.76
Not postulated	14	35	6	42.85	8	57.14

Graphs No.39

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: 65 % of the cases in the present study there was new rule postulated by the Judiciary in the judgment, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 69.23 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 30.76 %.

In 35 % of the cases, no new rule postulated, out of which in 42.85 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 57.14 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In only 6.66 % cases, new rule was postulated, out of which in 35 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 65 % it was not.

In 93.33 % of the cases, No new rule was postulated by the Judiciary, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 36.78 % cases and not proved in 63.21 % of cases.

Tables No.40
Previous Court's Decision and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

State commissi on decision	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
For patient	110	36.66	110	100	0	0
Against patient	190	63.33	0	0	190	100
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Previous court's decision	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
For patient	24	60	24	100	0	0
Against patient	16	40	0	0	16	100

Graphs No.40

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: 60 % of the cases in the present study, previous Court's decisions were in favour of Patients, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases. This proves the principle of patient protection.

In 40 % of the cases, previous Court's decision were not in favour of Patients, out of which in 100 % of cases the Medical Negligence was not proved in Supreme Court.

National Commission: 36.66 % of the cases previous Court's decisions were in favour of Patients, out of which in 100 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved in the National Commission. This proves the Consumer Protection Principle.

In 63.33 % of the cases, previous Court's decision were not in favour of Patients, Medical Negligence was not proved in all 100 % cases at the National Commission.

Tables No.41

**Complainant's Version and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

COMPLAINANT VERSION	TOTAL NO(N.C)	%	M.N.PROVED (N.C)	%	M.N NOT PROVED (N.C)	%
ACCEPTED	130	43.33	65	50	65	50
NOT ACCEPTED	170	56.66	45	26.47	125	73.52
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
COMPLAINANT VERSION	TOTAL NO(S.C)	%	M.N.PROVED (S.C)	%	M.N NOT PROVED (S.C)	%
ACCEPTED	19	47.5	16	84.21	3	15.78
NOT ACCEPTED	21	52.5	8	38.09	13	61.90

Graphs No.41

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 47.5 % of the cases in the present study the Complainant's version is accepted by the court, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 84.21 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 15.78 %.

In 52.5 % of the cases, the Complainant's version is not accepted, out of which in 38.09 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 61.9 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 43.33 % cases, the Complainant's version is accepted, out of which in 50 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 50 % it was not.

In 56.66 % of the cases, the Complainant's version is not accepted, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 26.47 % cases and not proved in 73.52 % of cases.

Tables No.42
Respondent's version and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

RESPONDE NT VERSION	TOTAL NO(N.C)	%	M.N.PR OVED (N.C)	%	M.N NOT PROVED (N.C)	%
ACCEPTED	170	56.66	45	26.52	125	73.57
NOT ACCEPTED	130	43.33	65	50	65	50
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
RESPONDE NT VERSION	TOTAL NO(S.C)	%	M.N.PR OVED (S.C)	%	M.N NOT PROVED (S.C)	%
ACCEPTED	21	52.5	8	38.09	13	61.90
NOT ACCEPTED	19	47.5	16	84.21	3	15.78

Graphs No.42

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 47.5 % of the cases in the present study the Respondent's version is accepted by the court, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 84.21 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 15.78 %.

In 52.5 % of the cases, the Respondent's version is not accepted, out of which in 38.09 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 61.9 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 43.33 % cases, the Respondent's version is accepted, out of which in 50 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 50 % it was not.

In 56.66 % of the cases, the Respondent's version is not accepted, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 26.47 % cases and not proved in 73.52 % of cases.

Tables No.43

**Judges' Version and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

Judges version	Total no (N.C)	%	M.N..proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Expert witness accepted	133	44.33	65	48.87	68	51.12
Expert witness not accepted	167	55.66	45	26.94	122	73.05
Supreme court cases analysis						
Judges version	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Expert witness accepted	34	85	22	64.70	12	35.29
Expert witness not accepted	06	15	2	33.33	4	66.66

Graphs No. 43

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 85 % of the cases in the present study the Judges' version, accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 64.7 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 35.29 %.

In 15 % of the cases, Judges' version, not accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which in 33.33 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 66.66 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 44.33 % cases, the Judges' version, accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which in 48.87 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 51.12 % it was not.

In 55.66 % of the cases, the Judges' version, not accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 26.94 % cases and not proved in 73.05 % of cases.

Tables No.44

**Use of Expert Witness and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

Expert witness used	Total no (N.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	119	39.66	56	47.05	63	52.94
No	181	60.33	54	29.83	127	70.16
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Expert witness used	Total no (S.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	30	75	19	63.33	11	36.66
No	10	25	5	50	5	50

Graphs No.44

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 75 % of the cases in the present study the Expert witness is accepted by the court, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 63.33 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 36.66 %.

In 25 % of the cases, the Expert witness is not accepted, out of which in 50 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 50 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 39.66 % cases, the Expert witness is accepted, out of which in 47.05 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 52.94 % it was not.

In 60.33 % of the cases, the Expert witness is not accepted, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 29.83 % cases and not proved in 70.16 % of cases.

Tables No.45

**Use of Expert Evidence and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

Expert evidence used	Total no (N.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	133	44.33	64	48.12	69	51.87
No	167	55.66	46	27.54	121	72.45

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Expert evidence used	Total no (S.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	31	77.5	20	64.51	11	35.48
No	9	22.5	4	44.44	5	55.56

Graphs No.45

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 77.5 % of the cases in the present study the Expert Evidence is accepted by the court, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 64.51 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 35.48 %.

In 22.5 % of the cases, the Expert Evidence is not accepted, out of which in 44.44 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 55.56 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 44.33 % cases, the Expert Evidence is accepted, out of which in 48.12 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 51.87 % it was not.

In 55.66 % of the cases, the Expert Evidence is not accepted, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 27.54 % cases and not proved in 72.45 % of cases.

Tables No.46

Reference to Case Laws and Medical Negligence NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Case law referred	Total no (N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	168	53.33	72	42.85	96	57.14
No	132	44	38	28.78	94	71.21
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Case law referred	Total no (S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	30	75	20	66.66	10	33.33
No	10	25	4	40	06	60

Graphs No.46

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 75 % of the cases in the present study the Case Laws were referred by the court, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 66.66 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 33.33 %.

In 25 % of the cases, the Case Laws were not referred, out of which in 40 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 60 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 53.33 % cases, the , Case Laws were referred by the Commission, out of which in 42.85 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 57.14 % it was not.

In 44 % of the cases, the Case Laws were not referred by the Commission, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 28.78 % cases and not proved in 71.21 % of cases.

Tables No.47
Reference to Medical Literature and Medical Negligence
National Commission Cases Analysis

Medical literature used	Total no (N.C)	%	M.N. proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	109	36.33	44	40.36	65	59.63
No	191	63.66	66	34.55	125	65.44
Supreme Court cases analysis						
Medical literature used	Total no (S.C)	%	M.N. proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
YES	30	75	20	66.66	10	33.33
NO	10	25	4	40	6	60

Graphs No.47

NATIONAL COMMISSION- GRAPH

SUPREME COURT- GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 75 % of the cases in the present study the Medical Literature was referred by the court, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 66.66 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 33.33 %.

In 25 % of the cases, the Medical Literature was not referred, out of which in 40 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 60 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 36.33 % cases, the Medical Literature was referred by the Commission, out of which in 40.36 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 59.63 % it was not.

In 63.66 % of the cases, the Medical Literature was not referred by the Commission, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 34.55 % cases and not proved in 65.44 % of cases.

Tables No.48
Contributory Negligence of Patient and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Contributory negligence of patient	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Proved	46	15.33	26	56.52	20	43.47
Not proved	254	84.66	84	33.07	170	66.92
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Contributory negligence of patient	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Proved	11	27.5	11	100	0	0
Not proved	29	72.5	13	44.82	16	55.17

Graphs No.48

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 27.5 % of the cases in the present study the Contributory Negligence by patient was proved, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases, so in spite of that the doctor was found to be negligent. That means contributory negligence by patients did not have negative impact on judgment.

In 72.5 % of the cases, the Contributory Negligence of patients was not proved, out of which in 44.82 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 55.17 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 15.33 % cases, the Contributory Negligence of patients was proved, out of which in 56.52 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 43.47 % it was not.

Similarly, in 84.66 % of the cases at National Commission, Contributory Negligence of patients was not proved, out of which in 33.07 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved, while in 66.92 % remaining case it was not proved.

Tables No.49

**Use of Bolam Principle and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

Bolam principle used	Total no(n.c)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	47	15.66	25	53.19	22	46.80
No	253	84.33	85	33.59	168	66.40

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Bolam principle used	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (s.c)	%
Yes	15	37.5	10	66.66	5	33.33
No	25	62.5	14	56	11	44

Graphs No.49

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 37.5 % of the cases in the present study, the Bolam principle was mentioned, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 66.66 % of the cases, and in remaining 33.33 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

. In 62.5 % of the cases, the Bolam principle was not mentioned , out of which in 56 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 44 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 15.66 % cases, the Bolam principle was mentioned, out of which in 53.19 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 46.8 % it was not.

Similarly, in 84.33 % of the cases at National Commission,, Bolam principle was not mentioned, out of which in 33.59 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved, while in 66.4 % remaining case it was not proved.

Tables No.50

**Deficiency in Services and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS**

Deficiency in services	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N. proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	110	36.66	110	100	0	0
No	190	63.33	0	0	190	100

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Deficiency in services	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N. proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	24	60	24	100	0	0
No	16	40	0	0	16	100

Graphs No.50

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 60 % of the cases in the present study, **Deficiency in service** was proved, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases. In 40 % of the cases, the **Deficiency in service** was not proved; obviously in all 100 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

National Commission: In 36.66 % cases, the **Deficiency in service** was proved, out of which in all 100 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Similarly, in 63.33 % of the cases at National Commission, **Deficiency in service** was not proved; in all the cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

Tables No.51

Award of Compensation and Medical Negligence

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Compensation awarded	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	110	36.66	110	100	0	0
No	190	63.33	0	0	190	100
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Compensation awarded	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	24	60	24	100	0	0
No	16	40	0	0	16	100

Graphs NO.51

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 60 % of the cases in the present study, Deficiency in service was proved, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases and compensation was awarded to all.

. In 40 % of the cases, the Deficiency in service was not proved; obviously in all 100 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved; no compensation was awarded.

National Commission: In 36.66 % cases, the Deficiency in service was proved, out of which in all 100 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and compensation was awarded.

Similarly, in 63.33 % of the cases at National Commission, Deficiency in service was not proved; in all the cases Medical Negligence was not proved, no compensation was awarded.

Tables No.52
Consumer Protection Principle and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Consumer protection principle	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	110	36.66	110	100	0	0
No	190	63.33	0	0	190	100

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Consumer protection principle	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N..proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	24	60	24	100	0	0
No	16	40	0	0	16	100

Graphs No.52

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 60 % of the cases in the present study, Deficiency in service was proved, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases and compensation was awarded to all, thus the Consumer Protection Principle was established in those cases.

. In 40 % of the cases, the Deficiency in service was not proved; obviously in all 100 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved; no compensation was awarded.

National Commission: In 36.66 % cases, the Deficiency in service was proved, out of which in all 100 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and compensation was awarded, thus the Consumer Protection Principle was established in those cases

Similarly, in 63.33 % of the cases at National Commission, Deficiency in service was not proved; in all the cases Medical Negligence was not proved, no compensation was awarded.

Tables No.53

Decision of Previous Court and Medical Negligence

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

State commis sion decision	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
For patient	110	36.66	110	100	0	0
Against patient	190	63.33	0	0	190	100
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Decisio n of previou s court	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
For patient	24	60	24	100	0	0
Against patient	16	40	0	0	16	100

Graphs No.53

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURTGRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 60 % of the cases in the present study, the decision of previous Court was for patient, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases.

. In 40 % of the cases, the decision of previous Court was against patient; obviously in all 100 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

National Commission: In 36.66 % cases, the decision of previous Court was for patient, out of which in all 100 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Similarly, in 63.33 % of the cases at National Commission, the decision of previous Court was against patient, in all the cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

Tables No.54
Informed Consent and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Informed consent taken	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.pro ved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	95	31.66	33	34.73	62	65.26
No	205	68.33	77	37.56	128	62.43

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS

Informed consent taken	Total no(S.C)	%	M.n.pro ved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	26	65	18	69.23	8	30.76
No	14	35	4	28.57	8	57.14

Graphs No.54

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 65 % of the cases in the present study, the Informed Consent was taken, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 69.23 % of the cases, and in remaining 30.76 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

In 35 % of the cases, the Informed Consent was not taken, out of which in 28.57 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 57.14 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 31.66 % cases, the Informed Consent was taken, out of which in 34.73 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 65.26 % it was not.

Similarly, in 68.33 % of the cases at National Commission, the Informed Consent was not taken, out of which in 37.56 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved, while in 62.43 % remaining cases it was not proved.

Tables No.55
Type of Judgment and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Type of judgement	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N.proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Structured	141	47	63	44.68	78	55.31
Unstructured	159	53	47	29.55	112	70.44
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Type of judgement	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N.proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Structured	34	85	22	64.70	12	35.29
Unstructured	6	15	2	33.33	4	66.66

Graphs No.55

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 85 % of the cases in the present study, the Judgment was structured one, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 64.7 % of the cases, and in remaining 35.29 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

. In 15 % of the cases, the Judgment was unstructured, out of which in 33.33 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 66.66 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 47 % cases, the Judgment was structured one, out of which in 44.68 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 55.31 % it was not.

Similarly, in 53 % of the cases at National Commission, Judgment was unstructured, out of which in 29.55 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved, while in 70.44 % remaining cases it was not proved.

Tables No.56
Judicial Behaviour and Medical Negligence
National Commission cases analysis

Judicial Behaviour	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N. proved (N.C)	%	M.N not proved (N.C)	%
Editorship	141	47	63	44.68	78	55.31
Authorshp	159	53	47	29.55	112	70.44
Supreme Court cases analysis						
Judicial Behaviour	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N. proved (S.C)	%	M.N not proved (S.C)	%
Editorship	34	85	22	64.70	12	35.29
Authorship	6	15	2	33.33	4	66.66

Graphs No.56

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Editorship: Judge gives decision after collecting information from, expert witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws etc.

Authorship: Without referring any relevant witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws, Judge gives decision as he thinks fit.

Supreme Court: In 85 % of the cases in the present study, Judicial Behaviour was Editorship, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 64.7 % of the cases, while it was not proved in 35.29 % of cases.

In 15 % of the cases, the Judicial Behaviour was Authorship; out of which in 33.33 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 66.66 % cases it was not proved.

National Commission: In 47 % cases, the Judicial Behaviour was Editorship, out of which in 44.68 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 55.31 % cases it was not proved.

Similarly, in 53 % of the cases at National Commission Judicial Behaviour was Authorship, in which 29.55 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 70.44 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

Tables No.57

Court's Analysis of each issue and Medical Negligence

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Court analysis	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N. proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Full	36	12	12	33.33	24	66.66
Mix	111	37	46	41.44	65	58.55
Minimal	92	30.66	26	28.26	66	68.75
No	54	18	22	40.74	32	59.25

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS

Court analysis	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N. proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Full	28	70	21	75	7	25
Mix	6	15	1	16.66	5	83.33
Minimal	6	15	2	33.33	4	66.66
No	0	0	0	0	0	0

Graphs No.57

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 70 % of the cases in the present study, Court's Analysis of each issue was full, meaning at length discussion, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 75 % of the cases, and in remaining 25 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

In 15 % of the cases, the Court's Analysis of each issue was mixed, a little less elaborate, out of which in 16.66 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 83.33 % remaining, it was not.

In 15 % of remaining cases Court's Analysis of each issue was minimal; the Medical Negligence in such cases was proved in 33.33 % of cases while it was not in 66.66 % cases.

National Commission: In 12 % cases, the Court's Analysis of each issue was full, out of which in 33.33 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 66.66 % it was not.

Similarly, in 37 % of the cases at National Commission, the Court's Analysis of each issue was mixed; out of which in 41.44 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved, while in 58.55 % remaining cases it was not proved.

In 30.66 % of cases the Court's Analysis of each issue was minimal, out of which 28.26 % of the cases Medical Negligence was proved and 68.75 % cases it was not.

Similarly, in 18 % of the cases at National Commission, there was no Court's Analysis of each issue, 40.74 % of the cases Medical Negligence was proved and 59.25 % of the cases it was not.

Tables No.58
Judicial Response and Medical Negligence
NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Judicial response	TOTAL NO(N.C)	%	M.N.PROVED (N.C)	%	M.N NOT PROVED (N.C)	%
Strongly response	79	26.33	53	67.08	26	32.91
Weakly response	51	17	19	37.25	32	62.74
No response	170	56.66	38	22.35	132	77.64
SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS						
Judicial response	TOTAL NO(S.C)	%	M.N.PROVED (S.C)	%	M.N NOT PROVED (S.C)	%
Strongly response	37	92.5	23	62.16	14	37.83
Weakly response	2	5	1	50	1	50
No response	1	2.5	0	0	1	100

Graphs No.58

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

Based on the one of the research articles, the judicial response to the issues was divided in strong, weak and no response.

Supreme Court: In 92.5 % of the cases in the present study, Judicial Response was strongly responsive, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 62.16 % of the cases, while it was not proved in 37.83 % of cases.

. In 5 % of the cases, the Judicial Response was weak to the issues; out of which in 50 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 50 % cases it was not proved. In 2.5 % of the cases, there was no Judicial Response, where Medical Negligence was not proved in all 100 % cases.

National Commission: In 26.33 % cases, the Judicial Response was Strong, out of which in 67.08 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 32.91 % cases it was not proved.

Similarly, in 17 % of the cases at National Commission Judicial Response was weak, in which 37.25 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 62.74 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

In 56.66 % there was no **judicial response** to the issues in discussion, where Medical Negligence was proved in 22.35 % of cases while in remaining 77.64 % of the cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

Tables No.59

Judges' unawareness and Medical Negligence

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES ANALYSIS

Judges unawareness of fallacies in the existing frame work	Total no(N.C)	%	M.N. proved (N.C)	%	M.N. not proved (N.C)	%
Yes	46	15.33	28	60.86	18	39.13
No	254	84.66	82	32.28	172	67.71

SUPREME COURT CASES ANALYSIS

Judges unawareness of fallacies in the existing frame work	Total no(S.C)	%	M.N. proved (S.C)	%	M.N. not proved (S.C)	%
Yes	2	5	0	0	2	100
No	38	95	24	63.15	14	36.84

Graphs No.59

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments:

In the present study it was found that,

Supreme Court: in only 5 % of case, Judges expressed the unawareness of the fallacies in the medical field and existing frame work, out of which in all the cases Medical Negligence was not proved. While in 95 % of the cases judges have not expressed their unawareness of the fallacies, where Medical Negligence was proved in 63.15 % cases and in 36.84 % cases it was not proved.

National Commission: In 15.33 % of the cases the members expressed their unawareness of the medical field and the existing frame work, out of which 60.86 % were negligent and 36.84 % it was not negligence.

In remaining 84.66 % of the cases, members have not expressed their unawareness of the medical fallacies, but still 32.28 found to be negligent and 67.71 % was not negligent.

Table No.60

Average Time Taken for Judgment

National Commission Analysis	
YEAR	AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR JUDGEMENT in Years
1990-1994	2
1995-1999	4
2000-2004	5
2005-2009	7
2010-2013	6
Supreme Court Analysis	
YEAR	AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR JUDGEMENT in Years
Before 1990	2
1990-1994	1
1995-1999	4
2000-2004	3
2005-2009	3.5
2010-2013	5.5

Graph No. 60

NATIONAL COMMISSION

SUPREME COURT

Comments:

As the tables and the graphs show, the average time taken for judgment is gradually increasing.

Supreme Court: from 2 years before 1990 to 5.5 years now in 2013.

National Commission: from 2 years at 1990 to 6 years now in 2013.

Table No.61

Supreme Court: Relationship of Number of Judges to Medical Negligence Decision

Sr. No	Number of Judges	Total No. of cases out of 40	Medical Negligence Proved	Percentage of Medical Negligence Proved	Medical Negligence Not Proved
1	1	1	0	0	1
2	2	30	19	63.33	11
3	3	9	5	55.55	4

Comments:

In the present study of 40 Supreme Court Judgments, it was found that total number of Judges of the National Commission were 47 for these cases.

Based on the number of Judges, it was found that the number of Judges ranged from 1 to 3. As shown in the table, 63.33 % of the decisions were Medical Negligence proved while number of members in bench was 2. Similarly, when number of members was 3, percentage of proving Medical Negligence was found, i.e. 55.55 %.

Table No. 62

National Commission: Relationship of Number of Judges/Members to Medical Negligence Decision

Sr. No	Number of Judges/Members	Total No. of cases out of 300	Medical Negligence Proved	Percentage of Medical Negligence Proved	Medical Negligence Not Proved
1	1	10	4	40	6
2	2	196	81	41.32	115
3	3	35	9	25.71	26
4	4	44	10	22.72	34
5	5	12	6	50	6
6	6	3	0	0	3

Comments:

In the present study of 300 National Commission Judgments, it was found that total number of Judges or the members of the National Commission were 37 for these cases.

Based on the number of Members in National Commission, it was found that the number of members ranged from 1 to 6. As shown in the table, 50 % of the decisions were Medical Negligence proved while number of members in bench was 5. Similarly, when number of members was 4, lowest percentage of proving Medical Negligence was found, i.e. 22.72 %.

4.4 Trends in decided Case Laws

In the present study, the researcher has identified, 5 criteria of trends in the Law of Medical Negligence, as follows

Criteria for trends

1. Principles:
 - a. Bolam Principle
 - b. Consumer Protection Principle
 - c. Case Law referral
 - d. Contributory Negligence
 - e. Bolitho Principle
 - f. New Rule in Judgment
 - g. Precedents: Excerpts Analysis
2. Deficiency
 - a. Deficiency in service
 - b. Medical Negligence
 - c. No Informed Consent
3. Method of Judging
 - a. Type of Judgment
 - b. Judicial Behaviour
 - c. Court's Analysis of each issue
 - d. Judicial Response to each issue
 - e. Judge' unawareness of fallacies
4. Evidences
 - a. Judge's Version
 - b. Expert Witness
 - c. Expert Evidence
 - d. Medical Literature referral
5. Quantum of Compensation
 - a. Compensation awarded
 - b. Method of Calculation

The studied case laws were analyzed for the decided criteria for the period from 1981 divided in phases of 10 years each as follows

1. First Phase 1981 to 1990
2. Second Phase 1991 to 2000
3. Third Phase 2001 to 2010
4. Fourth Phase 2011 and till today

The critical evaluation of the trends as per the selected criteria is given herewith

Figure 5

TRENDS WISE CASE LAW ANALYSIS

A) PRINCIPLES

Table No. 63

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES

SUPREME COURT CASES

Principle	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013	Principle	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Bolam Principle Mentioned in Judgment	0	1	19	27	Bolam principle Mentioned in Judgment	0	2	12	1
Consumer Protection Principle used	0	12	38	60	Consumer Protection Principle used	2	7	14	1
Case Law Referred	1	10	67	90	Case Law Referred	1	7	21	1
Contributory Negligence Proved	0	5	13	28	Contributory Negligence Proved	0	0	10	1
Bolitho Principle	0	0	5	8	Bolitho Principle	0	0	1	0
New Rule in Judgment	0	0	10	10	New Rule in Judgment	2	8	16	0

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

Graph No. 61

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

The traditional basis for deciding the Medical Negligence cases is the **Bolam Principle**. In the selected study of 300 National Commission cases, the principle is being mentioned in increasing number. Before 1990 it is not mentioned at all, while during 1991 to 2000, in 2.12 % cases (out of 47 cases) it was mentioned in the

judgment, during 2001 to 2010 it was mentioned in 16.37 % of Cases (out of 116 cases) and after 2011 till today it is mentioned in 19.85 % of the cases (out of 136 cases).

Sympathetic discussion about patient’s complaints done and patients are protected under the Consumer Protection Principle, in 1991 to 2000, is 12 %, while in 2001 to 2010 it was 32.75 % and from 2011 the principle is being used in 19.85 % of Cases.

Case laws are being referred in increasing number of cases, in one case before 1990 case laws were referred, while in 21.27 % of cases in 1991 to 2000, 57.75 % cases in 2001 to 2010 and after 2011 it is in 44.11 % of decided cases case laws are referred.

The contributory negligence of the patients is actively mentioned and sought as 10.63 % of cases in 1990 to 2000, 11.2 % of cases in 2001 to 2010 and now after 2011 it is 20.58 %, indicating increase in the awareness regarding the contributory Negligence.

The *Bolitho* Principle is not at all mentioned before 2000, while it is just mentioned sparingly, 4.31 % in 2001 to 2010 cases and after that 5.88 %. It indicates that the principle is now known to be mentioned more frequently though not applied up till now.

As such the National Commission has precarious role in developing new rules. In 2001 to 2010 8.62 % of cases and after 2011 (136 cases) it is 7.35 %

**SUPREME COURT CASES GRAPH
Graph No. 62**

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

In the Supreme Court cases, in 25 % cases of 1991-2000, the Bolam Principle is mentioned in the Judgments while in 42.8 % of 2001 to 2010 cases, it is mentioned. Presently since 2011 till today in all cases this important principle is mentioned.

Sympathetic discussion about patient's complaints done and patients are protected under the Consumer Protection Principle, during 1980 to 1991 it is used in 66.66 % of cases, in 1991 to 2000 is 87.5 %, while in 2001 to 2010 it was 50 % and from 2011 the principle is being used in 100 % of Cases.

Case laws are being referred in increasing number of cases, in 33.33 % of case before 1990 case laws were referred, while in 87.75 % of cases in 1991 to 2000, 75 % cases in 2001 to 2010 and after 2011 it is in 100 % of decided cases, case laws are referred.

The contributory negligence of the patients is actively mentioned and sought only after 2000, as 0 % of cases in 1990 to 2000, 35.71 % of cases in 2001 to 2010 and now after 2011 it is 100 %, indicating increase in the awareness regarding the contributory Negligence.

The *Bolitho* Principle is not at all mentioned before 2000, while it is just mentioned sparingly, 3.57 % in 2001 to 2010 cases and after that in no case it is mentioned. It indicates that the principle is now known to be mentioned more frequently though not applied up till now.

The Supreme Court has major role in developing new rules. Between 1981 to 1990 in 66.66 % of cases, in 100 % of cases in 1990 to 2000, and in 2001 to 2010 it was 57.14 % and after 2011 no case has developed new rules. Thus after the application of the Consumer Protection Act to the Medical Field, the very next decade there was an intense legal Judicial Activism that spelt various legal principles settled as law today.

B) DEFICIENCY

Table No. 64

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES

SUPREME COURT CASES

DEFICIENCY				
Deficiency	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136
Deficiency in Services Proved	0	12	37	61
Medical Negligence's Proved	0	12	37	61
Inform Consent Not Taken	1	20	40	34

DEFICIENCY				
Deficiency	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Deficiency in Services Proved	2	7	14	1
Medical Negligence's Proved	2	7	14	1
Inform Consent Not Taken	1	5	19	1

Graph No. 63

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

In the present study, during 1991 to 2000, in 25.53 % cases deficiency in services was proved, in 25.53 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 57.44 % cases Informed Consent was not taken. During 2001 to 2010, in 31.89 % of cases Deficiency in service was proved at the same time Medical Negligence was proved, while in 65.51 % of the cases Informed Consent was not taken. After 2011, in 44.85

% of cases deficiency was proved as well as Medical Negligence. In 75 % of the patients Informed Consent was not taken.

Thus over the years, there has been an increase in % of deficiency in service and Medical Negligence. Incidentally, there has been an increase in the % of incidences where Informed Consent is not being taken.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

In the present study of 40 cases, during 1981 to 1990, in 66.66 % of cases deficiency in service and Medical Negligence was proved. In 33.33 % cases Informed Consent was not taken.

During 1991 to 2000, in 87.5 % cases deficiency in service and Medical Negligence was proved. In 37.5 % cases the Informed Consent was not taken.

During 2001 to 2010, in 50 % cases deficiency in service and Medical Negligence was proved. In 32.14 % cases Informed Consent was not taken. While after 2011, in all cases deficiency and Medical Negligence was proved. But also in none of the cases Informed Consent was taken

C) METHODS OF JUDGING

Table No. 65

Type of Judgment: Structured / Unstructured

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES

SUPREME COURT CASES

Type of Judgment	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013	Type of Judgment	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Structured	1	20	56	64	Structured	2	7	24	1
Unstructured	0	27	60	72	Unstructured	1	1	4	0

Graph No. 64

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

During last 3 decades, there is an increase in structured as well as unstructured judgments, while in 1981 to 1990, only one case that has structured judgment.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

In Supreme Court, % of structured Judgment has increased over last 4 decades, serially 66.66 %, 87.5 %, 87.71% and 100 % as the graph suggests.

Judicial Behaviour: Editorship/ Authorship

Table No. 66

	NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES				SUPREME COURT CASES				
Judicial Behaviour	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013	Judicial Behaviour	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Editorial	1	16	51	41	Editorial	2	7	24	1
Authorship	0	31	65	95	Author ship	1	1	3	1

Graph No. 65

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

Only one case was included in this study from the 1981 to 1990 decade. The judgment delivered was by Judicial Behaviour that can be classified as Editorship. Next 2 decades, it was 34.04 % and 43.96 % Editorship was used, while after 2011 in 30.14 % cases the editorship was used. The editorship is supposed to be the best as the judgment depends on various references. The Authorship was used as principle in about 50 to 70 % of cases in last 4 decades.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

Over the last 4 decades, in Supreme Court, there has been an increase in Editorship as Judicial Behaviour, while Authorship has gradually reduced.

Court's Analysis of Each Issue: Full/ Mixed/ Minimal /Low

Table No. 67

Court's Analysis of each issue	NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES				Court's Analysis of each issue	SUPREME COURT CASES			
	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013		1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Full	1	8	18	9	Full	2	7	18	1
Mixed	0	23	43	46	Mixed	0	0	6	0
Minimal	0	15	34	48	Minimal	1	1	4	0
Low	0	1	21	33	Low	0	0	0	0

Graph No. 66

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

Over last 4 decades, when the judgments of National Commission cases are analyzed, it is found that there is reduction in % of complete analysis of the cases, i.e. issues under consideration. 17.02 % in 1991-2000, 15.51 % in 2001 to 2010 and from 2011 it is 6.61 %. In 3rd decade, 2001 to 2010, about 44.68 % judgments are seen with low analysis of issues under consideration.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

At Supreme Court, for the analysis of each issue under consideration, % of full or complete analysis has been increasing as depicted in graph. So thus it can be said that the apex court is through with its approach toward Medical Negligence.

Judicial Response to Each Issue: Strongly Responsive / Weakly Responsive / No Responsive

Table No. 68

Judicial Response to each issue	NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES				SUPREME COURT CASES			
	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	3	8	28	1
Strongly responsive	0	12	37	29	2	8	26	1
Weakly Responsive	1	12	14	25	0	0	2	0
No Responsive	0	23	65	82	1	0	0	0

Graph No. 67

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

When analyzed, the Judicial Response has been divided in to Strongly Responsive, Weakly Responsive and non Responsive. For the National Commission Judgments, the Judicial Response to each issue has been variable. Last 3 decades, rather it is found that the non responsive nature of Judge’s is increasing.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

The Supreme Court has been traditionally strongly responsive for the issues under consideration. The graph above shows the trend.

Judge’s Unawareness of Fallacies in the System and Medical Field

Table No. 69

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES

SUPREME COURT CASES

Judge’ unawareness of fallacies	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013	Judge’ unawareness of fallacies	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Yes	0	3	15	28	Yes	0	0	2	0
No	1	44	101	108	No	3	8	26	1

Graph No. 68

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

At the National Commission, there is an increased trend of accepting or formally quoting by the judges that, they are unaware of the fallacies of the Medical Field.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

At Supreme Court, only in the decade of 2001-2010, in 7.14 % of the cases, the Judges have formally mentioned that they are unaware of the fallacies of the medical field. Otherwise in all the past 2 decades they have formally not mentioned the unawareness.

D) EVIDENCE

Table No. 70

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES

SUPREME COURT CASES

EVIDENCE	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013	EVIDENCE	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Judges Version Expert Witness accepted	1	18	55	59	Judges Version Expert Witness Accepted	2	7	24	1
Expert Witness Used	1	17	48	53	Expert Witness Used	1	7	21	1
Expert Evidences used	1	10	67	90	Expert Evidences Used	1	7	22	1
Medical Literature Referred	1	12	48	48	Medical Literature Referred	2	7	22	1

Graph No. 69

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT GRAPH

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

Regarding use and acceptance of the expert witness, expert evidence and Medical Literature; there is variability between 25 to 66 % in all the 4 decades. It is true that there is an increase in the use and acceptance of the same.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

In Supreme Court, the trend to use and acceptance of expert witness, expert evidence and Medical Literature is increasing and last decade it was around 87.5 %, while after 2011, the use and acceptance is 100 %. So it is a positive sign of respecting the Expert Witness and Evidence.

E) COMPENSATION

Table No. 71

NATIONAL COMMISSION CASES

SUPREME COURT CASES

Quantum of compensation	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013	Quantum of compensation	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010	2011-2013
Total no of cases	1	47	116	136	Total no of cases	3	8	28	1
Compensation awarded	0	12	37	61	Compensation awarded	2	6	15	1

Graph No. 70

NATIONAL COMMISSION GRAPH

SUPREME COURT CASES GRAPH

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

In National Commission Judgments, the trend of awarding compensation is as follows

- 1991-2001 - 25.53 %;
- 2001 to 20110 - 31.39 %
- After 2011- 44.85 %

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

At Supreme Court, the trend of awarding compensation is much higher

- 1981 to 1990 – 66.66 %;
- 1991 to 2001- 75 %;
- 2001 to 2010 – 53.57 % and
- 100 % for the cases after 2011.

Thus trend of awarding the compensation is higher at Supreme Court than at National Commission.

Method of Compensation Calculation:³²⁸

In most cases the remedy for a victim of medical negligence through a Consumer Court would be to get compensated. But how is this compensation fixed? You cannot fix a value to your dear ones in terms of money. Can you? The Consumer Court has formulated a method to calculate, a not so accurate but fair, compensation amount. Let us read more on this below.

There are a lot of factors including pecuniary factors like loss of future earnings (if the victim is dead or disabled), medical expenses incurred, future medical expenses (if the victim still requires medical assistance), cost of litigation etc. and non pecuniary factors like compensation for the pain and suffering, non-enjoyment of life, shortening of life expectancy etc.

Calculating the loss of future earnings is a complex process. The Supreme Court in *Sarla Verma & Ors. Vs. Delhi Transport Corp. & Anr* has laid down the three step

³²⁸ Runjhun, Compensation in Medical Negligence Cases: A Quick Survey-Consumer Tadka, (October 28, 2011) <http://info.akosha.com/consumer-complaints/consumer-protection/compensation-in-medical-negligence-cases-a-quick-survey/> (last accessed 30 April 2013).

process through which this can be calculated. The first step would be to calculate the 'multiplicand' (a number that is to be multiplied with another – in $2 * 5$, 5 is the multiplicand). In this step the annual income of the deceased or the injured is calculated. The deceased/injured would have spent on himself is deducted. The balance is the Multiplicand.

Step 2 is to determine the Multiplier. In this step an estimate is made on the years of active career of the person. From this, some years are deducted under heads like imponderables in life, uncertain economic factors etc. The resulting number is the multiplier. For example if x, dies at the age of 35, and if his expected period of active service is estimated to be till 60 years, then the multiplier would be 25. From this, let's say, 7 years are deducted under imponderables in life and economic factors, then the final multiplier will become 18.

The third step is to multiply the Multiplicand with the multiplier, which will give the compensation amount under Loss of future earnings. The pecuniary factors can be, to an extent, accurate but the non pecuniary factors cannot be accurate. You cannot measure the mental sufferings and give a value to it. The courts usually fix an amount which it deems will compensate the non pecuniary damages.

These factors vary depending on the nature of the cases. For example in the case where a person has fully recovered from the damages caused due to the medical negligence, he may not be given compensation for loss of future earnings. Similarly if the medical expense of the victim is covered by a third party, for example, if it is covered by the company he works in, then he might not get compensation for medical expenses.

In most medical negligence cases the consumer court has awarded compensation less than the amount asked for by the complainant. One can argue that since it is the complainant who has suffered all the physical and mental damages, he is the best person to determine the compensation he needed. But there are times people ask for unreasonable amounts or may think that a particular amount is reasonable, when it is actually not. You will always over value yourself or your loved ones. So better leave it to the courts to decide and hope that you'll get a fair compensation. Or maybe, not go for a case and fall in love with the doctor.³²⁹

Anuradha Saha Case: Example: On October 21, 2011, NCDRC awarded a total of Rs. 1.7 Crores compensation against the Kolkata doctors and AMRI Hospital but

³²⁹ Ibid

deducted more than Rs. 40 Lakh on ground of alleged “interference” by Dr. Saha (although Apex Court held only the Kolkata doctors/hospital guilty for Anuradha’s death) and also due to the death of one of the guilty doctors, Dr. Roychowdhury. Although this was the highest compensation ever awarded in India for death of a patient due to “medical negligence”, Dr. Saha has challenged the said order passed by NCDRC on numerous grounds including the fact that the NCDRC did not follow settled principles for calculating compensation in “medical negligence” cases while dismissing more than 98% of Dr. Saha’s claim. The NCDRC also used the “Multiplier” method for calculation of compensation which has never been used any case of “medical negligence” until now. In fact, “Multiplier” method is used under Section 163A of the Motor Vehicle Accident Act for awarding compensation to auto accident victims in “no fault” accident. Obviously, the “Multiplier” method minimizes the compensation to be paid by the rash and negligent doctors and hospitals.³³⁰

³³⁰ Anonymous, Anuradha Saha Death Case Ends In Supreme Court: Judgment Reserved In Highest “Medical Negligence” Case In Indian Medico-legal History (April 11,2013) <http://pbtindia.com/archives/1815> (last accessed 30 April 2013)

4.5 Analysis of 10 cases from Pune district pending at State and National Commission

Introduction

After studying the 31 variables, of the case laws and the interrelationship between important variables the 10 Pune Cases were analyzed under same variables in order to compare the local trend and the local aspect of medical negligence was quantitatively studied.

The statistical analysis of the interrelationship between these selected variables and the medical negligence is given herewith.

Study of Pune's 10 Cases: Decided by District Forum and Pending at higher Commission (State / National)

Table No. 72

TYPE OF CASE	TOTAL NO CASE	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
ORIGINAL	10	4	6
APPEAL	0	0	0
REVISION	0	0	0

PATIENT PLACE	TOTAL NO CASE	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
URBAN	10	4	6
RURAL	0	0	0

Graph No. 71

Comments:

The analysis of 10 Pune Cases from Pune that included 7 decided cases at Pune District Consumer Redressal forum and 3 cases from Pune directly approached State Consumer Commission.

In 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved out of 7 cases at District Forum while in 6 cases it was not proved, that includes 3 cases at district forum and 3 cases at State commission.

All the 10 cases are from urban origin where the patients are from urban area, while no case is from rural area.

Table No. 73

PATEINT STATUS	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
DIED	1	1	0
DISABLED	9	3	6

PATIENT EDUCATION	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
EDUCATION	10	4	6
NOT EDUCATED	0	0	0
LAWYER	0	0	0

Graph No. 72

Patient Status:

Out of 10 cases, in 1 case patient died while in rest 9 cases patients were disabled. In the case where patient died, Medical Negligence was proved at district level, while from disabled cases, only 3 cases Medical Negligence was proved and in others not yet proved.

Patient Education status:

All the 10 cases, the petitioners were Educated, so as such no relation between Medical Negligence and the education of the petitioner was found.

Table No. 74

DOCTORS	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
SPECIALIST	10	4	6
GP	0	0	0

HOSPITAL	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
INCLUDED	2	2	0
NOT INCLUDED	8	2	6

Graph No. 73

Doctors:

In the sample of 10 cases, all the 10 doctors were found to be specialists and there was no General Practitioner. And 4 of the specialists were found negligent by the district forum.

Hospitals:

In 2 cases out of 10 cases, the hospitals were included and were respondents along with the doctors. In both the cases where hospitals were also made party, Medical Negligence due to deficiency in service was proved, while out of remaining 8 cases where hospitals were not included, in 2 cases the Medical Negligence was proved and rest 6 cases it was not proved.

Table No. 75

Appeal / CASE FILED BY	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
PATIENT	7	1	6
DOCTOR	2	2	0
HOSPITAL	1	1	0

COMPLAINANTS	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
ONE	9	3	6
MANY	1	1	0

Graph No. 74

Appeals / Case:

Out of 10 cases, the appeals in State Commission were filed by, 7 appeals by patients, 2 appeals by doctors and one appeal by a hospital.

Complainants:

Out of 10, in nine cases, one complainant and in one case many complainants filed cases against doctors.

Table No. 76
Number of Respondents

RESPONDENT	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
ONE	4	2	2
MANY	6	2	4

Complainant's Version	TOTAL NO CASES	COMPLAINANT VERSION	M.N NOT PROVED
ACCEPTED	3	3	2
NOT ACCEPTED	7	1	4

Graph No. 75

Respondents:

Out of 10 cases, in 4 cases single respondent and in remaining 6 cases many respondents were there. In each of the category, in 2 cases each Medical Negligence was proved.

Complainant's Version:

Out of 10 cases in 3 cases, the complainant's version was accepted and in 7 cases it was not accepted. In all the 3 cases where, complainants i.e. patient's version was accepted, Medical Negligence was proved, while in only one case where, though complainant's version was not accepted, Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 6 cases it was not proved.

Table No.77

RESPONDENT VERSION	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
Accepted	7	2	5
Not Accepted	3	2	1

Judge's version: EXPERT EVIDENCE / WITNESS	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
Accepted	4	4	0
Not Accepted	6	0	6

Graph No. 76

Respondent's Version

In 7 cases, respondent's version was accepted and in 3 cases it was not accepted. So out of 7 cases, in one case in spite of accepting respondent's version, Medical Negligence was proved and in 3 cases in which respondent's version were not accepted, the Medical Negligence was proved.

Judge's Version :Expert Witness/Evidence:

In 4 cases the expert witness/evidence was accepted by the Judges and in 6 cases not. In all the four cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Table No. 78

EXPERT WITNESS USED	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
Accepted	6	5	1
Not Accepted	4	0	4

EXPERT EVIDENCE USED	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
ACCEPTED	4	2	2
NOT ACCEPTED	6	2	4

Graph No. 77

Expert witness:

In 6 cases Expert witness was considered, out of which 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 2 cases as well as 4 cases in which expert witness was not accepted, Medical Negligence was not proved.

Expert Evidence:

Out of 4 cases in which Expert evidence was accepted, Medical Negligence was proved in 2 cases, and in remaining 6 cases in which Expert Evidence was not accepted in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Table No. 79

CASE LAW REFERRED	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
YES	4	2	2
NO	6	2	4

MEDICAL LITERATURE REFERRED	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
YES	3	1	2
NO	7	3	4

Graph No. 78

Case Laws Referred:

Out of 4 cases in which case laws were referred, 2 cases were Medical Negligence proved and out of 6 cases in which case laws were not referred, in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Medical Literature Referred:

In 3 cases Medical Literature was referred out of 10 cases, while out of that only one was found to be negligent. While out of 7 cases where Medical Literature was not referred, in 3 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Table No.80

CONTRIBUTORY NEGLIGENCE OF PATIENT	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
PROVED	0	0	0
NOT PROVED	10	4	6

BOLAM PRINCIPLE MENTIONED	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
YES	0	0	0
NO	10	4	6

Graph No. 79

Contributory Negligence by the patient:

In all the 10 cases, contributory Negligence was not proved, out which in 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Bolam Principle Mentioned:

In all the 10 cases, the Bolam Principle was not mentioned by the Judges in the Judgments, and in 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved, in remaining 6 it was not.

Table No. 81

COMPENSATION AWARDED	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
YES	4	4	0
NO	6	0	6

CONSUMER PROTECTION PRINCIPLE	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
CONFIRMED	4	4	0
NOT CONFIRMED	6	0	6

Graph No. 80

In 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved and compensation was awarded, thus the Consumer Protection Principle was confirmed in the Judgments.

Table No.82

NEW RULE IN THE JUDGEMENT	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
POSTULATED	0	0	0
NOT POSTULATED	10	4	6

BOLITHO PRINCIPLE USED	TOTAL NO CASES	M.N PROVED	M.N NOT PROVED
YES	0	0	0
NO	10	4	6

Graph No. 81

In all the 10 cases, no new rule was postulated by the Court, as well as the Bolitho Principle was not mentioned.

Table No.83

Informed consent taken	Total no cases	M.N. proved	M.N. not proved
Yes	3	1	2
No	7	3	4

Type of judgment	Total no case	M.N. proved	M.N. not proved
Structured	4	2	2
Un structured	6	2	4

Graph No. 82

Informed Consent:

In 3 cases Informed Consent was taken, out of which in one case Medical Negligence was proved. In remaining 7 cases the Informed Consent was not taken, out of which in 3 cases the Medical Negligence was proved.

Type of Judgment:

In 4 cases the Judgment was structured out of which in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 6 cases where the judgments were unstructured, in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Table No. 84

Judicial Behaviour	Total no cases	M.N. proved	M.N. not proved
Editorial	4	2	2
Authorship	6	2	4

Graph No. 83

In 4 cases the Judicial Behaviour was Editorship, meaning referred case laws, medical literature, witnesses and evidences, out of which in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved. In remaining 6 cases the Judicial Behaviour was Authorship, meaning decision was given without referring the witness, Evidences, case laws or Medical Literature. Out of that 2 cases were found to be Negligent.

Table No. 85

Specialty	Total no case	M.N. proved	M.N. not proved
Ophthalmology	2	0	2
Neurology	3	2	1
Orthopaedics	1	0	1
Cardiology	1	1	0
Gynaecology	2	1	1
Gastro enterology	1	0	1

Graph No. 84

Above are the specialties involved in the cases under study at local level at Pune. Out of 3 Neuro Surgery cases in 2, Medical Negligence was proved. In one cardiology case, Medical Negligence was proved. Out of 2 Gynaecology cases, in one Medical Negligence was proved.

From this caselaw analysis at both local and national levels, one can infer that there are certain similarities and correlations in terms of Pre-CPA and post-CPA approaches to medical negligence. The show that there is not much of difference in the impact of CPA in terms of approach of apex court or commission or local forum – whether in terms of compensation or evidence or sanctity of doctor patient equation or patient rights. However, these trends should be reviewed with actual perception of various stakeholders. The following chapter presents the outcome of such endeavour.

Chapter 5

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Outcome of Empirical Survey

In addition to the extensive case analysis on legal treatment of medical negligence under CPA in India which is presented in the previous chapter, the researcher has conducted an empirical survey, with different tools with different players in the healthcare system. This survey responds to the gaps in the system as evident in case law analysis. It targets these areas through questions in various tools and attempts to triangulate them for identifying and spelling out areas and approaches to law reform.

5.1 Analysis of awareness about the Consumer Protection Act Amongst Doctors, Hospital Administrators and the Community in Pune district: Doctors and Hospital Administrators

Introduction

The empirical study consisted of survey and interviews of doctors, hospital administrators and the community members. After testing the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaires, the questionnaires were mailed to the doctors, hospital administrators and community members and the response was as follows:

No.	Details of participants	Total number too whom questionnaires sent	Response received	Percentage
1	Doctors	2500	427	17.08%
2	Hospital Administrators at various levels	500	41	8.2 %
3	Community members	5000	428	8.56%

The questionnaire for doctors and hospital administrators consists of following themes:

1. Years of Practice
2. Type of Medical Practice- Specialist / General Practitioner
3. Pattern of Practice: Private / Service
4. Medical Specialty
5. Awareness of existence of CPA against doctors

6. Awareness: A consumer case can be filed against a doctor.
7. Awareness of details: Practice, Procedure claiming relief under CPA
8. Awareness of steps to be taken when a doctor receives Consumer Forum's notice
9. Awareness: Case law: IMA v VP Shantha
10. Awareness of Trend setting cases
11. Importance of documentation of Patient's records.
12. Best way to defend oneself is proper documentation
13. Meaning of Medical Negligence
14. Components of Medical Negligence
15. Awareness: Defenses available to a doctor in Medical Negligence case
16. Awareness: Bolam Principle for judging Medical Negligence cases
17. Bolam Principle
18. Should Bolitho Principle be used for judging Medical Negligence?
19. Bolitho Principle
20. Awareness: MCI Regulation for doctors
21. Awareness: Amendments of IMC Act
22. Awareness: Informed Consent
23. Knowledge about Doctor Patient Relationship
24. Knowledge about establishment of Doctor Patient Relationship
25. Existence of Medico legal Case against you.
26. Opinion: Cordial Relationship with patient avoids litigation
27. Professional Indemnity Insurance
28. Knowledge: Professional Indemnity Insurance
29. Knowledge: Terms and Conditions of Insurance Company
30. Knowledge: Principles of Vicarious liability
31. Opinion about Criticizing colleagues
32. Knowledge: Basis of Patient treatment
33. Awareness :Evidence based Medicine protocols
34. Opinion about Second opinion / Referring out complicated patients
35. Opinion: Attendance of conferences and workshops in the field of specialization.
36. Opinion: Need for updating skills for doctors
37. Opinion: CPA vs. Regulation by accreditation bodies / Medical Council of India

The answers given by doctors and hospital administrators were analyzed and presented here.

Empirical Study: Doctors and Hospital Administrators Survey

Table No.86
Years of Practice in Medical Field

Years of practicing in the medical field	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. of Doctors	%	No. of Hospital Administrators	%
0 to 5 years	46	10.8	9	22
5 to 10 years	66	15.5	6	14.6
10 to 20 years	126	29.5	9	22
More than 20 years	189	44.3	17	41.5
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.85

Comments:

In the present study, the maximum number of cases 44.3 % amongst Doctors and 41.5 % of the cases amongst Hospital Administrators who responded were with more than 20 years of practice.

Table No.87

Type of Medical Practice

Type of Medical Practice	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Consultant-Specialist	383	89.7	6	14.6
General Practice	44	10.3	35	85.4
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No. 86

Comments:

In the survey data, Doctors comprised of 89.7 % and Hospital Administrators comprised of 14.6 %, were Consultant Specialists while 10.3 % of the Doctors and 85.4 % of Hospital Administrators were General Practitioners.

Table No.88
Pattern of Practice: Private/ Service

Pattern of Practice / service	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Private practice with institution	222	52	2	4.9
Private Practice with own	127	29.7	2	4.9
Service in Private sector	56	13.1	29	70.7
Service in the Government	22	5.2	8	19.5
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.87

Comments:

As shown, 52 % of the doctors who responded are private practitioners with institutions. While 70.7 % of the Hospital Administrators are in Service with Private sector.

Table No.89
Medical Specialty

Doctors			Hospital Administrators		
Medical Specialty Practicing	No. Of Doctors	%	Medical Specialty Practicing	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Broad Medical Specialties	136	31.9	Hospital administration, health administration, human resources	27	65.8
Broad Surgical Specialties	176	41.2	Manager, medical stores	3	7.3
Medical Super specialties	42	9.8	OBG, operations, quality assurance & management ,others	11	26.8
Surgical Super specialties	43	10.1			
General Practice	30	7.1			
Total	427	100	Total	41	100

Graph No.88

Medical Specialty Practicing
■ Doctors

Medical Specialty Practicing
■ Hospital Administrators

Comments:

The maximum response was from Broad Surgical Specialties, 41.2 % while 31.9 % were practicing Broad Medical Specialties. The Super specialists represented by around 10 %, both medical as well as surgical.

Amongst the Hospital Administrators group, maximum response came from purely working as Hospital Administrators 65.8 %, various level managers were 7.3 % and Hospital Administrators who are practicing as clinicians as well as hospital administrators were 26.8

Table No.90
Awareness of existence of Consumer Protection Act against Doctors

Awareness of Existence of Consumer Protection act against M.N.	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	31	7.3	-	-
Yes	342	80.1	38	92.7
Not Answered	54	12.6	3	7.3
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.89

Comments:

80.1 % of the doctors and 92.7 % Hospital Administrators were aware of the existence of Consumer Protection Act against Medical Negligence.

Table No.91

Awareness-Consumer Case can be filed against a Doctor

Awareness a consumer case also can be filed against a doctor	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	7	1.6	-	-
Yes	408	95.6	41	100
Not Answered	12	2.8	-	-
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.90

Comments:

95.6 % Doctors and 100 % of the Hospital Administrators were found to be aware about **Consumer Case can be filed against a Doctor.**

Table No.92

Awareness of details: Practice, Procedure for Claiming Relief under Consumer Protection Act.

Awareness of the details of practice and procedure for claiming relief under Consumer Protection Act	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	278	65.1	6	14.6
Yes	75	17.6	31	75.6
Not Answered	74	17.3	4	9.8
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.91

Comments:

Though 75.6 % of the hospital administrators are aware of details of practice and procedure for claiming relief under Consumer Protection Act, only 17.6 % of the doctors are aware of the same.

65.1 % of the doctors said they are not aware of the details of the practice and procedure of claiming relief under CPA.

Table No.93

Awareness: Steps to be taken when a Doctor receives Notice from Consumer Court

Awareness of the steps to be taken when a doctor receives a Notice from consumer court	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	295	69.1	7	17.1
Yes	84	19.7	32	78
Not Answered	48	11.2	2	4.9
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.92

Comments:

78 % of the Hospital Administrators in the survey are aware of the steps to be taken when a doctor receives a notice from Consumer Court. 69.1 % of the doctors participated in survey said, they are not aware of such steps!

Table No.94
Awareness: Case Law, *IMA v. V.P.Shantha*

Awareness of the case law " <i>Indian Medical Association vs. VP Shantha</i> "	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	372	87.1	20	48.8
Yes	36	8.4	20	48.8
Not Answered	19	4.4	1	2.4
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.93

Awareness of the case law "*Indian Medical Association vs. VP Shantha*"

■ Doctors ■ Hospital Administrators

Comments:

Only 48.8 % of the Hospital Administrators in the survey are aware of the case of *IMA vs. VP Shantha*, while equal number of hospital administrators and 87.1 % of the doctors said, they are not aware of such case!

Table No.95

Awareness: Trend setting cases against Doctors under CPA

Awareness of the trend setting cases against doctors under Consumer Protection Act	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	278	65.1	8	19.5
Yes	100	23.4	28	68.3
Not Answered	49	11.4	5	12.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.94

Comments:

Regarding trend setting cases against doctors under Consumer Protection Act, 65.1 % of the doctors said they are not aware of the same. While 68.3 % of the Hospital Administrators were aware of the trend setting cases.

Table No.96
Importance of Documentation of Patient's Records

Agreement with the importance of the documentation of patient's records	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	2	0.5	-	-
Yes	396	92.7	39	95.1
Not Answered	29	6.8	2	4.9
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.95

Comments:

Both doctors as well hospital administrators agreed with the importance of documentation of patient records. 92.7 % of the doctors and 95.1 % of the hospital administrators agreed to the same.

Table No.97

Best way to defend one is Proper Documentation

Agreement with the statement-“Best way to defend yourself is proper documentation of patient’s records”	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	4	0.9	2	4.9
Yes	392	91.8	36	87.8
Not Answered	31	7.3	3	7.3
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.96

Comments:

91.8 % doctors and 87.8 % of Hospital Administrators agreed with the statement, “Best way to defend your self is proper documentation of patient’s records”

Table No.98
Meaning of Medical Negligence

Medical Negligence means	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not answered	23	5.4	2	4.9
All	308	72.1	30	73.2
Commission or omission of	32	7.5	1	2.4
Deviation from accepted	15	3.5	2	4.9
Lack of reasonable care	45	10.5	6	14.6
None of the above	4	0.9	0	0
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.97

Comments:

72.1 % of the doctors and 73.2 % of the Hospital Administrators correctly identified the meaning of Medical Negligence while others were confused with all other answers.

Table No.99
Components of Medical Negligence

Components of Medical Negligence are	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not answered	23	5.4	2	4.9
A legal duty to exercise	58	13.6	11	26.8
A legal duty to standard	29	6.8	2	4.9
A legal duty to take care	15	3.5	1	2.4
All of the above	294	68.9	24	58.5
None of the above	8	1.9	1	2.4
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.99

Agreement with the statement-“Best way to defend yourself is proper documentation of patient’s records”
■ Doctors ■ Hospital Administrators

Comments: 68.9 % of the doctors and 58.5 % of the Hospital Administrators correctly identified the Components of Medical Negligence while others were confused with all other answers.

Table No.100

Awareness: Defences available to a Doctor in Medical Negligence Case

Awareness of the defences available to a doctor in 'Medical Negligence case'	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	243	56.9	9	22
Yes	94	22	26	63.4
Not Answered	90	31.1	6	15.7
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.99

Comments:

The participants of the survey were confused over the knowledge of available defences to a doctor in Medical Negligence case. 63.4 % hospital administrators and 22 % of the doctors were aware of the defences available while all others are not aware.

Table No.101

Awareness: Bolam Principle for judging the Medical Negligence case

Awareness of the “Bolam Principle” used for judging the cases of medical negligence	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	309	72.4	17	41.5
Yes	52	12.2	18	43.9
Not Answered	66	15.4	6	15.7
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.100

Comments:

Bolam Principle is the principle being referred for judging a case of negligence. Only 12.2 % doctors and 43.9 % hospital administrators are aware of the existence of such principle and all others are not.

Table No.102
Bolam Principle

The "Bolam Principle" is	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not answered	53	12.4	4	9.8
Accepts the ordinary skill	6	1.4	4	9.8
All	58	13.6	12	29.3
Don't know	266	62.3	17	41.5
That tries to find whether	31	7.3	4	9.8
Used to define standard	13	3	0	0
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.101

Comments:

While 62.3 % of doctors and 41.5 % of Hospital Administrators accepted that they don't know the Bolam Principle, while all others tried to guess the responses. 13.6 % of the doctors and 29.3 % of Hospital Administrators correctly identified the components of Bolam Principle.

Table No.103

Opinion: Should Bolitho Principle be used for judging Medical Negligence?

Should India adopts “Bolitho principle” for judging the cases of medical negligence	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	22	5.2	2	4.9
Yes	34	8	7	17.1
Not Answered	371	86.8	32	78
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.102

Comments: Majority of doctors and hospital administrators have not answered this question, meaning that Bolitho principle is known to a handful of them.

Table No.104
Bolitho Principle

The "Bolitho principle" is	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not answered	53	12.4	4	9.8
All	194	45.4	19	46.3
Does not accept "accepted"	33	7.7	4	9.8
Use of logical thinking	86	20.1	9	22
Used when court decides	61	14.3	5	12.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.103

Comments:

In spite of not answering previous question, the participants tried to guess the answer to this question. 45.4 % of doctors and 46.3 % of the hospital administrators answered this question correctly.

Table No.105

Awareness: Medical Council of India Regulations for Doctors

Awareness about the regulations for the doctors by the Medical Council of India	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	133	31.1	-	-
Yes	173	40.5	35	85.4
Not Answered	121	28.3	6	15.7
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.104

Comments:

40.5 % of doctors and 85.4 % of hospital administrators are aware of the regulations for doctors by the Medical Council of India. It is shocking finding that 60 % of the doctors are not aware of these regulations!

Table No.106

Awareness: Amendments of Indian Medical Council Act (2002)

Awareness of the Amendments (2002) in the Medical Council Act	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	262	61.4	5	12.2
Yes	55	12.9	22	53.7
Not Answered	110	25.7	14	34.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.105

Comments:

Only 12.9 % doctors and 53.7 % of Hospital Administrators are aware of the amendment of Medical Council of India regulations, remaining are not aware.

Table No.107

Awareness: Informed Consent

Awareness of 'Informed Consent'	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	5	1.2	-	-
Yes	345	80.8	36	87.8
Not Answered	77	18	5	12.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.106

Comments:

80.8 % of doctors and 87.8 % of hospital administrators are aware of the concept of Informed Consent. It indicates that, the awareness about Informed Consent has been percolated well.

Table No.108
Knowledge: About Informed Consent

The concept of Informed Consent involves explaining the following information to the patient in comprehensible non medical terms in local language	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	1	0.2	-	-
Yes	341	79.9	36	87.8
Not Answered	85	19.9	5	12.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No. 107

Comments:

79.9 % of doctors and 87.8 % of hospital administrators are knowing the detailed concept of Informed Consent. About 20 % of doctors not answered this question.

Table No.109
Knowledge: Doctor Patient Relationship

Doctor Patient relationship is established on	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not answered	72	16.9	5	12.2
All	172	40.3	24	58.5
Doctor affirmatively	36	8.4	1	2.4
None of the above	14	3.3	1	2.4
Patient makes appointment	10	2.3	1	2.4
The relationship	123	28.8	9	22
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.108

Comments:

The detailed concept of doctor patient relationship was found to be known to 40.3 % of doctors and 58.5 % hospital administrators.

Table No.110

Knowledge: Establishment of Doctor Patient Relationship

Doctor examines a patient for some purpose	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	93	21.8	14	34.1
Yes	171	40	22	53.7
Not Answered	163	38.1	5	12.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.109

Comments:

This question was a tricky one; all options were not the examples of doctor patient legal relationship.

This was rightly identified by 21.8 % of doctors and 34.1 % of the hospital administrators.

Table No.111
Existence of Medico Legal Case

Do you have any medico legal case against you	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	328	76.8	35	85.4
Yes	18	4.2	1	2.4
Not Answered	81	19	5	12.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.110

Comments:

Only 4.2 % of doctors and 2.4 hospital administrators shared this confidential information affirmatively, while others said no.

Table No.112
Opinion: Cordial Doctor Patient Relationship

Cordial Doctor patient relationship avoids litigation	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	42	9.8	2	4.9
Yes	260	60.9	34	82.9
Not Answered	125	29.3	5	12.2
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.111

Comments:

Majority of doctors and hospital administrators agreed to statement, 60.9 % doctors and 82.9 % of hospital administrators,

Cordial Doctor patient relationship avoids litigation

Table No.113
Professional Indemnity Insurance

Insured under Professional Indemnity Insurance?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	64	15	23	56.1
Yes	280	65.6	11	26.8
Not Answered	83	19.4	7	17.1
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.112

Comments:

65.6 % of Doctors and 26.8 % of the hospital administrators are insured under Professional Indemnity Insurance.

Table No.114

Knowledge: Professional Indemnity Insurance

Professional Indemnity Insurance	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not answered	79	18.5	5	12.2
All	314	73.5	30	73.2
None of the above	3	0.7	1	2.4
Retroactive date is the d	1	0.2	0	0
The amount of the premium	8	1.9	0	0
The indemnity applies only	15	3.5	4	9.8
The indemnity insurance m	7	1.6	1	2.4
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.113

Comments:

73.5 % doctors and 73.2 % hospital administrators knew the details of Professional Indemnity Insurance. Remaining participants opted for other options.

Table No.115

Knowledge: Terms and Conditions of Insurance Company

Studied terms and conditions of Insurance company?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	174	40.7	14	34.1
Yes	120	28.1	16	39
Not Answered	133	31.1	11	26.8
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.114

Comments:

The opinion about the knowledge of terms and conditions of Insurance Company was divided in both the groups, doctors and Hospital Administrators. Only 28.1 % of the Doctors and 26.8 % of Hospital Administrators knew the terms and conditions of Insurance Company, in relation to Indemnity Insurance.

Table No.116
Knowledge: Principle of Vicarious Liability

Vicarious Liability means	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not answered	84	19.7	5	12.2
All	231	54.1	20	48.8
It is a legal concept that	78	18.3	10	24.4
None	19	4.4	1	2.4
The liability arises out	7	1.6	3	7.3
The negligent	8	1.9	2	4.9
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.115

Comments:

54.1 % of doctors and 48.8 % of Hospital administrators were found to have correct knowledge about the concept of vicarious liability; among the rest of the participants the opinion was divided.

Table No.117
Opinion: Criticizing Colleagues

Do you believe in criticizing your colleagues?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	309	72.4	27	65.9
Yes	15	3.5	7	17.1
Not Answered	103	24.1	7	17.1
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.116

Comments:

Surprisingly 3.5 % of the doctors and 17.1 % of Hospital Administrators opined that they believe in criticizing colleagues! 72.4% doctors and 65.9 % of hospital administrators clearly stated that they do not believe in criticizing colleagues, sizable number has not answered this question.

Table No.118
Knowledge: Basis of Patient Treatment

On what basis you treat a patient- Treatment Protocol or Prior experience?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
Not Answered	84	19.7	5	12.2
Both	293	68.6	25	61
Prior Experience	7	1.6	1	2.4
Treatment Protocol	43	10.1	10	24.4
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.117

Comments:

68.6 % of doctors and 61 % of the hospital administrators in the survey said, the basis of the treatment is both-prior experience and treatment protocols. Equal number was divided between the two, treatment protocols and prior experience. 19.7 % of the doctors didn't answer this question.

Table No.119

Awareness: Evidence Based Medicine Protocols

Are you aware of Evidence Based Medicine Protocols?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	29	6.8	1	2.4
Yes	285	66.7	33	80.5
Not Answered	113	26.4	7	17.1
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.118

Comments:

66.7 % of doctors and 80.5 % of hospital administrators said they were aware of Evidence based Medicine protocols. Remaining participants were not aware of that.

Table No.120

Opinion: Second Opinion/ Referring complicated patients

Do you take a Second Opinion or refer the complicated patients?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	3	0.7	0	0
Yes	333	78	30	73.2
Not Answered	91	21.3	11	26.8
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.119

Comments:

78 % of the doctors and 73.2 % of hospital administrators said, they will take second opinion in complicated cases and may refer these patients to higher centers.

Table No.121

Opinion: Attendance of Conferences and Workshops in the field of Specialization

Do you regularly attend conferences and workshops in your field of specialization?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	11	2.6	0	0
Yes	322	75.4	32	78
Not Answered	94	22	9	21.9
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No: 120

Comments:

75.4 % of doctors and 78 % of Hospital Administrators said they attend conferences and workshops in their fields of specialization. This is the result of CPA application that majority of medical experts now are participating in skill up gradation programs like conferences and workshops.

Table No. 122

Opinion: Need for updating skill for a Doctor

Do you think it is necessary to regularly update your skills in your specialty?	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	1	0.2	0	0
Yes	339	79.4	33	80.5
Not Answered	87	20.4	8	19.5
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.121

Comments:

79.4 % of doctors and 80.5 % of hospital administrators feel that it is necessary to regularly update the skills. This is again the after effect of application of CPA to the Medical Field.

Table No.123

Opinion: Consumer Protection Act v Regulation by accreditation bodies / MCI

Agreement with the following statement: Rather than the present coverage of doctors under Consumer Protection Act, it is the strict control of doctors' training by Medical Council of India and quality control by Accreditation bodies which is preferred.	Doctors		Hospital Administrators	
	No. Of Doctors	%	No. Of Hospital Administrators	%
No	29	6.8	5	12.2
Yes	252	59	25	61
Not Answered	146	34.1	11	26.8
Total	427	100	41	100

Graph No.122

Comments:

59 % of doctors and 61 % of hospital administrators, preferred strict control of doctor's training by Medical Council of India and regulation by that body while only 6.8 % of doctors and 12.2 % of hospital administrators said no to this concept and remaining were non-committal.

Table: 124:
Descriptive evaluation of Medical Negligence Knowledge of Doctors and Hospital Administrators

	Total number of statements	Max score	Mean score	Median score	SD score	% score
Doctors	57	285	219.80	224.00	20.79	77.12%
Administrators	57	285	209.43	214.00	17.61	73.48%
Community	10	50	36.82	37.00	3.83	73.64%

Graph No.123

Table 125:
Mean Knowledge levels of Doctors and Administrators according to Practice in years

Practice in years	Knowledge score	
	Administrators	Doctors
0 to 5 years	198.89±24.87	206.98±16.18
5 to 10 years	230.33±11.27	209.64±14.37
10 to 20 years	229.11±18.95	206.98±18.37
>20 years	222.24±14.51	211.58±18.28
Significance	F=5.719; P=0.003**	F=2.062; P=0.105

Graph No.124

Table 126:
Mean Knowledge levels of Doctors and administrators according to Type of Practice

Type of practice	Knowledge score	
	Administrators	Doctors
General Practice	221.51±20.82	202.18±18.76
Consultant Specialist	209.83±19.34	210.26±17.3
Significance	F=1.641; P=0.208	F=8.449; P=0.004**

Graph No.125

Table 127

Mean Knowledge levels of Doctors and Administrators according to working place

Working place	Knowledge score	
	Administrators	Doctors
Private Practice with own hospital set up	249.00±1.41	210.06±17.31
Private practice with institutional attachments	203.00±26.87	211.23±17.23
Service in the Government sector	227.25±10.94	206.50±14.59
Service in Private sector	216.9±21.37	202.00±19.18
Significance	F=2.543; P=0.071+	F=4.456; P=0.004**

Graph No.126

Table 128

Mean knowledge levels according to Doctors/ Specialists

Specialties	Number of doctors	Knowledge score
Broad Medical Specialties	136(31.9%)	208.20±16.06
Broad Surgical Specialties	176(41.2%)	211.73±17.25
Medical Super specialties	42(9.8%)	207.71±18.51
Surgical Super specialties	43(10.1%)	212.67±17.72
General Practice	30(7.1%)	199.2±21.23
Total	427(100.0%)	209.43±17.61

F=4.026; p=0.003**

Graph No.127

Table 129
Reliability Analysis of Knowledge and Attitude Questionnaire of Doctors and Administrators

Students	Administrative	Doctors
Number of items	57	57
Split –half method (Spearman Brown co-efficient)	0.804	0.791
Consistency by Cronbach's alpha	0.869	0.806

5.2 Analysis of awareness about the Consumer Protection Act Revealed in Community Survey

Introduction

This empirical part of the study was conducted amongst community members. Out of 5000 mails sent, only 428 responded. The questionnaire for the community members consisted of the following themes:

1. Age
2. Educational Background
3. Occupation
4. Awareness about doctors covered under CPA
5. Should doctors be covered under CPA?
6. Are you happy that the doctors are covered under CPA?
7. Are you satisfied with doctor's service and availability in hospitals?
8. Do you trust doctors totally?
9. Do you take second opinion always?
10. Do you find change in relationship with the doctors?
11. Do you find doctors are too cautious and afraid now?
12. Increase in Commercialization
13. Whether doctors should continue to be covered under CPA?

The analysis of the responses was done and presented here.

Empirical Study: Community Questionnaire

Table No.130
Survey findings of Questionnaire for Community Members

	Number of community members (n=428)	%
Q1. Please specify your age group		
• Below 20 years	46	10.7

• 20 to 30 years	250	58.4
• 30 to 40 years	45	10.5
• 40 to 50 years	12	2.8
• 50 to 60 years	66	15.4
• Above 60 years	9	2.1

Q2.Please give information about your educational background		
• 1.Below graduation	77	18.0
• 2.Graduate	184	43.0
• 3.Postgraduate	133	31.1
• 4.Above Post graduation	34	7.9
Q3.Kindly mention your occupation		
• 1.Academics	87	20.3
• 2.Business	22	5.1
• 3.Education / Student	111	25.9
• 4.Government service	33	7.7
• 5.Private service	110	25.7
• 6.Other	65	15.2
Q4.Are you aware that the doctors are covered under Consumer Protection Act, meaning now anybody having any grievance against a doctor or hospital can file a case against doctors in Consumer Courts?		
• No	146	34.1
• Yes	235	54.9
• Not answered	47	11.0
Q5.Please give your opinion: Should doctors be covered under the Consumer Protection Act?		
• No	28	6.5
• Yes	359	83.9
• Not answered	41	9.6
Q6.Are you happy with the knowledge of the applicability		

of this Act to the doctors?		
• No	99	23.1
• Yes	220	51.4
• Not answered	109	25.5
Q7.In your own experience about medical service: are you satisfied with doctor's service and availability of doctors in the hospitals?		
• No	165	38.6
• Yes	179	41.8
• Not answered	74	19.7

Graphs: 128

GRAPH 129

Comments:

The response was good from students 25.9 % and those with private work-practice, 25.7 %.Also 20.3 % academicians responded to this questionnaire.

Comments:

54.9 % of the respondents know that anybody having any grievance against a doctor or hospital can file a case against doctors in Consumer Courts. 34.1 % said they are not aware of this. 11 % preferred to remain silent on this.

Comments: 83.9 % of the respondents said, the doctors should be covered under Consumer Protection Act.Only 6.5 % are not in favour of this application to doctors and 9.6 % remained silent on this.

Comments: 51.4 % of participants said they happy with the knowledge of applicability of COA to Doctors.23.1 % said no while 25.5 % didn't answer this question

Comments:

41.8 % of the respondents said they are satisfied with doctors service in general, 38.6 % said they are not satisfied while, 19.7 % have not answered this question

Table No.131
Survey findings of Questionnaire for Community Members

	Number of community members (n=428)	%
Q 8.Do you have total trust in the doctors?		
• No	181	42.3
• Yes	116	27.1
• Not answered	131	30.6
Q 9.Do you always take a second opinion as a routine, because doctors cannot be trusted?		
• No	165	38.6
• Yes	174	40.7
• Not answered	89	20.8
Q 10.Do you find any change in the relationship between you and the doctor due to the Consumer Protection Act?		
• No	212	49.5

• Yes	69	16.1
• Not answered	147	34.4
Q 11.Do you find doctors are too cautious and afraid while dealing with the patient?		
• No	252	58.9
• Yes	71	16.6
• Not answered	105	24.5
Q 12.Do you think there is an increase in commercialization of the medical services due the Consumer Protection Act?		
• No	53	12.4
• Yes	255	59.6
• Not answered	120	28.1
Q 13.Do you think Doctors should continue to be covered under Consumer Protection Act?		
• No	22	5.1
• Yes	268	62.6
• Not answered	138	32.2

Graphs: 130

silent, indicating distrust in doctors.

always take second opinion, while 20.8 % remained non committal.

Comments:

16.1 % of the respondents said they find change in their relationship with doctors. 49.5 % have not noticed any change while 34.4 % have not answered this question.

Comments:

16.6 % of participants said, they now find doctors too cautious and afraid due to CPA. 58.9 % didn't find such change, while 24.5 % remained silent on this question.

Comments:

59.6 % of the participants in survey feel that there is an increase in commercialization of Medical Services

Comments:

62.6 % of the respondents feel that doctors

due to CPA, while 12.4 don't feel so.28.1 % of the participants have not answered this question.	should continue to be covered under Consumer Protection Act.
--	--

Table No.132:
Mean knowledge score according age in Community Group

Age in years	Knowledge score	
	Number of subjects	Mean ±SD
Below 20 years	46 (10.7%)	37.83±3.23
20-30 years	250(58.4%)	36.21±3.82
30-40 years	57(13.3%)	37.87±4.01
40-60 years	60(14.1%)	37.48±3.73
Above 60 years	9(2.1%)	37.00±3.54
Total	428(100.0%)	36.82±3.83

F=4.103; P=0.003**

Graph: 131

Table No.133:
Mean knowledge score according education in Community Group

Education	Knowledge score	
	Number of community members	Mean \pm SD
Below graduation	77	37.12 \pm 3.16
Graduation	184	36.47 \pm 4.12
Post graduation	133	36.88 \pm 3.84
Above post graduation	34	37.83 \pm 3.36
Total	428(100.0%)	36.82 \pm 3.83

F=1.558; P=0.199

Graph: 132

Table No.134:

Mean knowledge score according occupation in Community Group

Occupation	Knowledge score	
	Number of community members	Mean \pm SD
Academics	87(20.3%)	36.79 \pm 3.72
Business	22(5.1%)	37.36 \pm 3.79
Education/student	111(25.9%)	37.18 \pm 3.43
Government service	33(7.7%)	37.97 \pm 4.18
Private service	110(25.7%)	35.98 \pm 3.83
Others	65(15.2%)	36.88 \pm 4.25
Total	428(100.0%)	36.82 \pm 3.83

F=1.984; P=0.083+

Graph: 133

Table No.135:
Reliability analysis of Knowledge of Community Group

Community members	Community group
Number of items	10
Split –half method (Spearman Brown co-efficient)	0.852
Consistency by Cronbach`s alpha	0.911

Now, the qualitative data will be presented:

5.3 Analysis of Interviews

Some of the experts have been interviewed. The British expert Dr Laurie proposed ideas for future such as Health Tribunal. Besides, he was pointing out the current trends in UK which are similar to that of India³³¹:

“Traditionally in UK, has been courts differed medical profession.

1998,changing,case court made it clear, that the Courts will decide the cases of medical negligence and not the medical profession and you can understand that medical profession was under attack. But I don't see any increase in action against medical profession. And point of view of lawyers, I think most of the times court asks doctors to decide the negligence as compared to other profession like engineers, architects etc. There has been a difference against medical profession in British Courts.

The summary of interviews with Indian experts also partially indorses this view.³³²

³³¹See Annexure VII for details

³³²ibid

Interview Data: Doctors

1. Are you aware of the existence of Law, The Consumer Protection Act, 1986 against Medical Negligence?

YES	16
NO	2
CANT SAY	2

2. Do you know a consumer case also can be filed against a doctor?

YES	20
NO	0
CANT SAY	0

3. Do you know the details of practice and procedure for claiming relief under Consumer Protection Act?

YES	5
NO	15
CANT SAY	0

4. Do you know the steps to be taken when a doctor receives a Notice from consumer court?

YES	6
NO	14
CANT SAY	0

5. Do you know the case law "**Indian Medical Association vs. VP Shantha**"?

YES	2
NO	18
CANT SAY	0

6. Are you aware of the trend setting cases against doctors under Consumer Protection Act?

YES	3
NO	14
CANT SAY	3

7. Do you agree with the importance of the documentation of patient's records?

YES	20
NO	0
CANT SAY	0

8. Do you agree with the statement-“Best way to defend yourself is proper documentation of patient's records”?

YES	20
NO	0
CANT SAY	0

9. Medical Negligence means

Commission or omission of an act by a medical professional	2
Deviation from accepted standards of practice of the medical community	1
Lack of reasonable care and skill on the part of medical professional	4
All of the above	12
None of the above	1

10. Components of Medical Negligence are

A legal duty to exercise due care, Breach of the duty and Consequential damages	3
A legal duty to standard care, Act of omission and commission and Death of patient	2
A legal duty to take care, wrong treatment and Disability in the patient	2
All of the above	13
None of the above	0

11. Do you know the defenses available to a doctor in 'Medical Negligence case'?

YES	3
NO	14
CANT SAY	3

12. Are you aware of the Amendments (2002) in the Medical Council Act?

YES	6
NO	12
CANT SAY	2

13. Before performing an operation, the Surgeon should obtain **Legally Valid consent** from the patient, that means

Consent should be given by conscious and mentally sound person/patient	2
The age of the person/ patient should be above 18 years	4
Consent should not be obtained under fear, fraud or misrepresentation of facts	0
All of the above	14
None of the above	0

14. Are you aware of '**Informed Consent**'?

YES	17
NO	1
CANT SAY	2

15. The concept of **Informed Consent** involves explaining the following information to the patient in comprehensible non medical terms in local language.

- Diagnosis and Nature of treatment.
- Alternative method of treatment
- Risks and benefits involved in both proposed and alternative procedure.
- Prognosis if the procedure is not performed.
- The relative chances of success or failure of both proposed procedures so that the patient has the option to accept or reject the treatment.

The above statements truly explain the concept of informed consent.

YES	16
NO	2
CAN SAY	2

16. When a doctor examines a patient for some purpose other than providing advice and treatment, for example medical examinations for insurance, fitness, medico legal cases, disability, visa and any casual advice; whether legally doctor patient relationship is established?

YES	12
NO	4
CANT SAY	4

17. Do you have any medico legal case against you?

YES	7
NO	12
CANT SAY	1

18. Are you aware of **Evidence Based Medicine Protocols**?

YES	16
NO	2
CANT SAY	2

19. Do you take a **Second Opinion** or refer the complicated patients?

YES	20
NO	0
CANT SAY	0

20. Do you regularly attend conferences and workshops in your field of specialization?

YES	20
NO	0
CANT SAY	0

21. Do you agree with the following statement

Rather than the present coverage of doctors under Consumer Protection Act, it is the strict control of doctors' training by Medical Council of India and quality control by Accreditation bodies which is preferred.

YES	15
NO	2
CANT SAY	3

22. On what basis you treat a patient-Treatment Protocol or Prior experience?

Treatment protocol	2	
Prior experience	2	
Both of the above	15	
None of the above	1	

23. **Vicarious Liability** means

It is a legal concept that fixes the responsibility on the master for wrongdoing of his servants.	3
The liability arises out of employment relationship	7
The negligent conduct of the servant must be within the scope of employment.	0
All of the above	10
None of the above	0

24. Are you insured under **Professional Indemnity Insurance**?

YES	12
NO	7
CANT SAY	1

Qualitative analysis of Survey and interviews Comments: Interview Data: Doctors

1. In the interview, 80 % of the doctors said they are aware of the existence of the Consumer Protection Act..
2. All of them said, they know that a consumer case can be against doctors.
3. Out of 20 doctors interviewed, 60 % of them said, they don't know the practice and procedure for claiming relief under Consumer Protection Act.
4. Only 30 % of the doctors agreed that they know the steps to be taken when the doctor receives a notice from Consumer Court. So 70 % did not know that.
5. 90 % of the doctors interviewed said they don't know the case law, IMA vs. VP Shantha.
6. 70 % of the doctors were found to be aware of trend setting cases against doctors under Consumer Protection Act.

7. All the 100 % doctors agreed with the importance of documentation of patients records.
8. As well, all of them agreed to the statement that, Best way to defend one is proper documentation of patient's records.
9. The correct meaning of Medical Negligence was told by only 60 % of the doctors interviewed.
10. Again, all the components were correctly identified by 65 % of the doctors.
11. 70 % of the doctors did not know the defenses available to a doctor in Medical Negligence case.
12. 30 % doctors said they are aware of Amendments in the Medical Council Regulations.
13. 70 % of the doctors had knowledge of Legally Valid Consent.
14. 85 % of interviewed doctors were aware of the concept of Informed Consent.
15. 80 % of the doctors could actually confirm the meaning of Informed Consent.
16. Only 20 % of the doctors correctly told when legally Doctor Patient relationship.
17. 35 % of the doctors agreed that they had Medico legal cases against them.
18. 80 % of the doctors were aware of Evidence Based Medicine Protocols.
19. All 100 % of the interviewed Doctors told they prefer second opinion in case of complicated patients and they refer such patients to higher centers.
20. All 100 % doctors said that they regularly attend conferences and workshops in their field of specialization.
21. 75 % of the interviewed doctors said, Rather than the present coverage of doctors under Consumer Protection Act, it is the strict control of doctors' training by Medical Council of India and quality control by Accreditation bodies which is preferred.
22. 75 % of the doctors said, they treat patients on the basis of both, treatment protocol as well as Prior experience.
23. Only 50 % of the doctors could identify the meaning of Vicarious Liability correctly.
24. 60 % of the doctors knew details of Professional Insurance.

Summary of Opinions of Doctors and Hospital Administrators

Q. What is your personal opinion about the applicability of Consumer Protection Act to the Medical Field? Do you suggest an alternative?

1. One cannot compare other services and professions covered under consumer protection act with medical for no other deals with life and well-being. Even after looking through many medical negligence cases I am of the opinion that for most the root cause is not any wrong doing on part of the doctor but rather miscommunication/lack of communication between patient/their relatives and treating doctor, which leads to misconception as doctor being the cause of adverse result (either death/disability).Most importantly compared to other professions patient (i.e. consumer??) Expects lot more from their doctors more so on emotional level. Major paradox I see is that society blames doctors every now and then for commercializing and same society wants it to be under Consumer Protection Act. Instead I would suggest forming separate forum like it was done for consumer forum but here there should not be a single judge(with no knowledge or experience of medical field)there should a panel formed of retired medical practitioners , judges and hearing conducted in front of jury. This entire forum should be under MCI control and not any government or such agencies.

2. It should not be applied to medical field, training for doctors to build good relationship with patients and reduce financial burdens on the doctors by reducing their cost of education reduce commercialization by reducing establishment cost for the doctors.

Jun 20, 2012 7:16 AM

3. CPA is like a sword held over a Dr.'s head. It leads to working under fear, threat of litigation etc. For a Dr. to give his best, Point 39 and 28 are important. The process has already begun. Attending updates and collecting points has begun. However, we are not really sincere To make it foolproof to upgrade our skills and only collect points. There should be online examination once every three years in order to continue to practice. Perhaps lesser interval will be difficult to implement. I had one case against me in 2001. The result was in my favour. Incidentally I

have stopped practice on 1st April 2012 after 31 years of running a 12 bedded maternity home. Thank you for making me part of your study. Wishing you all the best.

Senior Lady Gynaecologist

4. Such legal act cannot be wished away. Defining reasonable care however is not easy especially as there is lack of standardization in medical practice in India. Market forces, patients' affordability make doctors to do some unwanted choices & then there is the fear of litigation. We are not working in environment where doing standard care is possible every time.

Jun 15, 2012 5:34 AM

5. Yes-- peer review of cases, Medical council being more proactive in this respect. Case to case medical insurance for the patient against mishaps--like in flight insurance. Limited liability clause in a doctor patient interaction. No fault compensation for untoward results in cases of surgery and intervention ends with complication.

Jun 12, 2012 6:00 AM

6. Better training of doctors, regular revalidation of registration and education of the society about the fact that medicine is NOT an exact science like mathematics. People have to realize that a doctor is trying to give you the best answer based on many variables and an error of judgment is not always deliberate!

Jun 10, 2012 8:18 AM

7. Expert medical board should look in to the complaints filed by the patients. The media should be restrained from publishing Dr's negligence before it is established by the expert committee.

8. Personally I think the Consumer Protection Act needs modifications, so as to avoid defamation of the doctors. Though the Act serves the purpose as Safety valve to diffuse the tension between the doctor and patient.

9. The Medical Council or any other Medical body strong and impartial enough to uphold any wrong doings in the profession in a very strict and unbiased manner to give confidence to the general public of its sincere attempt to uphold the high values of the medical profession is the alternative to the Consumer Protection Act.

Jul 6, 2012 4:57 AM

10. When I see a section of doctors fleecing patients...I think a CPA is right but I seldom see such doctors in the dock...it's usually against a doctor who has rightly suggested options and probably the less right option was exercised with patient's choice or it is used by ignorant / extra smart patients(so called consumers) . No I really can't suggest an alternative.

Jul 2, 2012 9:52 AM

11. Doctors who have CPA cases against them should be rehabilitated properly by governing bodies like IMA. They should be punished properly for negligence ,at the same time should have protection of the parent body for further rehabilitation to successful practice, may be IMA can ask them to qualify certain standards etc. but parent body should act as a parent. This will increase confidence of the doctors as well as patients in the system as patients will understand that parent body punishes the negligence. If we are not strict enough, at least on the face, the onus will pass on to courts which are non-medical professionals, and this makes us feel helpless.

Jul 2, 2012 1:55 AM

12. Board of respective specialties should be organized to fix the responsibilities and should be final authorities to give the opinion about the negligence in a particular case.

Jun 25, 2012 12:17 AM

13. I feel it wrong to equate doctors with traders. Doctor patient relationship is like servant master relationship. Patient can and has been doing what he wishes, changing doctor when he wishes, stops treatment when he feels it is not working, stops to revisit the doctor when follow-up is essential, etc.

14. It is just few wrong doctors doing wrong things & Govt. / Society thinks everybody is wrong make everyone to suffers that's what is CPA / PC & PNDDT / MTP etc... So as long as these "Notorious" people are there in our field & no one from our side in Assembly these things will continue!!!!!!!!!!!!

Jun 24, 2012 5:12 AM

15. A patient has the right to claim damages from a professional under the CPA. However if the claim is found unjustifiable the petitioner should be liable to at least 5 times what he is claiming for to avoid false claims.

Jun 22, 2012 4:36 AM

16. As self-regulation of our profession has utterly failed; as majority in the profession are not only self-serving but indulging in acts not good for the profession and utter lack of our fraternity to take positions and "criticizing" wrong doings of our colleagues unfortunately prompts me to say that in the absence of any regulatory mechanism at present CPA seems to be the only recourse people can have. If we all decide to clean up our own acts through stringent self-regulation we will not need such laws. Unfortunately as a group we have failed ourselves. For every bad example there are many good examples cannot be a justification of bad things. Everyone else in the society is bad so are we is also not a correct argument. There is need for lot of introspection rather than pointing fingers at the society. We all know that behind every litigation there are hundreds of cases not taken up by the people where there was injustice. It is high time we accept some kind of regulation of our profession.

Jun 22, 2012 3:45 AM

17. I think that CPA is an unrelated body giving decisions for something that may not be entirely clear to them. MCI would have a better say in these matters, but provided that it is done in a fair and just way, not based on seniority or connections.

Jun 22, 2012 1:43 AM

18. Liasoning Medical committee that examines the case independently and brings both parties to the discussion table, before any further proceedings are initiated

Jun 21, 2012 9:36 PM

19. IN CPA IF DOCTOR IS PROVED TO BE NOT NEGLIGENT THEN COMPLAINANT SHOULD BE PUNISHED HALF THE AMOUNT HE HAS DEMANDED AS COMPANSATION

Jun 20, 2012 10:33 PM

20. CPA WITHOUT REPRESENTATION OF THE SPECIALITY UNDER CONSIDERATION DOESNOT. GIVE PROPER JUSTICE. MEDICAL CELL TO REVIEW THE CASES IS IMP.

Jun 20, 2012 9:23 AM

21. Doctors must be answerable for their actions (omissions or commissions). In my view, we need to be more accountable for our practice/ actions. Quality Control is a hugely lacking area in medical field. Hence I feel doctors must be subject to CPA "AND" their CME must be regulated by the MCI/ MMC. There is no alternative to quality care for our patients and these needs to be monitored by a fair and just regulatory authority. If doctors do their bit well, they should never fear CPA or other such Acts.

Jun 19, 2012 12:03 AM

22. REGULATION OF A DOCTOR IS NECESSITY IN GIVEN SCENARIO , ONLY IT HAS TO BE FAIR FOR BOTH , DOCTOR AS WELL AS PATIENT THEN LET ANY BODY DO IT,

23. In this age of rampant corruption, kickbacks, cut practice and fraud, someone or somebody needs to protect the patients, but this is a slippery road, once patients get the taste of easy money from frivolous calms the whole system fall apart. The old style Patient Doctor relationship needs to be protected

Jun 18, 2012 9:03 AM

24. A team of experts in medical field, eminent citizens and judiciary , all together will be better in solving problem cases , without undue bias , a separate Medical Reimbursement Forum should be formed involving people from various sections as said earlier, the cases and their results should be published in the medical as well as general publications so as to make us and all people aware of their

mistakes , we can improve as doctors and general people by learning through ours and others mistakes .

25.It's difficult to say it in a statement as multiple factors have to be considered. Medico legal ethical committee comprised of personnel at the level of dean medical college ,in all different faculties ,should review the cases regarding medical negligence instead of CPA , both the parties should be heard and the decision justifying the sufferer with the chance to correct the negligence to be passed. also time to time surprise scrutiny of all hospitals to be done by such committees in all faculties. IMPROVING THE TEACHING STANDARDS AT COLLEGES AT FIRST WITH IMPARTING THE FAITH ABOUT THE SACRED JOB TO BE PERFORMED BY STUDENTS, THIS WILL STOP MALPRACTICES. ALL CONSULTANTS WHO ARE EARNING WELL MAY SPARE THEIR TIME FOR UNAFFORDING SECTIONS OF SOCIETY .AND THESE SERVICES CAN BE MONITOURED BY THE ETHICAL BODY MENTIONED BEFORE. FIXED CRITERIA TO BE FOLLOWED FOR ANGIOGRAPHIES, ENDOSCOPIES, WHEN TO PERFORM.

26.Doctor's should not be covered in CPA. There should be alternate redressal system which is governed by central & state level bodies in which doctors & non doctors should have equal representation.

Jun 18, 2012 3:20 AM

27.IT SHOULDN'T BE APPLICABLE TO MEDICAL PROFESSION AS EVERY MODEL IS NOT THE SAME & ALSO NO WAY TO CONFIRM WHETHER PATIENT SI STRICTLY ADHERING TO THE PRESCRIBED TREATMENT VIZ COMLETING THE COURSE OF ANTIBIOTICS/REST/

Jun 18, 2012 2:43 AM

28.There should be a Grievance Redressal committee composed of doctors related to the specialty of the doctor against whom complaint is made. There should also be non-medical members to ensure that no favoritism is being done.

Jun 18, 2012 1:03 AM

29. There is a need for the Doctors to be answerable to their patient management. Hence, till we find a better alternative, CPA should be applicable. I have no definite suggestions for an alternative.

Jun 17, 2012 10:33 PM

30. Rather than having a third private company giving professional indemnity, the consumer protection should be given by Medical council of India to all its members charging some nominal amount, and it should be made compulsory in the interest of doctors

31. IT SHOULDN'T BE APPLICABLE TO MEDICAL PROFESSION AS EVERY MODEL IS NOT THE SAME & ALSO NO WAY TO CONFIRM WHETHER PATIENT IS STRICTLY ADHERING TO THE PRESCRIBED TREATMENT VIZ COMPLETING THE COURSE OF ANTIBIOTICS/REST

Jun 18, 2012 2:43 AM

32. But do we have a central body that has expertise and legal powers to deal with consumer cases or cases relating to medical negligence without having bias or prejudice. Faith of the patient and doctors in any such system is mandatory. But I believe that it's too late for medical fraternity to get out of CPA now.

Jun 26, 2012 8:18 PM

33. Consumer Protection Act to the Medical Field Should Have Fast trial Courts more than as they are specified, Consumer protection Should also have Fast trial of the Cases of non-payments by the Insurance Company to the hospital of the treated patients

Jun 24, 2012 11:45 AM

34. Law should be reviewed regularly by expert committee so that neither the patient suffers due to lack of opportunities to approach legally nor the doctors suffer without doing anything wrong.

Jun 24, 2012 6:59 AM

35. If it is not a willful act the doctor should not be prosecuted. Mistakes are made by anyone in any profession, levels of skill also vary. The country already faces shortage of doctors and many are not opting for medicine and this is one reason for the same.

Jun 23, 2012 9:17 PM

36. Consumer Protection Act (CPA) is valid until self regulation continues to be corrupt as in the case of MCI where an MCI head was prosecuted. Self regulation via Medical Councils complemented with CPA and a bill of patient's rights and protection that is legally mandated is the preferred alternative. Present situation of CPA not complemented with a quality self regulation via MCI and sub-standard quality of medical college selection (especially seats for money) are a bane. Worse still is the corporatization of health and illness care where profits take precedence over quality and concern for the patient and their family. Example is the mushrooming of scan centers whose chief aim is to recover investment and make profits. To this end, such centers resort to unethical ways of influencing doctors to order investigations more frequently and even bribe them to do so. Such centers, and the medical professionals who join up such rackets all stem from the greed to make profits while patient centered care is forgotten and the patient suffers thus needing legal remedies like CPA and sometimes even criminal charges on negligence.

Jun 21, 2012 7:50 PM

Interview Data: Community

1. Are you aware that the doctors are covered under Consumer Protection Act, meaning now anybody having any grievance against a doctor or hospital can file a case against doctors in Consumer Courts?

YES	18
NO	5
CANT SAY	1

2. Please give your opinion: Should doctors be covered under the Consumer Protection Act?

YES	20
NO	2
CANT SAY	2

3. Are you happy with the knowledge of the applicability of this Act to the doctors?

YES	15
NO	3
CANTSAY	6

4. In your own experience about medical service: are you satisfied with doctor's service and availability of doctors in the hospitals?

YES	14
NO	8
CANT SAY	1

5. Do you have total trust in the doctors?

YES	11
NO	8
CANT SAY	5

6. Do you always take a second opinion as a routine, because doctors cannot be trusted?

YES	18
NO	5
CANT SAY	1

7. Do you find any change in the relationship between you and the doctor due to the Consumer Protection Act?

YES	6
NO	11
CANT SAY	7

8. Do you find doctors are too cautious and afraid while dealing with the patient?

YES	8
NO	15
CANT SAY	1

9. Do you think there is an increase in commercialization of the medical services due the Consumer Protection Act? (should we say: increase in the cost of private medical services)

YES	14
NO	5
CANT SAY	5

10. Do you think Doctors should continue to be covered under Consumer Protection Act?

YES	21
NO	1
CANT SAY	2

Comments: Interview Data: Community

1. 90 % of the community members said they are aware of the existence of the Law, CPA against Medical Negligence, meaning that a case can be filed against doctors in Consumer Court.
2. 80 % of the community members said, doctors should be covered under Consumer Protection Act.
3. About 60 % of the community members said they are happy with the knowledge of the applicability of the Act to the doctors.
4. About 56 % community members said they are satisfied with doctor’s service and availability of doctors in the hospitals.
5. About 44 % community members said they have total trust in doctors. Remaining 32 % categorically said they do not have trust in doctors, while 20 % remained non committal.
6. 72 % of the community members agreed that they always prefer to take second opinion, as doctors cannot be trusted.
7. After the application of Consumer Protection Act, 24 % have said there is change in the relationship between doctors and patients, while 44 % said no.
8. 32 % of community members feel that, it is found that doctors are too cautious and afraid while dealing with patients, while 60 % of them do not feel the same.
9. 56 % of the community members say that there is an increase in Commercialization of Medical Services due to consumer protection Act.
- 10.84 % of the community members feel that the doctors should be continued to be covered under Consumer Protection Act.

Opinions from the Community

Do you think Doctors should continue to be covered under Consumer Protection Act?

If you think, "Yes" regarding Question, Why do you think so?

If you think, "No" regarding Question, what can be the alternative?

1. Whatever it may be but people have blind faith on doctors .we know cases of lot of fake doctors , and their harmful practices .So in that case it's better to cover them under consumer Protection Act

Aug 13, 2012 10:43 PM

2. Since a doctor is offering a service against payment, patient becomes a consumer of the service. To ensure the best service and grievance redressal it is necessary that the doctors should also be covered under the act.

Jul 26, 2012 9:17 PM

3. Patients are not toy to be played or experimented with by the doctors. People put their complete faith on the doctors; so "Consumer Protection Act" will definitely force doctors to reward the faith of the people.

Jul 26, 2012 1:35 AM

4. Nowadays we here about so many cases in which parts of human body are sold outside India in some hospitals. So coverage of Doctor's under this act will help public keep a check on every suspicious threat coming up from medical field. Moreover Doctor's will be cautious and thus a peaceful patient doctor relation can be maintained.

Jul 25, 2012 4:37 AM

5. There should be central power located above doctors who will keep eye on them and would not harm or misuse consumers need in any respect and this can be achieved to some aspect by the consumer protection act. And at the end this will benefit society and the nation after all...

Jul 25, 2012 12:34 AM

6. Doctors are offering a service which can affect lives of people. It is same as the responsibility of a civil engineer to ensure that structure is reliable & it does not collapse claiming lives of people. (If the structure falls, then we do persecute the civil engineer, then why not have the same treatment for Doctors?)

Jul 24, 2012 1:26 AM

7. I do not know the full context of the law, but there must be a classification of doctors/ medical cases that can be taken to court. There is already plenty of commercialization in terms of back door marketing to Doctors, while I cannot say all doctors indulge in drug promotion, it is not non-existent. If we want to build patient confidence, we must empower them with the right to file cases. Having said that, a blanket law for all health services provided by doctors is not the right way to go about things.

Jul 23, 2012 8:22 PM

8. There is every possibility of miss leading the patients for monetary gains by the doctors and we are really seeing it in the rural areas where 'saline' is administered to the patient recklessly. In urban areas (as well as in rural), nowadays, hardly any child birth takes place naturally. Most of them are by caesarian procedure. An urgent look is needed in this matter.

Jul 18, 2012 11:32 AM

9. Consumer protection act is regarding injustice done to the consumer regarding a good supplied or a service rendered if we pay to it. Doctors render service and for that mostly we pay to them. Rarely doctors nowadays work free of cost for mankind. So I think they must be covered under the act. Because some doctors for getting more money get fake certificates made and if a patient loses his life then who is responsible for that? there are fake doctors in existence and they must be punished for their wrongdoing

Jul 4, 2012 8:37 AM

10. I think , "YES" because nowadays I came across many cases in which patients suffered due to negligence of doctors sometimes death so this act will give the patients to act against the injustice done to them and the doctors will become more cautious.

11. Doctors will not treat patients carelessly. In these days, Doctors occupation is for only money-bank. Private Medical Colleges, where they only get license without Experience or Knowledge, will be under pressure to teach their students to take responsibility of their patients.

Jul 2, 2012 9:55 PM

12. This is because; the service they are rendering to customers must be regulated by some agency. There needs to be stricter norms imposed on infrastructure of hospitals. In my opinion, instead of covering Doctors under Consumer Protection Act, an independent commission must be established for the said purpose.

Jul 2, 2012 8:08

13. Practicing doctor itself is a high honor service to society. Society is impacted by the manner in which citizens are treated. so indirectly they are they consumers and have the right to express their solidarity over service offered, hence consumer protection is an obvious option to citizen happiness.

14. In other cases of professions, consumer can launch cases if he is not well treated or not satisfied or cheated, then why not the medical profession??? Why doctors are afraid of Consumer Profession Act if they are doing their duty honestly? This act can helpful to minimize the effects caused by improper & costly treatment even if not necessary. Loyal doctors should not have problems with these acts.....,

Jul 1, 2012 10:41 PM

15. I think this would be a good way to make sure that the docs are doing the right thing and not taking advantage of the people. However, at the same time one must make sure that the patients due to their ignorance do not take advantage (unconsciously i.e.) and sue the docs when the doc was not at fault. Else, it will be difficult for them to provide the service. The doctors should make the patients

aware of the risks involved with any procedure when they get the consulting form signed.

Jul 1, 2012 9:07 PM

16. Because due to private practitioners this has become a business kind of thing, so it must be included in consumer protection act so that it can be treated as service provider-consumer relation and consumer or patient can complain about grievances like carelessness, malpractices by doctors etc. Also it may prevent some doctors from looting the patients.

Jul 1, 2012 11:00 AM

17. Yes they should be in the act as all the doctors are not that educated, some even get passed by giving money, not all doctors are bad but I think we should respect them and not fire on them like why are you treating like this and not like that. He is educated enough to take the decision and he is not limiting us to go to others. Only cause of few corrupt doctors, all the doctors are facing this issues. But it's for our best that they are monitored by this act.

18. This is because medical profession has become much more commercialized now as compared to 10-15 yrs back. Doctors tend to patients more for the reason of money than serving the society generally. Also since patients are a consumer of the services provided by doctors, doctors should be covered under Consumer Protection Act

Jun 28, 2012 11:43 PM

19. Doctors charge checking fees every time. They as well as patient do not compromise/ bargain .If patient does not get cured, no refund fee policy. Sometimes doctor gives costly medicine. Normally no doctor says" I do not know about this particular disease "Even if he doesn't know still he charges checking fees. There is variation in check up fees. It should be minimum. He must explain scientific/ technical reason behind disease and state it on the prescription.

Jun 27, 2012 5:07 AM

20. There should be some sort of accountability for every professional worry, especially when it is being charged. They should be more transparency on the services / treatment and the charges. Even in government hospitals, where it is free service, doctors should be accountable for what they are doing. They should always be aware that they are dealing with life of the patient.

Jun 27, 2012 1:29 AM

21. With increasing privatization of health care in our country none will be assured that patients are being treated honestly without any hidden benefits. There must be some check on malpractices. Genuine doctors don't need to fear about the law as it's not for them. So I think it will definitely help to curb illegal practices and improve our social health system.

Jul 17, 2012 11:25 AM

22. Doctors believe they are demi-Gods and have little regard for other mortals. There is no fear of being accountable and hence they get either callous of the patient and many of them do not hesitate to exploit the patients. Doctors and Hospitals need to be made (mandatorily) to follow some 'quality system', for which they can be inspected and certified/ accredited/ ranked; and their adherence to the system needs to be routinely verified by some ways and findings made known to the public; displayed on their clinics/ establishments. Good doctors and hospitals need not be afraid to be auditable.

23. Presently doctors have become more profit oriented. They never think about the patient's economic status. I experienced my doctor in childhood, he should be excluded from the ACT but my son's doctor, and my friends who are doctors should be under this act. Post treatment audit should be done. Unnecessary tests are suggested. They may have sufficient reasons but common Indian think it was unnecessary and doctor is exploiting them. When I go to my son's doctor, she charges even for talking with her. Some doctors treat 3 to 4 patients at a time. There are a lot of things to talk about doctors. I know you sir and you are also doctor, a good doctor but you will get maximum 20% people who will talk good things about this generation doctors. All the best for your studies.

Jul 4, 2012 5:12 AM

24. Sometimes doctors have vested interests with drug producers. So the cost of treatment unnecessarily increased. Recently I have to purchase Rs.16000 injections for miner dog bite of my wife in Bhakti Vedanta Hospital, Mira road. Dr.Mohan Jha is bargaining the price and insists us to take that injection.

Jul 3, 2012 7:00 AM

25. It is very difficult to determine if the Doctor has not acted in good faith. Many times it may be incompetency also. Due to reservation in education and overall bad practices in education standard of Doctors (even other professions) has gone down) Overall morality in the society also has gone down. The solution is not in act but in taking efforts for reinstating the old value system which the British purposefully destroyed for their own benefit.

Jul 2, 2012 8:37 PM

26. There are 2 aspects 1. Malpractice 2. Negligence 1. When it is malpractice - then "Consumer Protection Act" should work as a controller, keeping tab on doctors to stay away from malpractice. Or it should help the victim (patient) to at least punish the doctor. 2. In case of negligence - A small negligence from the doctor can turn a person's life upside down. But, this negligence could be a mistake and if the doctor admits it and further gives proper attention and treatment to patient, then it might not compensate for the loss but it's important the doctor is genuine.

Jul 2, 2012 10:33 AM

27. According to consumer protection act, consumer is the person who avails the service. While taking into the consideration of growing private medical institutions and hospitals who works for profit motive, many time found negligent while treating or operating the patient. the aggrieved patient however no option left to bear the irreparable loss caused to him and to his dear ones and that's why doctor should continue to be covered under consumer protection act.

Jun 27, 2012 12:49 PM

28. Because as relationship between doctor & consumer is as much as service provider & consumer. Further they are doing business / occupation & necessarily not philanthropy. Interest of consumer should be protected proactively. Thanks
Jun 26, 2012 8:45 AM

29. While everybody should be held accountable for their actions including negligent doctors, this ends up hurting 'good' doctors, who end up paying enormous 'malpractice insurances' and being overcautious in their approach for the fear of being sued. I trust my doctors and will not sue them. But I have run into new (to me) doctors in 'urgent care' who negligently made a wrong diagnosis (chose to not investigate an abscess and termed it hemorrhoid instead) and I suffered as a result. A 'one size fits all' approach does not work. There needs to be a credit rating type of thing for doctors where their insurance costs go down with increased tenure with excellent record.

30. Like other service sectors, medical field is also a service given by a doctor and a patient has full right to get justice if he has affected adversely due to bad service. Also cut practice issues are there hence we can't trust on a doctor. Also this field is related to human life hence we can't compromise

31. Yes, because that makes them more accountable to patients, and stop unnecessary investigations and favoring pharma companies and charging hefty commissions, thus bringing down treatment costs due to fear of being questioned..... But again, certain liberty of decision making and risk taking should be allowed, or else doctors will stop innovating, and it should be borne in mind that doctors are not Gods, and can make mistakes, they can't be categorized like other services and commodities. Each case should be dealt specially and merit of the doctor, past records, and mass opinion be taken into account.

Jun 24, 2012 9:55 AM

32. There is no other effective mechanism that will make answerable negligent doctors and hospitals. Having a system that ensures effectively that doctors will be responsible and liable is necessary. It generates a feeling of security among common people. If there is no other system that can ensure this, the existing system cannot be cast away.

Jun 23, 2012 11:30 PM

33. As recently shown in the TV programme 'Satyamev Jayate' and also from my own past experiences I can vouch for the increasing commoditization of medical services. Commercialization of medicine has pushed Hippocrates (sorry about the spelling mistake, if any) oath to the background and doctors take undue advantage of patient's ignorance and vulnerabilities to inflate their bills and fill their coffers. Thus it's very correct to include them in the consumer protection act.

Jun 23, 2012 12:40 AM

34. Medical treatment is also a professional stream and should be covered under the law. As in all professions trust will prevail but consumers should have a way to get protected. Doctors will feel more comfortable if medico legal cases are handled by specialized cells / judges who understand medical complications and judgments. Doctors are on weak ground since the people making the justice may not understand it at all.

Jun 22, 2012 10:02 PM

35. General medical understanding of a common person about health problems is always limited and he can easily get panic if there is any health problem. He is completely depending on doctor to detect and cure the medical problem. In this case he does whatever doctor says. In this if there is no check on doctors it is very much possible that a doctor can take disadvantage of this. There is no other system through which check could be kept. If customer is paying for healthcare service, I understand he must not expect miracles but at least he can expect the basic standard to be maintained. If he is not satisfied, there should be a way where he could fight back.

Jun 22, 2012 4:26 AM

36. Doctor is liable for his treatment. Of course there should be clauses in the protection act to protect the naive / gullible consumers who get fooled by doctors- either for doctor's monetary gains or by their act of negligence resulting in a physical/mental damage. There should be a punishment for breach of trust. But on the other hand, it should not be so much that the doctors will need to live a life full of fear. They should have ample freedom to do their treatments and patients should trust them for that. The balance is the trick!

Jun 22, 2012 3:27 AM

37. My answer is NO to this question; because many a times, treatment options do not fit into mathematical principles. No doubt, CPA has helped definitely to many patients. Still I feel, it should not be generalized to all medical practitioners. There have been instances of great injustice to Doctors as well. This would create a policy of playing extra safe

Jun 21, 2012 11:49 AM

38. These days, medical practice is not a 'social service' anymore but it's like a product (health service) being sold to a customer (patient). The customer should have the right to file a case against the seller if he is not happy with the product. In fact, I think this law is a MUST, and should have been implemented earlier.

Jun 21, 2012 1:44 AM

39. As we witnessed growth of commercial angle in the medical field cost were also reaching to high scale. In this context, though Indian medical system has tradition of family relations with doctors , breed of new private hospitals make it essential to cover doctors under consumer protection act as traditional bond between doctor and patient is not remained much strong like earlier

40. Generally Drs give appropriate advice and service. However India is a large country with huge population. Hence there has to be a mechanism for an appeal against the perceived injustice or lack of service. In all professions, there is such platform or else the individual can go to the court of law under civil or criminal acts. I think in medical field, there isn't any such platform and hence CPA is useful.

41. It is very difficult to determine if the Doctor has not acted in good faith. Many times it may be incompetency also. Due to reservation in education and overall bad practices in education standard of Doctors (even other professions) has gone down) Overall morality in the society also has gone down. The solution is not in act but in taking efforts for reinstating the old value system which the British purposefully destroyed for their own benefit.

Jul 2, 2012 8:37 PM

42. Points no 7,8,9 needs further clarification. They cannot be just simply answered in the form of MCQ. The alternative is to have a joint forum of doctors of various specialties on one side; and renowned personalities, NGOs, social workers on other side in equal number. This forum will not have judicial powers. It should address the problem of the patient from a neutral perspective. It should try to settle the problem in its own capacity. If settlement is not acceptable to either party, option of judicial system (court of law) is open. Of course, the judicial system needs improvement in terms of speed, effectiveness and easy approachability.

Jun 21, 2012 11:49 AM

43. Because by including doctors -patient under CPA will bring more commercialization and will make healthcare costlier...it will bring more apathy in the minds of doctors about patient and responsibility taking behavior will decrease on the part of doctorI think healthcare service should be made accountable by direct control of Government and not by legal means...otherwise private practice should be abandoned. There should be universal norms about how much to charge from patient...

Jun 21, 2012 9:57 AM

44. It's not a definite science nor are they selling a commodity. It's a service and things can still go wrong even after they give their full efforts. Every Hospital in a district should be subject to routine inspections and liable to questioning on the records of patients.

Jul 2, 2012 2:19 AM

45. There is always a thumb rule that, any professional will come from the society. So, the person reflects the character of the societal population. Beyond this, the person with high integrity towards the profession is the only alternative. To achieve this, a stringent training and orientation of the medical professionals is a dire need of the hour. Actually, it is the need of all professions. A person when opt for medical as profession, he/she should be given proper training. I would say, a doctor must carry high moral and good humane character of high order. It is the mission of his/her lifetime. Covering them under consumer protection act will hamper this missionary zeal among the doctors and also the doctor-patient relationship.

Jun 28, 2012 12:28 AM

46. The Medical Profession is a large one and the issues arising due to the disputes related to them are large in number. This actually merits a law on its own basis that will deal with the patient protection while also handling the fine aspects of the relationship that cannot be done justice by the Consumer Protection Act.

Jun 26, 2012 8:50 PM

5.4 Triangulation of Data: Trends in the Concept of Medical Negligence

Introduction

Selected important variables from case laws were selected to compare and contrast the empirical variables from doctors and hospital administrator's survey and also from community survey. So the variables from Doctrinal and empirical study identified to form **Triangulation Matrix**, which is analyzed to postulate the trends in the law of Medical Negligence. The statistics and opinions were studied and analyzed

Figure 6
Triangulation Matrix

Doctrinal Study

Doctor's Specialty

In the present study, in Supreme Court, maximum number of cases were against Broad Surgical Specialty 35 %, followed by Hospital 22.5 % and Medical Super specialty 15 %; while in National Commission maximum number of cases are against Broad Surgical Specialty 28.7 % followed by Surgical Super specialty 28.3 %, that is followed by Hospital and Specialty combined 17.7 %.

In the present study, 97.5 % cases of Supreme Court were from Specialists and Super Specialists were involved, and remaining 2.5 % were General Practitioners. Out of Specialists cases in the Supreme Court, 58.97 % of the cases were proved to be negligent and in 41.02 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was not proved.

In case of General Practitioner cases in 100 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved.

In case of the National Commission, 94 % cases were Specialists and Super specialists involved, out of which in 37.23 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved and remaining 62.76 % of the patients it was not proved.

In 6 % of the cases, General Practitioners were involved, out of which in 27.77 % of the cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 72.22 % of the cases it was not proved.

Education of the Complainant

Supreme Court: 90 % of the patients in the present study were educated, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 55.55 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 44.44 %.

In 10 % of the cases, the patients were uneducated, out of which in 100 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved. No lawyer was found to approach the apex Court.

National Commission: 78.66 % of the patients were educated, out of which in 33.05 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 66.94 % it was not.

In 18.66 % of the cases, patients were uneducated, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 53.57 % cases and not proved in 46.42 % of cases.

In 2.55 % of the appellants of the total cases in the present study were Lawyers. In those cases 25 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 75 % of them the Medical Negligence was not proved.

Number of cases per year

There is gradual increase in the number of cases in last 3 decades at both Supreme Court and National Commission level. There is an upsurge of cases reaching the National Commission, from 2011 till today. So present study comprises of 45.7 % of cases from National Commission, decided after 2011. Fewer cases reached and decided at the Supreme Court when compared with the National Commission cases.

Patient's Place

In the present study, 77.5 % cases of Supreme Court were from urban area, and remaining from rural area. Out of Urban cases in the Supreme Court, 51.61 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was proved and in 48.39 % of the cases, Medical Negligence was not proved.

In case of cases where, patient is from rural area, in 88.88 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved and in only 12.22 % of cases, the medical negligence was not proved.

In case of the National Commission, 80.66 % cases were from urban region, out of which in 35.53 % of cases, Medical Negligence was proved and remaining 64.46 % of the patients it was not proved.

19.33 % of the patients belonged to rural region, out of which in 41.37 % of the cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 58.62 % of the cases it was not proved.

Table No. 136
Duration of Case

National Commission Analysis	
YEAR	AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR JUDGEMENT in Years
1990-1994	2
1995-1999	4
2000-2004	5
2005-2009	7
2010-2013	6

Supreme Court Analysis	
YEAR	AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR JUDGEMENT in Years
Before 1990	2
1990-1994	1
1995-1999	4
2000-2004	3
2005-2009	3.5
2010-2013	5.5

As the tables and the graphs show, the average time taken for judgment is gradually increasing.

Supreme Court: from 2 years before 1990 to 5.5 years now in 2013.

National Commission: from 2 years at 1990 to 6 years now in 2013.

Acceptance of Expert Evidence

Supreme Court: In 85 % of the cases in the present study the Judges' version, accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 64.7 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 35.29 %.

In 15 % of the cases, Judges' version, not accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which in 33.33 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 66.66 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 44.33 % cases, the Judges' version, accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which in 48.87 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 51.12 % it was not.

In 55.66 % of the cases, the Judges' version, not accepted the expert witness and evidence, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 26.94 % cases and not proved in 73.05 % of cases.

Reference to Case Laws

Supreme Court: In 75 % of the cases in the present study the Case Laws were referred by the court, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 66.66 % of the cases while it was not proved in remaining 33.33 %.

In 25 % of the cases, the Case Laws were not referred, out of which in 40 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 60 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 53.33 % cases, the , Case Laws were referred by the Commission, out of which in 42.85 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 57.14 % it was not.

In 44 % of the cases, the Case Laws were not referred by the Commission, out of which in Medical Negligence was proved in 28.78 % cases and not proved in 71.21 % of cases.

Bolam Principle

Supreme Court: In 37.5 % of the cases in the present study, the Bolam principle was mentioned, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 66.66 % of the cases, and in remaining 33.33 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

In 62.5 % of the cases, the Bolam principle was not mentioned , out of which in 56 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 44 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 15.66 % cases, the Bolam principle was mentioned, out of which in 53.19 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 46.8 % it was not.

Similarly, in 84.33 % of the cases at National Commission,, Bolam principle was not mentioned, out of which in 33.59 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved, while in 66.4 % remaining case it was not proved.

Bolitho Principle

Editorship: Judge gives decision after collecting information from, expert witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws etc.

Authorship: Without referring any relevant witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws, Judge gives decision as he thinks fit, based on logical analysis, using Bolitho Principle.

Supreme Court: In 85 % of the cases in the present study, Judicial Behaviour was Editorship, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 64.7 % of the cases, while it was not proved in 35.29 % of cases.

In 15 % of the cases, the Judicial Behaviour was Authorship; out of which in 33.33 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 66.66 % cases it was not proved.

National Commission: In 47 % cases, the Judicial Behaviour was Editorship, out of which in 44.68 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 55.31 % cases it was not proved.

Similarly, in 53 % of the cases at National Commission Judicial Behaviour was Authorship, in which 29.55 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 70.44 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

Contributory Negligence

Supreme Court: In 27.5 % of the cases in the present study the Contributory Negligence by patient was proved, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases, so in spite of that the doctor was found to be negligent. That means contributory negligence by patients did not have negative impact on judgment.

In 72.5 % of the cases, the Contributory Negligence of patients was not proved, out of which in 44.82 % of cases the Medical Negligence was proved while in 55.17 % remaining, it was not.

National Commission: In 15.33 % cases, the Contributory Negligence of patients was proved, out of which in 56.52 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 43.47 % it was not.

Similarly, in 84.66 % of the cases at National Commission, Contributory Negligence of patients was not proved, out of which in 33.07 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved, while in 66.92 % remaining case it was not proved.

Deficiency in Service

Comments:

Supreme Court: In 60 % of the cases in the present study, **Deficiency in service** was proved, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases.

In 40 % of the cases, the **Deficiency in service** was not proved; obviously in all 100 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

National Commission: In 36.66 % cases, the **Deficiency in service** was proved, out of which in all 100 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved.

Similarly, in 63.33 % of the cases at National Commission, **Deficiency in service** was not proved; in all the cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

Compensation

Supreme Court: In 60 % of the cases in the present study, Deficiency in service was proved, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 100 % of the cases and compensation was awarded to all.

In 40 % of the cases, the Deficiency in service was not proved; obviously in all 100 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved; no compensation was awarded.

National Commission: In 36.66 % cases, the Deficiency in service was proved, out of which in all 100 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and compensation was awarded.

Similarly, in 63.33 % of the cases at National Commission, Deficiency in service was not proved; in all the cases Medical Negligence was not proved, no compensation was awarded.

Judicial Response to Issues

Based on the one of the research articles, the judicial response to the issues was divided in strong, weak and no response.

Supreme Court: In 92.5 % of the cases in the present study, Judicial Response was strongly responsive, out of which the Medical Negligence was proved in 62.16 % of the cases, while it was not proved in 37.83 % of cases.

In 5 % of the cases, the Judicial Response was weak to the issues; out of which in 50 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 50 % cases it was not proved.

In 2.5 % of the cases, there was no Judicial Response, where Medical Negligence was not proved in all 100 % cases.

National Commission: In 26.33 % cases, the Judicial Response was Strong, out of which in 67.08 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 32.91 % cases it was not proved.

Similarly, in 17 % of the cases at National Commission Judicial Response was weak, in which 37.25 % cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 62.74 % cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

In 56.66 % there was no judicial response to the issues in discussion, where Medical Negligence was proved in 22.35 % of cases while in remaining 77.64 % of the cases Medical Negligence was not proved.

Empirical Study: Doctor's Response

Medical Specialty

The maximum response was from Broad Surgical Specialties, 41.2 % while 31.9 % were practicing Broad Medical Specialties. The Super specialists represented by around 10 %, both medical as well as surgical.

Amongst the Hospital Administrators group, maximum response came from purely working as Hospital Administrators 65.8 %, various level managers were 7.3 % and Hospital Administrators who are practicing as clinicians as well as hospital administrators were 26.8

Years of Medical Practice

In the present study, the maximum number of cases 44.3 % amongst Doctors and 41.5 % of the cases amongst Hospital Administrators who responded were with more than 20 years of practice.

Basis for Treatment

68.6 % of doctors and 61 % of the hospital administrators in the survey said, the basis of the treatment is both-prior experience and treatment protocols. Equal number was divided between the two, treatment protocols and prior experience. 19.7 % of the doctors didn't answer this question.

Awareness about CPA

80.1 % of the doctors and 92.7 % Hospital Administrators were aware of the existence of Consumer Protection Act against Medical Negligence.

Doctor Patient Relationship

The detailed concept of doctor patient relationship was found to be known to 40.3 % of doctors and 58.5 % hospital administrators.

This question was a tricky one; all options were not the examples of doctor patient legal relationship.

This was rightly identified by 21.8 % of doctors and 34.1 % of the hospital administrators.

Majority of doctors and hospital administrators agreed to statement, 60.9 % doctors and 82.9 % of hospital administrators,

Cordial Doctor patient relationship avoids litigation

Documentation

Both doctors as well hospital administrators agreed with the importance of documentation of patient records. 92.7 % of the doctors and 95.1 % of the hospital administrators agreed to the same.

91.8 % doctors and 87.8 % of Hospital Administrators agreed with the statement,

“Best way to defend your self is proper documentation of patient’s records”

Updation of skills

79.4 % of doctors and 80.5 % of hospital administrators feel that it is necessary to regularly update the skills. This is again the after effect of application of CPA to the Medical Field.

75.4 % of doctors and 78 % of Hospital Administrators said they attend conferences and workshops in their fields of specialization. This is the result of CPA application

that majority of medical experts now are participating in skill up gradation programs like conferences and workshops.

Informed Consent

80.8 % of doctors and 87.8 % of hospital administrators are aware of the concept of Informed Consent. It indicates that, the awareness about Informed Consent has been percolated well.

79.9 % of doctors and 87.8 % of hospital administrators are knowing the detailed concept of Informed Consent. About 20 % of doctors not answered this question.

Bolam Principle Knowledge

Bolam Principle is the principle being referred for judging a case of negligence. Only 12.2 % doctors and 43.9 % hospital administrators are aware of the existence of such principle and all others are not.

While 62.3 % of doctors and 41.5 % of Hospital Administrators accepted that they don't know the Bolam Principle, while all others tried to guess the responses. 13.6 % of the doctors and 29.3 % of Hospital Administrators correctly identified the components of Bolam Principle.

Bolitho Principle Knowledge

Majority of doctors and hospital administrators have not answered this question, meaning that Bolitho principle is known to a handful of them.

In spite of not answering previous question, the participants tried to guess the answer to this question. 45.4 % of doctors and 46.3 % of the hospital administrators answered this question correctly.

Second Opinion

78 % of the doctors and 73.2 % of hospital administrators said, they will take second opinion in complicated cases and may refer these patients to higher centres.

Awareness about Medical Negligence

72.1 % of the doctors and 73.2 % of the Hospital Administrators correctly identified the meaning of Medical Negligence while others were confused with all other answers

68.9 % of the doctors and 58.5 % of the Hospital Administrators correctly identified the Components of Medical Negligence while others were confused with all other answers.

The participants of the survey were confused over the knowledge of available defences to a doctor in Medical Negligence case. 63.4 % hospital administrators and 22 % of the doctors were aware of the defences available while all others are not aware.

Whether CPA should continue?

59 % of doctors and 61 % of hospital administrators, preferred strict control of doctor's training by Medical Council of India and regulation by that body while only 6.8 % of doctors and 12.2 % of hospital administrators said no to this concept and remaining were non committal.

Indemnity Insurance

65.6 % of Doctors and 26.8 % of the hospital administrators are insured under Professional Indemnity Insurance.

73.5 % doctors and 73.2 % hospital administrators knew the details of Professional Indemnity Insurance. Remaining participants opted for other options.

The opinion about the knowledge of terms and conditions of Insurance Company was divided in both the groups, doctors and Hospital Administrators. Only 28.1 % of the Doctors and 26.8 % of Hospital Administrators knew the terms and conditions of Insurance Company, in relation to Indemnity Insurance.

Defensive Medicine

The participants of the survey were confused over the knowledge of available defences to a doctor in Medical Negligence case. 63.4 % hospital administrators and 22 % of the doctors were aware of the defences available while all others are not aware.

Medical Council Regulations

40.5 % of doctors and 85.4 % of hospital administrators are aware of the regulations for doctors by the Medical Council of India. It is shocking finding that 60 % of the doctors are not aware of these regulations!

Only 12.9 % doctors and 53.7 % of Hospital Administrators are aware of the amendment of Medical Council of India regulations, remaining are not aware

Personal opinion about CPA: An overview

Consumer Protection Act (CPA) is valid until self regulation continues to be corrupt as in the case of MCI where an MCI head was prosecuted. Self regulation via Medical Councils complemented with CPA and a bill of patient's rights and protection that is legally mandated is the preferred alternative. Present situation of CPA not complemented with a quality self regulation via MCI and sub-standard quality of medical college selection (especially seats for money) are a bane. Worse still is the corporatization of health and illness care where profits take precedence over quality and concern for the patient and their family. Example is the mushrooming of scan centres whose chief aim is to recover investment and make profits. To this end, such centres resort to unethical ways of influencing doctors to order investigations more frequently and even bribe them to do so. Such centres, and the medical professionals who join up such rackets all stem from the greed to make profits while patient centred care is forgotten and the patient suffers thus needing legal remedies like CPA and sometimes even criminal charges on negligence.

Community Response

Age

The response 58.4 % was more from the age group of 20 to 30 years. The other age groups were represented by variable response in the present study

Education Background

The response to the questionnaire was more from graduates 43 % and 31.1 % from post graduates. Also there was a good response from non graduates, 18 %.

Occupation

The response was good from students 25.9 % and those with private work-practice, 25.7 %. Also 20.3 % academicians responded to this questionnaire.

Awareness about CPA

54.9 % of the respondents know that anybody having any grievance against a doctor or hospital can file a case against doctors in Consumer Courts.

34.1 % said they are not aware of this. 11 % preferred to remain silent on this.

Any observed change in relationship with doctor

16.1 % of the respondents said they find change in their relationship with doctors. 49.5 % have not noticed any change while 34.4 % have not answered this question

Should doctors be covered under CPA?

83.9 % of the respondents said, the doctors should be covered under Consumer Protection Act. Only 6.5 % are not in favour of this application to doctors and 9.6 % remained silent on this.

Are you happy?

51.4 % of participants said they are happy with the knowledge of applicability of COA to Doctors. 23.1 % said no while 25.5 % didn't answer this question.

Satisfaction with doctor's service

41.8 % of the respondents said they are satisfied with doctors service in general, 38.6 % said they are not satisfied while, 19.7 % have not answered this question

Total Trust?

Only 27.1 % of the respondents said they have total trust in doctors, while 42.3 % said they don't have trust in doctors. A sizable number 30.6 % remained silent, indicating distrust in doctors.

Are doctors too cautious and afraid now?

16.6 % of participants said,they now find doctors too cautious and afraid due to CPA.58.9 % didn't find such shange, while 24.5 % remanied silent on this question.

Second opinion?

40.7 % of the respondents said they always take second opinion,indicating distrust in the doctors, 38.6 % respondents said they don,t always take second opinion, while 20.8 % remained non committal.

Increase in commercialization

59.6 % of the participants in survey feel that there is an increae in commercialization of Medical Services due to CPA, while 12.4 don't feel so.28.1 % of the participants have not answered this question.

Whether CPA should continue?

62.6 % of the respondents feel that doctors should continue to be covered under Consumer Protection Act.

Active suggestions by patients/community:

- There is always a thumb rule that, any professional will come from the society. So, the person reflects the character of the societal population. Beyond this, the person with high integrity towards the profession is the only alternative. To achieve this, a stringent training and orientation of the medical professionals is a dire need of the hour. Actually, it is the need of all professions. A person when opt for medical as profession, he/she should be given proper training. I would

say, a doctor must carry high moral and good humane character of high order. It is the mission of his/her lifetime. Covering them under consumer protection act will hamper this missionary zeal among the doctors and also the doctor-patient relationship.

- Doctors believe they are demi-Gods and have little regard for other mortals. There is no fear of being accountable and hence they get either callous of the patient and many of them do not hesitate to exploit the patients. Doctors and Hospitals need to be made (mandatorily) to follow some 'quality system', for which they can be inspected and certified / accredited / ranked; and their adherence to the system needs to be routinely verified by some ways and findings made known to the public; displayed on their clinics/ establishments. Good doctors and hospitals need not be afraid to be auditable.

Summary of Personal Opinion about CPA

The summary of all patient-respondents is, “Consumer protection Act is regarding injustice done to the consumer regarding a good supplied or a service rendered if we pay to it. Doctors render service and for that mostly we pay to them. Rarely doctors nowadays work free of cost for mankind. So I think they must be covered under the act. Because some doctors for getting more money get fake certificates made and if a patient loses his life then who is responsible for that? There are fake doctors in existence and they must be punished for their wrongdoing”

The qualitative analysis of survey projects the divide between doctors and other medical professionals and the community. This divide is rather created or enhanced by CPA in the post-CPA period, as shown converging in case analysis.

There is a need to critically evaluate these trends and explore law reform and other ways of comprehensively reforming the healthcare system as a participatory, mutually gainful and amicable venture.

Next chapter explores such possibilities, after critical evaluation of the trends analysed so far.

Chapter 6

CRITICAL EVALUATION

Of

The changing trends

In the law of

Medical negligence

6.1 Changing Trends visible in the case law analysis and interpretation

In the previous parts of the study, the researcher has identified, 5 indicators of changing trends in the Law of Medical Negligence, as follows

TRENDS WISE CASE LAW ANALYSIS

A) PRINCIPLES

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

The traditional basis for deciding the Medical Negligence cases is the **Bolam Principle**. In the selected study of 300 National Commission cases, the principle is being mentioned in increasing number. Before 1990 it is not mentioned at all, while during 1991 to 2000, in 2.12 % cases (out of 47 cases) it was mentioned in the judgment, during 2001 to 2010 it was mentioned in 16.37 % of Cases (out of 116 cases) and after 2011 till today it is mentioned in 19.85 % of the cases (out of 136 cases).

Sympathetic discussion about patient's complaints done and patients are protected under the **Consumer Protection Principle**, in 1991 to 2000, is 12 %, while in 2001 to 2010 it was 32.75 % and from 2011 the principle is being used in 19.85 % of Cases.

Case laws are being referred in increasing number of cases, in one case before 1990 case laws were referred, while in 21.27 % of cases in 1991 to 2000, 57.75 % cases in 2001 to 2010 and after 2011 it is in 44.11 % of decided cases case laws are referred.

The **contributory negligence** of the patients is actively mentioned and sought as 10.63 % of cases in 1990 to 2000, 11.2 % of cases in 2001 to 2010 and now after 2011 it is 20.58 %, indicating increase in the awareness regarding the contributory Negligence.

The **Bolitho Principle** is not at all mentioned before 2000, while it is just mentioned sparingly, 4.31 % in 2001 to 2010 cases and after that 5.88 %. It indicates that the principle is now known to be mentioned more frequently though not applied up till now.

As such the National Commission has precarious role in **developing new rules**. In 2001 to 2010 8.62 % of cases and after 2011 (136 cases) it is 7.35 %)

Comments: on **Trends in Supreme Court Judgments**

In the Supreme Court cases, in 25 % cases of 1991-2000, the **Bolam Principle** is mentioned in the Judgments while in 42.8 % of 2001 to 2010 cases, it is mentioned. Presently since 2011 till today in all cases this important principle is mentioned.

Sympathetic discussion about patient's complaints done and patients are protected under the **Consumer Protection Principle**, during 1980 to 1991 it is used in 66.66 % of cases , in 1991 to 2000 is 87.5 %, while in 2001 to 2010 it was 50 % and from 2011 the principle is being used in 100 % of Cases.

Case laws are being referred in increasing number of cases, in 33.33 % of case before 1990 case laws were referred, while in 87.75 % of cases in 1991 to 2000, 75 % cases in 2001 to 2010 and after 2011 it is in 100 % of decided cases, case laws are referred.

The **contributory negligence** of the patients is actively mentioned and sought only after 2000, as 0% of cases in 1990 to 2000, 35.71 % of cases in 2001 to 2010 and now after 2011 it is 100 %, indicating increase in the awareness regarding the contributory Negligence.

The **Bolitho Principle** is not at all mentioned before 2000, while it is just mentioned sparingly, 3.57 % in 2001 to 2010 cases and after that in no case it is mentioned. It indicates that the principle is now known to be mentioned more frequently though not applied up till now.

The Supreme Court has major role in **developing new rules**. Between 1981 to 1990 in 66.66% of cases, in 100 % of cases in 1990 to 2000, and in 2001 to 2010 it was 57.14 % and after 2011 no case has developed new rules. Thus after the application of the Consumer Protection Act to the Medical Field, the very next decade there was

an intense legal Judicial Activism that spelt various legal principles settled as law today.

B) DEFICIENCY

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

In the present study, during 1991 to 2000, in 25.53 % cases deficiency in services was proved, in 25.53 % of cases Medical Negligence was proved and in 57.44 % cases Informed Consent was not taken. During 2001 to 2010, in 31.89 % of cases Deficiency in service was proved at the same time Medical Negligence was proved, while in 65.51 % of the cases Informed Consent was not taken. After 2011, in 44.85 % of cases deficiency was proved as well as Medical Negligence. In 75 % of the patients Informed Consent was not taken.

Thus over the years, there has been an increase in % of deficiency in service and Medical Negligence. Incidentally, there has been an increase in the % of incidences where Informed Consent is not being taken.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

In the present study of 40 cases, during 1981 to 1990, in 66.66 % of cases deficiency in service and Medical Negligence was proved. In 33.33 % cases Informed Consent was not taken.

During 1991 to 2000, in 87.5 % cases deficiency in service and Medical Negligence was proved. In 37.5 % cases the Informed Consent was not taken.

During 2001 to 2010, in 50 % cases deficiency in service and Medical Negligence was proved. In 32.14 % cases Informed Consent was not taken. While after 2011, in all cases deficiency and Medical Negligence was proved. But also in none of the cases Informed Consent was taken.

C) METHODS OF JUDGING

Type of Judgment: Structured / Unstructured

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

During last 3 decades, there is an increase in structured as well as unstructured judgments, while in 1981 to 1990, only one case that has structured judgment.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

In Supreme Court, % of structured Judgment has increased over last 4 decades, serially 66.66 %, 87.5 %, 87.71% and 100 % as the graph suggests.

Judicial Behaviour: Editorship/ Authorship

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

Only one case was included in this study from the 1981 to 1990 decade. The judgment delivered was by Judicial Behaviour that can be classified as Editorship. Next 2 decades, it was 34.04 % and 43.96 % Editorship was used, while after 2011 in 30.14 % cases the editorship was used. The editorship is supposed to be the best as the judgment depends on various references. The Authorship was used as principle in about 50 to 70 % of cases in last 4 decades.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

Over the last 4 decades, in Supreme Court, there has been an increase in Editorship as Judicial Behaviour, while Authorship has gradually reduced.

Court's Analysis of Each Issue: Full/ Mixed/ Minimal /Low

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

Over last 4 decades, when the judgments of National Commission cases are analyzed, it is found that there is reduction in % of complete analysis of the cases, i.e. issues under consideration. 17.02 % in 1991-2000, 15.51 % in 2001 to 2010 and from 2011 it is 6.61 %. In 3rd decade, 2001 to 2010, about 44.68 % judgments are seen with low analysis of issues under consideration.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

At Supreme Court, for the analysis of each issue under consideration, % of full or complete analysis has been increasing as depicted in graph. So thus it can be said that the apex court is through with its approach toward Medical Negligence.

Judicial Response to Each Issue: Strongly Responsive / Weakly Responsive / No Responsive

Comments: on Trends in National Commission Judgments

When analyzed, the Judicial Response has been divided into Strongly Responsive, Weakly Responsive and non Responsive. For the National Commission Judgments, the Judicial

Response to each issue has been variable. Last 3 decades, rather it is found that the non responsive nature of Judge's is increasing.

Comments: on Trends in Supreme Court Judgments

The Supreme Court has been traditionally strongly responsive for the issues under consideration. The graph above shows the trend.

Judge's Unawareness of Fallacies in the System and Medical Field

Comments: on **Trends in National Commission Judgments**

At the National Commission, there is an increased trend of accepting or formally quoting by the judges that, they are unaware of the fallacies of the Medical Field.

Comments: on **Trends in Supreme Court Judgments**

At Supreme Court, only in the decade of 2001-2010, in 7.14 % of the cases, the Judges have formally mentioned that they are unaware of the fallacies of the medical field. Otherwise in all the past 2 decades they have formally not mentioned the unawareness.

D) EVIDENCE

Comments: on **Trends in National Commission Judgments**

Regarding use and acceptance of the expert witness, expert evidence and Medical Literature; there is variability between 25 to 66 % in all the 4 decades. It is true that there is an increase in the use and acceptance of the same.

Comments: on **Trends in Supreme Court Judgments**

In Supreme Court, the trend to use and acceptance of expert witness, expert evidence and Medical Literature is increasing and last decade it was around 87.5 %, while after 2011, the use and acceptance is 100 %. So it is a positive sign of respecting the Expert Witness and Evidence.

E) COMPENSATION

Comments: on **Trends in National Commission Judgments**

In National Commission Judgments, the trend of awarding compensation is as follows

In 1991-2001 - 25.53 %;

2001 to 20110 - 31.39 %

and after 2011- 44.85 %

Comments: on **Trends in Supreme Court Judgments**

At Supreme Court, the trend of awarding compensation is much higher

1981 to 1990 – 66.66 %;

1991 to 2001- 75 %;

2001 to 2010 – 53.57 % and

100 % for the cases after 2011.

Thus trend of awarding the compensation is higher at Supreme Court than at National Commission.

Method of Compensation Calculation:³³³

In most cases the remedy for a victim of medical negligence through a Consumer Court would be to get compensated. But how is this compensation fixed? You cannot fix a value to your dear ones in terms of money. Can you? The Consumer Court has formulated a method to calculate, a not so accurate but fair, compensation amount. Let us read more on this below.

There are a lot of factors including pecuniary factors like loss of future earnings (if the victim is dead or disabled), medical expenses incurred, future medical expenses (if the victim still requires medical assistance), cost of litigation etc. and non-pecuniary factors like compensation for the pain and suffering, non-enjoyment of life, shortening of life expectancy etc.

Calculating the loss of future earnings is a complex process. The Supreme Court in *Sarla Verma & Ors. Vs. Delhi Transport Corp. & Anr*³³⁴ has laid down the three step process through which this can be calculated. The first step would be to calculate the 'multiplicand' (a number that is to be multiplied with another – in $2 * 5$, 5 is the multiplicand). In this step the annual income of the deceased or the injured is

³³³ Runjhun, Compensation in Medical Negligence Cases: A Quick Survey-Consumer Tadka, (October 28, 2011) <http://info.akosha.com/consumer-complaints/consumer-protection/compensation-in-medical-negligence-cases-a-quick-survey/> (last accessed 30 April 2013).

³³⁴ (2009) 6 SCC 121

calculated. The deceased/injured would have spent on himself is deducted. The balance is the Multiplicand.

Step 2 is to determine the Multiplier. In this step an estimate is made on the years of active career of the person. From this, some years are deducted under heads like imponderables in life, uncertain economic factors etc. The resulting number is the multiplier. For example if x, dies at the age of 35, and if his expected period of active service is estimated to be till 60 years, then the multiplier would be 25. From this, let's say, 7 years are deducted under imponderables in life and economic factors, then the final multiplier will become 18.

The third step is to multiply the Multiplicand with the multiplier, which will give the compensation amount under Loss of future earnings. The pecuniary factors can be, to an extent, accurate but the non pecuniary factors cannot be accurate. You cannot measure the mental sufferings and give a value to it. The courts usually fix an amount which it deems will compensate the non pecuniary damages.

These factors vary depending on the nature of the cases. For example in the case where a person has fully recovered from the damages caused due to the medical negligence, he may not be given compensation for loss of future earnings. Similarly if the medical expense of the victim is covered by a third party, for example, if it is covered by the company he works in, then he might not get compensation for medical expenses.

In most medical negligence cases the consumer court has awarded compensation less than the amount asked for by the complainant. One can argue that since it is the complainant who has suffered all the physical and mental damages, he is the best person to determine the compensation he needed. But there are times people ask for unreasonable amounts or may think that a particular amount is reasonable, when it is actually not. You will always over value yourself or your loved ones. So better leave it to the courts to decide and hope that you'll get a fair compensation. Or maybe, not go for a case and fall in love with the doctor.³³⁵

³³⁵ Id

Anuradha Saha Case: Example: On October 21, 2011, NCDRC awarded a total of Rs. 1.7 Crores compensation against the Kolkata doctors and AMRI Hospital but deducted more than Rs. 40 Lakh on ground of alleged “interference” by Dr. Saha (although Apex Court held only the Kolkata doctors/hospital guilty for Anuradha’s death) and also due to the death of one of the guilty doctors, Dr. Roychowdhury. Although this was the highest compensation ever awarded in India for death of a patient due to “medical negligence”, Dr. Saha has challenged the said order passed by NCDRC on numerous grounds including the fact that the NCDRC did not follow settled principles for calculating compensation in “medical negligence” cases while dismissing more than 98% of Dr. Saha’s claim. The NCDRC also used the “Multiplier” method for calculation of compensation which has never been used any case of “medical negligence” until now. In fact, “Multiplier” method is used under Section 163A of the Motor Vehicle Accident Act for awarding compensation to auto accident victims in “no fault” accident. Obviously, the “Multiplier” method minimizes the compensation to be paid by the rash and negligent doctors and hospitals.³³⁶

6.3 Changing Trends in the selected case studies from Pune district

The 10 cases from Pune were studied and analyzed by applying same variables, as that for the case law analysis. This is compared and contrast between National and Local trends.

1. Type of Case

The analysis of 10 Pune Cases from Pune that included 7 decided cases at Pune District Consumer Redressal forum and 3 cases from Pune directly approached State Consumer Commission.

In 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved out of 7 cases at District Forum while in 6 cases it was not proved, that includes 3 cases at district forum and 3 cases at State commission.

2. Patient Place

³³⁶ Anonymous, Anuradha Saha Death Case Ends In Supreme Court: Judgment Reserved In Highest “Medical Negligence” Case In Indian Medico-legal History (April 11,2013) <http://pbtindia.com/archives/1815> (last accessed 30 April 2013)

All the 10 cases are from urban origin where the patients are from urban area, while no case is from rural area

3. Patient Status

Out of 10 cases, in 1 case patient died while in rest 9 cases patients were disabled. In the case where patient died, Medical Negligence was proved at district level, while from disabled cases, only 3 cases Medical Negligence was proved and in others not yet proved

4. Patient Education

All the 10 cases, the petitioners were Educated, so as such no relation between Medical Negligence and the education of the petitioner was found.

5. Type of Doctors

In the sample of 10 cases, all the 10 doctors were found to be specialists and there was no General Practitioner. And 4 of the specialists was found negligent by the district forum.

6. Inclusion of Hospitals

In 2 cases out of 10 cases, the hospitals were included and were respondents along with the doctors. In both the cases where hospitals were also made party, Medical Negligence due to deficiency in service was proved, while out of remaining 8 cases where hospitals were not included, in 2 cases the Medical Negligence was proved and rest 6 cases it was not proved.

7. Appeal Filed By

Out of 10 cases, the appeals in State Commission were filed by, 7 appeals by patients, 2 appeals by doctors and one appeal by a hospital.

8. Number of Complainants:

Out of 10, in nine cases, one complainant and in one case many complainants filed cases against doctors.

9. Number of Respondents:

Out of 10 cases, in 4 cases single respondent and in remaining 6 cases many respondents were there. In each of the category, in 2 cases each Medical Negligence was proved.

10. Complainant's Version:

Out of 10 cases in 3 cases, the complainant's version was accepted and in 7 cases it was not accepted. In all the 3 cases where, complainants i.e. patient's version was accepted, Medical Negligence was proved, while in only one case where, though

complainant's version was not accepted, Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 6 cases it was not proved.

11. Respondent's Version:

In 7 cases, respondent's version was accepted and in 3 cases it was not accepted. So out of 7 cases, in one case in spite of accepting respondent's version, Medical Negligence was proved and in 3 cases in which respondent's version were not accepted, the Medical Negligence was proved.

12. Expert Witness/Evidence:

In 4 cases the expert witness/evidence was accepted by the Judges and in 6 cases not. In all the four cases Medical Negligence was proved.

13. Expert witness:

In 6 cases Expert witness was considered, out of which 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 2 cases as well as 4 cases in which expert witness was not accepted, Medical Negligence was not proved.

14. Expert Evidence:

Out of 4 cases in which Expert evidence was accepted, Medical Negligence was proved in 2 cases, and in remaining 6 cases in which Expert Evidence was not accepted in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved

15. Case Laws Referred:

Out of 4 cases in which case laws were referred, 2 cases were Medical Negligence proved and out of 6 cases in which case laws were not referred, in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

16. Medical Literature Referred:

In 3 cases Medical Literature was referred out of 10 cases, while out of that only one was found to be negligent. While out of 7 cases where Medical Literature was not referred, in 3 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

17. Contributory Negligence by the patient:

In all the 10 cases, contributory Negligence was not proved, out which in 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved.

18. Bolam Principle Mentioned:

In all the 10 cases, the Bolam Principle was not mentioned by the Judges in the Judgments, and in 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved, in remaining 6 it was not

19. Compensation awarded & consumer protection principle.

In 4 cases Medical Negligence was proved and compensation was awarded, thus the Consumer Protection Principle was confirmed in the Judgments.

20. New Rule in the Judgment & Bolitho Principle Used

In all the 10 cases, no new rule was postulated by the Court, as well as the Bolitho Principle was not mentioned

21. Informed consent taken

In 3 cases Informed Consent was taken, out of which in one case Medical Negligence was proved. In remaining 7 cases the Informed Consent was not taken, out of which in 3 cases the Medical Negligence was proved.

22. Type of judgment

In 4 cases the Judgment was structured out of which in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved and in remaining 6 cases where the judgments were unstructured, in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved

23. Judicial Behaviour

In 4 cases the Judicial Behaviour was Editorship, meaning referred case laws, medical literature, witnesses and evidences, out of which in 2 cases Medical Negligence was proved. In remaining 6 cases the Judicial Behaviour was Authorship, meaning decision was given without referring the witness, Evidences, case laws or Medical Literature. Out of that 2 cases were found to be Negligent.

24. Specialty

The specialties involved in the cases under study at local level at Pune.

Out of 3 Neuro Surgery cases in 2, Medical Negligence was proved. In one cardiology case, Medical Negligence was proved Out of 2 Gynaecology cases, in one Medical Negligence was proved.

An overview of changing trends in a comprehensive manner is presented in the table as below:

Table No. 137

Overview of Changing Trends in the law of Medical Negligence

Factors	Pre CPA Trends	Post CPA Trends	Current Trends
Predominant legal principle	Tort law and Criminal Law	Tort law as aligned with the concept of deficiency and compensation	Delay due to multiple appeals, so new approach does not make much impact
Position of Medical professional	S/He was held with trust, high regard, infallible	S/He is doubted, shopping attitude, Commercialized relationship	Malpractice insurance increases cost in turn on patient
Pre eminence of expert opinion (Bolam Principle)	Yes	Partially present	Slowly changing, Discretion lies with the judge
Method of Judging	Editorship	Mixed between editorship and authorship	More towards authorship due to Bolitho principle
Deficiency	Not included in Negligence	Used interchangeably with negligence	Concept of informed consent is enforced with CPA
Logical Relevance of Expert opinion (Bolitho principle)	Not considered	Considered but not significant	The relevance is increasing with new cases
Position of Patient	Patient's rights limited to contractual and benevolent relationship	Multiple rights to patients predominantly as consumer. Penal liability is	Speed of remedy is slow, so no patient safe approach. So patients rights are unaddressed.

	between doctor and patient. Penal liability in serious cases	insignificant. Remedy is cheaper.	
Time Taken for judgment	Lengthy	Lengthy due to many appeals and pendency	Lengthy due to many factors
Approach to Compensation	Tort law approach based on extent of damage	Multiplier Method is applied	Patients demanding punitive approach like of US
Perception	Favourable to doctors, not sensitive to patient and only small number of patients approached court. 40 case at Supreme Court in 5 decade	High degree of proving negligence among medical professionals 36 % at National Commission 300 cases in 2 decades	Increase in cost of medical services and absence of uniform standards in medical profession. Comprehensive better mechanism is needed. Proper balancing of the professional integrity and patient safety is required.

6.5 Changing Trends in Professional approach

The image of medical professionals in India has veered from saint like saviours of life to demons by criticizing doctors for medical negligence and malpractice. Negligence claims clearly do have the potential to threaten the medical profession in a number of ways. They can expose doctors to external scrutiny by colleagues, media, the judiciary etc. harming their career prospects. It is very difficult for an Indian physician to accept that a negligence suit is now a professional hazard. At the onset of the suit the medical practitioner experiences intense anger because of the shock he experiences due to the break of the trust built up between him and the patient. He feels betrayed by his patient and the accusation of professional incompetence challenges the interior core of his professional integrity, resulting in anger and frustration. A medical negligence suit challenges the reputation, ego, self-esteem, and confidence of a physician. Mood swings, depression, and anxiety affect physicians, in turn affecting their personal and professional life.³³⁷

However, the Consumer Protection Act of 1986, which provides easy access to justice, has brought a legal revolution to India as a result of its cost-effective mechanisms and popular support. At the same time, these mechanisms pose a great legal challenge to the traditional courts which conduct litigation in orthodox ways. In this age of consumers, the regime of Indian consumer law will undoubtedly rule Indian markets and bestow a new phase on the existing Indian legal structure with its strong ancient legal foundations.³³⁸

Trends in Judicial Outcomes and Consequences for Health Care³³⁹

The last two decades have seen a phenomenal rise (compared to the earlier decades) in litigation concerning the health of individuals of communities and society at large. An obvious off shoot of these developments has been litigation concerning

³³⁷ Medico-Legal, Scientific Approach - Criminal Laws & Justice, www.legalserviceindia.com/medicolegal/medico.htm

³³⁸ A .Rajendra Prasad, Historical Evolution of Consumer Protection and Law in India, The Journal of Texas Consumer Law, www.jtexconsumerlaw.com/V11N3/JCCL_India.pdf

³³⁹ Mihir Desai & Kamayani Bali Mahabal, Healthcare Case Law in India, Report(2007); CEHAT Mumbai, pp.163

health care. However, before we see the recent trends it becomes crucial to look at the trends concerning health care in the first three decades after independence. Till the early 1980s, the judicial response to health related issues in India was essentially centred around cases of medical negligence or entitlements of employees under the Workmen's Compensation and ESI Acts. Apart from this, there were a few cases concerning drugs and other related issues. Under the welfares policies of the government many labour laws were enacted. Some of them dealt with health and health care. In the last 50 years, a majority of the decisions under these laws have been concerned with a very limited range of issues. Employees who suffer injury at the workplace are entitled to compensation. A large number of cases are around disputes about whether a disease or injury was acquired during the course of employment or not. The second type of controversy has been around whether a particular employer or employee falls within the mandate of the Acts under which protection is sought. The third major area of dispute has been the quantum of compensation to which an employee would be entitled. In recent times the courts have played a more proactive role and have laid down strict conditions of health and safety for the workmen like it was done by the Supreme Court in the case of asbestos manufacturing industry.

But it must be borne in mind that there are a relatively smaller numbers of employees governed by health care legislation in the private sector. Besides, in recent times the attitude of the courts towards these employees has not been very positive. For instance, recently the Supreme Court held that a casual workman is not covered under the Workman's Compensation Act.

The second branches of litigation concerning employees are cases regarding government servants. A large number of these cases pertaining to the rights of government employees to reimbursement of medical expenses incurred in private health care sector. At around this time patients started approaching the courts in matters concerning medical negligence. They were required to file suits in the district courts, which were highly time consuming, expensive and in many cases resulted in failure. The law followed in these matters was the English common law (judge made law) concerning torts and more particularly negligence. Though the legal tools to fight against medical negligence have always been available, the procedural tools

were highly inadequate. So the cases were few. This situation changed dramatically from the mid 1980s with the passage of the Consumer Protection Act and a consequent decision of the Supreme Court that medical services (except those providing totally free medical services) were covered under the Act.³⁴⁰

On matters of negligence the development of litigation has been quite phenomenal. Of course, the legal principles on this issue remain the same as they were more than 50 years ago. It is necessary to show duty to take care; it is important Healthcare Case Law in India 163 Adv. Mihir Desai to point out the standard of care required; and, it is crucial to establish the linkage between negligence and injury. Even so, the courts have started utilizing some recently derived principles such as informed consent. On the other hand, the Supreme Court in recent times has whittled down criminal responsibility of doctors by holding that doctors could not be held criminally liable unless they are guilty of 'gross' negligence. Besides, police complaints cannot be filed without another doctor's opinion concerning negligence. Such opinions are very difficult to obtain. Although victims of medical negligence have the option of also approaching medical councils, their experience, with these Councils has, by and large, been negative. The general feeling is that medical councils are overprotective of doctors.³⁴¹

Drugs and Cosmetics Laws have been existence since before independence. Judicial decisions under these laws have been mainly in respect of licensing conditions and classification of various items as drugs. The courts have not often interfered with the strict licensing conditions concerning drug manufacture, storage and distribution. They have also given a broad definition to the term 'drug' preventing escape route for manufacturers from strict quality control. The next decade, will of course witness gruelling battles on drug patents. With product patents being now available coupled with strategic ever greening of patents by large pharma industries there are likely to be pitched legal battles between patient rights groups, state and the industry.³⁴²

In recent years there has also been a large amount of litigation concerning the right to practice medicines by people holding qualifications not recognized under the law.

³⁴⁰ Id; pp.163

³⁴¹ Id; pp.163

³⁴² Mihir Desai & Kamayani Bali Mahabal, Supra note 6

Since the 1980s with the rapid privatization of medical education many unaffiliated, unrecognized colleges have cropped up offering diplomas and degrees in branches of medicines not recognized under the law. Instances of these are electropathy and electro homeopathy. Gullible students take these courses paying high fees only to realize later that these qualifications have not been duly recognized by any authority. The courts have consistently refused to interfere in these matters and have disallowed such persons from practising medicine. However, the courts have acknowledged the power of State governments to recognize certain qualifications on their own merits. Courts have also come down heavily against cross practice in medicine.³⁴³

The 1990s saw litigation in two new branches of health care law. First has been in respect of the law concerning HIV/AIDS. Though as yet there has been no central law relating to this, the courts have intervened in matters concerning the rights of HIV positive persons especially in employment related laws and through the use of the right to life to include the right to live with human dignity. The development in this area of law has been very interesting. In the 1980s when there was little awareness about this issue, the courts were inclined to focus on protecting society from HIV positive persons. But in the 1990s with a growing understanding of the issue the courts have stepped in to protect the confidentiality of positive persons, prevent discrimination in employment and other aspects of life. In the next few years, we are likely to witness a proliferation of litigation concerning this branch of law, especially if the new law in the making rolls out.³⁴⁴

Similarly, after the enactment of the Organ Transplantation Act in the 1990s some amount of litigation emerged on the issue. The litigation till now has been around the issue of who can donate organs. But as cadaver transplantation becomes more popular, a plethora of issues under this law are likely to arise. Euthanasia is not recognized in India. However, debates have started on this issue and one can foresee some litigation on this controversial issue. Another area where perspectives have changed over a period concerns mental health. From treating mentally ill patients as those who deserve to be locked up and forgotten the perspective now is

³⁴³ Mihir Desai & Kamayani Bali Mahabal, *Supra* note

³⁴⁴ *Id.*; pp.163

much more sensitive and favourable to them. This is also reflected in the Disabilities Act passed in the 1990s. Earlier the law as well as litigation concerned rights vis a vis the mentally ill. Now it is increasingly tending to be a perspective of the rights of disabled persons. Even so, the main area of litigation in this branch has been around conditions of homes for the mentally ill and their confinement in prisons. However, with the passage of time and more awareness of the complexities of the problem courts are likely to be more frequently approached.³⁴⁵

Women's health as a separate subject was always recognized through various provisions in the Factories Act, laws concerning abortion and the Maternity Benefit Act. But the special importance of women's reproductive rights emerged in the 1980s after struggles of women's groups on the use of women as guinea pigs for testing contraceptives. The courts have been called upon to restrain such experiments. The courts have been approached for failure of sterilization operations but in these matters they have, by and large, refrained from interfering.

In the only case relating the Right to Food currently pending in the Supreme Court, (P. U. C. L. vs. State of W. B. & Ors.) the Court has been satisfied with giving certain directions so as to see that people do not die for the want of food. The Right to Food includes the Right to Health and Health-care and it is not merely the right to receive food in terms of minimum calories, but, it includes the Right to Adequate Food. The adequacy will then be measured by not only what is necessary for survival, but by a person's health or by his ability to pursue a normal active existence. The concept of adequate food for the maintenance of health, not only requires a minimum calorific intake but also a certain balance of nutrients. The Right to Food should be understood together with a range of other rights – access to health care, medical facilities, drinking water and sanitary facilities. Unfortunately, the Supreme Court has not yet laid down the inter-relationship between Right to Food and Right to Health. Public Interest Litigation, Fundamental Right and its Consequences.³⁴⁶

Two developments in the 1980s led to a marked increase in health related litigation. First was the establishment of consumer courts making the suing of doctors and

³⁴⁵ Id;pp.163

³⁴⁶ Id;pp.163

hospitals for medical negligence and deficiency in service easier and cheaper. Second was the growth of public interest litigation, an expanded interpretation of the Right to Life as a fundamental right and one of its off shoots being the recognition of health and health care as a fundamental right. The public interest litigation movement in India began in late 1970s. Its foundation is the enforcement of fundamental rights guaranteed under the Constitution of India. Any citizen could trigger off the judicial mechanism by claiming a violation of Fundamental Rights, either of himself or of other individuals or of the citizenry at large. Fundamental Rights existed even before the late 1970s. The real push for the PIL movement came from an expanded interpretation of the Fundamental Right to Life which is enshrined in Article 21 of the Constitution. This reads:

No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except through procedure established by law.

Till the 1970s, by and large, the courts had interpreted 'life' literally i.e. right to exist. The late 1970s onwards an expanded meaning started to be given to the word 'life'. Over the years it has come to be accepted that life does not only mean merely animal existence but the life of a dignified human being with all its concomitant attributes. This has been interpreted to include a healthy environment and effective health care facilities. As we have seen in earlier Chapters to begin with, the right to health as a fundamental right grew as an off shoot of environmental litigation. Pollution free environment as a fundamental right presupposes the right to health as a Fundamental Right. Logically, the explicit recognition of the fundamental right to health should have preceded the fundamental right to good environment. However, the development of jurisprudence in this branch has been the reverse. To begin with, the right to decent environment was recognised and from that followed the right to public health, health and health care. Even while dealing directly with the right to health, the first issues concerned employees' health within a work place.³⁴⁷

It was only in 1991, in *C.E.S.C. Ltd. vs. Subhash Chandra*³⁴⁸ that the Supreme Court placed reliance on international instruments and declared that the right to health was

³⁴⁷ Mihir Desai & Kamayani Bali Mahabal, *Supra* note 6

³⁴⁸ AIR 1992 SC 573

a fundamental right. The question however remains whether a particular right is a positive or a negative right. A negative right is one which does not require the State to take any positive steps for its realization but only needs the State to ensure that no actions are taken that deprive the person of the right. For instance, a negative right to health would mean that the state should ensure that there is no pollution or that the drugs supplied by companies are of good quality. On the other hand, a positive right would mean that the State should build hospitals, ensure provision of drugs at cheap rates, etc. While the Supreme Court has on occasion implicitly held that the right to health was a positive right, on most occasions its treatment has been as a negative right.

In *Vincent Panikurlangara vs. Union of India*³⁴⁹, the Supreme Court observed “In a welfare State, therefore, it is the obligation of the State to ensure the creation and the sustaining of conditions congenial to good health.” Because of having recognized that right to health and health care as a fundamental right what follows? Fundamental rights are generally available only against the state. They prescribe the obligations of the State. In a poverty ridden country like India, does it mean that the State must provide free medical health care facilities to all? In a situation where there is increasing privatization of the health care systems, where the proportional annual budget for health is shrinking, where the cost of health education is growing exponentially this seems very unlikely. No court has yet said that the State is bound to provide free medical care to all the citizens. This would be the consequence if the right to health care was recognized as a positive right. The other aspect would, of course, be the quality of health care provided by the State. Infrastructure does not just comprise primary health care centres but even in government run hospitals in metropolitan cities service is crumbling. These institutions are plagued by a lack of enough beds, sufficient medicines and other similar problems. The Courts including the Supreme Court have not adequately dealt with this aspect. They have mainly been concerned with pious declarations of health being a fundamental right and peripheral and not so peripheral issues such as the rights of government employees to be treated in government hospitals, emergency medical care and the like. Even in respect of emergency health care, the private sector has not yet come within the sweep of the Courts. In the case of *Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samiti vs. State of*

³⁴⁹ AIR 1987 SC 990, (1987) 2 SCC 165

W.B.³⁵⁰ the Supreme Court observed that providing adequate medical facilities was an essential part of the obligation undertaken by the State in a welfare state. And failure on the part of a government hospital to provide timely medical treatment to a person in need of such treatment results in the violation of his right to life guaranteed under Article 21. Although the responsibility of the State and government hospitals is well provided by a radical interpretation of the Constitution, there is no definite corresponding legal duty imposed on private hospitals and practitioners to treat emergency cases. The judgments mainly focus on the duty of the State and the government hospitals. Of course, in respect of medico legal cases, the Supreme Court has held that doctors are obliged to treat medico legal patients in without insisting on prior paper work in both private and public sector.³⁵¹

The Supreme Court and the high courts have been intervening in a much more active manner in the last few years on the issue of healthcare. However, these courts are required to look into the issues of patents and drug price control also as the private obligations in public interest, in order to create real impact. As in the case of education, private sector should be held accountable in the area of healthcare with universal coverage for poor masses. Meanwhile public sector healthcare system also should improve since healthcare has deeper socio-political and economic significance.

The judiciary will be vexed with the task of elaborating the right to healthcare and spell out the joint and several obligations of state and private sector healthcare providers.³⁵²

As a human right, health is a social, economic and political issue adversely affected by inequity and poverty. Current scenario has urban bias and regional imbalances. Health expenditures are declining. Thus, the existing system requires reconstruction especially due to the dearth of a comprehensive legislative framework on national health policy..Such a comprehensive legislation should create conditions conducive to restoring balance in the health sector. It should be further sustained by making it enforceable as a fundamental 'Right to Health Care'. Universal Access to Health

³⁵⁰ (1996)4 SCC 37

³⁵¹ Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samiti vs. State of W.B; Supra Note 17

³⁵² Id.

Care will require further restructuring of health finance and the introduction of universal coverage of health care.³⁵³

Recent Judicial Trends in Medical Negligence³⁵⁴

In *A.S.Mittal v. State of UP*,³⁵⁵ an irreparable damage was done to the eyes of some of the patients who were operated at an eye camp organized by the government of Uttar Pradesh. Some of the patients who underwent surgery could never see the light of the day, i.e. whatever little vision they had even that was lost. The apex court coming heavily on the erring doctors held that, “the law recognizes the dangers which are inherent in surgical operations and that will occur on occasions despite the exercise of reasonable skill and care but a mistake by a medical practitioner which no reasonably competent and a careful practitioner would have committed is a negligent one.” The compensation was awarded. Most important contribution of this decision is that even though service rendered free of charge does not come under the purview of the Consumer Protection Act yet the court went a step ahead in recognizing that although no direct charges were paid by the patients but the State had paid on behalf of the patients to the doctors engaged in the free eye camp. But the Punjab State Commission did not give relief to the complainant who has undergone sterilization operation in the Punjab Government Hospital free of charges and became pregnant subsequently and gave birth to a child. The State Commission was of the view that the complainant was not a consumer because services offered were free of charge.³⁵⁶

Further, in *State of Haryana v. Santra*,³⁵⁷ the court upheld the decree awarding damages for medical negligence on account of the lady having given birth to an unwanted child due to failure of sterilization operation because it was found on facts that the doctor had operated only the right fallopian tube and had left the left fallopian

³⁵³ See, Policy Brief-Moving towards Right to Health Care, published by CEHAT 2005 available at www.cehat.org

³⁵⁴ Rajivkumar Khare, LAW OF TORTS, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND CONSUMER PROTECTION, 2010 pp.37

³⁵⁵ AIR 1989 SC 1570

³⁵⁶ See, *Paramjit Kaur v. State of Punjab*, III (1997) CPJ 394 (Punjab SCDRC)

³⁵⁷ (2000) 5 SCC 182

tube untouched. The patient was informed that the operation was successful and was assured that she would not conceive a child in future. A case of medical negligence was found and a decree for compensation in tort was held justified. However, the apex court has explained in *State of Punjab v. Shiv Ram*³⁵⁸, that “merely because a woman having undergone a sterilization operation becoming pregnant and delivering a child thereafter, the operating surgeon or his employer cannot be held liable on account of the unwarranted pregnancy or unwanted child. Failure due to natural causes, no method of sterilization being fool proof or guaranteeing 100% success, would not provide any ground for a claim of compensation.” The court after referring to several books on Gynecology and empirical researches concluded that „authoritative text books on gynecology and empirical researches recognize the failure rate of 0.3% to 7% depending on the technique chosen out of several recognized and accepted ones.”

Facts of *Achutrao Hari Bhau Khodwa v. State of Maharashtra*³⁵⁹, bring a different kind of negligence exhibited by the doctors. In this case it was alleged that a mop was left in the body of the patient which resulted in the formation of pus and eventually leading to her death. The court held that the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur* is clearly applicable and the State is liable to pay compensation for the negligence of the doctors. *Poonam Verma v. Ashwin Patel*³⁶⁰, reflects yet another reckless act on part of the doctor. In this case a doctor who was registered as a medical practitioner and was entitled to *practice in homoeopathy* was found to be guilty of negligence for prescribing allopathic medicines resulting in the death of the patient. The doctor was grossly negligent and in clear breach of duty as a doctor. He defied all sense of logic and forgot his ethics. It is submitted that it would have been better had the doctor been prosecuted under criminal negligence as he violated section 15(3) of the Medical Council Act, 1956. His conduct also amounts to actionable negligence for having failed to take due care as indicated in earlier Supreme Court decision in *Dr. Laxman Joshi* case³⁶¹. The claim of the appellant was decreed as against the defendant for Rs. 3,00,000/-. After more than a decade of the decision in *Poonam*

³⁵⁸ (2005) 7 SC 1

³⁵⁹ AIR 1996 SC 2377

³⁶⁰ AIR 1996 SC 2111

³⁶¹ AIR 1969 SC 128

Verma case,³⁶² another matter came before the National Commission in *Prof. P. N. Thakur & Anr. vs. Hans Charitable Hosp. & Ors.*³⁶³ Wherein allopathic treatment was given by non-medical practitioner *specialized in Unani System*. The patient suffered from fever and repeated bleeding from nose which resulted in rigors in patient as a result of which his condition deteriorated. A small nasal pack was placed anteriorly. The patient died due to choking of air passage. No efforts were made to clear blocked airways by the doctor as he did not appreciate properly the course of action to be followed in such case. The Opposite Party, i.e. the Hospital was held liable for allowing unqualified person treat complicated and emergency cases.

In certain cases, it is seen that the complainants have requested the relief which is not given under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. In such cases, the courts/forums have refrained to award remedies so claimed. For example, in *Parmod Grover & Ors. v. Manvinder Kaur (Dr.) & Ors.*,³⁶⁴ complications during pregnancy resulted in death of the patient. The complainant alleged medical negligence and claimed *relief in the form of permanently restraining and debarring Opposite Parties from practicing medical profession and cancellation of their medical certificates*. The relief was denied to the complainant as, according to the court, it cannot be granted under section 14 of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. Similarly direction regarding closure of OP nursing home was also not allowed under section 14 of CPA with a direction that the complainant is at liberty to approach civil court.³⁶⁵

*Indian Medical Association v. V.P. Shantha*³⁶⁶ is considered to be the landmark judgment as it has not only widened the ambit of the Consumer Protection Act by stating that the *Medical practitioners are not immune from a claim for damages on the ground of negligence* but also have issued several directions of immense significance for ensuring welfare of the consumers. In *Kishori Lal v. E.S.I Corporation*¹⁰⁸, the appellant was insured with the ESI Corporation and deductions were made from his salary by the employer and deposited with the ESI Corpn. The appellant's wife was admitted in ESI dispensary at Sonapat for treatment of diabetes, where her condition deteriorated and who later was examined in a private

³⁶² Supra note-103

³⁶³ II (2007) CPJ 340 (NC)

³⁶⁴ II (2007) CPJ 63 (NC)

³⁶⁵ Id.21

³⁶⁶ II (2007) CPJ 25 (SC) 41

hospital. There it was found that she was wrongly diagnosed at ESI dispensary. The appellant alleging deficiency in service filed a complaint under CPA. The Supreme Court in revision petition held that „services rendered by medical practitioners of hospitals / nursing homes run by ESI Corporation cannot be regarded as service rendered free of charge since sections 39 and 42 of the ESI Act contemplate contributions from both the employer and the employee, which can be deemed to be fee for the service. Thus wife of the complainant was considered to be the consumer under the CPA.

Some of the directions include: (i) a medical insurance policy -beneficiary of the service for which payment has been made by the insurance company - consumer. (ii) the relationship between the doctor and a patient carries with it certain degree of mutual confidence and trust and therefore the services of personal nature but no relationship of master and servant contract between them cannot be treated as a “contract of personal service” but a “contract for services.” (iii) The three categories: (a) Where services are free of charge to everybody - Doctors and hospitals are outside the purview of “service” under Act; (b) Where charges are required to be paid by everybody- Doctors and hospitals would clearly fall within the ambit of “service”. (c) Where charges are required to be paid by persons availing the services but certain categories of persons who cannot afford to pay are rendered service free of charge. Doctors and hospitals would fall within the ambit of the expression “service”; persons who are rendered free service are the “beneficiaries” and as such come within the definition of “Consumer”. (iv) In complaints involving complicated issues requiring recording of evidence of experts, the complainant can be asked to approach the Civil Court for appropriate relief as provided under Section 3 of the Act. (v) Where the deficiency in service is due to the obvious faults such as removal of the wrong limb or the performance of the operation on a wrong patient or giving injection of a drug to which the patient is allergic without looking into the outpatient card containing the warning or use of wrong gas during the course of an anesthetic or leaving inside the patient swabs or other items of operating equipment after the surgery, such cases can be disposed of by the consumer courts.³⁶⁷

³⁶⁷ Id. 21

In one of the most recent decision in *Kusum Sharma v. Batra Hospital*³⁶⁸, the Hon^{ble} Supreme Court has settled the law relating medical negligence. Mr. Dalveer Bandari, J., scrutinizing the cases of medical negligence both in India and abroad specially that of the United Kingdom has laid down certain basic principles to be kept in view while deciding the cases of medical negligence. According to the court, „while deciding whether the medical professional is guilty of medical negligence „*the following well-known principles must be kept in view:*³⁶⁹

- Negligence is the breach of a duty exercised by omission to do something which a reasonable man, guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulate the conduct of human affairs, would do, or doing something which a prudent and reasonable man would not do.
- Negligence is an essential ingredient of the offence. The negligence to be established by prosecution must be culpable or gross and not the negligence based upon the error of judgment.
- The medical professional is expected to bring a reasonable degree of skill and knowledge and must exercise a reasonable degree of care. Neither very highest nor a very low degree of care and competence judged in the light of the particular circumstances of each case is what the law requires.
- A medical practitioner would be liable only where his conduct fell below that of the standards of a reasonably competent practitioner in his field.
- In the realm of diagnosis and treatment there is scope for genuine difference of opinion and one professional doctor is clearly not negligent merely because his conclusion differs from that of the other professional doctor.
- The medical professional is often called upon to adopt a procedure which involves higher element of risk, but which he honestly believes as providing greater chances of success for the patient rather than a procedure involving lesser risk but higher chances of failure. Just because a professional looking to the gravity of illness has taken higher element of risk to redeem the patient out of his/her suffering which did not yield the desired result may not amount to negligence.

³⁶⁸ (2010) 3 SCC 480

³⁶⁹ Id. Para 89

- Negligence cannot be attributed to a doctor so long as he performs his duties with reasonable skill and competence. Merely because the doctor chooses one course of action in preference to the other one available, he would not be liable if the course of action chosen by him was acceptable to the medical profession.
- It would not be conducive to the efficiency of the medical profession if no doctor could administer medicine without a halter round his neck.
- It is our bounden duty and obligation of the civil society to ensure that medical professionals are not unnecessarily harassed or humiliated so that they can perform their professional duties without fear and apprehension.
- The medical practitioners at times have to be saved from such a class of complainants which use criminal process as a tool for pressurizing the medical professionals/hospitals, particularly private hospitals or clinics for extracting uncalled for compensation. Such malicious proceedings deserve to be discarded against the medical practitioners.
- The medical professionals are entitled to get protection so long as they perform their duties with reasonable skill and competence and in the interest of the patients. The interest and welfare of the patients have to be paramount for the medical professionals.

The court did not rest the case here, i.e. by laying down eleven principles for determining the breach of duty by medical professionals/hospitals, but went a step ahead by observing that, *“In our considered view, the aforementioned principles must be kept in view while deciding the cases of medical negligence.”* The court further adds a word of caution by stating that, *“We should not be understood to have held that doctors can never be prosecuted for medical negligence. As long as the doctors have performed their duties and exercised an ordinary degree of professional skill and competence, they cannot be held guilty of medical negligence. It is imperative that the doctors must be able to perform their professional duty with free mind.”*³⁷⁰

Article 141 reads: *“Law declared by the Supreme Court shall be binding on all courts within the territory of India”.*

³⁷⁰ Supra note 94, para 90

The above listing of „basic principles“ with a direction that „they must be kept in view while deciding the cases of medical negligence“ reflects the judicial attitude of the honorable apex court. It may be noted that any decision, judgment passed by the Supreme Court becomes law of the land and is automatically binding on all other lower courts in the country by virtue of Article 141 of the Constitution of India.³⁷¹ Thus the above principles must be taken as „*law of the land on medical negligence*“. On one hand, these principles provide adequate protection to the doctors and hospitals provided they have exercised a „reasonable degree of care which is neither the highest nor a very low degree of care and competence judged in the light of the particular circumstances of each case.“ They give free hand to the doctors to choose from various available alternate courses of treatment/diagnosis, the best course of action which is in the interest and well-being of the patient (consumer). On the other hand, they did provide that „the medical practitioner would be liable only where his conduct fell below of the standards of a reasonably competent practitioner“. Also the decision is progressive in nature as it provides a safety-net to the medical professionals against unnecessary harassment and humiliation which will allow them to perform their duties without fear and apprehensions and would save them from undue pressure for extracting uncalled for compensation. Ultimately the doctors are not the insurers of life. Error in judgment in prescribing treatment so long as it is within the prescribed medical standards should not incur unnecessary liability to the doctor/hospital. This decision would benefit both the parties, i.e. the doctors/hospitals shall not be put to unnecessary harassment and at the same time any casual, careless or negligent performance of professional duty on their part shall definitely hold them liable in negligence. The judgment is likely to ensure welfare of consumers.³⁷²

6.5 Implications for the Future:

Public awareness of medical negligence in India is growing. The lucky doctors of past were treated like God and people revered and respected them. With the speed and influence of commercialization and globalization on all spheres of life, even the medical profession has witnessed many ethical and legal challenges in practice.

³⁷¹ Id. para

³⁷² Supra note 94

Doctor-patient relationship has undergone swift and adverse changes fuelled by factors such as commercialization of medical practice, ignorance towards medical ethics, zero tolerance and high expectation of patients and the inclusion of health care service within the ambit of Consumer Protection Act.

In the last decades, technical advances in medical field have meant a better quality of life. But it is sad to mention that there has not been a corresponding shift in the standard of medical profession. This article focuses on medical negligence and the Consumer Protection Act in India and its implication on whole of the medical profession.

More and more cases relating to medical negligence are being filed in India after the passing of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 but then this has also resulted in number of frivolous complaints against innocent doctors. Thus judging the negligence of doctors has become a technical issue. There is an urgent need for the transformation in the doctor-patient relationship to the advantage of patient, doctors and the society at large.

The doctor patient relationship is one of the most unique and privileged based on mutual trust and faith. But presently there is a great decline in the doctor patient relationship. The reason may be communication gap, commercialization of health service, raising expectation from doctors or increased consumer awareness.³⁷³

Concept of Medical Negligence

Negligence is the breach of duty caused by omission to do something which a reasonable and prudent person guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulates human affairs would do or doing something which a prudent and reasonable person guided by similar considerations would not do.^[1] But the dictionary meaning is 'Lack of Proper Care'. It means carelessness in a matter in which law mandates carefulness. In the law of negligence, professionals such as

³⁷³Preeti Singh, 2013, Medical Negligence and the Consumer Protection Act: Issues and Challenges, www.mightylaws.in/1100/medical-negligence-consumer-protection-act1. Last accessed on 28th April 2013

lawyers, doctors, architects and others are included in the category of persons professing some special skill or skilled persons generally.³⁷⁴

Any reasonable man entering into a profession which requires a particular level of learning to be called a professional of that branch impliedly assures the persons dealing with him that the skill which he professes shall be exercised with reasonable degree of care and caution.

Judged by this standard, a professional including medical professional may be held liable for negligence on one of two findings: either he was not possessed of the requisite

Preeti Singh, *Mighty Laws in Medical Negligence and the Consumer Protection issues and Challenges*, (march 27, 2013) skill which he professed to have possessed or he did not exercise, with reasonable competence in the given case, the skill which he did possess.³⁷⁵

Deficient system of remedies in cases of Medical Negligence³⁷⁶

After *VP Shantha's* case it was believed that by providing remedy through consumer forums, availing damages for the injury caused, would become easier for the patients to seek remedy for the wrong done to them. It was considered that this will deter the careless doctors and would thus help in improving the general standards of health services in India. However, the current scenario presents a complete different picture. The numbers of medical negligence suits have grown up by several times in the last 10 years. Considering the objects of COPRA to provide speedy, less expensive, more accessible and simple remedy, it would be difficult to conclude that the act has failed in achieving its goals.

The Complex Procedure for claiming Medical Negligence³⁷⁷

In every complaint of medical negligence the complainant is expected to furnish in the forms of exhibits certain documents to establish a prima facie case. However the

³⁷⁴Id.

³⁷⁵Supra note

³⁷⁶Indian Medical Association vs V.P. Shantha & Ors, 1996 AIR 550

³⁷⁷Id.

patients rarely have access to these medical documents and are generally not delivered to patients especially in cases where something goes wrong on pretext of confidentiality. Thus at this stage it becomes difficult for the patients to establish their case and many cases are dismissed summarily. The procedure that is followed afterwards is equally complex and unnecessarily lengthy involving submission of evidence, examination, cross examination of witnesses and other formalities.

Apart from these complexities the trickiest part is proving the negligence of doctor. The test applied for determining liability is the *Bolam* test, which apart from 'reasonable care' standard also validates the 'generally accepted practice' argument. Further there is very little scope for applicability of judicial mind and the direct bearing of this is that the law of medical negligence has not evolved and the principles applicable remain the same irrespective of the fact that medical negligence has progressed in leaps and bounds in this time.

Even the functioning of consumer courts has not been very commendable. This was admitted by Supreme Court in *Dr.J.J Merchant v. Shrinath Chaturvedi*³⁷⁸, where the PIL questioning the functioning of the consumer courts was filed and the Supreme Court commented that even after the enactment of the CPA, appropriate steps have not been taken by the government for ensuring that the National Commission or the State Forums can function properly. Also the consumer dispute redressal agencies have not been fast enough in disposing cases.

Medical Negligence beyond Compensation³⁷⁹

Merely providing of compensation is not enough to deal with the issue of medical negligence. What is required is a proper mechanism to check to check the cases of medical negligence. One cannot forget that the purpose of law is not just to punish a wrongful act and give remedy to the adversely affected party but also to ensure that such deeds are not repeated again. A complete consumer care system should include steps for prevention of such incidents.

There is lack of effective implementation of the act. The undecided cases have already crossed the statutory limit. The overall performance of judicial and quasi

³⁷⁸ III (2002) CPJ 8 (SC)

³⁷⁹ Id.

judicial bodies can be concluded in one sentence i.e. “*Justice delayed is justice denied*”. This shows that judiciary has not shown proper concern to cases of medical negligence filed under the CPA.

Though CPA covers broad area of consumer rights but it failed to define service in proper way and failed to give way out to medical negligence cases. Thus there is a strong need of separate act to regulate medical negligence cases and special separate courts for speedy as well as proper justice.

6.5.1 Is it amendment? Or New Act?

With the present study, it is found that there are many loopholes in the Act and the Implementation of the Act. At the same time the application of this act to the Medical Field has impacted doctor patient relationship and the social environment at large.

Impact of application of CPA to the medical field on the society in the form of increased Medical Negligence litigation is as due to following parameters

- Altered Doctor Patient relationship
- Commercialization and Consumerism
- Role of Media in raising awareness
- Declining Professional standards among Doctors
- Lack of good teachers
- Good students are not keen on Medicine
- Technological advancements in the Medical Field
- Lack of infrastructure and adverse doctor patient ratio.

So the real **impact on the medical profession** is that

- Change in the doctor patient relationship
- Increased practice of defensive medicine
- Rising cost of the treatment
- Loss to the students
- Deficiency in the number of specialists

Though medical professionals tend to blame the CPA for the deteriorating doctor patient relationship, they must introspect and acknowledge the other reasons which are connected to the standards and behaviour of doctors themselves. Medical professionals must realize that the trend of seeking legal intervention to resolve conflict will not subside if they do not change their mode of practice and correct the anomalies that have crept in to the medical profession.

The CPA has been beneficial to aggrieved patients, but it has also damaged medical practice in several ways. The main damage has been the loss of trust of the patients on their doctors. Without trust and faith, it is not possible to build a good doctor patient relationship which is central to successful treatment. Hopefully in the future both doctors and patients will realize the ultimate futility of doctor patient conflict and resolve their grievances amicably, relegating the CPA to the pages of history.³⁸⁰

6.5.2 Feasibility for the law reform

A new Act named as Patient Protection and Safety Act 2013 is suggested as an Act to provide better protection and safety of patients and for that purpose to make provision for the establishment of Medical Board, other authorities and system of Expert Medical Evidence for the settlement of patient's disputes and for matters connected there with.

It can exclusively work as Health Tribunal on the basis of limited Fault Based Administrative System and Quick Review Systems for Merit. It will ensure Speedy disposal. It will incorporate views of medical experts on the basis of Daubert's Criteria and evidence Based Practice of Medical Experts

Further, it will emphasise Patient Safety and quality, thus diffusing the current hostile environment in healthcare stakeholders. More details are provided among suggestions in the following chapter.

³⁸⁰ Tapas Kumar Kole, MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND THE LAW IN INDIA-DUTIES, RESPONSIBILITIES, RIGHTS(2010), pp.12

6.5.3. Regulations by professional community and Medical Council

The Medical Council of India (MCI) in an amendment to its existing code of conduct, the Indian Medical Council (professional conduct, etiquette and ethics) regulations 2002, has proposed sweeping guidelines on the relationship between the pharmaceutical industry and the medical profession in India.

The Code of Medical Ethics as described by the Medical Council of India in 2002, states that the medical professional should maintain good medical practice. Chapter 1.2.1 says that, the Principal objective of the medical profession is to render service to humanity with full respect for the dignity of profession and man. Physicians should merit the confidence of patients entrusted to their care, rendering to each a full measure of service and devotion. Physicians should try continuously to improve medical knowledge and skills and should make available to their patients and colleagues the benefits of their professional attainments. The physician should practice methods of healing founded on scientific basis and should not associate professionally with anyone who violates this principle. The honoured ideals of the medical profession imply that the responsibilities of the physician extend not only to individuals but also to society.³⁸¹

The inherent quality of any professional service depends on its ethical values as imbibed by its professionals.; Every profession has to zealously safeguard its autonomy, and at the same time take appropriate measures to extract professional accountability, in the event that the professional indulges in any kind of professional misconduct. The kind of assurance alone infuses confidence in the minds of the public. Therefore, in this respect, the professional bodies prescribe codes of ethical behaviour, which every professional is expected to adopt and comply with. This is how a professional body, in a democratic way, conceives, prescribes and enforces its code of ethics.³⁸²

In the present study, when the doctors and the hospital administrators were asked about,

³⁸¹ Code of Ethics Regulations, 2002, Medical Council of India, Chapter 1.2.1

³⁸² S.V.Joga Rao, LAW, MEDICAL ETHICS AND SYSTEMATIC FRAMEWORK : AN OVERVIEW - MEDICAL ETHICS, A READY REFERENCER, 1st Edition 2004, Legalaxy Publications Bangalore, pp. 37

Agreement with the following statement: Rather than the present coverage of doctors under Consumer Protection Act, it is the strict control of doctors' training by Medical Council of India and quality control by Accreditation bodies which is preferred. The doctors answered in the following way: 59 % of doctors and 61 % of hospital administrators, preferred strict control of doctor's training by Medical Council of India and regulation by that body while only 6.8 % of doctors and 12.2 % of hospital administrators said no to this concept and remaining were non-committal.

6.5.4 Exclusive Health Tribunals /Medical Boards

Since Medical field is a complex field and uncertainties are quite common, the issue of Medical Negligence should be settled by the authorities belonging to both Medical as well as legal field. This is to avoid the dilution of the legal system that judges the professionals and experts of the Medical Field, by having non experts as judges and use summary procedure or *res ipsa loquitur* as principle for judging the complicated issues of Medical Negligence.

The system of Health Tribunals and Medical Boards should be established

1. Basis of the system, "**Limited Fault based Administrative System**".
2. This being a three tier system, District Medical Boards and State Tribunals as well as National Tribunal needs to be setup.
3. Constitution of Medical Board: should have Medical Experts, legal experts, members of Medical Council and professional organizations
4. Constitution of State Tribunals: Medical Experts, legal experts, members of professional organization and State Medical Councils and retired high Court Judge to guide.
5. Constitution of National Tribunal: Medical Experts, legal experts, members of professional organizations and Medical Council of India, Retired Supreme Court Judge to guide
6. The duration of any Medical Negligence Case should be 90 days only.
7. Three phases for any case: Prehearing, Hearing and limited appellate hearing.
8. Prehearing Phase: Sorting out of the cases that are really cases of Medical Negligence.

9. Hearing Phase: To be heard by Board, expert witnesses to examined and Expert Evidence from registered Medical Experts should be obtained, hearing within 90 days.
10. Limited Appellate hearing: To avoid repetition and only to examine technical aspects again by superior tribunal, within 30 days of the appeal.
11. The decisions of National Health Tribunals should be final with no provision for appeal further. If patient feels aggrieved he should approach Civil Court separately if he wants.
12. There should be cap on compensation.

6.5.5 Review of Medical Curriculum

The Medical Practitioner is an important duty bearer who influences access to justice of the poor, disadvantaged and the vulnerable. 'A Medical Practitioner can no longer restrict himself to his traditional role of diagnoser of ailments, prescriber of pills and potions and exciser of lumps. His/her role now includes being an educator, counsellor, case finder and an agent of social change'. Dr.K Park.³⁸³

Medical Practitioners are one of the crucial neutral expert opinion makers in the Medico-legal cases. The unique Medical Practitioner-patient relationship built on an edifice of mutual trust and respect enables the Medical Practitioner to be privy to the truth regarding both the patient and the facts pertaining to the crime. Diligent clinical examination, appropriate documentation by the Medical Practitioner of the facts revealed by the patient and the findings elicited by him/her provides the scientific evidence. The court seeks the expert opinion of the Medical Practitioner in all Medico legal cases. Further, The Indian Medical Council Act, 1956 in Section 15(2) (C) states that no person other than a medical practitioner enrolled on a State Medical Register shall be entitled to give evidence at any inquest or in any court of law as an expert under section 45 of the Indian Evidence Act, 1872 on any matter relating to medicine. The Medical Practitioner being a neutral (neither a prosecution witness nor a defence witness) expert opinion maker is in a lofty position of having the opportunity to bring to the Court the truth related to the case.

³⁸³ Dr.K.Park,as mentioned in DRAFT FOR APPROVAL RESTRUCTURED MEDICO-LEGAL CURRICULUM FOR MBBS COURSE IN INDIA, 2007

Thus, the Medical Practitioner does play a pivotal role in aiding administration of justice in all Medico legal cases. In addition, the trusted position of the Medical Practitioner in the society enables him/her to counsel the patient and the family and offer appropriate guidance for the social, psychological and vocational rehabilitation of the patient.³⁸⁴

The opinion of most practicing Medical Practitioner and also medical students in the country is that they are ill equipped to handle this essential responsibility with the knowledge gained from the present design of the Undergraduate Medico Legal problems. Medico Legal Cases provides an unique opportunity for the Medical Practitioner to play the duty bearer's role effectively. In all Medico Legal Cases the Medical Practitioner is one of the key neutral experts giving scientific evidence. The unique Doctor-patient relationship built on an edifice of mutual trust and respect enables the Medical Practitioner to be privy to the nearest truth regarding both the patient and the facts pertaining to the disputed issue. Diligent clinical examination, appropriate documentation by the Medical Practitioner of the facts revealed by the patient and the findings elicited by him/her provides the scientific evidence. 385

Thus, the Medical Practitioner does play a pivotal role in aiding administration of justice in all Medico legal cases. In addition, the trusted position of the Medical Practitioner in the society enables him/her to counsel the patient and the family and offer appropriate guidance for the social, psychological and vocational rehabilitation of the patient. Thus the Medical Practitioner is an enabler of access to justice. As Harrison said "No greater opportunity, responsibility or obligation can fall to a lot of a human being than to become a physician. In the care of the suffering he/she needs technical skill, scientific knowledge and human understanding. He/ She who uses this with courage, humility and with wisdom will provide a unique service for his fellow men and will build an enduring edifice of character within him/herself. The physician should ask for his/her destiny no more than this; he/she should be content with no less."³⁸⁶

³⁸⁴ Final Draft – Restructured Medico Legal Curriculum for MBBS Course, 2007, http://www.svym.org/assets/pdf/Medico_Legal_curriculum_for_MBBS_course.pdf Accessed on 28 April 2013

³⁸⁵ Id.

³⁸⁶ Id.

One of the key neutral experts giving scientific evidence. The unique Doctor-patient relationship built on an edifice of mutual trust and respect enables the Medical Practitioner to be privy to the nearest truth regarding both the patient and the facts pertaining to the disputed issue. Diligent clinical examination, appropriate documentation by the Medical Practitioner of the facts revealed by the patient and the findings elicited by him/her

6.5.6 Assistance and Awareness Generation required among doctors and other stakeholders

The empirical data as extracted below shows the need for the same.

Amongst Doctors

80.1 % of the doctors and 92.7 % Hospital Administrators were aware of the existence of Consumer Protection Act against Medical Negligence.

72.1 % of the doctors and 73.2 % of the Hospital Administrators correctly identified the meaning of Medical Negligence while others were confused with all other answers

68.9 % of the doctors and 58.5 % of the Hospital Administrators correctly identified the Components of Medical Negligence while others were confused with all other answers.

The participants of the survey were confused over the knowledge of available defences to a doctor in Medical Negligence case. 63.4 % hospital administrators and 22 % of the doctors were aware of the defences available while all others are not aware.

65.6 % of Doctors and 26.8 % of the hospital administrators are insured under Professional Indemnity Insurance.

73.5 % doctors and 73.2 % hospital administrators knew the details of Professional Indemnity Insurance. Remaining participants opted for other options.

The opinion about the knowledge of terms and conditions of Insurance Company was divided in both the groups, doctors and Hospital Administrators. Only 28.1 % of the Doctors and 26.8 % of Hospital Administrators knew the terms and conditions of Insurance Company, in relation to Indemnity Insurance.

40.5 % of doctors and 85.4 % of hospital administrators are aware of the regulations for doctors by the Medical Council of India. It is shocking finding that 60 % of the doctors are not aware of these regulations!

Only 12.9 % doctors and 53.7 % of Hospital Administrators are aware of the amendment of Medical Council of India regulations, remaining are not aware

Amongst Community

54.9 % of the respondents know that anybody having any grievance against a doctor or hospital can file a case against doctors in Consumer Courts.

34.1 % said they are not aware of this. 11 % preferred to remain silent on this.

Based on the study findings:

1. Awareness generation is needed among doctors about the law of Medical Negligence and its practical implications.
2. Awareness generation among the community about the patient Rights and Responsibility
3. Knowledge dissipation about good doctor patient relationship, legal aspects of doctor patient relationship.
4. The community should be aware about the limitations of medical science due to uncertainty beyond human control.
5. Efforts to reduce the enmity between the doctors and the society should be done at national level
6. The information about the new Act, The patient Protection and Safety Act, should be passed on to the community and continuous education programs should be organized for community.

Next chapter summarises the findings, conclusions and offers suggestions for reform.

Chapter 7

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In matters of truth and justice, there is no difference in large and small problems, for issues concerning the treatment of people are all the same.

Albert Einstein

Diagram represents the whole scheme of legal approach to medical negligence. It captures different remedies predominantly based on fault liability; hence there an alternative approach is required

Figure 7

7.1. Summary

This research has elaborated the legal treatment of Medical Negligence in the last few decades in India and in the light of international developments. It develops concepts of Medical Negligence and Consumer protection. Further it examines their inter linkage in the wake of CPA. The medical professionals and hospitals are held accountable under multiple laws and MCI regulations. The burden of proof lies on the patient. However there are factors of high standard mitigating the link between medical advice and damage suffered by patients' attitude such as unscientific beliefs, alternative medicines, avoiding taking medicines etc.³⁸⁷

Medical professionals those who are aware of law can take care. Ignorance of Law is not an excuse in Medical practice. Even before entering into medical profession every medical person should know the law that directly or indirectly regulates their profession. A duly qualified medical professional, i.e. a doctor has a right to seek to practice medicine, surgery and dentistry by registering himself with the Medical Council of the State of which he is a resident, by following the procedure as prescribed under the Medical Act of the State. Duties and obligations of doctors are enlisted in ordinary laws of the land and various Codes of Medical Ethics and Declarations both at national and international level.³⁸⁸

Professional negligence is defined as the breach of a duty caused by the omission to do something which a reasonable man guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulate the conduct of human affairs would do or doing something which a prudent and reasonable man would not do. Medical negligence or malpractice is defined as lack of reasonable care and skill or wilful negligence on the part of a doctor in the treatment of a patient whereby the health or life of a patient is endangered. Professional indemnity insurance cover became available for Doctors and Medical establishments only recently, i.e. from December, 1991.³⁸⁹

The Medical profession has reached new horizons, facing many ethical and legal challenges in the practice of the profession. Doctor-Patient relationship is changing swiftly and adversely. The patient, who in earlier days had full faith in his treating

³⁸⁷ S.Ramesh ,S.V.S.S.Sita Rama Lakshmi , MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE-- WHAT IT IS AND HOW TO AVOID IT? <http://www.iameconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

³⁸⁸ *Id.*

³⁸⁹ *Id.*

doctor, now suspects negligence as a cause of his sufferings. Commercialization of modern medical practice, ignorance towards medical ethics, zero tolerance and high expectation of patients, inclusion of health care services within the ambit of Consumer Protection Act have ultimately created such a vicious circle which is manifesting as an ever increasing incidence of litigation against the doctors and hospitals. No doctor can afford to remain ignorant to the Ghost named “Medical Negligence or Malpractice”.

A patient approaching a doctor/hospital expects the best medical treatment available at any corner of the globe and in case the results are not favourable, considers medical negligence as the sole culprit. On the contrary, actual status regarding medical negligence is clear from various leading judgments on medical negligence. Doctors have legal duties to comply with, in their daily practice. Ignorance of law will be detrimental to the practitioners even if they are treating the patient in good faith. Recently there has been a shift from “BOLOM” to “BOLITHO” in deciding the ‘Standard of Care’ expected from doctors. It is imperative that doctors from all the specialties must have a continuing medico-legal education. This project aimed at giving an insight into the meaning, scope and legal interpretation of the term “Medical Negligence”. Medico-legal issues emerging from landmark judgments on medical negligence have also be discussed.³⁹⁰

The term consent means voluntary agreement, compliance, or permission. The Section 13 of Indian Contract Act lays down that two or more persons are set to consent when they agree upon the same thing in the same sense at the same time (meeting of the mind).It can be implied or express. Sections 87 to 93 of IPC deal with various aspects of consent. The commoner, implied consent is not written, provided by demeanour of the patient is legally effective and implies up to clinical examination. The commoner, implied consent is not written, provided by demeanour of the patient is legally effective and implies up to clinical examination. The express consent can be oral or written. In India, a person of age 12 years or above can give consent for medical examination and treatment, except for surgical interventions in which case it is 18 years (Sec.87 I.P.C.). Doctor has to examine or treat any patient

³⁹⁰ Dr.V.P.Singh, *MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE- IT'S MEANING, SCOPE AND LEGAL INTERPRETATION?* <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

after obtaining his consent but in a traumatized, unconscious patient doctor can examine and treat the patient to save his life without obtaining consent but should not go beyond saving life. In all other circumstances, a properly taken consent forms an effective shield against future litigations.³⁹¹

The changing face of the doctor patient relationship has once again brought forth the importance of consent in medical practice. Due to the phenomenal increase in the number of negligence suits against the medical personnel as a result of partial or lack of consent in present world, it has once again become imperative to understand the legal issues and their implications along with the remedies to safeguard the medical professional. The impetus in the present scenario is on informed consent and greater stress is being paid on the patient autonomy in making decisions regarding the treatment options available. It is important to take a valid consent, considering the competence, understanding and voluntariness of the patient and disclosing all information that will help the patient in judging the facts and coming to a reasonable conclusion. Failure of obtaining express written consent can lead to various legal issues like suits for physical assault, indecent assault and negligence. The suits of negligence were being judged against the prescribed standards of care of the medical profession by taking evidence of medical men of repute, though recently the judgments have not considered the doctors opinion in deciding certain cases of negligence emphasizing on the changing trends in the judiciary and the increasing need of the doctors to protect them legally.

Here in this project it is emphasized and elaborated upon the various aspects of consent and its interpretation by the Indian legal system in the present scenario by illustrating some recent judgments.³⁹²

Article 21 of the constitution says “No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law.” The new interpretation of

³⁹¹ Munish Sharma, Adarsh Kumar, Ashish Jain, *CONSENT AS DEFENCE IN MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE* ; <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

³⁹² Mohit Gupta, Mamta Panwar, Manish Kumath, *CONSENT- RECENT INTERPRETATION BY THE INDIAN LEGAL SYSTEM*, <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

Article 21 has ushered a new era of expansion of the horizons of right to life and personal liberty. The right to life enshrined in this Article includes right to health, and the right to live with dignity. No one can violate the right to life. If anybody including a medical professional causes harm and injury to any person without his consent, he commits a criminal wrong giving rise to criminal liability. A doctor can be tried under Section 304-A of the Indian Penal Code, for causing death by a negligent act. The foremost pre-requisite of liability in criminal cases is the presence of a guilty mind (*mens rea*). Therefore, before a person is punished for an act done by him, it is imperative to test the mental attitude of the doer so as to determine whether the intention was to do harm to the other person or not. Thus, the mental stance of the medical practitioner will have to concur with the act before he can be tried under Section 304-A IPC. 'Bolam' test principle and Sections 87, 88, 89 & 92 of IPC provide immunity to the medical professionals. To conclude in view of various decisions of the Supreme Court, it is emphasized that doctors are covered generally under the civil liability and hence 304-A is not applicable for their negligent act except in cases where the damage and its 'amplitude' caused to the patient is so obvious "Res ipsa loquitor" (things speak for themselves) that no proof as to the negligent act of the doctor is required.³⁹³

The Hon'ble Supreme Court of India, has ruled that to prove a case of negligence against a professional, the degree of negligence required is much higher than that of ordinary cases. In cases wherein negligence against a medical professional is to be proved, the court shall presume the presence of the word "grossly" to be present before negligence. A professional can never guarantee a 100% success rate to his client. His only job is to ensure that he possesses the skill required by a professional, and wasn't exercising his skill without reasonable competence. Since the abovementioned rulings were brought to light in the case of *Dr. Jacob Mathew v. State of Punjab*, medical negligence claims have reduced greatly in number because of these margins provided by the courts. Also the judiciary faces criticism because people contend that with the relaxations provided, professionals tend to disregard

³⁹³ R.Balamurugan, P.Janaki, *A CRITICAL VIEW OF SECTION 304-A INDIAN PENAL CODE THROUGH 'MENS REA' WITH ARTICLE- 21 OF CONSTITUTION OF INDIA*, <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

the ethics they are expected to follow and tend to be a little more lax in their duties.³⁹⁴

One understands that there is a proliferation of human needs in respect of goods and services. The suppliers of goods and providers of services have to be careful and efficient in carrying out their business. It is noteworthy that the level of awareness among the people regarding consumer law is raising. In the light of this development, the litigation management becomes vital in the continuation and progress of every service. A new type of approach has been started in the litigation procedure with the enactment of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. The Act provides for setting up of quasi-judicial bodies vested with jurisdiction concurrently with the established courts for redressal of consumer disputes at the District, State and National levels. It aims at providing speedy and inexpensive justice to a class of litigants designated as consumers.

For this purpose the procedure prescribed is simple and free from technicalities. The Act imposes obligation on the service providers to render service without any 'deficiency'. The law seeks to improve the quality in all kinds of services. The quality is the hallmark of every service to sustain in the competitive market. The Consumer Courts expect that the element of 'negligence' should never be allowed to enter into the domain of professional services. At times, even with utmost care, injury takes place. It is very much essential to realize the importance of self regulation. The professional control bodies need to re-examine policy manuals and update them taking into account the exigencies of a modern state. It is always better to evolve meaningful dispute redressal procedures for consumer satisfaction. A satisfied consumer is the backbone of prosperity and strength of nation. The service provider should be comfortable with the prevalent legal system. No legal technicalities should come in the way of rendering service with spirited commitment.³⁹⁵

Medical Ethics which is a code of behavior imposed by the profession itself and voluntarily accepted by doctors. In any profession the moral obligation is embedded, but when it comes to medical profession this obligation tends to have a great

³⁹⁴ Madhav Misra, *IS THE INDIAN JUDICIARY RESPONSIBLE FOR DIMINISHING ETHICS AND INCREASE IN MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE?*, <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

³⁹⁵ Rajendrakumar Hittanagi, *THE ROLE OF CONSUMER COURTS IN MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE*, <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

importance as it is directly related public health. Today ethical issues and moral challenges have become an increasingly complex aspect of a medical profession. Medical ethics is not merely a moral code but also a legally sanctioned code of conduct acceptable and normal within the medical profession. This does not mean that morality or moral theories do not influence medical ethics, but instead it should be understood, and practiced from a rational standpoint as is prevalent within the profession at a given point of time. The code of medical ethics expressly states that doctors should be uninfluenced by motives of profit. This is because medical aid is a matter of service to humanity. Medical ethics is a set of moral principles which guides members of the medical profession in their dealings with others concerned. Medical ethics must be peevied as involving the moral maturation of medical professionals. Apart from the legislative control of the medical profession by the government there is yet another controlling mechanism upon medical practitioners. The basic objective of the medical profession is thus to serve the humanity with full respect and dignity of a man due to this obligation western developed countries have invoked mouldered lens of judicial response for fully providing safeguards to protect the interests of patients. Finally the researcher would like to explore the Medical profession is a noble profession. There should be high moral quality medical ethics to medical practitioner, that during medical treatment they should be fair and concentrate. Present research deals with a legal viewpoint of medical ethics with special reference to medical negligence.³⁹⁶

To examine the recent developments in medical negligence in the light of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. The landmark judgment of the Supreme Court in the case of *I.M.A v. V.P. Shantha* brought the services rendered by doctors within the ambit of the CPA, 1986. This transformed the doctor-patient relationship into a contractual relationship wherein the doctor can be sued for a “deficiency” in service. However, government hospitals and doctors are exempt from liability under this act as they charge their services free of cost. This distinction highlights the transformation of the doctor- patient relationship which was primarily based on trust into a commercial relationship. The research question addressed in the paper is,

³⁹⁶ Pradeep Kumar, *MEDICAL ETHICS VIS-A-VIS MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE: A LEGAL VIEWPOINT*, <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

“Whether the inclusion of Medical Practitioners within the ambit of the CPA, 1986 has led to the commercialization of the Medical Profession”?³⁹⁷

A number of cases related from the National Consumer Redressal Commission and Supreme Court have been analyzed in this research. Also, a number of medical practitioners have been interviewed in order to gain the perspective of medical professionals on the issue. Also, the change in the attitude of the patients towards doctors, the increase in frivolous litigation, allegations of criminal medical negligence and other such issues have been touched upon by the researcher so as to analyze the changing trends in the doctor patient relationship.³⁹⁸

Yes, the inclusion of Medical Services under the CPA, 1986 has led to the commercialization of the medical profession. Trends like medical malpractice insurance among doctors clearly indicate the commercialization of the “Noble Profession” as the traditional notion of trust between doctors and patients has diminished.

The researcher has arrived at the conclusion that the consumer redressal forums have not been effective in dealing with the menace of medical negligence and thus, there is a need for reforms.³⁹⁹

The objective of this research was to examine the existing trends in the Supreme Court of India with regard to medical negligence and critically analyze the standard of care that is expected of medical practitioners in cases, both civil and criminal in nature. Up till now the courts in India have been applying the *Bolam* test. But a more progressive view was determined wherein the courts expect a standard of care that is higher than that expected in the *Bolam* Test. There are two landmark cases that deal with the two different lines of thought. The researcher has already explored the two lines of thought followed in two landmark judgments of the Indian Supreme Court namely the *Jacob Mathew Case* and *the Spring Meadows case*.

³⁹⁷ Namit Jain, Rayan Azmi, *CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT, 1986 AND MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE: COMMERCIALIZATION OF THE “NOBLE PROFESSION”*, <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

³⁹⁸ *Id.*

³⁹⁹ *Id.*

The method of research used by earlier researcher is doctrinal with the use of secondary sources while this researcher has used both online sources as well as books. From the research, the researchers have found that there is a weakening in the authority of the *Bolam* Test followed in many Indian cases including the Supreme Court case of *Jacob Mathew v. State of Punjab*. There is an existing line of thought that has faded over the years, which is echoed in the *Spring Meadows* Case wherein a higher standard of care was required. In this research, the researcher has attempted to bring out the differences in the two judgments and then determine the path forward in the field of medical litigation. The researcher has concluded that with increasing improvements in medical science, the standard of care that is expected of doctors has also increased. There is a higher expectation of the doctors and consequently the reasonable standard of care seems inadequate; a higher standard of care is expected. This ushers a new era of medical litigation.⁴⁰⁰

Consumer Protection Act has adversely affected the medical community in many ways

- There is increase in enmity between doctors and patients

There is disturbed Doctor Patient Relationship

- Increase in the cases against doctors

There is gradual increase in the number of cases in last 3 decades at both Supreme Court and National Commission level. There is an upsurge of cases reaching the National Commission, from 2011 till today. So present study comprises of 45.7 % of cases from National Commission, decided after 2011. Fewer cases reached and decided at the Supreme Court when compared with the National Commission cases.

- Delays in deciding at all the levels in spite of being Quasi Judicial nature
(Average time 5 to 6 years)

⁴⁰⁰ J.Megha, Harshad Pathak, *MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE: THE EXPECTATION OF EXPERTISE*, <http://www.iamleconf.in/images/31/10.%20Medi%20Law.pdf>, Accessed on 28 April 2013

Table No. 138

National Commission Analysis	
YEAR	AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR JUDGEMENT in Years
1990-1994	2
1995-1999	4
2000-2004	5
2005-2009	7
2010-2013	6

Supreme Court Analysis	
YEAR	AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR JUDGEMENT in Years
Before 1990	2
1990-1994	1
1995-1999	4
2000-2004	3
2005-2009	3.5
2010-2013	5.5

As the tables and the graphs show,⁴⁰¹ the average time taken for judgment is gradually increasing.

Supreme Court it increased from 2 years before 1990 to 5.5 years in 2013.

In National Commission it increased from 2 years at 1990 to 6 years in 2013.

Thus the trend that research establishes the following

- The very purpose of fast Redressal of cases through CPA is being defeated though the Consumer case is supposed to be disposed within 6 months of time.

⁴⁰¹ Refer to Previous Chapter

- **It is shown how it disturbed Doctor Patient relationship due to Concept of Consumerism and Commercialization.**
- **Community Response** to survey so show how there is substantial patient satisfaction, although there is erosion of trust in doctors. Trend of second opinion seeking or “shopping” has increased. Commercialization is seen by majority. However, community justifies the inclusion of doctors in CPA. This is the indication that medical profession needs to look within.

Only 41.8 % of the respondents said they are satisfied with doctors service in general.

- **Because of fear of CPA, doctors have started practicing Defensive Medicine**
- The practice of defensive medicine, which may be positive or negative.

Positive Defensive Practice includes the following:

1. Advising costly and sophisticated tests
2. Prescription of Medicines that are often not required
3. Referral to other consultants and super specialists
4. Performing Caesarian section when not indicated
5. Prolonging the stay in the hospital
6. Insisting on frequent follow ups

Negative Defensive Practice includes:

1. Avoidance of high risk branches of medicine
2. Limiting practice hours
3. Limiting number of patients per day
4. Avoiding emergency and high risk cases
5. Avoiding high risk procedures

6. Change of profession

7. Early retirement from practice

- **In the view of the above, it is concluded that Application of CPA to medical profession, requires to be reviewed for abolition.**
- **It should be replaced by a separate Act applicable to Medical profession which may deal with patients as patients and not as consumers.**

Mainly delinking the medical liability from Consumerism is needed.

7.2. Findings

To the first Research question on locating the Concept of Medical Negligence has been defined under various laws in India and Abroad, certain landmark cases have been analyzed and legislative provisions are described.

The second Research question on developing the variables of Consumer Protection that determine the nexus between Medical Negligence and its Consequences under CPA were studied in various Judgments of Consumer Commissions. The parameters are culled out of all the comparative and different laws, to include dimensions of.

The third Research question on analyzing the Changing Trends found in the approach towards the Law of Medical Negligence from study of collected Data are addressed as follows:

- **Movement from *Bolam* to *Bolitho*** is not clearly established. The influence of *Bolam* is evident in a minority of Supreme Court decisions and lesser in National Commission.

In 37.5 % of the Supreme Court, the Bolam Principle was mentioned in the judgment, while in remaining 62.5 % of the case it was not mentioned.

In only 15.7 % of the National Commission cases, the Bolam principle was mentioned in the judgments, while in remaining 84.3 % of the cases it was not mentioned.

Judge's role veers between Editorship and authorship. Editorship is where; Judge gives decision after collecting information from, expert witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws etc.

Authorship: Without referring any relevant witnesses, evidences, Medical Literature, Case laws, Judge gives decision as he thinks fit.

In the present study, in 85 % of Supreme Court cases, the judicial behavior is Editorship while, 15 % of the cases it is Authorship. In the National Commission, the Editorship was found in 36.3 % as against 63.7 % cases Authorship was found. This movement clearly heralds the emergence of Bolitho influence.

Authorship in majority of judgments at National Commission itself shows that the Judge's are already utilizing their discretion without mentioning the Bolitho principle.

- **Expert opinion not being accepted in Consumer cases**

In 85 % of the Supreme Court cases, the Judges accepted expert witness as well as expert evidence while in remaining 15 % of the cases that was not accepted.

In 44.3 % of the National Commission cases, the Judges accepted expert witness and evidence while in remaining 55.7 % of the cases the same was not accepted.

- **Punitive Approach**

It depends on proving the doctor negligent. So automatically the element of punishing attitude in the community and reduced patience due to commercialization and ease of access to the information on the internet; are responsible for the present change in the doctor patient relationship.

- **Compromising doctor patient relationship**

By the findings of the Community survey it can be easily made out that there is compromising doctor patient relationship, out of fear of litigation.

- **The Consumer Protection Act may prove to be counterproductive if continued to govern Medical Negligence in India.**

In the present study, in the 60 % Supreme Court cases Medical Negligence was proved while in remaining 40 % of the cases it was not proved.

Similarly, in 36.7 % of the cases of the National Commission, Medical Negligence was proved while in remaining 63.3 % of the cases, it was not proved.

As already found in the present study that, at National Commission level very high- 36.7 % doctors were proved negligent and at Supreme Court it is 60 %.

It is rapidly proving to be disastrous.

7.3. Suggestions to existing mechanism

As Lord Justice Otton aptly said:

'The question [that need to] be asked is [a]s a civilized society, are we content with a system where a person who has by ill-fortune suffered grievous injury as a result of medical treatment can be denied all form of compensation due to the failure to establish negligence? The present system requires...serious thought. It is time that society, government, doctors, judges and academics, and in particular members of this prestigious and influential society considered the possibility of thoroughgoing change.'⁴⁰²

In USA, the answer is sought through reforms in Tort Law since the 1970s, by state legislators. These reforms related to state tort laws, the information on the quality of medical care and its oversight, and the structure of the medical liability insurance market. Reforms of the first type usually focus on limiting medical negligence arrangements—such as medical malpractice damage caps (mainly on compensation due to pain and suffering)—which are very common in state law, limiting legal fees and shrinking the limitation period in medical negligence lawsuits, such as the requirement to prove negligence through expert testimony and setting standards for selecting the expert witness, the requirement for pre-trial screening of groundless claims through a medical panel or a mediation mechanism, and setting alternative dispute resolution mechanisms, or ADRs. Florida and Virginia, two of the states that

⁴⁰² Lord Justice Otton, 'Medical Negligence - Is there something wrong? [2001] 69 Medico-Legal Journal 72, at p. 75.as mentioned by Dr Puteri Nemie bt. Jahn Kassim in **MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE LITIGATION IN MALAYSIA :WHITHER SHOULD WE TRAVEL?** *The Journal of the Malaysian Bar* (2004) XXXIII No 1

have intervened in their applicable tort laws, have gone so far as to impose a partial arrangement of strict liability in medical liability lawsuits in the obstetrics area.⁴⁰³

Other's Recommendations:

The following are some recommendations⁴⁰⁴ (as stated by some researchers) to make COPRA more effective:

- A. One major problem envisaged by the enactment of this Act is the emergence of a defensive culture because of which the cost of care is likely to increase considerably. To overcome this, the medical councils and associations should look at the charge structure for various procedures. Already some concerns have been raised in the Parliament about the fees charged by doctors. The committee of the upper house recommended that doctors should notify the Medical Council of India of their schedule of fee charges and the Council, in turn, should make this information available to the public.
- B. The Act, at present, has no provision for punishing people who file false cases. There is strong apprehension among the providers that the number of false cases will increase and the legislation will be used for harassing and blackmailing the providers. To minimize the misuse of this legislation, it is suggested that there should be a screening committee to review the cases before they are formally taken up for hearing by the consumer forums. The responsibility of the screening committee should also be to categorize cases in such a way that only medical negligence cases posing damage or loss to patient should be pursued further. Other matters should be referred to the Medical Council.
- C. Most of the doctors feel that the absence of medical professional on the panel of councils is one of the major drawbacks of the CPA. It was pointed out that the providers in the health sector were not involved in the process of enacting CPA until late in its development. It is argued that non medical people serve judgment when they are not qualified to make an accurate assessment about medical

⁴⁰³ Noam Sher, *NEW DIFFERENCES BETWEEN NEGLIGENCE AND STRICT LIABILITY AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS ON MEDICAL MALPRACTICE REFORM*, *Southern California Interdisciplinary Law Journal* (Vol. 16:335, pp.350)(2007)

⁴⁰⁴ Rahul Raizada, *Regulatory issue-COPRA, Health care Industry in India- Present Scenario*, 2012

evidence. It is suggested that medical people be better represented, especially in medical negligence cases.

D. There should be an orientation program for newly graduated doctors who want to start private practice.

E. Medical Council of India and State Medical Councils (SMCs)
The character of medical care in India has changed drastically and these changes present many challenges. These challenges need to be addressed by the MCI. In order to do so, however, the basic structure and financing of the MCI has to be strengthened to make it an effective organization. The role of MCI and SMCs as regulators has been less than impressive in India. They have failed to regulate the medical profession and to set adequate standards to safeguard the interest of patients, particularly in the area of medical practice. As first step, the role of regulating education should be separated from the role of regulating practice. This would require a separate commission to establish adequate standards and ensure the implementation of basic minimum standards.⁴⁰⁵

F. The Nursing Homes Act, 1949

The NHAs do not specify minimum standards for nursing homes to uphold. Since legislation such as the Nursing Home Act does not normally specify the standards, the medical associations or the Medical Council of India could do this. The standard setting agency should then be empowered to implement those standards.

The process of registration and renewal should be tightened and should be strictly implemented. The local supervising authorities should be made responsible for registration and renewal of registration.

The Ministry of Health in India should take a broad view of the regulation of Nursing Homes in India and should lay down basic policy guidelines for all states.

⁴⁰⁵ Ibid

Recommendations

The researcher would strongly recommend for a Fault Based Administrative System in line with US System. In 1988, the American Medical Association proposed a new alternative for resolving medical liability disputes that would remove disputes from the traditional tort system and decide liability on the basis of fault through existing Medical Boards. This theoretical proposal was never implemented in any states at the time; however, it remains a viable option for states to explore.

Under this model, an administrative fault-based system would be established in existing state medical disciplinary boards or in a new state agency. The administrative system would consist of a pre-hearing process, formal hearings before a hearing examiner, full appellate review by a state-chartered board, and a limited review in the courts.

- *Pre-hearing*: all claims would be reviewed quickly for merit. Those without merit would be dismissed; those with merit would be submitted to an appropriate expert in the same field as the health care provider for further review of merit. Patients would receive free legal assistance in litigating the case and in evaluating settlement offers.
- *Formal hearing*: if the claim is not settled, it would be assigned to a hearing examiner who would pursue the case and conduct a formal hearing. The examiner would oversee the expedited discovery and ensure that the parties have valid expert evidence available to support their case. At the hearing itself, the examiner has broad authority to conduct the proceedings, and will issue a written decision within 90 days. The examiner would determine whether the health care provider is liable for the claimant's injury and if so, the size of the award.⁴⁰⁶
- ***Appellate review***: The examiner's decision is subject to a review by the medical board. The medical board consists of three members who make a full independent review of the case and of the health care provider's liability. Appeals of the medical board's review are made to the intermediate appellate court of the state, where the review would be limited to whether the medical board acted contrary to the statute of the board's own rules.

⁴⁰⁶ Emily V. Cornell, Addressing the Medical Malpractice Insurance Crisis, 2002, Issue Brief, pp.8

1. Fault Based Administrative System and Compensation should be developed, to delink accountability of professionals from Consumerism and Fault.
2. Specialized Health Tribunals should be created with an amicable approach than adversarial approach.
3. Enterprise Liability should be imposed as more of Liability Reform
4. Hospital Grievance Redressal Committees should be created as primary safety Valve, to manage unreasonable patient expectations, patient education.
5. Patient education should be taken up in a systematic way to add to this measure.
6. Strengthening the role of MCI as controlling body by empowering it to derecognize and penalize professionals.
7. Medical Curriculum should include-Ethics and Communication
8. Elaborate Patient Education and Counseling System should be in place.
9. Expert Evidence: Daubert Criteria to be introduced
10. Rather than establishing Negligence under Consumer Rights concept, the relationship based on early disclosure and Compensation with Limited fault liability could be explored.
11. Creation of Health Tribunals/ Medical Boards that will be authorized to deal with the Medical Negligence Cases⁴⁰⁷

7.4 Recommendations for a new comprehensive law governing the medical liability.

Researcher proposes the following new legislation

1. Patient Protection and Safety Act 2013

The two bases for this framework shall be limited Fault Based Liability System and Fast Track Settlement

The scheme of the proposed enactment is as follows:

CHAPTER I PRELIMINARY

An Act to provide for better protection of the interest s of patients and for that purpose to make establishment of patient protection councils and

⁴⁰⁷ Ref: Personal Interview with Dr.Graeme Laurie, Dean of Edinburgh Law School, UK on 9thApril 2008

other authorities for the settlement of patient's disputes and for matters connected therewith.

CHAPTER II PATIENT PROTECTION COUNCILS

1. The Central Patient Protection Council
2. Procedure for meetings of the Central Council
3. Objects of the Central Council
4. The State Patient Protection Councils
5. The objects of the State Council
6. The District Patient Protection Council
7. Objects of the District Council

CHAPTER III HEALTH TRIBUNALS-MEDICAL BOARDS

1. A three tier system: District, State and National Tribunals
2. Establishment of District Medical Boards, State Health Tribunals and National Health Tribunal.
3. Composition of Boards and Tribunals
4. Jurisdictions
5. Process of Appeals
6. Limitation Period
7. Hearing within 90 days.

CHAPTER IV SYSTEM OF EXPERT MEDICAL EVIDENCE

- To follow the Daubert Criteria⁴⁰⁸ of the US System
- Special provisions to regulate the role of Medical Experts in Court
- Registration of Medical Experts
- System will assist the Judiciary to decide reasonableness and admissibility of the expert medical evidence

⁴⁰⁸ Based on Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals Inc. 509 US 579,113 S.Ct. 2786 (1993):

CHAPTER V MISCELLANEOUS

1. Protection of action taken in good faith
2. Power to remove difficulties
3. Rules about vacancies
4. Power of Health Tribunals: Medical Boards

2. PATIENT PROTECTION AND SAFETY RULES

1. Definitions
2. Constitution of Medical Boards and Tribunals
3. Procedures and functioning of the Boards and Tribunals
4. Sitting of State and National Tribunals
5. Staff
6. Fee for making complaints
7. Number of Members in the Boards and Tribunals
8. Procedure for selection of members
9. Procedure of Limited appeal
10. Various forms

Such legislation will replace piecemeal approach and will act as one stop for all legal requirements.

7.5. Scope for future research

As such the Medical Negligence is complex subject and depends on number of parameters. In the present study the researcher has tried to study this complex phenomenon by applying multiple methods and then triangulating them. The study was restricted to Pune district, by and large an urban study. Further, the case laws from the National Commission and the Supreme Court were also studied.

For future research, the following scope exists.

1. For an extensive research that represents the opinions from even rural regions, as 70 % India resides in rural locations.
2. Study of all case laws from District and State levels will depict the real picture of what is going on in the periphery and how far the consumer fora are able to bear this challenge of distinguishing the simple cases from complex cases, when the authorities do not have the expert knowledge about the medial field.

3. Extensive use of mass media may be undertaken for study of awareness and formation of opinion about the Medical Negligence.